

Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the audiovisual and radio industry

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Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the audiovisual and radio industry

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Work package	<p>The CICERONE project consists of seven work packages (WPs). This report is part of WP2, which constitutes the empirical backbone of the project. WP2 contains case study research that focuses on networked production in eight cultural and creative industries: 1) architecture, 2) archives (including libraries and cultural heritage), 3) artistic crafts, 4) audiovisual media (film, television, videogames, multimedia) and radio, 5) design, 6) festivals, as well as performing and visual arts, 7) music and, 8) publishing. The purpose of the case study research is to understand key linkages and mechanisms within real-life production networks in the cultural and creative sector (CCS) and the relationships of these networks to context-dependent variables.</p> <p>Drawing on the case study research, the CICERONE project explores a policy framework that may contribute to enhancing policy support for the cultural and creative sectors. Furthermore, the case study research facilitates the identification of gaps in extant sources of quantitative data, suggesting approaches on how these gaps can be plugged. For this reason, WP2 is not just the empirical backbone of CICERONE, it also provides critical inputs for the work in other WPs (most notably WP4 and WP6).</p> <p>This deliverable (D2.4) reports on the case studies on cultural heritage, archives and libraries. Together with reports D2.1 to D2.3 and D2.5 to D2.8, it provides strategic snapshots of the rich and variegated tapestry of European production networks in the CCS.</p> <p>All deliverables of the CICERONE project are publicly disclosed on the project's website www.cicerone-project.eu and through its Zenodo community on https://zenodo.org/communities/cicerone-h2020.</p>

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Executive summary

The 2009 UNESCO framework for cultural statistics, used by the European Union 2017 report, divides the audiovisual sector into three main categories: Film, television and Radio Broadcasting, Videogames and Multimedia. The aim of this report is to present the audiovisual sector through the lens of the concept of global production networks (GPNs). The theory of global production networks is relatively new and is mainly associated with classical industries such as automotive, textiles, etc. Its application to the cultural industries, and specifically to the audiovisual industry, goes beyond the economic dimensions and highlights the cultural and socio-political aspects of these markets.

The report consists of four parts. The first part is the basis for the subsequent analysis. It deals with the specificity of the goods and services produced in the audiovisual sector, labour as a unique resource, embeddedness and its cultural, economic and social dimensions. The final part of this section looks at current policies and regulations in the sector at national and European level.

The second part provides a statistical mapping of the audiovisual sectors – film industry, television and radio and video games. The statistical data used is from Eurostat (at European level) and by the Observatory of Cultural Economics – at the national level, in Bulgaria. The analysis is made applying the GPN framework to the existing range of statistics. Those activities that are not covered by statistics have been analysed and recommendations made.

The third part presents the four case studies, selected and developed by the Bulgarian and Austrian research teams: the Bulgarian film production company KLAS film and its co-production production network; the European Broadcasting Union represented through the production network of the European Eurovision Song Contest (ESC) with the entry point Bulgarian National Television; the EBU radio activities represented through the production network of the music radio exchange platform MUS with the entry point Bulgarian National Radio and Austrian VIENNESE gaming production. The fieldwork (interviews) for the case studies was conducted in the unusual situation created by the COVID pandemic. Almost all of the interviews were online, and we had a total of 44 interviews: 17 in the film industry, 12 in the television and radio industry and 15 in the games industry.

The final fourth section of the report is a brief summary of the achievements, with comments on the research questions that arose.

The emerging economic, social and health crisis caused by the global COVID19 pandemic has raised many issues for the cultural industries to address. It is evident that we are going through a "moment" of de-globalization (in the production of food, medical equipment, medicines, etc.), but how will

economic stagnation affect the development of production networks in the audiovisual industry? In this changed context, we believe that analysis through the lens of global production networks is particularly productive in the area of audiovisual industries and it deserves to be further developed.

Key words

Global production network, audiovisual industry, film industry, television industry, radio industry, gaming industry

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Introduction

This report examines the global production networks in audiovisual industries in Europe, looking into the four audiovisual industry sub-sectors: Film, television and Radio Broadcasting, Videogames and Multimedia (per UNESCO Institute of Statistics classification from 2009). The first part of the report describes the key features of these industries, their production network phases, and introduces the specificities of their goods and services, types of labour, as well as their level of embeddedness locally, nationally, and globally. The second part of the report shows the outcomes of the statistical mapping and analysis of audiovisual industries at national and European level. The third part contains the findings of our qualitative analysis of case studies, which were built on semi-structured interviews with actors involved in all phases of the production networks of the audiovisual industries from Bulgaria and Austria. By selecting four case studies presented in the third part, the CICERONE project has aimed at grasping the diversity of projects and their production networks and providing important insights for policy at national, local as well as European level.

While following strictly CICERONE's methodology and structure applied for all CCIS, we have researched four different and very diverse, vast and complex industry production networks. All of them involve many actors and tasks, a great variety of linkages and interactions, and their markets are regulated both nationally, and at EU level. This complexity, unlike other CCIS' networks, have led to this large volume of analysis, which we believe offers a rather complete picture, as well as new insights and useful knowledge in the field.

The CICERONE approach to production networks

The point of departure for the analysis of the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS) is the Global Production Network (GPN) approach, which was developed by Neil Coe and Henry Yeung on the basis of the Global Value Chain (GVC) approach (Coe & Yeung, 2015; Kloosterman, Pratt, D'Ovidio, Greco & Borén, 2019). The GPN approach is increasingly used to unravel production networks that involve a complex cross-border spatial division of labour. Such production networks have proliferated across many sectors as a consequence of technological advances in communication and transport as well as due to the liberalisation and deregulation of trade (Kano et al. 2020). These processes have also affected (many) CCSs. However, the GPN approach has rarely been applied to them (Coe, 2015 is an exception). By opting for this innovative approach to the CCS, the CICERONE project generated new insights on its functioning.

In a sense, we have used the GPN method to spatialise. Sociological approaches were already proposed by Howard Becker (Becker, 1982), with his concept of the *art world*, and by Pierre Bourdieu (Bourdieu, 1996), who developed the concept of *field*. Both approaches, the differences between

them notwithstanding (Buttero & Crossley, 2011), aim at embedding the process of creation into a broader societal setting and at going beyond the identification of individual genius. When we use the GPN approach, we cannot simply position the CCS in that broad context – we must also highlight its spatial footprint. We thus employ the GPN approach as a tool for analysing a wide variety of production networks in the CCS. In other words, the approach is a heuristic tool that explains how the products of the CCS progress from inception to sale and whether and how they may be preserved for future generations.

On the pages that follow, we first briefly summarise the key elements of the GPN approach that guided our fieldwork. Thereafter, we focus on the process by which we selected the units of analysis for our case studies. This section is followed by an explanation of the manner in which our sample of case studies lays the foundation for a concise typology of the CCS which can be used by policymakers to devise more targeted combinations of interventions to foster economic growth and employment as well as social and cultural diversity.

Key elements of the GPN approach

Phases and the spatial footprint

Evidently, the most obvious feature of the GPN approach is the carving up of the value chain into distinct value-adding stages which can unfold in different locations and which may involve different sets of actors (including other firms). We have inserted the archiving phase into the value-adding stages because many (if not all) of those who participate in cultural and creative endeavours draw on the works of their predecessors in one way or another (Pratt, 1997). Therefore, in the CICERONE project, we, in principle, distinguish between the following stages:

- 1) **Creation** (the initial conception of an idea or a set of ideas that define aesthetic quality),
- 2) **Production** (the realisation of those ideas through an actual good or service),
- 3) **Distribution** (the sale of the good or the presentation of the service in front of an audience),
- 4) **Exchange** (the wider setting which enables distribution), and
- 5) **Archiving** (the formal preservation of the cultural product).

Creation

It is in this part of the cycle that new ideas, processes or approaches are devised. The notion of “creation”, in the sense in which the term is used here, is a social one – what is new is also relational, situated and conditional. Therefore, a “creative process”, that is, a method, is involved (“design” is an example). Reference is also made to history and to previous instances of creation (the preceding stage). Sometimes, this is referred to as “ideation”, that is, having ideas.

Production

An idea or a creative new thing remains provisional, potential and conditional until it can be stabilised or made. The intervening period is often called the prototype stage. Usually, the product is

also developed during the multiple (or mass) production phase. Technology and labour costs, production decisions, and technological and regulatory standards affect costs and potential access to the products. Marketing and advertising are also relevant, but we allocate them to the exchange phase here.

Distribution or circulation

Products, even if they are new and unusual, are unformed and inaccessible unless they can be moved or migrated to markets or audiences. Physical distribution is clearly a key issue for access and reach. The same is true of digital approaches, which may overcome some barriers. Generally, distribution systems (or platforms) are expensive to develop and susceptible to monopoly control.

Exchange

Exchange is the stage at which the product of service engages the audience or customers. It is a critical moment of information exchange, and one in which (e)valuation occurs. That (e)valuation may take forms as varied as market transaction, participation or critique. Values are made and stabilised at this stage. Therefore, marketing and expectation setting provide a link to distribution. In the experience economy, and particularly in the cultural one, the negotiation of value is a critical element of the transaction, and institutions have been developed that normalise it and reduce risks. The engagement of the audience or consumer is also shaped directly by advertising and marketing – to refer to the previous stages once more, the exchange process can determine which products are available for production and distribution.

Archiving

Since cultural value is relational, history and cultural diversity always interact with the present. Moreover, the process of reflection and learning (or that of rejection) is part of the critical appreciation of culture. The archiving of culture creates both normative structures that enable cultural production systems and the disruptive elements that facilitate new approaches. This stage also includes education (of audiences or consumers as well as of creative practitioners), institutions such as universities and media systems, and repositories such as libraries, museums and galleries. It is at this point that heritage is identified and later mobilised via the production system. More generally, archiving constitutes the resource from which new ideas are developed, which refers back to creation.

Source: D'Ovidio et al., 2019

We treat this model of the phases as a *point of departure*, not as a given, and we employ the case studies to explore the extent to which these distinctions may explain production in the CCS. As Throsby (Throsby, 2010, p. 25) observed, in some production processes in the CCS, there is no simple and neat sequence, and “[t]he apparent linearity of the value chain may be replaced, for some cultural products, by something more akin to a value network, where multiple inputs, feedback loops, and a pervasive ‘value-creating ecology’ replaces a simple stage-wise process.” Although he was rightly critical of the slavish application of a value chain approach to the CCS, he also observed that “[f]rom a policy point of view, depicting the cultural production process as a value chain allows an analysis of the effects of policy intervention at various points in the chain. For example, in assessing the impacts

of existing policy measures, or in determining the optimal point at which to apply prospective measures, the policy analyst can use the value-chain concept to clarify where the effects of intervention have been or will be felt, and who are the affected stakeholders upstream or downstream from the point of intervention.”

It therefore stands to reason that one should start with the conceptual framework of these stages and then determine which phases can be identified as distinct, which boundaries are blurred and which phases overlap or are deeply intertwined. Subsequently, we locate phases or combinations of phases – the spatial footprint – and we identify the parties that are involved. In this manner, we extend our focus beyond creation to include other parts of the input-output structure of the CCS.

Governance

The second element that we derive from the GPN approach and which we use to open the black box of the production network is the concept of governance. The complex global value chains and production networks which have been studied (mostly in manufacturing) typically exhibit asymmetrical power structures, with one lead firm engaging in explicit coordination (Gereffi, 2005). This lead firm may be involved in the production phase (producer-driven chain) or in the distribution phase (buyer-driven chain). If power dynamics are asymmetric and a lead firm takes charge of coordinating the network, it may be inferred that it is capable of forcing the other actors to act in a certain way but also that it can capture much of the value that is created in the network. Similarly to our approach to the stages, we do not take the existence of a lead firm in the CCS for granted. Instead, we attempt to identify a more explicit hierarchical power distribution or a more dispersed horizontal one. Furthermore, we do not assume that the presence of a lead firm or actor necessarily results in an asymmetrical distribution of (economic) value, and we examine this issue as a research question.

Embeddedness

The third element that we use to understand the production networks of the CCS is that of embeddedness. In his seminal work on the transformation of the British economy in the 19th century, Karl Polanyi (Polanyi, 1957) emphasised the importance of the institutional context in which all economic actions are embedded. In this context, differences in embeddedness affect economic actions, the likelihood of their occurrence, the manner in which they unfold and their consequences (Granovetter, 1985). This view became widespread in economic sociology, organisation studies, strategic management (Smelser & Swedberg, 2005) and, somewhat later, in economic geography. The GPN approach explicitly aims to apply embeddedness to make sense of the spatial footprint of the production network: why are such-and-such activities located in such-and-such places? According to Kleiber and Horner (Kleibert & Horner, 2018), the operations of actors within the same universalistic category of a transnational production system is very much contingent on their embeddedness in a particular society, place and social network. Embeddedness thus becomes crucial for understanding the spatial and social division of labour within a production network. The forms of embeddedness are also critical for the design of effective policies for the CCS (Salder, 2022).

We have adopted the multi-layered approach to embeddedness that Coe and Yeung (2015) proposed. We therefore distinguish between three levels of embeddedness.

- i. Societal embeddedness: the influence of institutional contexts on the actions taken by actors in production networks (rules, laws and regulations) which are mainly located at the EU level and the national level.
- ii. Territorial embeddedness: the local context of the location where a certain activity takes place, which is closely related to local clusters and ecosystems with distinct sets of agglomeration economies that selectively sustain and foster economic activities (Scott, 2000).
- iii. Network embeddedness: the linkages between different actors and the functional and social connectivity of those relationships (e.g. social network relationships based on trust).

As with the phases, the boundaries between these forms of embeddedness are not set in stone. Place-based communities are an essential element of agglomeration economies, but they are also closely linked to social networks. We analyse these levels of embeddedness more comprehensively.

Unit of analysis

The CCSI are characterised by their emphasis on unique aesthetic qualities and, importantly, on near-infinite horizontal differentiation (Caves, 2000), volatile (cross-sectoral) cooperation, and, crucially, forms of collaboration that are often ad hoc and usually involve several actors with different skills and functions. Those forms of collaboration often permeate the legal boundaries of firms. This particular way of producing involves, as a result, “complex teams – the motley crew property”, as well as “close temporal coordination of their activities” (Caves, 2000, p.8). Watson (Watson, 2012, p. 617) added that “[t]he complexity of the [jointly produced product or service] necessitates the coordination of multidisciplinary skills” and that permanent centralisation is not economically efficient (Lorenzen & Frederiksen, 2005). Production must often be completed under severe time constraints (Hobday, 2000; Staber, 2004) Temporary networks, interpersonal collaboration and projects in the CCS are therefore very much intertwined. As de Klerk (de Klerk, 2015, p. 829) observed, “[t]he dynamic environment in the industry is mostly project-based... thus often obliging these workers to find alternative employment between projects to optimise their limited work opportunities [...]”

The GPN approach has mainly been used to analyse the large-scale production of goods. Some CCSIs, such as parts of the fashion industry, seem to fit this format of production well. However a substantial part of CCSI activities are different from the usual subjects of the GPN literature, which tends to focus on production networks in which large firms manufacture large volumes of standardised goods.

A substantial part of CCIS, such as audiovisual industries, music industry, as well as performing arts in its various manifestations, produce specific services – some of them reproduced and distributed to mass audiences, and others – in limited numbers and targeting much smaller segments of customers or audiences. This leads to variations in the composition, the governance and the levels of embeddedness of these productions networks. A performance, a song or a painting are all unique products which are typically created by such ad hoc production networks that vary from product to

product (Power & Hallencreutz, 2002; Power & Jansson, 2004; Pratt, 2006). (See 1.1.1 on audiovisual products and services).

In some CCSIs, such as the television or fashion industries, large international companies prevail. In festivals and visual arts, small firms or entities have leading roles, the composition of their networks is much more contextual, and their projects involve very different stakeholders.

In order to cover production networks in the CCS that are volatile and project-based, we focus in most case studies on projects as a unit of analysis. This approach is very much in line with the literature on the forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. In more recent economic-geographic studies and in sociological research on CCS, project-based work, which involves a multiplicity of organisational and personal social networks, is a key component of the analysis (see Watson, 2012 for a very thorough overview). Notably, studies on labour conditions in the CCS have benefited from departing from the project-based approach. The important role of project-based work has been corroborated in many CCSs (de Klerk, 2015).

In the CCSIs, then, the firm should not be granted a privileged ontological status. Instead, networks should be central. One could even go a step further and conceptualise the firm as a more permanent or sustained project or as a collection of long-term projects (although it is evidently subject to recombination and change) that has been solidified into a legal entity. The temporal dimension of the project and therefore of its network then become a crucial variable for the case studies. This shift evidently dovetails into our GPN approach, which emphasises the role of networks. In the CICERONE project, we conceive of these networks not *a priori* in terms of firms but in terms of interpersonal networks that are organised around a specific project. In *Art Worlds*, Howard Becker also highlighted interpersonal relationships (Becker, 1982). Our focus also allows us to emphasise the role of cultural value, which may trump economic value, and the salience of motives other than profit maximisation, especially in the creation phase. These distinguishing features of the CCS have significant consequences for the functioning of its production networks.

A key feature of audiovisual industries's networks and their projects in the European context is the role of the public policies, national and EU regulations and funding of these markets. Public owned media (TV, radio) are typical for Europe, as a form of guarantee of safe media environment, whereas film industry can be market based, and subsidised art form (for the sake of linguistic and cultural diversity).

A more practical advantage of circling on specific projects is that it enabled us to select respondents more easily – we could simply focus on those individuals who were involved in a given project. It then also became easier to limit the number of respondents (only project-related key or lead actors or firms, strategic partners, strategic suppliers and key customers) that we had to consider.

Selection of cases

The main purpose of the CICERONE project is to provide a new foundation for CCS policies on the basis of a production network approach that generates novel insights on the functioning of the CCS and its

cultural and social impact. Our approach situates the CCS in networks of production that extend far beyond the creation phase. We use case studies to map the configuration of production networks and to analyse relationships between actors in creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving. The case studies are thus intended to uncover linkages and mechanisms within these production networks and to lay the foundation for more informed policies which not only extend beyond the creation phase but also take spatial footprints and governance structures into account.

Business models within the CCS vary widely. That variance obtains not only across sectors but also within them. There are differences in staff numbers, turnover, type of products, barriers to entry, the use of technology, capital needs, end markets and strategies, to name but a few. Networks also differ in terms of power relationships, shape and organisation, and the nature, complexity and geography of their linkages. At present, no data sets cover these characteristics comprehensively. Representative sampling is certainly not feasible within the timeframe of the CICERONE project. The investigation of the variance in question, accordingly, is a voyage into uncharted waters.

We have therefore opted for a purposive selection of cases, whereby researchers select the units to be sampled on the basis of their knowledge, which in our case is the background research that we conducted prior to the cases studies. The aim of this selection was to include cases, which may plausibly be assumed to represent a sufficient range of easily assessable variations in key business model characteristics, notably staffing and turnover. This approach yielded cases that typify a significant proportion of the population of the CCS while also exhibiting sufficient differences to represent its variability (Gerring, 2007). In the case study reports that follow, each case study is positioned within the wider sector.

Typology matrix

While the case studies are intended to present a rich picture of the key mechanisms and the main linkages that show how spatial footprints, governance structures and levels of embeddedness are intertwined in real-life situations, a higher level of abstraction that transcends the study of individual production networks must be accessed if general insights are to be derived. We must simplify characteristics and relationships in order to present a clear narrative for policymakers. The key elements of our approach – spatial footprints, governance structures and multi-layered embeddedness – guided us in reducing the complexity of the case studies to distil insights from findings.

The first step is to position concrete cases from the CCS in a simple grid, which combines the spatial footprint with the governance structure. The two variables are crucial determinants of societal effects. A completely local production network with a horizontal governance structure and a mainly global and hierarchical network that is coordinated by a lead firm or actor differ starkly in their social, economic and cultural impact, as well as in the policy interventions that they require. Furthermore, if creation is local but production and distribution are global, targeting policy only at the creation phase may have unforeseen consequences for the wider network.

In principle, the typology matrix of production networks distinguishes between the different phases. In some cultural and creative industries and sectors these phases may overlap. For each phase or set of phases, it is possible to determine whether a single or multiple actors are in charge of the activities. Different phases may then exhibit different governance structures and relationships. It may also be the case that one actor is ultimately in charge of the whole network and is clearly present in the coordination of each phase. Alternatively, a small number of actors may control the network. Using this typology matrix enables us to draw cross-sectoral comparisons between cases and therefore to depart from the conventional siloed approaches. We expect that certain combinations will transpire to be much more likely to occur than others: the likelihood of a small local network having a more horizontal governance structure is evidently much higher than that of a complex and truly global network adopting governance type, which requires much more extensive coordination.

CCSs are embedded in multi-layered contexts, which range from the EU and the national level to that of the territorial and social network. Our empirical work shows how these contexts affect individual cases. Cross-case analysis shows how the forms of embeddedness are related to the typology matrix more generally. Power relations, for instance, may also depend on institutional conditions. Those conditions may allow an actor to assume leadership or to take advantage of the network.

This typology matrix is a starting point for an exploration of the potential role of hard policy levers (e.g. tax incentives, public subsidies etc.) and soft policy levers (e.g. strengthening the institutional framework, establishing platforms for collaboration, improving education etc.) that various policymakers at different spatial levels may in principle manipulate. Policy makers can use this typology matrix as a tool for assessing the key characteristics of the concrete CCS populations, which may be defined narrowly or widely, whose societal impact they wish to improve. Filling this typology matrix clearly also requires new sets of data which allow the larger CCS populations to be profiled.

The typology matrix is crucial to constructing an overarching narrative that transcends the idiosyncrasies of individual cases. Moreover, it supplies a basis for our policy recommendations, which are phase and location specific and must be sensitive to the organisation of network governance. We strove for high uniformity to enable comparisons. We present a guide to achieving that goal below.

It is often difficult to compress information for a whole production network on the spatial footprint dimension from the outset. Instead, we divide the network into phases and then locate the actors in each phase. This process yields a refined stepwise analysis of the production network. The next step is to summarise the findings for the whole network. Production networks may be local from the creation phase to archiving or global from start to finish. It may also be the case that creation and production are entirely local or regional but distribution and exchange are national or even global. Identifying such spatial footprints would convey important information to policy makers.

Similarly, we adopt a stepwise approach to assessing the organisation of network governance. For each phase, we inquire which actor initiates, organises, monitors and controls activities. It may be that one actor is in charge of the whole network. It may also be the case that two actors are in charge of different phases. A more horizontal governance configuration without clear leading actors is also a possibility. How policies impact production networks depends on their governance configurations.

Throwing money at a specific cultural and creative industry which is controlled by a transnational corporation that is located outside the EU would be a different proposition from financing a network in which the leading actor is close to the others, in the same country or even in the same city.

We use the typology matrix to systematise the classification of the cases that we studied. This matrix must be completed by using the actor categories in Table 2. We use the labels from Table 2 to ensure consistency.

Table 1. The typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation					
Production					
Distribution					
Exchange					
Archiving					
Network level					Lead actor/ multiple actors/ horizontal

Table 2. Key actors in the production networks

Creators	Actors who participate in the initial creation (individuals, such as writers and musicians, or collectives, such as fashion brands and film crews)
Specialised suppliers	Suppliers that provide specialised/dedicated services or products and are hard to replace in the short term
Strategic partners (private sector)	Providers of strategic resources (capital, labour, knowledge and certifications) such as banks, educational institutions, professional associations, tastemakers and critics
Strategic partners (civil society)	Actors that operate at neither the state level nor the market level and which provide essential goods, services or resources (funding, labour, information and certifications)
Strategic partners (public sector, multilevel)	Public sector actors at the level of the EU, the national, the regional or the local government that provide strategic resources (e.g. funding and certifications)
Distributors	Actors (individual or collective) in charge of delivering the good or service to the customer or consumer
Consumers	B2C (business to consumer): final market with large number of buyers
Customers	B2B (business-to-business): final market, typically with a single buyer (e.g. real estate firm commissioning a design for a building)
Lead actors	Actor(s) who initiates, organises, monitors and controls the activities of the network

Phases

We depart from the GPN approach with its five phases. In many cases, however, the phases overlap, and borders are blurred. Such issues can be addressed easily by merging the cells for phases that overlap or by drawing dotted lines if the phases are distinct but their boundaries are blurred.

The spatial scales

We distinguish between four scales: the local or the regional, the national, the intra-EU and the global. These scales, in principle, correspond to different policymakers and, in many cases, also to different policies (from local policies to provide workspaces through national subsidy programmes to EU competition regulations and trade policies). The anchor point for *the local or regional* scale is the point at which initial creation occurs, that is, the point at which the aesthetic component of the good or service is created. This spatial level may coincide with a particular city, a large metropolitan area or a rural region. The origin of the value chain may be located elsewhere, as in the case of architectural design, a domain in which the customer may be located across the globe. However, our focus here is on the first moves of concrete actors from a specific CCS. We then inquire, for each phase, where the other key actors in the production network are located. The location of an activity is where the actors are from: e.g., flying in a choreographer from Norway and a light engineer from Israel to create a modern dance work in The Hague is still a form of global import.

Governance

Governance pertains to the whole network. We distinguish between three options: a) networks with a lead actor, b) networks with multiple lead actors (not more than 2 or 3) and c) bottom-up horizontal arrangements.

PART 1. The European production network of the audiovisual and radio industry: an overview

1.1 Overview of the audiovisual industry and radio

Profile of the audiovisual industry and radio

The 2009 UNESCO framework for cultural statistics, used in the European Union 2017 report, divides the audiovisual sector into three main categories: film, television and radio broadcasting, and videogames and multimedia. The film, television, and gaming industries have multiple sub-sector variations and different value chains and management types. Digitisation in the audiovisual sector has created a converging environment and a strong drive towards vertical integration, which has stimulated the emergence of global conglomerates uniting film, television, and gaming companies.

This section provides an overview of the main trends, the size and scale of the European audiovisual industries, and their economic importance in terms of revenue and growth. Section 1.1.1 introduces the key features of audiovisual goods and services, followed by Section 1.1.2, which describes the specificity of labour in each of the four sub-industries. Section 1.3.3 introduces the concept of the embeddedness of the production networks in each of the audiovisual industries. The legal frameworks and policies of the European audiovisual and media industries are introduced in Section 1.1.4.

The global entertainment and media market has grown steadily over the past years, by about USD 0.1 trillion annually, reaching USD 2.1 trillion (1.9 trillion Euros) by 2019, according to PwC Global Entertainment and Media Outlook (2022). The COVID-19 pandemic interrupted that steady trend in 2020, but the markets quickly recovered to reach an expected USD 2.5 billion in 2022, and the perspective is to grow in the coming years. The largest markets appear to be those of the USA and China, as well as India. Digital content is leading in consumption, and its fastest-growing segment is internet video (over-the-top video streaming market). Global companies have created multimedia platforms (e.g. Alibaba and Amazon) to build globally distributed ecosystems, of which cinema, games, and television are just one element (PwC 2022).

Europe's audiovisual market was estimated at EUR 127 billion in 2017. The European market reflects the global trends, but there are some specifics related to its size and fragmentation, to the European concept of “cultural exception” in the film industry, and to the role of public media in the television industry. Public funding in the European television market accounts for 22% of the total sector revenue, up from 0.5% for the US, according to EAO data for 2017. Pay television revenues accounted for about USD 12 billion in 2018, but the fastest-growing segment, at nearly 30% annually, is on-demand pay revenues (IABM, 2019, European Audiovisual Observatory, Yearbook 2015, Blazquesz, F. et al., 2019).

In addition, the concentration process of the European television market is increasing, with a strong presence of US capitals.

The gaming industry reached EUR 134.9 billion in 2018, up 10.9% from 2017, according to Newzoo. The video game market in the European Union grew by 15% in 2018, to 21 billion Euros, according to the latest Interactive Software Federation of Europe (ISFE) report (2021). The report shows that the four main markets in the EU are France, Germany, Spain, and the United Kingdom. In the console games segment, these markets accounted for 47% of the revenues. Mobile games ranked second, with 34% of total revenue, or EUR 12.3 billion, from these four regions, followed by PC (18%) and handheld (2%) games. The ISFE report also shows that 54% of the EU population plays video games, equivalent to around 250 million players in the region. The age group with the highest growth is the 25–34 age group. The average playing time per week is 8.7 hours.

The largest gaming markets in the world, by revenue, are China, USA, and Japan. Among the EU Member States, five countries are in the top 10 of the rankings: Germany (5th place), UK (6th place), France (7th place), Spain (9th place), and Italy (10th place), according to Newzoo's Global Games Market Report.

The audiovisual industry's value chains and markets are very dynamic and dependent on distribution, as well as on customers' preferences and accessibility. The product of audiovisual industries is considered risky as a prototype (Debane, Chetrit 2001) and is connected with multiple market defects, for example, the unpredictability of customers' tastes and informational asymmetry, which leads to lost effectiveness (Tomova, 2019). Expensive production leads to high value of the first copy, and a relatively short value chain of these "experienced goods" exceeds the supply over the demand of these products several times. Therefore, there are higher expectations for the distribution, marketing, and promotion of the product, as well as for diverse competition strategies for surviving in these markets (Picard, R. 1990; Albarran, Dimmick 1996). Two out of every ten films make profit (Gasson, 1996 in Doyle, 2013). Only 5% of pilot television programmes turn profitable (Doyle, 2013). A comparative analysis of the European and American film markets, performed by the European Investment Bank, states that (a conclusion made by Doyle, confirmed by Debande and Chetrit) in the nature of the film and television industries, there are characteristics that define them as risky enterprises, irrespective of their stage of market development.

The increased technological advancements make consumption technology-dependent for customers. PwC shows vast disparities in per capita spending on broadband internet across the globe, including a worrying gap between Western Europe and Central and Eastern Europe (PwC 2022, p. 6).

This incredibly insecure return on investment in the audiovisual industries, combined with high production costs, influences the market model as well as the competition. As a result, companies develop survival strategies based on vertical integration (the Hollywood approach) or horizontal mergers aiming at the economy of scale and communalities. Authors Doyle and Ellen Goodman argue that the economy of scale is dramatically higher in the information and communication services, in comparison with other sectors, and that this often leads to economies of multiple formats, in which one corporation operates in two or more industries (for example, television, film industry, advertising,

computer games). In this way, companies seek economies of scope. Seeking market concentration often leads to oligopoly markets and the existence of almost natural monopolies in these industries (Goodman 2004). This trend, combined with the need for diversification, stimulates the emergence of new competition models (Daidji, 2011).

The rapid development of multimedia streaming platforms has completely changed the world of the cultural and creative industries and has led to the emergence of complete ecosystems such as Google and Amazon.

These features of the audiovisual sector ecosystem, especially in the European audiovisual and film industries, have defined an important role for the state. The state is directly involved through public policies and direct financial support in individual national markets, as well as through a common regulatory framework created at the European Union level.

1.1.1 Goods and services in audiovisual industries

The film, television and radio, and video gaming industries create content that is immaterial by nature, exists in the form of (digital) services, carries intellectual property rights, qualifies as “experience goods” (films and video games), and elicits individual audience appreciation based on personal experience and feeling.

The mode of distribution affects the economic characteristics of audiovisual services. For example, a film distributed in a physical medium (DVD, a good), becomes a service when it is shown in a movie theatre. Today, the individual or domestic usage of audiovisual products on hard-copy media has been replaced largely by digital formats and services, which we discuss further in this chapter.

If an audiovisual product is subsidised, it becomes a mixed good. According to the theory of well-being, it is for collective consumption, which brings collective benefits. These collective benefits are indivisible from collective consumption (no one from the audience can take home a material piece of the benefit). When a film is distributed and sold in a hard-copy medium (DVD), the consumer buys a private product with positive externalities (e.g. it is relevant for his or her education, traditions, aesthetic experience, etc.) (Tomova, 2014).

“Audiovisual media goods are rather goods in the field of culture, than economic goods,” but they are also classified as “communication services” (Ognianova, 2015). Television and radio broadcasting (news, series, editorial, music) create media content that reaches the audience in aggregated and branded form, as a television programme. These services are impossible to consume without their complementing devices, products and services: television and radio sets, television transmission boxes, game consoles, DVD players, computers, smartphones, software applications, paid internet access, and many more.

A **video game** is a software development and a digital commodity that can be easily distributed and used around the world. The consumption of games is not limited in place and time. In fact, we can consider the games industry a global digital player.

Games have evolved from a product offered on a physical medium (floppy disk or CD) to a digital service. The cause for this transformation is the technology shift and the aim to offer games on various digital and online platforms. The industry is moving from product-based games to service-based games (Silvennoinen, 2020) (Xie, 2018).

Depending on their type, digital game products can be distributed in a physical medium, as is typical for video games, that contains a digital product that can be kept and collected in physical collections; or as a service in which games and their media are both digital, which is available through gaming platforms and is related to ongoing streaming. In this case, we consider games to be software. This software can be continually updated and thus complements the user's experience (Kucheza Gaming, 2019). Offering games as a service is related to the tech evolution of the video game industry, as well as to the development of so-called "cloud gaming services." These services have emerged with increasing broadband internet speeds and the widespread use of smartphones (Cai, Chen, & Leung, 2014).¹

Offering games as a physical product and as a digital service is a prerequisite for various business models.

Complexity

Audiovisual content is a unique and heterogeneous good with a great deal of diversity and diversification.

- *Genre diversity* in the film industry and video games, as well as in specific television formats: According to Torre, the taxonomy of genres in the audiovisual industry is a work in progress (Torre, 2014). The emergence of multi-platform media enterprises, and the convergence and hybrid business models and crossover distribution channels, support such a thesis.
- *Technological diversity*: According to the type of content creation, there are analogue or digital goods; according to the device for using the video games, there are PC, console, handheld-based, or mobile; and according to their distribution channels, there are cable, satellite, IPTV, and more.
- *Diversification according to ownership*: In the case of the television industry, there are private broadcasters and public broadcasters.
- *According to their consumption model*: In the case of the television industry, there are free services, subscriptions, and OTT.

¹ In 2020 the global smartphone penetration rate is projected to be 44.9 percent. (O'Dea, 2020). The average global broadband speeds for 2020 more than doubled year on year to 24.83 Mbps. (Hawdle & Ashton, 2020).

- *According to their business- and revenue models*, in the case of the television industry—a mixed economy in a two-sided market—companies finance their activities through advertising, public subsidies or subscription contracts (as well as pay television, VOD, OTT).

The film industry has a specific place in the European audiovisual industry, with its status of "cultural exception" in the EU (i.e. it is an industry with cultural, political, and social dimensions). Cinema is a highly syncretic art form uniting creative expressions from almost all cultural areas. Film production is a complex process carried out over 2–2.5 years. Films are among the most capital-intensive and expensive cultural products. From the original idea to the film showing, film production involves a wide range of authors in value creation. The insecure market return from the final product also defines the film sector as very risky, with high transaction costs due to the product specifics (Tomova, 2014).

Economies of scale are very important in the audiovisual sector and catalyse convergence processes. That is why the horizontal and vertical integration of key players in the business and value chains give the sector serious competitive advantages. “[The] development of a blockbuster is like the detection of oil. Like in the petroleum business, in the media industry as well the trend is that these companies that include the whole cycle from production to distribution have an advantage” (Doyle 2002:4-5).

Digitisation and convergence have led to the emergence of hybrid business models and iridescent value chains between cinema, television, multimedia and games, and telecommunication companies and internet suppliers.

The **multi-platform companies** (e.g. GAFA: Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon) have substantially transformed the audiovisual industries. Large platforms develop multi-platform ecosystems. Through control over the entire system, they capture value, which is not necessarily their ownership but for which they provide the medium for exchange. The structures of the business models also change and become more complex. They contain the linear production chains on the one hand and the platform networks for transfer of value, resources, and users on the other.

In these complex models, value is exchanged between different applications, and the creation of audiovisual content is no longer a core activity but one of the many. The main purpose and resource are the users. The audiences that watch films, play games, and stream video applications are encouraged to consume (as well as to bank, to insure, etc.) thousands of other products and services from the applications available on the platform ecosystem.

In these multi-platform ecosystems, which are at the same time intermediaries and gatekeepers, cinema, television, and games have a dual structure. In addition to the linear structure of their production, they become part of the structure of the larger platform enterprise (production, financial, marketing, or consumption).

Historically, in the audiovisual sector, **video games** have become increasingly complex thanks to fast technological progress. This complexity is related to the addition of more and more structural elements in the games (audio and video elements, artificial intelligence, etc.). It relates to the development of storytelling and the creation of ever-larger virtual worlds, in which players can be

immersed and amplify their experience. The complexity features as many elements of the games' value chains and the diversity of forms of work in the industry, which we have mentioned above. Darley (2000) defines a game as a specific purpose activity that takes place in a microworld controlled by relatively simple and coherent norms. According to Levis (1997), the game is situated in a computer environment and follows pre-programmed rules. The creation of such a microworld implies the unity of multiple elements (sound, video, animation, history, software code), arranged according to certain rules in a logical connection, to contribute to the experience that engages the player. In one of the first empirical studies of the psychostructural characteristics of video games, Wood et al. analysed twelve structural elements: sound, graphics, background and setting, game duration, play rate, advancement rate, use of humour, game dynamics, winning and losing features, character development, brand assurance, and multiplayer features (Wood, Griffiths, Chappell, & Davies, 2004).

The structural characteristics of video games are focused on the possible addiction of players and the psychological effects that new technologies create: social characteristics, manipulation or control, narrative or identity, reward and punishment, and presentation. Social characteristics encompass functions that allow communication and relationship building, including comparison with other players through different rankings (King, Delfabbro, & Griffiths, 2009).

The genre diversity of games confirms the strong differentiation of this product. The genres focus on how the game is built as a story: on the components and patterns of the game design. That is why a player is offered a specific experience in the game. Meanwhile, some genres are highly standardized and have their conventions of strictly defined functions, while others give much more freedom and are more open (Cășvean, 2015). The following main genres of games are listed in MobyGames' famous dictionary: action; adventure; educational; racing or driving; role-playing games (RPGs); simulation; sports; strategy; compilation; DLC or add-on; puzzle; and special edition (Moby Games, 2000). Often these genres can be mixed and successfully blended into each other within a game.

The complexity of the games is related to their structural characteristics, to the intertwining of many elements (like history, music, painting, animation technology, psychological typology), and to the genres of the games. Each genre has its own set of rules on which it is based, which suggests that the development of some games is harder than others when it comes to division by this criterion.

Positioning in the final markets

Audiovisual industry products, while unique and heterogeneous, are products for mass consumption. There is a general trend towards mainstream appeal, in order to reduce the risk of high investment costs. There are non-homogeneous products with increasingly homogeneous content: a series of blockbusters with common characters, prequels, adaptations of winning stories and characters for film, television, games and multimedia, and the invasion of the "infotainment" form.

With digitalization, the competition expands beyond national boundaries. For example, a national television (public television operator) is part of a global competition. For instance, competition based on quality leads to additional extras for the customer. The price acquires strength depending on the specific form of national competition (monopolistic, monopoly, oligopoly).

The creation of mainstream content is an important survival strategy for the television market. These markets are characterised by oversupply and increasing internal competition and by plenty of content, combined with scarce attention to the audience (Goodman, 2004). Therefore, the role of marketing and advertising is very important: to get product visibility and to attract the over-satisfied audience.

In this oversaturated television market, all television operators compete for the audience's attention (measured by rating of transmissions), which subsequently translates into increased interest by advertisers as measured by income from advertisements for each television operator. Measuring the audience's demand is not straightforward, as in ticket sales, because it measures the time and the attention paid by television spectators on the transmission (Tomova, 2019).

The pursuit of sustainability through growing advertising revenues is an additional catalyst for content homogenization. According to Goodman, in this situation 1) expectations of public media rise and 2) the "voice of the audience" becomes more important for niche television, but the audience becomes more stratified, which leads to decreasing advertising revenues. The latter requires from television channels to "re-package their success, in order to gain larger audiences" (Goodman, 2004).

The security of the homogenized product, which Goodman refers to as the escape from "programming gambling," attracts advertisers but leads to homogenization of the entire television programme. This is how the unpredictability of public attention could lead to conformist culture (Goodman, 2004).

The main measurement of quality for media products is the ratings of the media and its separate transmissions. Chronic financial deficit influences the quality of public television products. The issue of the quality-to-rating ratio has led European public television operators to issue a joint statement advocating for communications beyond profits, for media that work as public goods, and for programmes directly engaging with democracy, audience development, and society. These are the "new horizons for European media" defined in the Declaration of the European Public Broadcasters (Tomova, 2019).

The situation in the **film industry** is as complex. The films in the top-30 chart of views and box office sales, are commercial, high-tech (3D), and low-risk in terms of original ideas. Half (15 in 2011) of top box office films are based on sequels and non-original scripts. The majority of them are produced by Hollywood studios (Tomova, 2014). "This brave new globalised world has its complications, of course. As studios grow ever more reliant on international sales and merchandising, they pour more and more of their resources into superhero and science-fiction blockbusters" (Barber, 2016).

We are seeing more often **video game** characters being involved in Hollywood plots. Video games are mass products that rely on economies of scale for their market survival. Although genres targeting certain players looking for a particular game genre, the goal of the developers is to reach the maximum number of users so that they can better monetize their game. "A successful game is considered if more than 250,000 copies are sold worldwide" (Bonev, 2006). Nevertheless, for most winning games, there are millions of users (copies sold).

At a time when game creation is becoming more widespread due to increasing numbers of independent developers and new technologies, competition in the market focuses mainly on content rather than competition between sub-markets. Games that manage to attract and retain consumer attention for longer are the key to success in the industry. While discussing the previous generation of consoles, Robert M. Grant even pointed out that "the success of PS3 will depend on the appeal of the games developed for it" (Grant, 2008).

In the last few years, the competition in content (history, graphics, technologies used) has intensified due to the growing number of online game streaming platforms, cloud storage platforms, and others. They offer large catalogues of video games for users to choose from. Moreover, players are looking for games that are interesting, enjoyable, and engaging. This commitment can motivate the user to make transactions and buy additional elements in the game, new parts of it, or merchandise.

That is why creating a sophisticated and engaging story within the game is becoming an increasingly important strategy for player engagement. In this race, two opposing approaches to market success emerge: successful games are created by purchasing a franchise license (a story or element of another game, television series, movie character) or by cannibalizing a plot or character that simultaneously appears on the same market as a cheaper similar game, but in a different medium, for example, for consoles instead of smartphones.

This content competition is observed both on platforms, such as Steam and Stadia, and on consoles, which usually advertise themselves using the titles they offer. The focus is not on their hardware side but on their new software. In this regard, in 2020, before the premiere of the PlayStation 5, Sony organised several events at which it presented the new games that its console would support (Kaser, 2020).

In summary, we can outline two trends:

- cloud games, which provide a technological opportunity for the simultaneous participation of a large number of users in immense and increasingly complex worlds, and
- niche genres with strong specialisation (Zarzecki, 2015).

In an environment of oversupply, both directions of development have their futures.

Ability to travel across borders

Audiovisual services, thanks to their digital form, have no direct restrictions on distribution abroad. Globalization reinforces this opportunity, and they become part of the global market. Possible barriers are language, intellectual property, and oligopoly markets. News are often restricted to local/regional areas, due to the news value of "geographic and cultural proximity."

Two important questions arise about the future of **public broadcasters in Europe**:

- Public broadcasters are not commercial; however, the national television markets are not geographically limited to the spectators in terms of content access. Public broadcasters are challenged by national and global competition in television content. They are weak players on the global broadcasting market, both financially and because of their public mission; nevertheless, they are expected to provide content that is not infotainment, which predetermines their lower ratings.
- The market of television content produced by public national broadcasters, competes directly with non-linear media contents (e.g. VOD) on the national market. They must also compete with the largest global content providers and rights holders, such as Netflix and HBO (SVoD), which are accessible via subscription, as well as OTT (Tomova, 2019).

The European public broadcasters are crucial elements of the audiovisual sector, but they are in a difficult market situation defined by limited funding, strong global competition, and increasing direct competition with non-linear content suppliers (such as world streaming platforms, multiplatform media companies, etc.).

The United States **film industry** is benefiting the most from global distribution opportunities. Most of their box office income is from outside the USA. The North American market is far ahead in this, compared to many other markets (Statista). In 2019, the box office income in USA and Canada amounted to USD 11.4 billion. “According to recent figures from the Motion Picture Association of America (MPAA) almost 70 per cent of the studios’ annual revenue from box office now comes from international markets. As global cinema audiences grow, their appetite for US movies is having a profound effect on the way that Hollywood films are being made” (Brook, 2014).

Other authors confirm the aggressive approaches of the Hollywood studios, and their global production chains have been well settled in Europe. “Based on these EAO figures, European films represent 2.35% of the box office in the United States/Canada and 1.2% in China. That year, American films took 63% of the total box office in Europe ...These results show that the impact of European films has been marginal on the American film market and even weaker in China. This is in contrast to the predominant American films in the European marketplace” (Richeri, 2016).

The European countries are trying to counter the US film invasion through protectionist policies and support for co-productions. China uses a different approach: they allow only 34 US films per year on the Chinese market (ibid).

The European Audiovisual Observatory study compared the commercial circulation and shows of European co-productions, for single-national films within and outside the respective national markets (EAO, 2014). The study found that

- a) co-productions cover twice as many markets (in average), compared to single-national films;
- b) co-productions have, on average, 2.8 times higher box office income, compared to single-national films; and
- c) international turnover is larger for co-productions, compared to national productions; hence, the international markets provide 41% of co-production revenues, compared to 15% for

national productions. In the global production networks for **video games**, we do not observe such centralised geographic hegemony. The distribution of video games is not strictly regulated globally, and the fact that the product is digital makes its ability to cross geographical boundaries even easier. The restrictions facing these types of services and products are related to access and the ability to own hardware such as smartphones, consoles, personal computers, and televisions. In this sense, the product is highly dependent on the hardware on which it can operate and the availability of services such as broadband internet (when it comes to console games, cloud games, and streaming). The third factor is the purchasing power of the population excluding the business model that involves offering free games through the "freemium" model.

The European Union has taken care to remove borders in digital content. In 2017, it introduced new rules allowing Europeans to use all their digital subscription services when traveling to another Member State of the bloc in the same way as they use it at home. Previously, access had been blocked in many cases when users travelled abroad (European Parliament, 2018).

Regulatory regime is a possible barrier and a limitation to free movement.

As mentioned before, regulatory video games are most affected in China. Beijing's censorship poses significant challenges to developers because

- the access of some games in the Chinese market is restricted because they do not meet the conditions of the censor, and
- developers are forced to make changes in the offered product or service to meet these conditions if they want to gain access to the market.

The Chinese market allows strictly defined products and closely monitors their content and messages. In this case, the regulatory regime is a barrier for many, who are unable to cross digital and geographical boundaries.

Every year, the European Education, Audiovisual, and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA) financially supports European game developers. Their assistance is aimed at those who offer original and innovative ideas that have high creative value and cultural diversity and are related to cultural identity and heritage. Also, projects are being sought that have a greater chance of being realized abroad and reaching international markets (Education, Audiovisual, and Culture Executive Agency, 2020). The main goal of such programs is to encourage the development of innovative products that distinguish the continent and have the potential to reach the general public.

Meanwhile, the enormous challenges posed by the new coronavirus crisis have motivated many countries to support their game developers. One of the brightest European examples of this is Italy. In May 2020, the Italian association of the video gaming industry, IIDEA, created the First Playable Fund as part of the Relaunch Decree approved on 13 May. The measure aimed to support the financing of video game prototypes and the industry at the national level (IIDEA, 2020).

Such programs aimed to maintain the momentum gained in the industry and to support the creation of local products that have international development potential.

In the pandemic, governments in Europe and worldwide are showing a willingness to support the development of gaming products because they see them as having economic, cultural, and social potential.

Technological development

The **video game industry** would not exist if not for technology because games are technological developments: software that uses some hardware. That is why we can say that technological development is at the heart of gaming, and innovation in this area is crucial for companies operating in this sector.

The list of technologies that have stimulated the evolution of the gaming industry is immense. Let's focus on the main ones.

Table 3: Technologies that have helped the development of the gaming industry

Technology	Nature	Affects
Hardware/devices	Smartphones, tablets, screens, consoles, video cards, audio speakers, personal computers, laptops	All types of games
Network technologies	2G, 3G, 4G, 5G networks	All types of games
Graphics/2D/3D Design	Improve the images, characters, and atmosphere throughout the game	All types of games
Virtual reality/ augmented reality / mixed reality	New technologies for immersive experience	Console games, PC games, and mobile games
Streaming	Fast data transfer	E-sports, PC games, console games
Cloud services	Data storage on remote servers which are not owned by the user	All types of games
Artificial intelligence /machine learning	Analysis of the environment and developing different scenarios	All types of games
Online platforms	App stores, streaming platforms, game stores	All types of games
Face recognition	Individual player recognition and game customization	All types of games
Gesture control	Game control by gestures	Console and mobile games

Source: Based on the article "How has technology changed the gaming industry"? in *European Business Review* (EBR, 2020).

The importance of technology R&D

When talking about GPN's, Ernst emphasises the role of research and development (R&D) in the network, referring to the transfer of technology and knowledge (Ernst, 2002). The gaming industry has always been highly dependent on tech innovation, which is why R&D is so important.

Greater investments in research and development also mean more in-house knowledge that can be passed on to the network and used as a competitive advantage.

The major gaming companies invest more than others in R&D. As a result, they respond more quickly to changes in consumer demand and perform better than their competitors, including smaller independent companies. Around 35 percent of the total expenditures of Electronic Arts (EA), one of the biggest gaming companies in the world, go towards R&D. According to Forbes, the figure is higher than that of companies like Activision Blizzard and Zynga (Trefis Team, 2019).

In addition, enhanced R&D means that gaming companies have more control over their products and that they are the copyright owners. This means that they can increase their profit margins.

While small indie companies cannot invest as much in R&D, large studios rely on R&D processes that are often territorially dispersed. Nintendo, for example, has several hardware and software development units in its home market. The Nintendo Kyoto Research Institute and the Nintendo Kyoto Development Complex are based in Kyoto, Japan. At the same time, the company has an R&D unit in Europe: Nintendo European Research and Development, based in Paris, France. These units work with different talents from many countries and constantly exchange knowledge, research, and expertise. This helps companies to cultivate powerful ecosystems.

1.1.2 Labour in audiovisual industries

This section of the report aims to give an overview of the specificities of work and labour conditions at the different stages of the film and audiovisual production cycle in the audiovisual and media industries, as well as in games. It also examines the socio-economic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on employment and working conditions in these sectors across Europe.

Labour in the film industry, television, and radio

The rapid growth of audiovisual media markets in the past decade has led to increased employment opportunities in the field of audiovisual media and film production. In 2020, the EU27 has employed 7.2 million people (3.6 % of the total employment in the EU) (Eurostat 2020). According to GESAC, the audiovisual industries were the third largest CCI employer, with 1.122 million employees in EU28 (before Brexit) (GESAC, 2021). Statistical data mapping in Bulgaria between 2008 and 2018 has shown a 2.5-fold increase in the number of companies in the film industry (from 460 to 1,025), whereas the added value almost tripled for the same period and the FDI increased 1.5 times. (Bulgarian National Statistics & OCE, 2021).

The technological shift to digital media and the convergence of digital media platforms have changed the global production networks, covering partly or entirely their value chains (from creation to exposure and archiving). These market transformations have also led to the geographical redistribution of the networks and to shifts in employment patterns.

The audiovisual and media industries in EU27 employ a total workforce of 580,000. More than a half of these workers are employed in only three Member States: in Germany (22%), France (22%), and Spain (11%). More than half of the EU27 workforce is found in these three Member States.

The predominant types of employers in the audiovisual industries are small enterprises (96% of the European companies in the audiovisual sector) with fewer than 10 employees, but these employ 28% of the European sectoral workforce. On the other hand, the larger companies (with 50 to 249 employees) represent about 0.5% of all employers but employ about 36% of the total workforce (Eurostat, Structural Business Statistics 2017).

The sector has a younger workforce than the European average. According to Carta et al. (2016), 59% of the workers in the audiovisual sector were aged between 25 and 44, compared with 48% of workers in the whole economy. The sector is also characterised by a highly educated workforce and by a variety of artistic, technical, and administrative functions (Creative Skills Europe, 2016).

The employment trends in these sectors show a shift from typical employment contracts with fixed, full-time hours, towards “atypical” ones² (Carta et al. 2016). Atypical employment includes part-time work or temporary employment, fixed-term or agency contracts, and other flexible work types (EurWORK). Self-employment, in turn, can be differentiated into two subcategories: self-employed workers without employees (i.e. own-account workers) and self-employed workers with employees. Some of these work contracts exist at the boundaries between labour law and commercial or civil law, which makes these types of work relations difficult to trace in national statistics. They also “lead to the growing concerns amongst unions that workers in this area do not have adequate social and labour protection and end up in precarious work” (Carta et al. 2016). **Temporary work contracts** are very typical for the film industry, where the creation and production phases involve the largest number of creative and technical crews. For example, in Bulgaria (where CASE 1 comes from), the largest number of temporary employed people is in film and television production and increased from 700 in 2008 to 2,500 in 2018.³ Employment in film production almost tripled between 2008 and 2018, (from 1,841 to 5,107). Temporary employment in the film industry in Bulgaria nearly tripled, from 1,493 in 2008 to 4,369 in 2018 (OCE statistical mapping).

Self-employment in the audiovisual industries can be differentiated into two subcategories: self-employed workers without employees (i.e. own-account workers) and self-employed workers with employees:

Across the EU, one third (33 %) of the cultural workforce was self-employed in 2020,

² Carta et al., Analysis of the EU audiovisual sector labour market and of changing forms of employment and work arrangements 2016

³ Source, Observatory of Cultural Economics mapping of statistical data for cultural and creative sectors in Bulgaria.

compared with an average of 14 % for the whole economy (see Figure 7); as such, the relative weight of self-employment in the field of culture was more than twice as high as the average for total employment. (Eurostat 2020)

The largest share of self-employed people seems in the EU seems to be in film and motion picture, video, and television programme production (NACE 59), while television presenters, journalists, and crew employed by the main television and radio broadcasters (NACE 60) are more likely to enjoy full-time and permanent contracts.

As the International Labour Organisation (ILO) pointed out, “Regardless [of] the increased employment opportunities in these industries, the sector has a long tradition of insecure work, characterised by unclear contractual arrangements and questions over the employment status of its workforce” (ILO 2014).

The global pandemic caused by COVID-19 in 2020 severely impacted the film and audiovisual industries and temporarily paused the creation and production phases. Thus, it exacerbated the already-precarious situation of creative labour in the field. According to Eurostat data published in 2021, in the first pandemic year (2020), the cultural employment in the EU decreased by 195,000 persons, registering a fall of 2.6%, in comparison with 2019. The highest decreases were observed in the sectors of “creative, arts and entertainment activities” (NACE 90) and “Motion Picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities” (NACE 59).⁴ The mapping of the prolonged unemployment due to the pandemic, carried out by different organisations, has found discrepancies how official statistics in different EU countries count self-employed workers. There are also different national inventories and registers for creative and cultural workers. In some countries, they count as enterprises (SMEs) or as self-employed individuals; it is also not easy to trace the multiple jobs that professionals in this field take at the different network phases: from creation and production, through acting, teaching, research, publishing, and more. Even before the pandemic, the data by FERA showed that creative authors in audiovisual industries could hardly survive on their audiovisual work only and that over 60% of them have other jobs, while about 75% of them feel financially insecure (FERA 2019).

The pandemic’s unprecedented restrictions on the entire creative sector have exacerbated the already-insecure situation of the creative workers, revealing enormous gaps in national and European labour legislation, the status of freelancers, self-employment, and social security schemes.

The issues have arrived at the top political level, accelerating progress towards a European Status for self-employed cultural professionals.

Labour conditions in the GPN phases in audiovisual industries

Temporary contracts and self-employment (with or without employees) are typical for film production networks, and ILO confirmed these trends in the audiovisual and media sectors:

⁴https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Culture_statistics_cultural_employment#Cultural_employment_.E2.80.94_overall_developments

There is a trend towards freelance, self-employed or informal economy work. This can mean that such [media and culture] workers can no longer depend on legislative provisions on social security, even in countries where social security has good coverage. (ILO 2014)

The film production market in Europe is dominated by small and micro companies. The independent film production companies have a limited number of permanent employees and operate through a complex of different professions at the different production stages. The producer, in the case of KLAS Film (Bulgaria), is at the core of the production network, and concentrates both the creative and the managerial decision-making power about the film project. The producer contracts the professionals for all the roles and positions for the project to be achieved.

At the **creation** phase, the creative idea is at the core; there, the personal driver is the producer, who is in the centre of the chain and has control over contracting all the other suppliers and participants. The producer has both the creative skills and the knowledge to recruit the film director and the script writer, as well as to make key decisions. Creative authors' work is crucial at this phase, mostly in creating their copyrighted content for the idea, script, and director's concept. The **median profile of the authors in audiovisual industry**, as defined by the FERA study (2019), is a 46-year-old, male with a master's degree and about 16 years of professional experience in the field. Eighty-five percent of these authors work as freelancers (FERA, 2019).

The authors in the audiovisual industries in Europe generally have two main sources of income:

upfront payments at contract signature [...] that can include their work in creation, payment for the transfer of rights to contractual counterpart, advance payment or buy-out for share of future exploitation revenues; and, secondly, subsequent secondary payments for repeat screenings of the work (e.g., share of exploitation revenues), and compensation for copyright exceptions. (FERA, FSE, 2019)

The secondary sources of income stem from the collectively administered rights to receive remuneration from cable retransmission (Directive 93/83/EEC) and private copying in countries where such levies exist. In different countries, there are also other secondary rights, managed by the respective collecting societies, that could bring additional important payments to the authors (e.g. in television broadcasting, from on-demand uses, video sales, rental and public lending, educational uses, etc.) (FERA, FSE, 2019). Depending on how successful their audiovisual works have been over the years, the secondary payments could be continuous and substantial for the authors. However, creators in these industries function in a rather unstable financial environment and are dependent on a mix of funding sources and regulations, both nationally and at the European level.

Significant amounts of unpaid work are usual for creative workers in the film and audiovisual industries, especially during the creation and preparation (the first stage of production) phases. Thirty-eight percent of directors interviewed in the FERA study indicated that they did not receive remunerations for project development they undertook in 2016, and 36% were only sometimes remunerated, leaving only 26% who always received payment for project development. Sixty-five

percent of directors did not receive remunerations for promotional work (FERA 2019).

In the production stage of the audiovisual network, a variety of skills and professions is involved. Apart from the creative workers—including the director, cinematographer, designers of costumes, light designers, stage designers, and composers—there are a great deal of technical skills and professions involved.

Technological progress and the transformation from analogue to digital technologies in audiovisual industries has led to demand for new skills, which has increased the need for the professional training and qualification of audiovisual workers. Such new skills include the management of cybersecurity, mobile, and cloud computing; knowledge of big data analytics; innovative usage of social media for reaching audiences; developing new business models; management of intellectual property rights; and knowledge about green and sustainable operations. Those developments have impacted almost all technical and support occupations in the audiovisual sector (Tepper D, 2016).⁵

The digital environment has not only transformed production and distribution channels it has also offered a renewed importance to content creation. It has brought the creative and cultural sectors back into the heart of our economies and societies, dependent more than ever on its innovative capacities. (Creative Skills Europe, 2016)

In the **distribution** phase, the key roles include the film distributors, sales agents, and festival programmers, while key roles in successful distribution and exhibition include professional critics and reviewers, mostly at international levels, who give ratings or influence public opinion.

The process of **archiving** audiovisual content comprises very specific skills and competencies in the classification, inventory, storage, and digitisation of specific materials. They also include in-depth knowledge of audiovisual history and archives. While today most audiovisual output is digitised, the role of the archivers still implies the careful preservation of the remaining hard copies that carry audiovisual contents from the past.

Table 4: Phases, processes, and job profiles, using the film industry as an example

Phases	Processes	Job Profiles
Creation	Development of the idea; script; director’s book; fund development for creation and production process; distribution contracts (TV rights or other)	producer, writer, director, cinematographer or director of photography, casting company
Production	1 - Preparation 2- Shooting on location 3- Post-production	1- producer, director, director of photography, casting company 2- most diverse professions and skills involved: lighting, sound, wardrobe, makeup, catering,

⁵ Tepper, D. “Creative Skills Europe. Trends and skills in the European audiovisual and live performance sectors”, 2016

		stunts, props, producer, director, cinematographer, tech teams
Distribution	Distribution	distributors, film reviewers, social media, sales agents, festival organisers
Exchange	Presentation, promotion at film venues, festivals; screenings in cinemas; festival screenings; usage via digital platforms	film programmers, sales agents, festivals; platforms, streaming, VOD, pay television, etc.
Archiving	Re-selling digital platforms; art assets; digital copies	Film archives, national television and film libraries; digital platforms

Trade Unions and Professional Associations

Audiovisual industries, and film production in particular, use a highly skilled and specialised workforce. The working conditions, the difficult market sustainability of small businesses, and the fact that a film product is as much an industry as it is a culture, have led to the emergence of multiple unions and professional support organisations in the film industry. These organisations are important stakeholders in the overall ecosystem of Europe's audiovisual sector and influence the market and labour policies, shaping the cost of labour in the sector, creating influence with scarce resources in negotiations, influencing through petitions, conducting market studies, and lobbying for EU decision-making.

There is a strong history of international industrial relations in the audiovisual sector, going back to the 1950s and 1960s, and there are numerous social partners that represent the audiovisual industries' workers and employers.

Table 5: Organisations represented in the audiovisual ESSDC

Representing works	Representing employers
UNI Europa – Media, Entertainments & Arts (EURO-MEI)	Association of Commercial Television in Europe (ACT)
European Federation of Journalists (EFJ)	International Federation of Film Producers' Associations (FIAPF)
International Federation of Musicians (FIM)	European Audiovisual Production Association (CEPI)
International Federation of Actors (FIA)	European Broadcasting Union (EBU)

Source: Representativeness of the European social partner organisations: audiovisual sector p. 1

Unions and social partners exist in most of the countries, and the aforementioned study has identified 155 sector-related trade unions in EU 27 and about 70 employers' organisations which operate in the field.⁶

Collective bargaining is common in the field, albeit with different amplitudes in different countries. It could take place on either the organisation or employer's level or on the sectoral level. Sectoral bargaining tends to be more widespread in the Northern and some Western European countries, whereas in Eastern European countries and the United Kingdom, for instance, organisational- or company-level bargaining is more widespread. Collective bargaining, however, does not cover the self-employed, including young professionals and women, which makes them more vulnerable on the labour market (Carta et al. 2016). The great divergence in how creative employment is organised at the national level raises the urgency of better EU regulation of labour in this field. Transnational film and audiovisual co-productions have become vital for the European film industry, for example, by bringing to light the diverse fees and payment rates across the Union for highly specialised and professional skills and competencies. Hence, a number of creative workers' networks, unions, and alliances are advocating at the EU level to achieve fairer and more equal labour conditions for transnational work by artists and cultural professionals.

These organisations have the behaviour and power of stakeholders in the film industry and the creative sector of Europe: they represent the entire value chain and participate in the creation of sectoral regulations and other European initiatives.

Diversity and inclusion, gender profile, and balance

The Eurostat data shows that there were more males than females employed in the audiovisual sector in 2013 (EAO). The gender gap seems to have increased slightly ever since. Some fluctuation in the gender balance could be explained by the dynamics of the market and also by cuts to public funds (specifically for subsidised film sectors and for broadcasters).

The latest "European study on the remuneration of audiovisual authors" (2019) looks specifically into the gender distribution and equal pay of the authors involved in production (directors, screenwriters, or others). It found a persisting discrepancy between the payment of male and female authors in the field, which also extends across the different network phases.

To improve gender equality and diversity in the audiovisual sector, some guidelines and frameworks have been developed (e.g. the *Good Practice Handbook* by the social partners of the EU Audiovisual social dialogue committee.)⁷

Training and Education

The audiovisual sector employs mostly highly educated and specialised workers in most of its phases. For creative authors, including directors, screenwriters, and others, over 80% have a university degree

⁶ Representativeness of the European social partner organisations: Audiovisual sector, p. 28.

⁷ Tepper, D. ed. Achieving gender equality and promoting diversity in the European Audiovisual sector

in a discipline related to the audiovisual area, such as directing, cinematography, media or television-related disciplines, screenwriting, producing, editing, and others. Over 40% of directors have a master's degree or higher (FERA 2019).

All creative authors acquire the additional training or skill development needed in a competitive and temporary-employment-dominated market marked by technological transformation. However, as most of the workers in these industries are self-employed (as well as atypical in many countries), very few of them could access paid lifelong professional training, for which they must pay. Training programmes are more common for public sector audiovisual companies (Carta et al. 2016).

Labour in gaming industries

At each stage of the gaming industry GPN, there is a need for different skills, requiring collaboration between people with different professional profiles. Games are seen as a form cultural expression based on specific skills or crafts (Anthropy, 2012). This means that developing a game requires not only technical skills but also the craftsmanship to invent and build new digital characters and imagery involved in different stories (Flanagan, 2009, Westecott, 2013).

The gaming industry operates through a complex of different professions, from creative activities to engineering and design. This creates the need for better-qualified gaming project managers and for the development of soft skills among the teams that must collaborate with each other.

Historically, the development of the gaming industry and the emergence of new types of games have also led to changes in occupations in this sector and created needs for the development of new skills, as for example in mobile gaming. Although mobile gaming has a much shorter value chain, it is closely linked to the emergence of new digital platforms with which the industry players must be able to work. In this case, the designers and programmers work together on a game but are highly specialised in the field of mobile applications, due to the different infrastructures on which the game is based.

Creation

Professional diversity is most evident in the first phase, the creation of the game. Table 1 shows that the development of a more complex game (PC or console title) involves experts in at least 10 professional fields. In Europe, as well as worldwide, when a major studio develops a game, the person who creates its story and the script is at the beginning of the process of creating that software product. Their expertise is in storytelling through that specific medium. The foundation of the game is its software code, which is written by software developers and game programmers. The designers, visual artists, and animators have the task of creating the digital images that are to be seen on the screen by the end user—the gamer. At this stage, there is a strong intermingling of creative individuals and people with technological expertise. In the creation process, there are technical experts, who monitor the quality of the product and look for gaps in the software code, and there are game testers, who play the game prior to its market release to identify weaknesses and potential bugs. Before that, composers and musicians create the game's musical environment, and audio designers also join the

sound team.⁸ Critical players in this phase include the managers of the individual teams and of the entire project, who must work with a large number of staff with different expertise.

Production

After the development of the complete software product, which is the most complex stage in the gaming industry, the game is released. This is the point at which software and hardware are combined, which requires staff with highly technical profiles in programming.

Distribution

In the distribution phase, the focus on marketing and sales, and hence the role of marketing and social media experts, is most important, regardless the type of game. In distribution, the differences in expertise between game types are very clear. For mobile games, this phase includes employees who manage uploading the game to the app stores. For cloud-based PC and console games, there are similar experts who make sure the game appears on the online platform for which it was developed. In the case of physical-copy sales, traditional sales experts are needed to liaise with the retail industry or manage online sales through the company's stores. If the game is sold on hard copies, the distribution company also works with logistics experts regionally, nationally, and internationally.

Table 6 Phases, Processes, and Job Profiles

Phases	Processes	Job Profiles
Creation	Development - idea, software development, storytelling	Storytellers/scriptwriters Project managers Producers Visual artists/animators Software developers and game programmers Quality assurance experts Game designers Composers/musicians Audio engineers Interpreters and translators Game testers
Production	Publishing: combining software and hardware	Developers/dev-ops IT experts
Distribution	Sales and marketing in digital environment: different platforms and social networks	Marketing experts Social media experts Sales representatives Logistics experts
Exchange	Transmission: audience feedback, alpha and beta versions	Technical/customer support specialists Customer experience specialists

⁸ Rosenberg McKay, D. "Jobs in Video Games Industry" (2019) last visited 22-04-2022 ([link](#))

Archiving	Development of video game emulators; re-selling digital platforms; art assets; digital copies	Developers Logistics experts
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Exchange

At this phase, we observe a concentration of personnel with technical skills. While users give their feedback on the game, their requests and comments are taken up by experts in technical and customer support. This information is collected, stored, and passed on to the development phase team in order to resolve any issues identified. At this stage, the focus is on the users' experience and how to improve it so that users are continuously engaged with the game.

Archiving

The process of archiving, backing up, and storing games involves logistics experts, when involving preserving physical copies, as well as IT experts and developers of emulators. Many people who have worked in the film industry—mostly playwrights and animators or designers—are employed in the gaming industry, which has led to a confluence of value between these two industries. In this respect, Europe has benefited greatly from the well-developed film industries of France, Germany, and the UK.

Required skills

The diversity of job positions in the gaming industry implies a demand for different skills in the workforce.

Technically oriented employees focus on ICT skills and on those related to the use of specific programmes and platforms, such as GDevelop, Unreal Engine, BuildBox, and Unity. At the same time, they need to know programming languages such as C# and C++. Creative positions require skills in design and animation, character design, scenery design, and user interface design. For this, they must be skilled in working on various computer softwares such as Photoshop and InDesign.

Project managers and individual teams need management skills. Their focus is on managerial functions and on so-called soft skills including emotional intelligence, adaptability, teamwork skills, work ethics, and active listening. Experts in marketing and sales must develop strong analytical capacities but also have knowledge of market trends. The main tools they handle are online sales platforms and social networks, such as Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, and Snapchat.

Employees dealing with the distribution of physical copies and with archiving need logistical skills.

Prejudices and beliefs

The conditions mentioned in subsection (b)—under which the gaming industry was born in South Korea, and to some extent in Europe via PCs and internet cafes—still largely affect the way the industry is perceived around the world. Gaming is still seen as a youth-oriented product serving an underground culture (Molesworth and Watkins, 2014). Although it has already proven its economic potential, the industry faces stigmas and myths that make jobs in this market seem less attractive compared to those in the IT industry, for example. First and foremost, gaming is seen as a masculine

and boyish entertainment liked by a small number of women (Ensmenger, 2015). This in turn affects the diversity of the workforce in gaming companies.

The myth that gaming is a hobby for the immature continues to affect the market. At the same time, gaming is associated with specific types of games (action, shooters, warfare), although the variety of genres is much greater. This implies that the personnel in this market must advocate for better justification and credibility for their work to prove their talent and justify the real added cultural, social, and economic value of their professional achievements (Styhre, Szczepanska, Remneland-Wikhamn, 2018).

Racism and sexism

Several trends make positions in the gaming industry less attractive to recruiters and cause them concern. According to the International Game Developers Association's (IGDA) 2019 developer survey, a large proportion of respondents believe that the industry's negative image is due to sexism (72%) and racism (55%). Fifty-four percent believe that sexism in the workplace casts a bad light on the entire industry. The same survey showed that 73 percent of developers believe poor working conditions are a factor in the negative perception of the entire industry. However, recent data is promising because it shows that the introduction of anti-discrimination policies is beginning to have a positive impact on the industry.⁹

Crunch

Another reason for the negative image of the job market in gaming is overworking, which is why jobs in the industry are sometimes referred to as "extreme jobs" (Burke, 2009). In the last decade, there has been increasing talk about so-called "crunch time": the excessively long working hours, over and above the usual working hours, that gaming developers have when they need to complete a project. The term is used to refer to project-based work, as seen in games. Teams work intensively for between 40 and 90 hours, instead of the standard 40 hours per week, before a deadline to complete a game (Legault and Westar, 2016). The problem mostly affects those working in phase one, creation.

All of this raises questions and criticisms of the industry's concern for employee mental health and the increasing pressure on them. At the same time, the industry operates with an ultimate goal of keeping players as engaged as possible so that game consumption and game revenues keep increasing. That is why developers often receive last-minute requests to make changes to the software based on players' feedback, after alpha and beta releases. These changes are painful for game developers, who often experience burnout, but they mean more revenue for companies (Samuels, 2019).¹⁰

The pressure on workers is observed not only in the big studios, which are in fierce competition with each other, but also among independent and smaller players as they try to break into a highly competitive, populated, and profit-driven market (Consalvo, 2006; Johns, 2006, Kerr, 2006; Williams, 2002).

⁹ <https://www.pocketgamer.biz/news/72476/igda-developer-satisfaction-survey-2019-results>

¹⁰ <https://time.com/5603329/e3-video-game-creators-union/>

Unionizing

Poor labour market conditions in the gaming industry are the reason for the increasing trade-unionisation of workers. These workers push for more rights and argue that better work-life balance would benefit gaming companies, whose employees would not be exhausted to the extreme, and would lead to game development. Well-known unions in Europe are Game Workers Unite, a grassroots advocacy organisation with unions in the UK and Ireland, and the union of video game workers—Syndicat des Travailleurs du Jeu Vidéo (STJV)—in France (Marx, 2019).¹¹

Workers' demands for greater fairness, flexibility, and an end to crunch time clash with the studios' views. The International Game Developers Association strongly opposes such unions. This clash between studios and workers also makes jobs in the industry, particularly in game development, less attractive (Sinclair, 2018).¹²

These industry trends presuppose a toxic work culture that spans the entire market when it comes to game creation, from the developers of the simplest mobile games to the makers of complex console titles. Unionization is typical for those most directly affected—developers, designers, artists—rather than for marketing, sales, or archiving.

Workplace conditions

Game development is a collective effort that requires many office hours. As long as most employees do not meet with clients, the office environment is much more casual and informal than in other sectors, such as banking. It is common for offices of gaming companies to be well-equipped, with recreational areas including the option to play games for fun, and with sports or socializing. Whether it is a small and independent company or a large studio, the dress code is something out of the ordinary.

When it comes to pay, according to Statista's 2018 data, the median salary in the gaming industry in Western Europe stands at USD 44k and in the UK at USD 40k. By comparison, salaries in the US and Canada are significantly higher at USD 52k and USD 53k, respectively.¹³

Beyond that, employees may receive additional compensation in the form of annual bonuses, completion bonuses, stock options, or profit sharing. The smaller the company, the smaller the benefits may be for its employees.

Given the lack of movement of workers in gaming offices, companies try to encourage employees to live more actively by providing them with free passes to the gym or for other sports, and large studios also have their own sports facilities. Additional packages include medical and dental insurance and pension plans.

Large studios tend to look for new recruits from different company structures around the world, with the possibility of easier transfer from one country to another when filling a specific position. In this

¹¹ <https://onezero.medium.com/toxic-workplaces-are-driving-video-game-developers-to-unionize-cda5c8b73317>

¹² <https://www.gamesindustry.biz/articles/2018-03-28-igda-head-on-the-problem-with-unions>

¹³ Source [Games industry salaries by region 2018 | Statistic | Statista](#)

way, the big players can secure someone who already knows the culture and how the organisation works without having to introduce them to the whole process. For smaller and independent players, this option is almost out of the question, which is more of a negative for both them and for the people who work for them.

Contractors

In 2016, 10 to 15% of the people working in the creative departments of medium and large game development companies were not employed full-time but on a project basis. They are contractors who work for short periods of time under worse conditions than those employed by the company itself (Campbell, 2016). According to Statista, in 2019, 71% of the workforce in the gaming industry was employed in permanent (full- and part-time) positions, and 15% were self-employed. Independent contractors or freelancers accounted for 11% and temporary workers (full- and part-time) for 3%.¹⁴

Higher-end contractors can earn USD 100 an hour while working from home. However, most work for USD 15 an hour and do not enjoy the benefits and protections offered to in-house studio employees. At the same time, many contractors feel undervalued (Campbell, 2016).

Training and Education

The gaming industry requires people with different backgrounds and education and has significant differences between positions. This also indicates different barriers to entry for individuals in the industry.

Video game designers, for example, need to combine creativity, technical skills, and soft skills because they work in teams. For video game programmers, the skills need to be more technical. Hence the differences in the education of different industry representatives. Designers can find a job on the market with only an art school diploma or a certificate in a design course, or more specifically, in game design. For programmers, qualifications are typically much higher and include a university education: a bachelor's degree in game development, computer science, software engineering, or mobile app development. Programmers' jobs require a concise knowledge of various programming languages such as Java and C++.¹⁵

- The education of personnel in the gaming industry combines two elements:

- **Formal Education:** the growing popularity of video games is leading many educational institutions to develop their own curricula in key industry areas such as 3D modelling, character animation, world design, storyboarding, and simulation programming. The state has a role to play here in enhancing and developing specialised educational programmes to support different niches of the gaming market by directing the right people to them.
- **Specialised parts courses and trainings,** online or in-person, focus in a specific subject area, for example, courses for mastering specific programming languages in IT academies

¹⁴ <https://www.polygon.com/features/2016/12/19/13878484/game-industry-worker-misclassification>

¹⁵ Source: <https://work.chron.com/education-training-necessary-game-designer-4875.html>

(SoftUni, Telerik in Bulgaria) or basic online programs on the digital platform for informal online learning (Udemy).

At the same time, there is a spillover of value from other industries. Personnel with expertise in storytelling, design, online distribution, programming, and more are finding places in the gaming business in all parts of the value chain.

Conclusions

Labour in audiovisual industries is highly specialised and atypical. Often people are hired on a project basis, not with full-time employment contracts.

The job market in the gaming industry encompasses many and varied occupations. However, the career path is not always clearly established, and the perception of the industry as creating products for men and adolescents causes many in the industry struggling for recognition. Different cadres face different barriers to entry. For some, only a high school education is enough, while for others, a higher education in a specific niche or a specialised course is required. While in small companies one person can do many things, in large studios the work is clearly distributed and there is more specialisation. In-demand skills range from highly creative skills to technical and engineering, marketing, logistics, and sales skills. Europe is making progress in improving working conditions in the industry. Proof of this is the IGDA survey, which shows that in 2019 the French company Ubisoft as the second most desirable place to work in the gaming industry, with 6% of the vote (IGDA, 2019). It was only surpassed by one of the pioneers in the gaming industry on a global scale, Nintendo (Japan), but beat another popular name, Activision Blizzard (USA).

Despite its many problems, the labour market continues to mature, and more and more women and members of minority groups are finding their place in it (Styhre, Szczepanska, Remneland-Wikhamn, 2018).

1.1.3 Embeddedness in the audiovisual industries

An important feature of the GPN approach is embeddedness (a detailed explanation of the theories on embeddedness can be found at the beginning of this study: Key Elements of the GPN Approach). Here, we examine how network participants influence, and are themselves influenced by, the different types of embeddedness in which they participate.

Embeddedness in film, television, and radio

Embeddedness as a network effect

The activities by the different actors in the audiovisual GPN affect the entire network: the other actors, the final product, the creation and redistribution of value, and the distribution of power in the production network. The CICERONE project adopts the multi-layered approach to embeddedness

proposed by Coe and Yeung (2015), in which societal embeddedness, territorial embeddedness, and network embeddedness are distinguished.

We can assume that embeddedness is a network's effect because the effects multiply across all participants. In addition, some researchers find a dialectical relationship (Henderson et al. 2002) (i.e. two-directional effects in territorial embeddedness). For example, if a particular place or a city attracts capital and labour resources, they have an effect on it. As a result, the economic environment and the quality-of-life changes; thus, the effects of the new investments have multiplied. These investments translate into specific knowledge, innovation, and a growing educational level of the employed, and consequently to different consumer environment forms. In the case of cultural industries, new audiences form.

This is an example of the spillover of different types of local embeddedness effects, but we can hardly say that the positive externalities and welfare created are consequences of territorial embeddedness alone. The *societal embeddedness* of that particular production network also contributes to these effects.

The dialectical relationship, on the other hand, reflects the inverse influences that the particular place, city, and region have on the network. Therefore, the city would change the new labour and capital invested through its institutions and regulatory framework through its history, traditions, and values. Moreover, in doing so, the city or place would add value and also seek and stimulate the recreation of its social values and cultural aesthetics. Indicative of this relationship is the so-called "cultural test," cultural criteria that are mandatory for beneficiaries of most regional film funds in Europe, as well as when applying for tax shelter for a film project.

The key features of embeddedness, which are specific in culture and the audiovisual sector, can be summarised as

- spillovers between the different effects of territorial embeddedness;
- spillovers between the three types of embeddedness (societal, territorial, and network) and
- a dialectical relationship, that is, mutual influence between the specific production network and the specific place (city, region), as well as between the production network and the specific society.

Embeddedness in the film and television industries—key features

The embeddedness of production networks in the audiovisual industries show some different features, which we detected through the case studies described in Part 3 of this report.

- 1) Audiovisual industries have strong political dimensions in addition to their economic and cultural aspects. A prime example is the film industry, which has been used as an ideological and propaganda tool. The history of the Cold War is a sad example in this direction, but also a proof of the role of the past in shaping societies, traditions, and norms.
- 2) Territorial embeddedness in audiovisual industries is not limited to the context of the specific geographic location where the network is positioned. The technical possibility of

unrestricted signal transmission (i.e. broadcasting) removes limits to the territorial embeddedness of a particular television or radio network.

Access to television content is not geographically restricted to viewers of a single country. In this neo-liberal market context, public service media (PSM) face not only national but also global competition in the global television content market. Moreover, commercial broadcasters whose content is mainly infotainment dominate there. The market for television content produced by national PSM also directly competes with non-linear media content such as on-demand delivery. In the television market, content creators and rights holders are often large global players such as Netflix and HBO (SVoD), which are also available without subscription but through OTT-type delivery. Therefore, **territorial embeddedness is not limited to the local geography of product creation; hence, the service is extended along with the retransmission of the signal and the specific television content. Geographical embeddedness extends to those geographical locations where the audiences are.**

- 3) This almost unlimited territorial distribution of audiovisual content is also a *form of societal embeddedness because as content becomes globally accessible, it also shapes global cultural, aesthetic, and moral values*. These values are no longer linked to the traditions of a specific geographical place and society but are supranational. Thus, we are witnessing the formation of global values in a generation of viewers. These can range from innocent fashion trends and musical tastes to destructive aspirations to violence, aggression, and nihilism.

Solutions to these limitless global influences are again sought in societal embeddedness but this time in its national institutional dimensions. An example is the struggle to encompass global multimedia platforms by national and pan-European regulations and institutions.

Societal embeddedness—the institutional context

The film and television industries are characterised by strong legislative regulation at the national and European levels. In the film industry, state support can be obtained on a project basis. The subsidy has the possibility to cover all phases of value creation. The institutional context impacts the production network and is clearly distinguishable at three levels: the European (Eurimages fund, MEDIA programme), national (national film centres), and regional (through regional support funds) levels.

In an institutional and regulatory context, emerging multimedia platforms are a challenge. They not only affect the phases of distribution and display but also have become serious creators of their own content.

Societal embeddedness (through regulation and supportive institutions) is especially needed in the phases that are most financially risky: the creation and the production. In film industry, the co-productions supported by different regional funds obviously influence national or regional labour and tax legislation. This impacts the prices of different types of labour and equipment, which are higher in countries with higher living standards. This is also reflected in existing special criteria for the hiring of teams, where local protectionism is very possible.

The regulatory framework for national and European support is based on bilateral and multilateral European conventions and agreements on cooperation and co-production. Therefore, regulations in the audiovisual sector can be a factor in the territorial embeddedness of a production network.

Territorial embeddedness—the local context, local clusters, and ecosystems

Territorial embeddedness in the form of a cluster is an important feature of the creation phases (participation in specialised pitching and meetings), production (quality specialised work), promotion, and dissemination (through festival participation).

Media clusters are an integral part of the urban economy and culture, in which we observe the concentration of cultural organisations, governmental and non-governmental institutions, universities, and a large potential audience. This environment creates a natural intensity of specialised activities, knowledge, and innovation.

In addition to the production of classic media content such as films, television productions, and games, the cluster is overflowing with activities and specialised work related to design, the music industry, software, performing arts, and more. The relationships and spillovers between different industries are directly dependent on the specificities of local development.

In this report, the strong territorial context is revealed through a case study of the production company KLAS Film through the audiovisual cluster in Sofia. It brings together corporate, government, academic, and civic institutions. The cluster has also become a base for upgrading: Sofia applied for and received the title of UNESCO City of Cinema.

Benefits—social, economic, cultural—for the local community can be realised thanks to the critical mass of economic actors specialising in the audiovisual field. A good example of this is the educational initiatives of Sofia Meetings and the masterclasses led by global names from the film industry. The degree of territorial embeddedness can partly explain the scale of a network. For example, a local cluster stimulates the development of a national film industry, but this is not enough for a production company to acquire European dimensions. However, if the cluster has a regional film fund (under the condition that part of the money is invested in the region), this automatically attracts international co-producers. Legislative conditions can also be an incentive for co-production (i.e. for the production network to expand from national to European). For example, in Bulgaria, the Film Industry Act allowed for the support of European productions with minority participation of Bulgarian producers (up to BGN 300,000). This attracted a substantial number of film productions, especially Romanian ones, to look for Bulgarian minority co-producers. At that time, there was no such financial opportunity in neighbouring Romania.

This raises the question of the possibility for a regional or national cluster to grow into a global one. “The critical challenge for urban media clusters is to secure enough synergies between the global and the intra-regional networks to expand import-replacing multipliers in order to add export multiplier. Urban media clusters that successfully secure these synergies might be characterised as global media clusters” (Sassen, 1994 in Karlsson, Rouchy, 2013).

Different authors see different ways to achieve this synergy. Glowacki and Jackson (2019), for instance, see the relationship between media clusters, high technology, and the public service media (PSM) as an important part of the changing media ecology.

In this report, the public sector media are introduced in two case studies dedicated to the Eurovision Song Contest and the EBU Music Radio Exchange. The case studies reveal that delivering public services in a rapidly changing media environment is challenging. The activities of these two global

production networks show how synergies are created within them, as well as in the context of the current neoliberal media market.

Network embeddedness—social connectivity of relationships within networks

The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) network unites PSM in Europe based on public service media's mission, traditions, and common policies. Uniting them is a way and a means to maintain high journalistic and technological standards and an opportunity to transfer knowledge and policies, as well as to lobby and advocate in individual cases. For example, the music exchange enriches programme content with high-quality music, free of charge, which positions PMS better in national radio markets. The exchange of European music, to and from associate members, can be seen as a form of soft diplomacy.

PSM's overall activities and programs to fulfil its mission are based on its core values of universality, independence, professionalism, diversity, accountability, and innovation. These values are reflected in the activities along the entire value chain. Both production networks of EBU discussed in the report—the Eurovision Song Contest and the Music Radio Exchange—are examples of knowledge, technology, and policy transfer.

Evidence of the resilience of the relationships built within the network is the mutual support between members during the COVID-19 pandemic. The sharing of television content between EBU members, for which they are not paid and nor obliged to provide counter content, is highly appreciated by all.

Trust between network members is also a leading value in the film industry. The production network in film goes beyond the lifetime of a project. The professional relationships built are long-lasting and are based on professional and personal reputation. The teams formed are also together because they share common cultural and aesthetic values. This is especially true for the creative teams. In the case of co-productions, additional criteria for building a common network are common history, geographical proximity, and the possibility of common European co-financing.

Embeddedness in video games

Europe is one of the three leading regions in the world in the development of the gaming industry, along with Asia and North America. Europe is a leader in the development of mobile games but is considered a major world player in all segments of the value chain.

This analysis aims to identify Europe's place in the gaming industry's GPN and what resources and values are transferred between continents and individual countries in social, cultural, and economic terms. The idea is to follow how one culture is embedded in another, thanks to this industry. Although gaming was not born in Europe, the aim is to trace the territorial and social dimensions of local industry and the importance of Europe in the global gaming market—as a leader in mobile games or as an incubator for ideas and talents in other varieties of games—including consumer capacity and as a wave of emerging markets in Central and Eastern Europe.

Currently, all top 10 markets by game revenues are from Asia, Europe, or North America, according to Newzoo. Number one is China, followed by the United States and Japan. There are three Asian

companies in the top 10, five European, and two North American (Newzoo, 2020). The data are from Newzoo's forecast for 2020 and are based on consumer spending in each country, excluding hardware sales, tax, business-to-business services, and online gambling and betting revenues.

Table 7: Top 10 Countries by Gaming Revenues

Country	Region	Revenue (USD)
China	Asia-Pacific	40.854M
United States	North America	36.921M
Japan	Asia-Pacific	18.683M
South Korea	Asia-Pacific	6.564M
Germany	Europe	5.965M
United Kingdom	Europe	5.511M
France	Europe	3.987M
Canada	North America	3.051M
Italy	Europe	2.661M
Spain	Europe	2.626M

Source: Newzoo

Territorial distribution—global and European aspect

According to Statista's data (Gough, 2020) from Q4 of 2019, no European corporation is in the top 10 of the most profitable public gaming companies. We must specify that these revenues are from the sales of games, as well as from publishing, distribution, and other processes related to games.

Game development is led by companies with established brands and their ecosystems of software, hardware, users, and, in some cases such as Google and Microsoft, from infrastructure such as cloud computing. Although the leading gaming company in the world is the Chinese Tencent, the top 10 is led by American players, a total of five. The other players are from the Asia-Pacific region: China and Japan.

Table 8: Gaming revenue of public companies worldwide in the fourth quarter of 2019

Company	Country	Revenue (in billion U.S. dollars)
Tencent	China	5.23
Sony	Japan	3.88
Apple	USA	2.89
Microsoft	USA	2.83
Nintendo	Japan	2.29
Google	USA	1.88
Activision Blizzard	USA	1.75

NetEase	China	1.67
EA	USA	1.59
TakeTwo Interactive	USA	0.93

Source: Statista

Each of the European countries has its own approach to gaming related to regional economic factors: the level of telecommunications; access to high-speed and multi-band internet; the ability of household members to have a computer, tablet, or smartphone; the degree of digitalization; and the convergence of the entertainment and media sectors.

For example, the British market is focused on the development of PC and console games and on self-publishing. Thanks to its big player Ubisoft, France is an important part of the gaming ecosystem in the development of AAA games. Two of the top three manufacturers of telecommunication networks, Ericsson and Nokia, are based in the Scandinavian countries. The concentration of R&D activities and new technologies in the mobile sphere is the reason why there are large and successful mobile game companies, such as Rovio, in this region.

Central and Eastern Europe (Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, etc.) are new market players in this industry, but they have traditions in the IT sector and good engineering education. "In Eastern Europe, countries led by Poland are benefiting from strong regional economic growth to exploit their resources of technology and development skills. It means that the region games markets are some of the fastest-growing globally" (Williamson, 2019).

For example, when it comes to Eastern Europe, the Bulgarian gaming industry has built a complete ecosystem. There are over 60 game development companies in Bulgaria with more than 1,300 employees. Bulgaria is among the best IT outsourcing destinations in the region, with three of the biggest gaming companies represented in the country: UBISOFT, Gameloft, and SEGA. Bulgaria has its own success stories: the creators of Tropico Series, Victor Vran, and Tsar are Bulgarian. One of the best MMORTS studios in the world is Imperia Online (Kadinov, Velinova, 2018).

Game development according to type

When it comes to the hardware on which games are played today, we distinguish four types of games: PC, console, handheld-based, and mobile games.

"The mobile gaming segment is the fastest-growing segment, likely to expand at a CAGR of 9.6% over the forecast period 2017–2030," according to Goldstein Market Intelligence.

In the production of games, Europe has a leading role in the creation of mobile games. Thanks to their easier and shorter production path, mobile games are finding a greater place in Europe. According to the consulting company Deloitte, "the mobile games industry is one area of the global tech industry where Europe is a global leader and has been driving digital innovation, not just across the continent, but worldwide" (Deloitte, 2015).

Some of the most popular and large-scale companies in the sector are European, including Zynga, the developer of the Angry Birds franchise, and GameLoft, with games such as City Mania and Pastry Paradise. Because mobile games are less expensive and are often made by independent players, they thrive in Europe, where the risk capital, a limitation for start-up developers, is significantly less than in Asia and the United States. The reason for Europe's becoming a leader in mobile games is its reliance on the so-called "freemium" model, in which users download the application for free and can then buy individual items within it. Easy user access to games, without the need for any financial base, is why mobile games make global expansion quick and easy (Deloitte, 2015).

Unlike mobile games, the console market is oligopolistic, and Europe is not the leader. In discussing territorial integration, we should note that the production of consoles is concentrated mainly in Asia, thanks to the companies Sony and Nintendo, which produce PlayStation and Switch, respectively. The third player in the top three is based in North America: Microsoft, which develops consoles in the Xbox series. Although it does not produce hardware, much software is being developed in Europe for these devices. The most striking examples of this are world hits such as "Assassin's Creed" (Ubisoft, France) and LittleBigPlanet (Media Molecule, UK).

European contributions, new markets, and the emergence of complete gaming ecosystems

Europe's role in the development of the global gaming industry cannot be denied. The continent has a well-developed IT industry that is a driver of innovation in various fields, including gaming, hardware, and software. The ICT industry is based on a solid foundation of quality engineering and computer education, both in higher education and in specialised private academies and schools. Thanks to their good education and skills, European developers, artists, and other gaming talents are appreciated by, for example, Silicon Valley corporations.

At the European level, and in individual countries (e.g., Bulgaria), an important factor in the development of the industry is its many accelerator programs, venture capital funds, and business incubators. Co-working spaces (e.g. betahaus, SOHO, puzl, and Work & Share, based in Sofia) have become spaces where IT and gaming talents work together, exchanging ideas and knowledge.

The small European markets here do not feel the limitations of closed language communities because the language of games is universal. In Bulgaria, two universities provide a master's degree in this subject. The potential of the sector is also acknowledged by the mobile operator A1 Bulgaria, which organises the A1 Gaming League (<https://www.a1.bg/gaming>). Bulgaria is part of the Global Game Jam Network, and there is a Sofia Game Jam, and within the framework of the event is also a Game Industry Job Fair. The Southeast Europe Centre for the ESL Electronic League is based in Sofia. In March 2019, the Bulgarian team Windigo Gaming became the champion of the World Electronic Sports Games (WESG) in China.

The competitive advantages of the Eastern European countries promise a good future in this industry: "Bulgaria is an ideal place for a growing game development community, already being a European leader for IT development and having a history of technological accomplishment and innovation. It offers a new hub of talented aspiring game developers that we can nurture in an experienced AAA

environment,” according to Tim Heaton, Studio Director at Creative Assembly and EVP of SEGA Studios in the West (Creative Assembly, 2019). There are great opportunities in the IT sector in Bulgaria, according to the CEO of the parent company of Tokyo Tatsuaki Miyazaki:

It's hard to find people for this industry. Globally, we face competition from China. They are constantly buying studios and game developers. Our studies show the great potential of Eastern Europe. Before selling the games, we must make sure that the necessary tests are done. Therefore, we hope that this place here can become central to game testing. Why Bulgaria? Because of the potential in the game industry here. You have great shots to choose from. And even if it's small, the gaming community is good. There are good schools here that provide quality talent. The price for quality we get here is competitive. (Kalfova, 2019)

Historical factors

Historically, the expansion of the global gaming industry is highly dependent on technologies that lead to major cultural changes. The clearest example of this is Asia. Games became very popular in Asia due to the strong development of information and communication technologies on the continent. This process was often associated with active policies promoting the ICT sector. For example, South Korea has been investing billions of dollars in its mobile networks for years. The country officially became the first to launch a 5G network. In the 1990s, South Korea positioned itself as a global leader in broadband internet services, leading to the emergence of local PC cafes where young people gathered to use the internet and take their first steps in the gaming universe (Jin & Schneider, 2016). This created a culture of visiting such places and holding gaming tournaments, and the gaming industry began to gain strength.

The development of the gaming industry in Asia is strongly associated with the emergence of local technology companies creating innovations in hardware and software. Two of the world's three largest console manufacturers are Asian: Sony and Nintendo. They produce consoles, develop games, including mobile games. Companies like Sony and Nintendo later evolved into huge conglomerates that dictate the major gaming innovations in the gaming industry. Tech companies that also contribute to the industry include South Korea's LG and Samsung, China's Lenovo and Xiaomi, and Taiwan's HTC.

The fact that these technologies became part of every home on the three continents sparked game development. The '90s and '00s were times of rapid innovation development, and society came to expect constant innovation. PC cafes were places where strong friendships were created. The social element here was very important. These places were where the gaming community was formed. PC cafes became an arena for socializing and sharing experiences, and they were part of the pop culture in Korea at the time. At a later stage, these cafes established the foundations of the e-sports segment. Such internet cafes were popular in Europe in the 1990s, when the internet was making its first steps, and gave game access to teenagers in these regions, who have entered the online world using games.

Other factors

Europe does not have a strong tradition of entrepreneurship in gaming, as in Asia and the United States, but it has a tradition in the film industry that has helped it to develop talents in game

development. Using its knowledge of storytelling, Europe became a pioneer in open-world design (Latorre, 2013). Open-world games became very popular after the launch of Grand Theft Auto, which was created by the Scottish video game programmer David Jones and the Scottish video game designer Mike Dailly, in the late 1990s.

Individual European countries are trying to support the gaming industry because they see its economic potential. “The UK, France, Spain, Denmark, Belgium and other European countries, provide state aid schemes, grants, loans and tax breaks. These have helped the quoted value of the European games sector grow by roughly 50% per annum, on average, for the last five plus years” (Williamson, 2019).

Publishing and promotion

Specialised media have played a key role in the development of communities and gaming culture in Europe. For example, in Bulgaria, the leading editions in the last 20 years have been the magazines *PCWorld* and *PC Mania*. In her work *Cheating: Gaining Advantage in Video Games*, Mia Consalvo emphasises the key socio-cultural role of such media for the industry (Consalvo, 2009). Globally, one of the most popular examples is *Nintendo Power Magazine*, founded in 1988. It is the official magazine of the Japanese company Nintendo for the North American market, which is gaining high popularity. The publishing and promotion of games are closely related to the construction of fan bases for specific games, game characters (e.g. Mario), and universes. One tool for achieving this is to give access, to the beta and sometimes to the alpha versions of a game, usually to a limited number of users. It happens on platforms like Google Play, PreApps, Indie Quality Assurance, Betalist, and Alpha Beta Gamer. The very access to games unknown to anyone creates a sense of community and privilege, and it contributes to user commitment to the brand in question.

For their part, game developers and other members of the gaming industry are actively developing the gaming community. In Bulgaria, for example, before the pandemic, meetings of the Game Dev Summit were regularly organised and visited by industry representatives and fans. Sofia Game Night is an annual event that brings together companies in the sector and gamers.

The creation of large fandoms is typical for e-sports and sparked the creation of this branch of gaming. It is this enthusiasm that makes users watch more games online and have their favourite games. According to Fandom 250, the titles with the most solid fandoms are Call of Duty, e-Sports, FIFA, League of Legends, Madden, and Pokemon (Hill, 2017). E-sports, which have been booming in recent years, also play a huge role in the development of these consumer databases. Usually, e-sports are related to multiplayer games, so here the social element is particularly strong. As early as 2012, Paul Tassi of Forbes noted that “Viewership has gone from the hundreds to hundreds of the thousands. Prize pools have gone from a pittance to millions” (Tassi, 2012).

Distribution

The major online game distribution platforms belong to large companies in the technology and gaming industry. However, they are not positioned in Europe, which does not have its own market player in large app stores and relies on foreign solutions. This element of the value chain is in the hands of corporations with large scales, capital, developed customer bases, and entire ecosystems. In mobile

games, the dominance of the application stores, Apple's App Store and Google's Google Play (owned by the parent company Alphabet), is obvious. Driven by US sanctions, the Chinese technology company Huawei Technologies is currently developing its AppGallery (Phelan, 2020) app store, which is still not as influential or with as rich of a library as its competitors. In this aspect, there is a concentration of power in North America.

The developers of the three main consoles have their own platforms, through which they distribute their games online. These are Nintendo eShop, Xbox Live Marketplace, and PlayStation Store.

Europe is one of the main regions in the development of e-sports over the years. According to Newzoo's "An overview of e-Sports in Europe" report from 2017, "Europe is a key region for the e-sports industry and one of the world's largest e-sports companies—ESL originates in Germany. It accounts for almost one-third of all global e-sports revenues and is host to more than 70 million e-sports viewers" (Newzoo, 2017). Over the years, the ESL has built a large fan community by organising record-breaking events such as ESL One in Cologne, Germany, and Intel Extreme Masters in Katowice, Poland. The popularity of e-sports tournaments in Europe grew and led to the launch of specialised television broadcasters such as ESTV (launched on Samsung television Plus) and SK Sports (launched by Serbia Broadband) for the distribution and active promotion of gaming content in Europe.

Consumption

The opportunities for socialization are referred to in the latest report of Simon-Kucher and Partners' "Global Gaming Study: Impacts of COVID-19" (Jaeger et al., 2020), which argues that gaming is one of the few industries which have grown during the pandemic. The report shows that pre-COVID-19 estimations were for the gaming market to reach USD 160 billion and 9% growth on an annual basis. The crisis has supported the industry, and the new forecast is for USD 170 billion and 12–15% year-on-year growth. For comparison, the figure for 2019 was USD 148 billion. More importantly, the report highlights two main effects of the pandemic on the gaming industry. Firstly, consumers have started spending more on games. Secondly, users have turned to more socially oriented (multiplayer) games and seek contact, albeit *in absentia*, with other people by watching video streaming games.

Sixty percent of respondents have reportedly played various games during the blockades and were looking for games with higher social components, as confirmed by the high increase in consumption of multiplayer online battle arena games (MOBAs), such as League of Legends, and games like Fortnite (battle royale games) with social and communication components. The consumption of games is encouraged both by increasingly personalized titles and by social isolation and the increased search for online contact. Under conditions of social isolation, the entertaining and communicative character of the games intensified, and large gaming communities have emerged.

According to the Global Web Index for media consumption in the COVID-19 era, video games have become most popular among younger users. About 31% of Generation Z respondents have reportedly started playing or have played more video games. The share is 31% for Millennials, 19% for Generation X, and 10% for Baby Boomers. More interestingly, Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X have

seen a high increase in the consumption of online video, as well as online or television streaming channels through which gaming content can also be accessed (Jones, 2020).

The expansion of games also has its dark sides. After 2000, studies began to appear (including in Europe) on the existence of problems and risk factors related to gaming, the largest of which is addiction. Although there are special funds in Europe to combat gambling addiction, there are no such funds set up to treat video game addiction. In China, for example, the state has a more radical approach to games, requiring a special registration for each title, and a state regulator monitors how addictive a game is and decides whether it should be released on the market.

On the other hand, methodologies developed by the video game industry have found spillover applications in other areas. Gamification is one such example. The successful use of video games for educational purposes has proven effective in both educational systems and the corporate world. At the same time, gaming methodologies have helped to create immersive experiences related to the development of technologies such as virtual reality. These technologies, albeit experimental, would influence consumption. In addition, games offer a new way of storytelling to users. Recent examples include the overflow of content from movies, series, and games (such as *Game of Thrones*) and, not the least, the emergence of “serious games” that are “used for purposes other than entertainment and applied in various fields such as education, defense, medicine, health, job security or culture” (González-Piñero, 2017).

In conclusion, we must note that Europe is a fundamental and indispensable part of the global gaming industry. Europe has sufficient resources—talents, companies, and ideas—that could successfully compete with regions such as Asia and North America. In fast-growing and converging global digital markets, what Europe does not yet have is ownership of the digital distribution networks for games.

1.1.4 Policies in audiovisual industries

Cultural and audiovisual policies have been distinctive features in the development of mutual understanding and the safeguarding and promotion of cultural heritage and diversity, and have been fundamental in re-building European communities after World War II. The Council of Europe has played an important role in the development of policies for audio-visual and culture across the European continent. As an intergovernmental organisation dedicated to human rights, culture, education and media in Europe, CoE developed an active cultural remit from the start, with the adoption and the implementation of a package of cultural conventions, starting with the European Cultural Convention, Paris 1954. After the fall of the Iron Curtain in 1989 through the end of the 2000s, the Council of Europe played an important role in developing capacities and knowledge among CoE members, bridging gaps, and preparing the former Eastern bloc countries to reform their cultural and audiovisual systems and policies into market-oriented mixed systems.

At the EU level, the Treaty of Rome included culture, establishing the European Economic Community in 1957, but with reference to the protection of works of artistic value (Kolokytha 2019). It was only

in 1992 that the Treaty of the European Union (aka the Treaty of Maastricht) included the first legal dispositions on audiovision and culture in the EU. Article 128 (revised as Article 151 of the 1997 revision, to become Article 167 of the Lisbon Treaty TFEU 2009) introduced the European Community's complementary support of culture to Member States, safeguarding cultural heritage, as well as in the audiovisual sector (TEC 1992). This delineates the "subsidiarity" model of supporting the non-commercial value of cultural production and diversity of content in Europe and laid the foundations for community programmes such as Creative Europe and MEDIA to evolve.

Legal frameworks in audiovisual industries

The main purpose of the European Union's audiovisual policies and regulations is to create a single and strong European market for audiovisual services, mostly audiovisual media, for which the EU has developed a serious regulatory framework.

In the European Union (EU) legislation, "audiovisual media service" is defined as a service by Articles 56 and 57 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, in which the principal purpose of the service or a dissociable section thereof is devoted to providing programs, under the editorial responsibility of a media service provider, to the general public in order to inform, entertain, or educate, by means of electronic communications networks. Such an audiovisual media service is either a television broadcast, an on-demand audiovisual media service, or audiovisual commercial communication. There are four types of audiovisual commercial communications: advertising, sponsorship, teleshopping, and product placement (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMD 2018/1808, Article 1) The term "audiovisual" refers to moving images with or without sound, as detailed in Article 1(b) of the AVMSD, thus including silent films but not audio transmission or radio services. This does not affect the freedom of the Member States (MS) to regulate such services at the national level, and all MS provide legal measures concerning radio services.

Fourteen EU Member States (AT, BE, FR, CZ, DK, ES, FR, GR, HU, IT, LV, PT, RO, SE, and SK) provide for a specific definition of "cinematographic works" based on the European Convention on Cinematographic Co-production, in which "film" is defined as "a moving image work crafted to express an idea or tell a story—fictional, factual or artistic—regardless of production process, recording medium or distribution channel" (EAO, 2020, p.14).

The rules governing the audiovisual sector in each EU Member State are in three different, albeit interconnected, legal frameworks: the international, national, and EU legal frameworks.

National legal framework

Each EU Member State regulates audiovisual media services in its national legislation. In some federal countries (e.g., Germany, Spain), there are also regional frameworks. Radio and television are more circumstantially regulated than publishing because of the need for government intervention in the allocation of radio frequency spectrums, which are a limited resource. For this reason, a special established government administration decides on the use of frequencies needed for the broadcasting of audiovisual content. The decisions are based on principles and criteria strictly defined in the national legislation.

The whole process of production, distribution, promotion, and support of cinematographic works is also the subject of national legal measures. The specifics of national legal frameworks in audiovisual industries and film, and their relations to the global production networks, are explained in the context of the case studies (Part 2).

International legal framework

The international legal framework consists of sources of international law, bilateral and multilateral international treaties. The acts of international organisations with global or regional scopes and aims in the fields of human rights, culture, and media are of particular importance. The contractual framework arising from trade negotiations conducted by the World Trade Organisation (WTO) plays a key role. Acts of the United Nations and its specialised organisations, such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), are also central to the international legal framework for audiovisual. The UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions (2005) is the basis of the EU's cultural policy, as the EU is a party to the Convention, along with the majority of its Member States, which ratified the convention separately. The Council of Europe is a regional intergovernmental organisation aimed at the development of democracy, human rights protection, culture, education, and the media. The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR) is the heart of the CoE's work. The ECHR has a role, confirmed by the case law of the EU Court of Justice, in the implementation of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000) is in compliance with the ECHR and, in some respects (media pluralism), further develops the protection of rights important to audiovisual media, such as the freedom of expression and the right of access to information provided by Article 10 of the ECHR. The link between the EU Charter and the ECHR is ensured by the rule of Article 52 (3) of the Charter, which envisages that "In so far as this Charter contains rights which correspond to rights guaranteed by the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the meaning and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention. This provision shall not prevent Union law providing more extensive protection." The content and scope of guaranteed rights are determined not only by the texts of these legal instruments but also by the case law of the European Court of Human Rights and the Court of Justice of the European Union. In any case, the level of protection afforded by the Charter can never be lower than that guaranteed by the ECHR.

The Council of Europe's major contribution to the audiovisual sector in Europe is through the European Convention on Cinematographic Co-production, first adopted 1992 and revised in 2017, which led to the establishment of the Eurimages fund in 1989 to support European co-productions and theatrical display, as well as the establishment of the European Audiovisual Observatory in 1992 in Strasbourg. Both instruments have proven crucial the value chains in film and television in Europe, as well as for data collection about the European audiovisual markets. In 2001, the CoE also adopted the European Convention on the Protection of the Audiovisual Heritage, in force as of 2008, ensuring the systematic archiving and safeguarding of audiovisual content.

CoE conventions have been ratified and entered into force in many EU countries, as well as in non-EU members across Europe. Some of these conventions explicitly stipulate that international law takes precedence over domestic law. The European Convention on Transfrontier Television (ECTT) and its

Amending Protocol have the purpose of facilitating cross-border transmission and re-transmission of television programme services between the state parties of the Convention. It has been of particular importance after Brexit, given that the United Kingdom is a party to the Convention but has left the EU.

EU legal framework of audiovisual policy

EU audiovisual policy was created relatively late, compared to core EU policies regarding the single market, when technological developments allowed the transmission of television programme services to leave the country of origin. The contradiction between globalizing media markets and national laws extends to the Court of Justice. For several years, the Court has adopted a number of rulings relating to violations of domestic media legislation in cases of cross-border transmission of television programme services. MS decided that the audiovisual policy, as cultural policy, should include the country-of-origin principle. In 1986, the European Commission set out to draft a directive, adopted in 1989: the *Television without Frontiers Directive*, the main legal instrument for implementing EU audiovisual policy. “The country of origin principle should be regarded as the core of this Directive, as it is essential for the creation of an internal market. This principle should be applied to all audiovisual media services in order to ensure legal certainty for media service providers as the necessary basis for new business models and the deployment of such services. It is also essential in order to ensure the free flow of information and audiovisual programs in the internal market” (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMD, Directive 2010/13/EU, Rec 33).

The principles of audiovisual regulation have determined (European Commission 1999. COM [1999] 539 Final) that future AV regulation should:

- be based on clearly defined audiovisual policy objections;
- be the minimum necessary to meet those objectives;
- further enhance legal certainty in a dynamic market;
- aim to be technologically neutral, irrespective of the means services are delivered; and
- be enforced as closely as practicable to the activities being regulated.

The Directive has undergone three revisions—in 1997, 2007 and 2018—and was renamed in the second revision as the *Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD)* that is used to date. AVMSD governs the EU-wide coordination of national legislation on all audiovisual media, including includes both traditional television broadcasts and on-demand services.

EU: the dynamics of audiovisual regulation

Television without Frontiers Directive

As the first of its kind, the Television without Frontiers Directive does not comprehensively cover all aspects of television programming. Its main purpose is the free transmission of television across the EU Member States. Advertising and sponsorship are regulated in detail, insofar as they are essential for the liberalizing television market as an industry. The directive answers the question of the applicable law in cross-border transfers: the law of the country of origin. In order to promote a strong, competitive, and integrated European audiovisual industry and enhance media pluralism throughout

the EU, only one Member State should have jurisdiction over an audiovisual media service provider; the principle of freedom of reception and retransmission of programs in the EU is explicitly envisaged in the text.

The Directive introduces measures for the protection and development of European audiovisual works: Member States shall ensure, where practicable and by appropriate means, that most of the programming time for European works is maintained, with the exception of news and sports competitions, games, advertising, and teletext services. Measures for the development of audiovisual production outside of television have been adopted, with at least 10% of programming time or at least 10% of television budget being earmarked for European works created by independent producers.

Although the wording of the requirements has been criticized by strong supporters of the European quota because of the stipulation "when it is practically possible," the new requirements are quickly yielding statistically visible results, both in the EU Member States and in EU accession states, which is important from the perspective of the task of protecting Europe's cultural and linguistic identity.

First revision: 1997

The preamble to Directive 97/36 / EC describes the most important factors that led to the first revision of the Television Without Frontiers directive. The revision clarifies the applicable law in cases of a more complex nature, develops the legal framework for electronic commercial communications, legalizes teleshopping, and introduces new measures for minors' protection and audience access to important events. This revision is considered a difficult consensus between the Member States on the one hand and the Commission, providers, producers, and rights holders, on the other. Some text from the original drafts has been dropped, and provisions on media pluralism and intellectual property have not been included in the final version.

The development of information technologies creates preconditions for deep interaction between three sectors separate until then in the information sphere: media, electronic communications, and information technologies. The transition to convergent laws, convergent regulators to enforce them, and converged services through converged devices begins. The first convergent regulator (AGCOM) was established in Italy in 1997. The convergent legislation in the United Kingdom entered into force on 1 January 2004. A convergent regulator (OFCOM) was established on the basis of the five existing regulators.

In 1999, the European Community became a member of the European Audiovisual Observatory. EAO collects and disseminates information and statistical data on the audiovisual sector in Europe, which serves the industry as well as the policymakers. With regard to the implementation of the AVMSD, the European Parliament has recommended that the role of the European Audiovisual Observatory be strengthened, as this would be an appropriate solution for collecting data on the promotion of the European audiovisual industry (European Parliament, 2013).

Second revision: 2007 and Audiovisual and Media Services Directive (AVMSD)

The media in the new century has been strongly influenced by the effects of convergence. The preparation of the European Commission for more effective enforcement of media policy objectives

is carried out through several acts, the most important of which is the Principles and Guidelines for Community Audiovisual Policy in the Digital Age (1999). It is clear that media services go beyond television as we know it. The media has begun to discuss “the end of television.” Many new services are emerging. A “second pillar” of services was introduced for the first time in the AVMSD: on-demand services (VOD).

The regulation of commercial communications is being liberalized again. Member States can legally allow one more type of commercial communication: product placement. The legalization of product placement gives a strong positive impetus to the production of audiovisual content.

In 2010, a codified Directive on audiovisual media services (AVMSD) was adopted, consolidating in a single act the basic directive Television without Frontiers and existing revisions (European Parliament and the Council, 2013, AVMD, Directive 2010/13/EU, Rec 33, 3.4. Third revision: 2018).

The audiovisual media services market has evolved significantly and rapidly due to the ongoing convergence of television and internet services. Technical developments have allowed for new types of services and user experiences. Viewing habits, particularly those of younger generations, have changed significantly. While the traditional television screen remains an important device for sharing audiovisual experiences, many viewers have moved to other, portable devices to watch audiovisual content. Traditional television content still accounts for a major share of the average daily viewing time. This convergence of media requires an updated legal framework in order to reflect developments in the market and to achieve a balance between access to online content services, consumer protection, and competitiveness (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMSD, Directive (EU) 2018/1808 Rec.1).

The third revision extended the scope of the directive. For the first time, some aspects of video-sharing platforms were included in the directive, as the platforms are widely used, especially by young people. The scope also includes social media services, which have become an important means of sharing information, including by providing access to broadcasts and user-generated videos. The scope of regulation was extended in order to ensure the protection of minors from harmful content and of all citizens from incitement to hatred, violence, and terrorism. A new Chapter IXa, “Provisions applicable to video-sharing platform services,” was created, defining VSPs as those in which “the principal purpose of the service, or of a dissociable section thereof, or an essential functionality of the service is devoted to providing programmes and/or user-generated videos, or both, to the general public, for which the video-sharing platform provider does not have editorial responsibility and the organisation of which is determined by the video-sharing platform provider, including by automatic means or algorithms in particular by displaying, tagging and sequencing” (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMD 2018/1808, Art.1). The European Commission has also recently published guidelines on “essential functionality” (European Commission, 2020).

According to the Article 28b, Member States shall ensure that VSP providers take appropriate measures to protect: (a) minors from programmes, user-generated videos, and audiovisual commercial communications which may impair their physical, mental, or moral development; (b) the general public from programmes, user-generated videos, and audiovisual commercial

communications containing incitement to violence or hatred directed against a group of persons or a member of a group; and (c) the general public from programmes, user-generated videos, and audiovisual commercial communications containing content the dissemination of which constitutes an activity which is a criminal offence under Union law, namely public provocation to commit a terrorist offence, offences concerning child pornography, and offences concerning racism and xenophobia.

The directive provides for new measures to promote European works in video-on-demand services, which must have at least a 30% share of European works in their catalogue, ensuring the visibility of that content. As before, the obligation for countries to periodically report to the European Commission on the achieved levels of European works in television (not less than 50%) and in on-demand services (not less than 30%) is maintained. With the revision, a new liberalization of the legal framework of advertising is carried out.

The market for television broadcasting has evolved and there is a need for more flexibility with regard to audiovisual commercial communications, in particular for quantitative rules for linear audiovisual media services and product placement. The emergence of new services, including those without advertising, has led to a greater choice for viewers, who can easily switch to alternative offers. (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMD 2018/1808, Rec 32)

It is important, therefore, that broadcasters have more flexibility and ability to decide when to place advertising in order to maximise advertisers' demands and viewers' flow (European Parliament and the Council, 2018, AVMD 2018/1808, Rec 41).

An important change related to the governance and the implementation and enforcement of the directive has been introduced. At the national level, for the first time, there is a requirement for legal separation and functional independence of the regulator from the government and any other public or private body, as well as for guaranteeing financial and human resources for the performance of the functions of the regulators. At the supranational level, the establishment of a regulatory group (ERGA) is envisaged (ERGA will include representatives of national audiovisual regulators and is tasked with providing technical expertise to the European Commission in its efforts to ensure accurate implementation of the Directive and to facilitate the interaction of regulators). Measures to achieve objectives of common interest, such as the protection of children and people with disabilities, continue to be strengthened. For the first time, states are obliged to provide in their national laws for measures to promote media literacy among citizens of all ages and for all types of media.

European film industry policy and film heritage

Despite its fundamental role in initiating the legal and policy frameworks for audiovisual industries in Europe, the Council of Europe has in the past years retained a softer policy-making signature, while the EU, despite reluctance by the Member States and the sector itself, is today the most prominent European-level film policymaking actor (Barbato, 2008, Vinck and Lindmark, 2012).

The real surge in European-level film policy activities happened in the 1980s. It is then that a pragmatic approach puts the idea of European-level film support on the policy agenda. From the early 1980s on, privatisation and liberalisation swept the European audiovisual sector, as exemplified by the abolishment of the public service broadcasting monopoly throughout Europe. Competition on television markets had become fiercer, leading to increased demand for content. (Vinck, Lindmark, 2012)

The European Convention on Cinematographic Co-production (ECCC), in force since 1994 and ratified by 43 CoE members, replaced bilateral co-production treaties between European countries and established a definition of “European works” which, among other things, entails benefits in terms of access to national funds (Katsarova, 2014). With the development of AVMSD, some of the definitions and concepts by CoE in the field of film industry exist in parallel with those by AVMSD, such as audiovisual, cinematographic, domestic, and European works. While all EU Member States have defined the concept of “European works” in compliance with Art. 1 of the AVMSD, a definition of the term “audiovisual works” is provided in 15 Member States (BE FR, CZ, EE, ES, FR, GR, HR, IT, LV, MT, PL, PT, RO and SK) (EAO, 2020:13).

There is a link between the ECCC and the AVMSD: Member States should encourage broadcasters to include in their programming adequate shares of co-produced European works or European works of non-domestic origin (European Parliament and the Council, 2013, AVMD, Directive 2010/13/EU, Rec 70).

The EU aims to encourage its Member States to cooperate in the conservation and safeguarding of cultural heritage of European significance (Article 167, TFEU). The recommendation to Member States is to methodically collect, catalogue, preserve, and restore Europe’s film heritage so that it can be passed on to future generations. EU Member States are asked to report every two years on what they have done in this context, and the Commission produces an implementation report based on that information.

Financial instruments

The first European fund for supporting the film industry value chains is *Eurimages*, established in 1989 as a cooperation instrument by the Council of Europe members; it currently has 39 member countries from Europe, except the United Kingdom, and including Canada. The fund supports international co-productions, as well as their distribution, exhibition, and promotion.

The European Union has developed various financial instruments to support the democratic media and the European public sphere. Initially this was done through sectoral MEDIA programmes, launched every seven years since 2000 and which aimed to increase the competitiveness of European audiovisual productions to provide more and high-quality productions to the growing number of European television broadcasters. The Creative Europe programme (2014–2020) succeeded the earlier sector programmes Culture and MEDIA, bringing them under one framework. The current Creative Europe programme (2021–2027) includes a Culture strand, which supports cross-border cooperation, platforms, networking in the performing and visual arts, cultural heritage, and other areas, including literary translation; and the MEDIA strand, which supports the value chain in the

audiovisual media and film industry in Europe, focusing on content production, business innovation and scalability, as well as on audiences. The programme also has a cross-sectoral focus. Creative Europe's budget is EUR 2.44 billion for 2021–2027 (European Commission 2022).

Interaction of audiovisual policy with other EU policies

Copyright in the digital single market

While the EU aims to achieve widely distributed and accessible creative content across the EU, it also must ensure that EU copyright rules continue to provide a high level of protection for rights holders and to maintain a good balance with other public policy goals, such as education, research and innovation, and equal access for persons with disabilities in the digital environment. Hence, in 2015, the European Commission adopted a strategy for the modernisation of copyright protection in the digital era (European Commission, 2015. COM(2015) 626 final, p. 7).

Ambitious to deliver on its Digital Single Market Strategy, the European Commission has modernised the EU copyright framework to meet the current challenges of the global digital age. In April 2019, the European Parliament and the Council approved the new Directive (EU) 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amended Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC. The modernization of the EU copyright legislation aimed at (a) more cross-border access to online content; (b) more opportunities to use copyrighted materials for education, research, and cultural heritage purposes; (c) a better-functioning copyright marketplace; and (d) implementation of the WIPO Marrakech Treaty (2013) in EU law.

The Commission underlined that fragmentation of copyright rules in the EU is very distinctive in its exceptions. Exceptions are often not defined in detail, which leads to an exception in which the legislation of one Member State may not exist in another, may vary in scope, or may be subject to different conditions. This situation is posing problems particularly for exceptions related to education, research, and access to knowledge. The Commission's ambition was therefore to ensure that a relevant EU framework on exceptions regarding access to knowledge, education and research, would be effective in the digital age.

The Commission considered whether solutions at the EU level are required to increase legal certainty, transparency, and balance in the system that governs the remuneration of authors and performers in the EU, taking national competencies into account. The adoption of Directive (EU) 2019/790 of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market is only a step towards the "full harmonization of copyright in the EU, in the form of a single copyright code and a single copyright title, which would require substantial changes in the way our rules work today" (European Commission, 2015. COM (2015) 626 final, p. 12).

Whereas the new Copyright Directive is expected to affect global online platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, and Google News, not all experts and researchers accept or agree with the changes. This concerns more specifically Articles 11 and 13 of the Directive, which raise concerns about restricting the freedom of internet consumption and filtering content without clear criteria. According to

Ognyanova, the imposed filter is not only for information without copyright: this act is also the beginning of a vague regulation of a relatively free market (Ognyanova, 2018).

Competition and state aid

Competition law cannot replace measures to ensure media pluralism. Article 21 (4) of the Merger Regulation allows EU MS to apply additional measures to protect media pluralism. The control mechanisms for media concentration vary considerably from one Member State to another, and they rely on different measures to assess the impact of media companies on the market and to limit the impact (number of licenses, capital shares, voting shares, revenue from advertising, and participation in a number of media sectors).

The link between competition policy and pluralism is ambiguous: even if media concentration is limited, media pluralism is not necessarily guaranteed. In smaller countries, securing external media pluralism through a large number of competing and diverse channels, or headlines controlled by many different players, may be more difficult to achieve, according to different research and marketing reports (EUI, 2020).

Media pluralism depends on the situation of each link in the production chain: acquisition of rights to cover (broadcast) certain events, advertising and other types of commercial communications, production of programs and other programme services' elements, composing programme services, multiplexing, and transmission of media services.

The right of the audience to be informed may be limited by the limited competition in each of these areas. For example, limited competition in the transmission of programme services allows the broadcaster to dictate conditions or to put pressure on broadcasters and producers.

The gaming industries have grown substantially in recent years. In 2019, the expected growth in the USA between 2020 and 2025 was estimated at 45%, in France at 38%, the UK at 29%, and in Germany at 20%. According to the comparative legal report of WIPO, "video games are complex works of authorship—containing multiple art forms, such as music, scripts, plots, video, paintings and characters—that involve human interaction while executing the game with a computer programme on specific hardware. Therefore, video games are not created as single, simple works, but are an amalgamation of individual elements that can each individually be copyrighted (i.e., the characters in a given video game, its soundtrack, settings, audiovisual parts, etc.) if they achieve a certain level of originality and creativity" (WIPO,2013). Video games now include numerous forms of expression. The idea/expression debate has been followed by discussion of intellectual property rights protection.

State aid and audiovisual services

The European Commission has adopted two important Communications on state aid for audiovisual services: the Communication from the Commission on the Application of State Aid Rules to Public Service Broadcasting, adopted by the Commission on 2 July 2009, and the Communication from the Commission on State Aid for Films and Other Audiovisual Works, adopted on 15 November 2013.

The Commission underlined that “films in particular face strong competition from outside Europe. On the other hand, there is little circulation of European audiovisual works outside their country of origin. This limited circulation results from the fragmentation of the European audiovisual sector into national or even regional markets. While this is related to Europe's linguistic and cultural diversity, proximity is also built into the public support for European audiovisual works, with which national, regional and local funding schemes subsidise many small production companies. It is generally accepted that aid is important to sustain European audiovisual production” (European Commission, 2013, p.2-3).

COVID-19 and its effect on EU policies

The COVID-19 pandemic has mobilised European institutions in backing up unprecedented financial measures for the cultural and creative sectors. The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) have dedicated specific measures to green transition; digital transformation; smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth; social cohesion; and the culture and creative sectors and industries. NextGenerationEU will be the main instrument (European Commission, 2020 COM (2020) 456 final) to enable the economic, social, and green recovery. The massive lockdowns during the pandemic, in 2020–2021, boosted online business models, and digital tools became vital for companies, as well as for individuals. This trend will accelerate in the months and years to come. However, the online environment is currently dominated by many large platforms. Their greater access to key data resources has an impact on the ability of smaller European companies to start up, scale up, or make the most of the Single Market.

One of the aims of the new Digital Services Act will be to improve the legal framework for digital services, with clear rules for online platforms. It will offer greater security for consumers online, prevent the abuse of market power by platforms and ensure a fair marketplace with equal opportunities for smaller businesses.” (ibid)

The audiovisual industry in a pandemic: emergency policies and regulations

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the ecosystem of the cultural industries in Europe, an expected decline in turnover up to 80% for the second quarter of 2020 (GESAG, 2020). The audiovisual sector, and cinema in particular, are among the sectors most affected globally. Losses are estimated at USD 24.4 billion over the next five years, according to Ampere Analysis (Petrov, 2020). The European film industry has been hit hard by the lockdowns and social distancing measures: discontinued productions, stagnant distribution, postponed first screenings, closed cinemas, failed festivals, and creators and technical teams (many of them freelance) with no prospect of income.

Neither was the television business spared by the overall decline in advertising revenues: media advertising revenues dropping as much as 80%, job cuts, and an influx of fake news (European Parliament, 2020).

The video gaming industry seemed to be the only one to keep and increase its profit in the times of home isolation and growing online consumption. "Since the beginning of the pandemic, the industry has experienced massive growth, with 82% of people playing video games and watching video content with games. According to Nielsen Games Video Game Tracking (VGT), the number of gamers who say they are playing video games more now due to the COVID-19 pandemic has increased since March 23, 2020. The increase was highest in the U.S. (46%), followed by France (41%), the U.K. (28%) and Germany (23%) ("3, 2, 1 Go! Video Gaming is at an All-Time High," 2020).

The losses for the film and television industries have led to long-term uncertainty, which stems from the specifics of their production cycles: a chain of authors, large numbers of self-employed creative workers, numerous sub-markets creating value, and long production processes (in feature film, the optimistic period is 2.5 years from script development to screening). The specificity of small European markets added to that uncertainty, through by lower returns on the production scale and dominant micro-production companies on the market, as well as business models based on projects.

The pandemic caused serious health, social, and economic crises. Most of the extraordinary decisions and the applied instruments have been implemented through specific regulations.

Emergency support for the audiovisual sector during the pandemic can be considered from several perspectives.

- 1) According to the scope of the applied measures, we distinguish
 - general horizontal support measures (i.e. covering the entire economy of a country);
 - vertical support measures (i.e. sector-specific, e.g. culture); and
 - support with a narrower focus (measures aimed at the audiovisual industry—film, radio and television industry, and games—where it is possible to have specialised support for individual sub-markets across stages of the production chain, e.g. support for script development and cinema screening).

- 2) Depending on the type of the support instrument, we distinguish
 - financial support via a grant or loan, the creation of a new programme or complementary funds for an existing program, a new support instrument such as a new fund or new tax, or simply compensation for losses incurred, deferred payments, and social support);
 - legislative change in the sector, or the emergence of a new specialised law;
 - dissemination of information, as through initiatives for media literacy and misinformation;
 - health recommendations for work in the sector, for cinemas and film crews and for journalists; and
 - specialised studies and impact assessments to enable informed decision-making in an environment of growing uncertainty.

- 3) According to the object to which the financial support is directed—the product, organisation, or worker in the sector—we distinguish
 - project support for product creation (through organisation or creator);

- structural support for the organisation (covering or eliminating fixed costs such as rent and tax); and
 - social support for employees in the sector who have lost their jobs.
- 4) According to the institution that implements (i.e. legitimises and provides for financially) the specific support measure, we distinguish international supranational organisations, governments, regional authorities, film agencies, media regulators, copyright companies, and stakeholders in the sector.

Public institutions in many countries, both independent organisations and professional associations in CCIS, have carried out studies mapping their needs and anticipating what would be the best measures for them. It is important to address the crisis in audiovisual markets and sectors by identifying which instruments and how much must be decided. In order to manage more effectively and efficiently in a period of economic and social insecurity, several studies have been conducted, including relevant ones such as “The impact of COVID 19 on media economics” (Poland); “Assessment of the crisis and its impact on culture” (Ireland); “Need for new forms of support for journalism and freedom of expression” (Finland). Notably, in these countries the measures applied are not fragmented but cover all stages of the production chain in the film industry. In searching for effective measures to support, professional organisations in culture have engaged more actively at the national and at EU policy levels to make their case. "Over 30 surveys of the needs of these sectors, were initiated by the professional associates across Europe and the world" (ECF-CAE, 2020, p.15).

Horizontal support measures

Horizontal support measures have emerged in every European country. They are usually short-term and have social goals. These exceptional measures relate to the deferral of tax receivables, support for small- and medium-sized enterprises, the granting of interest-free loans, compensation for lost income, and social assistance with age or income criteria. Without being specifically targeted at the culture sector, part of this support can reach the audiovisual sector, as most of the companies in it are micro-enterprises and the self-employed are strongly represented in it. The AV industry is traditionally characterised by a variety of employment contracts, high shares of non-standard employment relations, and self-employment (as of 2013, 22% were self-employed) (ICF CS Ltd, 2016).

According to a CAE-ECF study conducted in 25 European countries, however, horizontal support measures do not always reach the culture sector. Sixty-nine percent of the CAE-ECF survey respondents reported that emergency measures for supporting arts and culture sectors existed in their countries, and 30% mentioned that there were no measures in their countries or that the existing measures did not include cultural and creative workers or organisations adequately.

Support for the film industry

Chronologically, the first to be affected by the pandemic were the last in the value chain: cinema exhibitions and festivals. According to the International Union of Cinemas (UNIC, 2020), only 2% of all cinemas in Europe were open at the end of April 2020. In support of closed cinemas were the first measures aimed at recovering, to some extent, the losses from their closure and at supporting their

future activities. The financial amount of the aid varied and was both unconditional aid (Italy) and aid related to certain criteria (Greece):

- 1) Italy: grant from the state, as direct aid to cinemas in the amount of EUR 20 million. Each cinema hall could receive EUR 10,000.
- 2) Spain: extraordinary support of EUR 13,252,000 for cinema exhibitions, including campaigns to bring viewers back to the cinema, as well as a "Plan for the transition to a new normal."
- 3) Finland: Additional funds of EUR 1 million to ensure the future operation of cinemas and EUR 1 million for postponed festivals.
- 4) Greece: financial aid for cinemas with one or two screens and which must have shown at least two Greek or European films in a certain period.
- 5) Denmark: three programs for compensation of missed events, including in the field of AV.

Some festivals that did not take place during the pandemic period received compensation or direct support from the state through the National Film Agency. Financial assistance for failed cultural events was directed institutionally (for a distribution organisation or for a festival organisation). We are examining other solutions aimed at streaming broadcasts of all or part of the film competitions (Goya Festival, Spain; Sofia Film Fest, Sofia; Annecy International Animation Festival; Vilnius Film Festival); broadcasting through platforms or creating screening platforms (Norway); creating outdoor shows (in summer); and creating an online movie market (Cannes).

No stage of the audiovisual production chain in Europe has been unaffected by the COVID-19 crisis. While there is support, the overall national programs to support the film industry are fewer. More additional funds and overall support along the value chain are available in the large European markets (Spain, Italy, and France) that have also recorded large losses from COVID-19.

Germany takes a complete approach to supporting the film industry. All liabilities to the National Film Agency are deferred, and each stage receives additional funding of up to 30% of the original production costs, up to 50% of the original distribution costs, and up to 30% of the original screening costs.

Other European countries support the film industry with smaller funds but with various measures that have strategic aspects: in Ireland, support for young screenwriters and for companies in the sector; and in Poland, a focus on the creation and distribution of content on the internet through the Culture on the Web program.

The scope of exceptional grants in Denmark is throughout the value chain, with a focus on long-term sustainability. All self-employed, as well as SMEs are compensated, with a proven drop in turnover of at least 30%. Postponed and discontinued productions receive additional funds, and an additional session was announced to support screenplays for films whose screening did not take place. Marketing costs are also subsidised to run on an online platform. At the initiative of various film associations, an online educational platform for training directors, "Video tutorials in a corona-age," is being created.

Support at each stage in the creation of the film product

It can be assumed that the differences in the form, direction, and amount of aid in different countries reflect the lack or presence of several main factors: national cultural policy, strategy for film industry development, economic opportunities in the market and the state, and the power of the main professional organisations in the sector.

If we trace the stages in the creation of the film product, the following forms of support can be seen in the European Union.

- scripting support increases funding through additional funds or through new programs (Germany, Denmark, Poland, Norway, Ireland, and for young screenwriters emerging talent);
- support for project development through additional project funds which supports not only the producers but, indirectly, the directors and screenwriters working with them (in Norway and Greece, EUR 1.8 million for the development of documentary, short, and animation projects);
- support for the creation of new projects, through additional funds to existing programs or through new funding programs (in France, a EUR 50 million commitment from the President; in Ireland, an additional EUR 2 million, as well as new funding of up to EUR 1 million for small companies with smaller slates; and in Poland, creation of a new support programme for artists, creators, and institutions for the digital creation and dissemination of creative content on the Internet, with a programme budget of PLN 20 million);
- support for projects that have had interrupted shooting processes due to the pandemic, with additional funding for the incurred additional costs available in many European countries;
- support for the distribution stage, with increased marketing funds and financial support for online display (in Portugal, the limit for state support for distribution and festivals increases from 15 to 30% per project; in Poland, a new support program, "Culture on the Web");
- support for access to film products, including creation of online platforms for showing national film production, streaming access to festival screenings, and free streaming of Croatia and European works on various platforms in Croatia; and
- support for education in the film industry, most often through initiatives of professional organisations in the sector, conducted online, and for this purpose special platforms have been created (Denmark, Ireland).

Legislative changes

At the distribution stage, overcoming the consequences of the pandemic also requires legislative changes. The change is related to the inability of many films to have their first screening in cinemas. Amendments to the Act on Cinematography allowed film premieres on VOD platforms, on the Internet, and on television. A change in the law assumed that the first window for showing may not be a cinema but an online platform or television show (Spain). In Poland, this also has led to a change in the definition of a film. These changes are made in order for films that do not have their first screening in cinemas to have access to future festival appearances. The European Film Academy

decided to exceptionally extend its eligibility rules for films eligible to participate in the European Film Awards 2020, removing the need for an official first screening.

As an anti-crisis measure, Poland introduced a 1.5% levy collected from on-demand audiovisual media services that was included in the update of the anti-crisis protection with the aim of strengthening the Polish film market.

New legislation to address the economic and social impact of COVID-19 in the field of culture also exists in Spain's Royal Decret 17/2020. Its goal is to build a comprehensive system to support the cultural ecosystem of employment, production, and access. This legislation guarantees access to finance for SMEs through loans and guarantee financing. A guarantee fund has been created, the Sociedad De Garantid Reciproca Audiovisual Franzas. The guarantor is the Ministry of Culture and Sports (EUR 20 million), and any financial entity can be a partner. The total amount of support for the culture sector is EUR 720 million, of which for audiovisual is not less than EUR 40 million. The percentage and amount of tax relief is also increasing; the goal is to stimulate the industry and attract co-productions. "Registered producers will be entitled to increase tax deduction for expenses incurred in Spain. The maximum amount to be deducted will increase from EUR 3 million to EUR 10 million " (Jefatura del Estado, 2020).

Stakeholders and partnerships

In the audiovisual industry, key stakeholders have come together to make calls for action and specific recommendations to European and national decision-makers to minimize the economic, social, and cultural impacts of the crisis. The organisations of producers, directors, distributors, and copyright companies have emphasised the specifics of the sector and offered specific support measures tailored to the individual elements in the production chain:

- Joint Declaration of Animation in Europe, CEPI, EUROKINEMA, FIA, FIAPF, FERA, FSE, UNI MEI (52 organisations from the film and audiovisual sector in Europe): "Fighting the global COVID-19 crisis in the film and television production sector." Direct subsidies are granted to help cover immediate fixed costs, including employment, while ensuring that they remain above and beyond production and distribution support from funding bodies. Subsidies should be preferred to loans. Loan guarantees do not fit with the specificities of the audiovisual sector: many production companies cannot provide securities or collateral to the extent required for loans since IP rights are not qualified as collateral (CEPI, 2020).
- Joint Film and Audiovisual Sector COVID-19 Statement (5 May 2020), signed by FERA and 116 organisations: "Our sector could play a major role in the healing and recovery processes that our societies are going to face in the months and years ahead, but only if its basic infrastructure can be saved" (FERA, 2020).
- Europa Distribution and FIAD have called for urgent support to mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 crisis on film distribution in order to avoid a long-term catastrophe. They offer a list of recommendations for measures to be adopted at national and European levels (Europa Distribution and FIAD, 2020).

- GESAC has joined over 90 other organisations in calling on EU leaders to revise the European Commission’s proposals for the creative sector “NEXT GENERATION” and to “invest in Europe’s next generation by investing in culture”(GESAC, 2020).

In the conditions of public–private partnerships, many crisis funds have been launched for social support for creative and technical teams and professionals. Here the funds are provided by the states and the national film agencies. In larger markets, the base of support organisations is expanding to include leading professional organisations. Collecting societies have also supported their constituencies (the authors) by providing them financial support, or information free of charge. Some amount of support has been tied to the age or contribution of the particular artist or the amount of income they receive. The amounts could be one-off or monthly for a certain period of time and vary from EUR 200 to EUR 1,500 (again, directly depending on the specific market and opportunities).

In addition to social goals, many partnerships between the state and private organisations stimulate the trend towards digitalization in cinema. Such a partnership initiative is the MOJEEKINO.PL project. “It is an online platform created to allow cinema distributors and theaters to cooperate in the online distribution of films. The partners are: Polish Film Academy, Polish Chamber of Audiovisual Producers, Culture Without Barriers Foundation. The project is implemented with the support of the Polish Film Institute.”

The American streaming company Netflix is also a partner in social initiatives aimed at audiovisual workers. The support amounts to EUR 1 million each for the five main European markets: Italy, Spain, France, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. Europe has been among the fastest-growing markets for this company during the last 12 months. According to Ampere Analysis, globally and in a pandemic, the big winner will be streaming; their forecast is for 12% additional revenue growth over the five-year forecast period (Petrov, 2020).

Support to the television industry

The trend is not surprising; what is important is the answer that the audiovisual sector in Europe can give, the balance of which most researchers define as fragile: "A fragile balance would probably be the most accurate way to describe the pre-COVID-19 crisis of the European audiovisual sector. Key characteristics include a stagnation of resources: television advertising, although resisting better than print, is challenged by Internet advertising; Linear pay television is challenged by SVOD; and a massive number of consumers switching from pay television to SVOD" (EAO, 2020, p.2).

The television business is going through a difficult period, despite its undeniably growing audience during lockdown. For commercial television, the main source of revenue is advertising: "TV advertising dropped, despite increasing audiences, as advertising is not correlated with audiences but with general economic welfare. Initial figures suggest that the television advertising market could decrease by 15% to 20% in 2020 compared to 2019" (EAO, 2020, p.6).

During the first few months of the pandemic, the demand for sustainability in the European television industries took several directions:

- In implementing the mission in a health, economic, and social crisis, public service media (PSM) adapted their content and programming by creating new educational and cultural channels and programmes, channels, and programmes with specialised information about the pandemic. There was also a change in the programming of commercial media, as well as support for them to create social content (Latvian).
- Media regulators massively initiated the fight against misinformation and to achieve high standards in journalism. For this purpose, online resources for media literacy were also provided. The French media regulator CSA called for "special attention to the actions of the platforms in times of crisis."
- The weakest units in the geography of television business - independent small regional media were subject to financial support:
 - Thuringia (Germany): one-time state aid for local television operators;
 - Italy: support for regional radio and television broadcasters through extraordinary access tax credit for advertising investments;
 - The Netherlands: new state support for local and regional broadcasters;
 - Support for the production of independent television producers:
 - Televisao de Portugal: support for independent AV producers by purchasing display rights for their products and broadcasting them on television or online platforms
 - BBC: a fund to support small independent producers in television through a small indie fund and "increase investment in archive and acquisition rights during the COVID-19 period in a bid to 'broaden the range of content available to audiences'" (Middleton, 2020)
- Financial support for freelance journalists (e.g. Croatia has established social fund).

These short-term and urgent measures are mainly related to the changed content and the new information expectations of the citizens towards television. Here, unlike the film industry, there are fewer financial resources, as well as the emergence of new programs and funds. Unlike the project financing of the film industry for independent producers, revenues for television, with the exception of advertising, have a one-year predictability. "A significant proportion of linear pay-TV subscribers are bound by one-year contracts. The cancellation of subscriptions may therefore be postponed until the renewal date. The media service providers' public resources are defined on a yearly basis. Even if short-term budget cuts cannot be totally discarded, austerity measures on the PSMs' budgets may take place in 2021. ...Hence, even in the (optimistic) hypothesis of a fast 'rebound' after the end of the lockdown, the effects of the COVID-19 crisis are still likely to be felt well into 2021" (EAO, 2020, p.6).

Games

The global games industry was expected to register an annual growth rate of 12% during the period 2020–2025 (IMARC Group, 2019). The video games sector in Europe experienced its strongest growth (+5.8% per year) between 2013 and 2019, more than doubling its turnover in six years, which was due mostly due to the growth of its online activity in the main European markets (+155% in France, the UK, Germany, and Spain combined) (GESAC, 2021). During the first year of COVID-19, video games were the only audiovisual industry that did not decline, and it has shown by the end of 2020 a growth of 9% (ibid.) The global revenue of the gaming industry has risen with about 8.4% between 2020 and

2021, mostly due to the increase in social and casual gaming. The estimates by PwC for 2022–2025 are that this trend will continue (PwC 2022).

Looking ahead

The measures taken in the short term are passive: they try to compensate for the losses caused in the sector and most often have a horizontal nature and social aspect. In Europe, and in particular in individual European markets, measures to support the AV sector have reaffirmed the inevitable role of the nation state (especially in the film industry) and revealed the strength of stakeholders in the audiovisual sector.

Proactive measures that have long horizons are those that enable sustainability in the sector, stimulating new business models, practices, and trends.

The crisis has accelerated latent trends in the audiovisual sector, making them more visible and somewhat without alternatives: for digitalisation, new digital cinema channels, a more secure internet environment, and better media literacy of consumers; for a spillover of television advertising to social media; and to consolidate the power of multi-platform companies (e.g. GAFA) as oligopolies in a networked environment.

These trends are the environment for the emergence of new business models, of which European audiovisual is not yet ready to take the best:

- Transition from paid television to streaming services.
- European platforms such as NETFLIX, UniversCinéa, MUBI, Tënk, Cinetek, the site Arte, and Filtov are not among the leaders in the global aspect, are relatively newer, and do not always have profitable business models in place (e.g. the film can be bought or rented but there is not always a subscription option).
- Shifting from exhibition in the cinema hall (as the first exhibition window) to digital platforms.
- Screening in cinemas will be a major window for blockbusters but with the potential for synergy and even displacement from the distribution of digital art cinema platforms, according to an analysis by Jean-Marc Quinton (2020). However, "The much-hyped increase in online film audiences has created a route to release for some films but it only represents a fraction of the revenues generated by a full theatrically led campaign. Indeed, online success is still more severely linked to successful physical release" (Europa Distribution and FIAD, 2020).
- Multiplatform ecosystems have emerged as new global oligopolies in a networked environment. Their main resource is the users, not the content. All business models outside their ecosystem are in unequal competition with them.

The European media and the European film industry have their economic and cultural ecosystems. They are creating economic value along their sectoral production chains. Multiplatform ecosystems in which cultural industries are one of the elements, do not simply transform into individual consumers' models (with individual choices of consumption place, time and medium). They turn their users into a

resource. The audience is a bargaining chip that they can transfer between the various participants in the system, offering applications from banking and health services to streaming music and movies.

These emerging business models need balance before they can become sustainable practices. A regulatory balance is needed to find "solutions that balance innovation, consumer welfare and corporate responsibility of every stakeholder" (WEF,2020).

The European audiovisual industry is facing changes that are accelerating from the pressure of the crisis and for which solutions are to be sought at the national and European levels.

Conclusions

In the past decade and a half, the Council of Europe has retained a softer policy-making signature in the European audiovisual and cultural sectors and has gradually reduced its cultural competencies to become a guardian of the CoE conventions, which have set the stage for European audiovisual cooperation. At the same time, the EU has expanded its competencies in the audiovisual field through legislative and subsidiarity measures to become the most prominent European-level film policymaking actor today (Barbato, 2008, Vinck and Lindmark, 2012). The EU audiovisual directives (TWF to become AVMSD) have evolved into fully fledged frameworks for the EU common audiovisual market but also as a guarantee of pluralism, access, and fundamental rights of citizens, as well as the internet safety of the users, specifically minors and vulnerable groups.

The European film industry has continued to be part of the EU "cultural policy" remit through its specific State Aid exception, allowing Member States to directly subsidise national productions and international co-productions, as well as through project subsidies via the MEDIA programme. In the 30 years of its existence, MEDIA has expanded its support to all phases of the audiovisual value chain, including working on audiences and business modelling. Since 2014, game development has also been part of the programme's remit. EU support is complemented nationally by direct public subsidies allowed under State Aid, as well as indirectly via fiscal incentives.

The gaming industry in Europe functions on a purely competitive market basis, and it has made a substantial and steady growth in the past decade, which remained uninterrupted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

1.2 Production network configuration of the audiovisual industries

1.2.1 Film industry

Identification of the key phases of the film industry production network

In the film industry, value is created primarily at the production stage but is also added at the distribution stage via product marketing and advertising. Film distribution, as an intermediary between the producer and the consumer or audience is key in rendering product value. Displaying films in cinema theatres may create additional marketing effects and added value through the viewers (word-of-mouth dissemination or the influence of the so-called reference group as a factor in demand). Additional value is created by the usage of new technologies, which results in reduced shooting time and production costs, as well as increased aesthetic value that improves audiences' satisfaction and aesthetic experience with the film (3D cinema, Dolby stereo sound, etc.).

Creation

The creation phase consists of the development of the project ideas, writing the script, and the creation of a screenplay by the author (scriptwriter, director, or another creative professional). At this phase, the producer acquires the rights and ensures the pre-financing, prepares the production budget, establishes the locations, books the facilities, and arranges the scenes. At this most risky stage of the idea development, the director and the producer attract film stars to the team, who are supposed to attract the interest of potential funders to secure pre-financing of the film. Thus, the monopoly of "the stars pyramid" pays off, as renowned names guarantee the trust of the investors pre-financing the film. At this phase, the main resource is the talent of the script creator, while the film director adds value by creating a director's book. Creation is completed by securing the budget, hiring the crew, signing the contracts, and arranging the formalities needed to start the production phase, all done by the producer.

Production

The production phase consists of the shooting and post-shooting processes, film financing, involvement in content production, and negotiation of commercial agreements for distribution and post-production, such as editing, sound-tracking, and effects.

The most powerful role in this phase is that of the producer, who is also ensuring the funding of the project. Possible sources of financing for film production are national specialised funds (estimated to about EUR 2.1 billion per year) (KEA, 2017), European sectoral programmes such as MEDIA and Eurimages, television broadcasters, film distributors, credit institutions, and private investors (rather exceptionally in some countries). Power, under certain conditions, is also held by those who invest in

the film production. The film product is unique, very costly to produce, and contains high investment risks. A film is created by several authors, among whom the film director has a major role in artistic and creative value creation that is inseparable from the value created by the actors, cinematographers, and other co-owners of the product copyright. Specialised technical teams contributing to its creation can also produce creative value. This is possible mostly when these competences or services are scarce in the country (e.g. Bulgaria) and there is trade union protection.

Distribution and Exhibition

The distribution of films can be physical (in cinema theatres), through national or territorial, broadcasting and cable retransmission (cable television, pay television, free-to-air television). The online film distribution includes digital distribution via over-the-top (OTT) services and video-on-demand (VoD) (ibid), as well as sale of rights and bundling.

Distribution is key for assigning value to the created product. Distributors buy the commercial screening rights; hence, they can add extra value via product marketing (e.g., “Cinema Secret”) (KEA, 2017). Small independent distributors dominate the market. They are represented only nationally and do not guarantee international screenings. In some national markets, there are a few large distributors (an oligopoly structure) and many small distributors. A few European distribution companies also operate internationally, such as Pathé Distribution, UGC, and Kinopolis Film Distribution (ibid).

Digitisation has created new distribution opportunities, creating new distributional windows for film productions. Yet cinema theatres remain the best place for market realisation of fiction films. Although cinema shows do not generate the highest revenue, they add the most value via the film’s marketing and promotion. The highest profits come from the paid television channels. Revenues from digital VOD channels are a promising channel for film exchange; however, VOD represents only 5% of the revenues (ibid).

Archive (video library, digital archive, educational aspects, cultural heritage)

At this phase, there is a possibility to add value by re-selling through specialised platforms. Use and re-use of the film from an archive can be done by specialised libraries, both analogue and digital. Digital libraries, or “mediathèques,” could add value to the archive (by subscription), to the creators (by copyright), and to the buyers (schools, researchers, universities, and individual users).

Governance typologies in the film industry

In the film industry, we could observe a variety of governance models. Many of them overlap, and we could also see several sub-models combined into one business model. It is complicated to distinguish between models because each film has its own specific business model (Vitkauskaitė, 2020) adapted to its unique features.

For example, the model of major film studios is characterised by vertical integration. However, the studio model, in which part of a conglomerate can unite the production and distribution not only of films but also of television production, games, streaming platforms, and even amusement parks. This

leads to horizontal integration and the emergence of a very different management and business model. The studio model also includes a) a market-oriented model, in which the market role is key; b) horizontal integration, hence expansion into new markets; c) a product-oriented model in which the quality of the film plays a vital role; and d) a 2.0 business model or digital business model, which can also exist as a stand-alone business models, integrated models that complement each other, or other business models (ibid.).

In the case of European film production, studios do not define the sector unlike the small independent production companies. For independent companies, horizontal integration is possible. They have power over the whole value chain, and we could undoubtedly consider them as leader firms in the film production network. Their power has a strong dispersion towards the other actors. This is particularly evident in co-productions. In this production network, we also observe key roles and strong positions of film distributors who can capture part of the value and have the role of gatekeepers.

In the EU, the film industry comprises multiple fragmented sub-markets, each representing an element of the value chain. **The major subjects (market players) in the European film industry can be divided into several types.**

First, there are micro-, small-, or medium-sized companies, autonomous in organisational and economic regards and independent market participants. The role of the independent producer is a leading one in European audiovisual policy, in which "Audiovisual media services are more cultural than economic ones" (Directive 2007/65/EU), and cinema falls explicitly in the "cultural exception" column. Independent producers are also the most numerous organisational units in the European film industry. They are participants in the creation and production stages and control the film's commercial exploitation. Recently, they have also been trying to enter the distribution stage, with the same firms registering a second company aimed at the distribution stage. Their participation in this sub-market has not been, on the whole, successful. Independent producers rarely have portfolios (catalogues) of several films in development and production and most often work on one, which makes them vulnerable on the market. Very often, they work in the television and advertising markets as a means of financial stability for the company. Not all European funds and national film institutions accept "under the line" costs, or company overhead costs, as eligible costs in a film's budget.

This network is production company-led with a strong national dispersion; the concentration is primarily horizontal at the production stage, with vertical concentration as an exception. Territorial concentration exists in larger cities where the emergence of audiovisual clusters is also possible.

Second, there are several major film studios in Eastern and Central Europe offering a full closed cycle of production services, including Barandov and Bufthea (offering horizontal integration at the production level).

Third, we can also distinguish a limited number of major European producers with vertical integration (production–distribution and/or screening), such as Pathé, Nordisk, UGC, and KIVIC. They have over a

5% market share in production, distribution and/or screening on the European market (KEA et al., 2017).

Fourth, but not least, with a structure that is one of the dominant ones globally, are Hollywood studios. The majors are vertically integrated structures, which themselves are part of conglomerates. The Big Five—Walt Disney Pictures—WD (bought by Twentieth Century Fox in 2019), Warner Bros.—AT&T, Universal Pictures—Comcast, Columbia Pictures—Sony, and Paramount Pictures—Viacom—have strong presences in the European market.

Still, one thing remains unchanged: the US movie industry's dominance. Despite a high production rate in the EU - 1,650 feature films a year were produced on average in the EU between 2012 and 2016 - US blockbusters still take the biggest slice of the cake at the box office. (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2018)

A fifth variant, as a typology of rising power management, is streaming platforms. Their asset and strength is their ability to distribute widely. They offer new distribution channels, such as VOD, but not only these. In recent years, they have also become content creators for film and television. The model they use could include both creation of their own movie and television content (e.g. NETFLIX), as well as cooperating (e.g. Amazon, Sony, and Paramount contract to create movies for Amazon Prime's video streaming service). Most often, the streaming platforms are part of the new global players, the **multi-platform media**. Third-party content distribution and management makes them strategic partners. Creating their own content, in addition to unlimited access to consumers, establishes them as a leading market power in the future. Platforms can also cause asymmetry in the network towards labour depreciation and devaluation, as well as oversupply of content. However, at the same time, access without restriction on time, place, and device is democratizing the system of consumption and drives the disappearance of the classic movie-screening infrastructure.

In the film industry's structure of power and control, we observe several key aspects:

- The film industry in Europe is underfinanced. Although the budgets of the produced films may range from EUR 300,000 to 11 million (ibid), the sector is heavily dependent on state funding. Producers cannot reduce costs since they are not part of vertical integration, and state funding has a key role. The state also forms the legislative environment for the sector in the different countries.
- TV broadcasters and distributors involved in pre-financing at development stage or later, as co-producers, also have control over the product and future revenues.
- The producer, as an authorized entity holding the commercial copyright, also has strong power and control over the value chain both at the production stage and with the subsequent copyright use.
- Distribution companies have strong power roles, especially if they have vertical integration with the screening (the cinemas). They can define the screening conditions, and they also create and form demand, making supply policies. The European market at the distribution stage is dominated by representatives of the leading American distribution companies (the

big six: 20th Century Fox, Warner, Paramount Pictures, Columbia, Disney, and Universal); they receive 63% of the box office of the European market (ibid).

There are two types of asset resources. The first resource is the created product and the revenue from it. The box office profit ratio between the manufacturer (the creative team) and the distributor is an indicator of power distribution. When a distributor has oligopoly power and is representative of large international companies, the distributor can receive 70% of ticket revenue.

The second resource is public access, that is, the possibility of the film being shown in public, or in other words, to be socialized. Access and visibility in the era of oversupply is determined by several factors:

- the number of distribution windows to which the movie has access, including large screen, VOD, streaming platform, pay television, and premium channels;
- the timing of the distribution windows, and the number of weeks on screen are very important;
- the ability to overcome information asymmetry such that the audience understands the appearance of the film and is interested; to buy a ticket depends on advertising agencies, festival events, film criticism, and specialised sales agent who will direct the film to the exact markets. Each of these market participants adds value to the product by contributing to its socialization.

The added value at this stage is in proportion to the power that each player has, first in making the movie accessible to the public and second, in increasing their revenues:

- There is scope for collective action among workers to influence the labour conditions.
- From an institutional aspect, two focus points are being outlined. First is the state, through financing from and the rules definition for this specific market in the creation of an economic (e.g. producer support rules) and cultural values (e.g. the existence of a culture test related to tax incentives or other forms of economic instruments). Second is the distributors who are emerging as gatekeepers of the market. They are mediators who may capture some of the value, but they add value as well. Much of the added value has explicit cultural dimensions projecting images that reflect particular approaches to societal issues. That is why the leading presence of the major American distributors on the European market has not only economic parameters.

Small production companies cannot control their film's screening and distribution. Without public funding, sustainable development of film production is impossible. However, public (state) funding is focused on production and not on marketing and distribution. This fragmentation of the market and the under-capitalisation of production is a major problem in the European film market.

European films cannot reach international markets.¹⁶ The barriers that limit them are diverse, but some of them relate to the structure of the European film industry:

- The value chain is fragmented. The phases of value creation are not vertically integrated, as in Hollywood.
- Production is the focus of state support. Financial support for film exhibition and film distribution is low and hence insufficient to overcome the pressure of US blockbusters.
- The inability to concentrate production leads to an inability to economize in scope.
- The film industry value chain is insufficiently financed, which limits the opportunities for new technologies and innovations to enter.

Barriers to entry into the film industry can be:

- High fixed capital for film production and marketing. This barrier can distort competition in the quasi-market by shifting it towards competition for subsidy.
- High minimum-efficiency scale in looking for economies of scale but also of scope. This natural characteristic of the audiovisual market creates difficulties for the sustainable development of companies and their retention on the market. Co-productions are the solution to overcoming the small internal market, and the distribution of more movie copies is the solution, which allows maximum product conversion in the largest number of cinemas.
- Monopoly on copyrighted parts of the product, for example on music and scripts.
- Specific education requirements for the filmmakers to be eligible for public funding.

To overcome some of these market weaknesses in the European film industry, European film producers collaborate in co-productions, and the EU has established specific legislation and policies for support.

European instruments for support of the film industry

Europe has been able to build a complete financial ecosystem in the European audiovisual production industry (EAO, 2017), which includes:

- **Support by film funds.** Each European country has set up film funds at the national and sometimes at the regional and/or local levels. According to the report by the European Audiovisual Observatory from 2016, there are over 250 such funds across Europe that operate on the national, subnational, and supranational levels. Altogether, the public film funds have EUR 2.53 billion at their disposal to support all phases in the film value chain.
- **Tax incentive schemes** to entice investment into the production business.

¹⁶ The main difference between the US and European audiovisual industries lies in the market share that the players of each respective region have gained in the other. US films accounts for 66 % of admissions in Europe, whereas European films comprise only 2% of US cinema admissions. US films accounts for half of all films available on video on demand in Europe. (Blazquez, F. at al., 2019).

- **Television and VOD quotas.** The Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) contains rules for linear and non-linear audiovisual media services.
- **Investment obligations.** In respect of the obligation under Article 17 (AVMSD) to support independent productions, half of the Member States have opted for a financial contribution, as provided for by the Directive; the other half have opted for a share in broadcasting time (while France and Italy have opted to make a financial contribution to productions) (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2018).

Specific support instruments for the European film industry emerged in the 1990s, as a political decision in response to the invasion of Hollywood films in the European markets, as well as anticipating digital technology developments. The *Eurimages* fund, established in 1989, was the first pan-European instrument supporting co-productions of feature films, exhibition, and promotion; today, it is available for the 39 Member States of the Council of Europe. The distribution strand was abandoned as of 2020. Its total annual budget is EUR 26 million. As mentioned in Section 1.1.4 above, the CoE has also founded the European Audiovisual Observatory, which collects very important data and information comparing the European audiovisual sector with global industry trends. The support takes the form of soft loans for co-production and subsidies for the promotion and exhibition of co-productions (*Eurimages* regulations, 2022). The soft loan is repaid from the first Euro of the producer's net receipts until full recoupment of the amount (Chimney, 2018).

There are also regional supranational funds uniting several countries and covering different territories. These funds aim to support co-productions in the region, but they also operate as regional networks and often have a variety of promotional initiatives. Some good examples are

- Nordisk Film & Television Fond. Established in 1990 and based in Oslo, Nordisk Film & Television Fond's primary purpose is to promote film and television productions of high quality in the five Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden) by providing support for top-up financing of feature films, television fiction and drama series, and creative documentaries.
- RE-ACT is an initiative set up in 2015 by the Croatian Audiovisual Centre, Friuli Venezia Giulia Audiovisual Fund, and Slovenian Film Centre, joined by Film Centre Serbia in 2019.
- The South Eastern Europe Cinema Network was set up in 2000. The goal is to financially support the film industry of the Southeast European states (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia, Cyprus, and Kosovo) for short and feature films co-produced between at least two of the member countries.

In 2001, the European Commission made progress, resulting in its allowing state aid for the European film industry. Article 107 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) declares state aid incompatible with the common market. However, there are exceptions from this rule, the most relevant for the cinema industry being Article 107(3)(c) and (d). According to these paragraphs, aid facilitating the development of certain economic activities, and promoting cultural and heritage conservation without affecting competition, may be considered compatible with market rules. In its Communication from 2021, the Commission set out the assessment criteria for state aid support (*ibid*). These support rules have been extended and supplemented in 2004, 2007, 2009, 2010, and 2013 and

implemented in national legislation. The latest of them is the 2013 Communication from the Commission on State aid for Films and Other Audiovisual Works, which emphasises that films play important roles, including in shaping European identities and reflecting the cultural diversity of the EU Member States. Article 4 of the Communication states the importance of aid for film producers to support their production up-front, as well as the high level of risk this implies.

Two types of state aid schemes are implemented at the national level today in the EU. First is the Individual State Aid Scheme incorporating all sub-markets in the film industry into one scheme (The EC's Notification of State Aid Scheme SA.30569 (NN33 /2010); second is the Regulation ORGO651 (Regulation 651/2014 of the European Commission), which operates four schemes for different sub-markets in the film industry with a total of EUR 50 million.

The state subsidy supports all stages of the creation of a film product: the idea, production, distribution, and exhibition. The degree of support for creating a movie product ranges from 50% to 80% (for low-budget and difficult films) of the film budget. This state aid goes through the national regulatory system (i.e. through national legislation in each country). For example, Bulgaria has general legislation affecting the sector: the annual State Budget Act of the Republic of Bulgaria, as well as the Public Finance Act, the State Aid Act, and the Rules for Implementation of the State Aid Act. There is also specialised legislation on the television and film industries, which includes the Law on Protection and Development of Culture, the Film Industry Act, the Law on Radio and Television, the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act, and the Law on the Administrative Regulation of the Production and Trade of Optical Discs, Matrixes and Other Media Containing Copyright Objects and Related Rights.

The European Parliament has also been active in the domain of film, introducing the LUX Prize in 2007, which provides access to funding for subtitling in order to make works known to a wider public (Kolokytha and Sarikakis 2018). Despite criticism of the budget of the Prize, especially amidst the crisis, LUX has expanded to include screenings of the winning films in all EU Member States (ibid).

The European Union's multiannual sectoral programme Creative Europe supports the film and audiovisual industry through its sub-programme MEDIA (Mesures pour Encourager le Développement de L'Industrie Audiovisuelle), which celebrated 30 years of its existence in 2021. MEDIA supports the development, distribution, and promotion of film and audiovisual projects. It supports the creation and production of films, television series, and documentaries, and it supports cinemas (the European cinemas network), festivals, and film marketplaces. In addition, MEDIA supports talent and film education through training and invests in audiences' development. The programme has upgraded its scope and today includes support for video games and immersive content (MEDIA programme, 2022).

Knowing that in 2019 1,881 new feature films were produced in the EU and that at least 53% of the 381 MEDIA-supported feature development projects will be successfully produced, MEDIA contributes to the creation of about 11% of European film output. (Creative Europe 2020 Monitoring Report, p. 52)

According to MEDIA Programme data, EUR 2.6 billion were invested during the period from its creation in 1991 through 2018. The programme supports per year over 400 film productions (feature films, television series, documentaries, and videogames), supports the distribution of more than 300 films, supports 1,144 cinemas in 34 countries in showing European films, invests in the training of about 2,400 professionals, and reaches out directly and indirectly to 65 million people (3.5 of them at festivals) (MEDIA website). The programme support leads to an increased number of European films being released in the European markets, as well as in increased sales of films outside their domestic markets (Creative Europe 2020). The positive effect of MEDIA promotion has been visible in the marketing of European VOD services, in increasing the number of European films in VOD catalogues, and in stimulating innovative distribution strategies (ibid).

1.2.2 Television industry

Identification of the key phases of the production network in the television industry

Creation: content and script writers, journalists, presenters

The idea of a television product (its script, or bible for the reality format) can be both owned and purchased (i.e. under license, which is common in reality formats). At this stage, the resource is talent. Content creation, when related to news, reflects, in addition to the journalist's talent, the television's financial capacity to access the coverage, event, personality, and information. In this way, any television organisation, depending on its financial capacity, can create additional value (this is especially evident in investigative journalism and television series related to travel or expensive archival material).

Production

Production in the television industry consists of content production, which may vary between in-house production by the television, external production (transmissions or films/series by external producers), and advertisement production. Service aggregation (broadcasting) in television could be private or public. Content aggregation is through Video-on-Demand (VOD), catch-up viewing, and podcasting (KEA, 2017).

Aggregation of a program, branding

The most important value is created in the programme aggregation, which is a kind of unique offer, and in branding that creates additional value for the television company. Offering the distribution of a complete programme allows for a stronger position regarding the distributor, when offering a set of programs for distribution increases the chances to ask a higher fee or price for it.

Dissemination

Pay television management and marketing, as well as OTT management and marketing, are the main dissemination channels for television production. Many new players are emerging to disseminate audiovisual content; they are mediators who capture some of the value but also add value through

advertising via social networks. The global audiovisual platforms play a central role in this phase of the value chain. However, the most profitable one remains the first distribution window.

Transmission/broadcasting

Analogue, digital, and online transmission are carried out by distributors and broadcasters, which negotiate the conditions of the transmission of a television signal to the final consumer.

Archive

Digital archives, video libraries, médiathèques, and others provide the possibility of re-selling or lending audiovisual content through specialised platforms. Archives clearly support education and provide resources for research and the use of audiovisual content; they also gather, inventorize, and protect audiovisual material, on hard copies and digitally, as cultural heritage.

Digitisation in the audiovisual sectors has diluted some of the roles and production phases in the field; hence, it is difficult to highlight the role of each phase and each participant in value creation. For instance, NETFLIX is one of the pay-television packages, but it also produces its own content and is already cooperating to create content, besides being a global distribution platform. So-called hybrid chains have appeared as well. Vertical integration in the sector has further contributed to this, merging the roles of television broadcasters, distributors, and OTT players.

Prevailing governance typology and other possible governance typologies—Television industry

The main content producers (market players) in the European television industry are

- public television broadcasters (state budget financing, from fees or taxes);
- commercial private television broadcasters; pay television falls here as a separate niche, most often offering premium content, also has the highest earnings in the sector;
- independent producers;
- OTT streaming service providers (e.g. Netflix and HBO), which are new players on this market, as well as content producers and non-linear service providers; and
- telecommunication companies that also start entering the content market from the position of distributors.

Types of governance structures

Based on the review of the literature in the preceding sections of this report, several main types of television market governance emerge. Our aspiration is to select a case study based on these models: state-funded public service broadcasters, commercial broadcasters with diverse market revenues, and specialised (“niche”) broadcasters offering so-called premium content.

In the television market, there is a wide variety of definitions concerning the business models under these forms of governance. Some authors (Baumann, Hasenpusch, 2016) highlight the shift in consumption from television content to online platforms, which has also led to the emergence of hybrid television models (IPTV, OTT-TV, etc.) and multi-platform television.

In the power and control structure of the television industry, we can distinguish several key actors:

- *The state*, as a creator of rules for the regulation of the sector, including screening quotas and ethical regulation, and an important financial source for public televisions.
- *Advertisers and viewers* (“active audience”), the two financing sources for commercial broadcasters. There is a general trend towards mainstream in order to reduce the risk of high investment costs. Striving for sustainability through increasing advertising revenues is an additional catalyst for homogenizing content (i.e. non-homogeneous products but increasingly homogeneous content).
- *National and multinational audiovisual corporations* that oligopolise the market, offer expensive and quality content, and hold the rights to large sports events or international reality shows’ license rights.
- Distributors grow power for firms, which control large chunks of distribution networks. Depending on in which part of the value chain the distributors are located, they may have different roles and powers: A.) telecommunication companies, which are providers of bundled internet and home television are a strong player, gradually displacing small cable operators from the market as local providers; B.) cable operators, who mainly retransmit content locally and are forced to set a price for the television package they offer, in accordance with the dominant television companies; and C.) VOD providers that can be independent and use the OTT model. Processes of capital concentration, which is a reflection of global media convergence, are happening in the television business. There is a vertical capital integration among television broadcasters entering the radio industry and online media, as well as horizontal engrossment (e.g. Sky/Comcast, Eurosport/Discovery, and mergers of cable broadcasters), while concentration is above all horizontal among the independent producers.

Several national private television companies and television broadcasters tend to dominate the separate national markets, which usually display an oligopolistic structure. Despite European quotas for creating content by independent producers, their survival is difficult as powerful multinationals encroach upon their markets. The power of these national television firms is primarily related to the size of the domestic market, with large firms located in Germany, France, Italy, and Spain. Globally, however, only nine of the European audiovisual groups are among the top 50 in the world (Blazquesz, F. at al., 2019).

Public broadcasters are a majority among the top 100 players on the European television market, but they have declining revenues and market power (Blazquesz, F. at al.,2019). Most of them have limited opportunities for vertical integration. Content creation and its aggregation in a programme is subsidised, but the rest of the chain is private. Very often, they are united in search of funding for better and bigger productions (e.g. expensive television series). Public television has a special place in the European audiovisual policy, and their activity and funding are tied to their public mission.

The market share of audiovisual groups of American origin is very strong (e.g. Sky/Comcast, NETFLIX, Discovery, Amazon, Viacom, Qurate, 21st Century Fox, AT&T). They generate 26% of the revenues of the top 100 European companies, and if public broadcasters are excluded, the proportion increases to 41% (Blazquesz, F. at al.,2019). Most often, they provide versions of their programs.

This market was invaded particularly strongly and quickly by the OTT content creators and SVOD services providers. A certain slowdown in this type of services in Eastern Europe is being observed. The OTT players require billions worth of budgets to create their own content. For example, NETFLIX is the ninth largest audiovisual revenue group in Europe, and Amazon is the eighteenth.

The barriers that arise for broadcasters to enter the television market are diverse:

- a license obtained from the national media regulator;
- market distortions by mastering a limited technological resource (e.g. digitalisation of the television market and the multiplexes created did not necessarily lead to market liberalization) because the prices are high for small television operators to create enough content and pay the price to access the multiplex channels, and the number of multiplexes can also be a limitation, as when they are few they acquire oligopolistic power (EAO, 2016);
- Consolidation of the television market is a natural feature of television. For television operators, it is vertical and aims at reducing production costs, and for horizontal television producers, horizontal enlargement takes place. These processes create an oligopolistic market with a large number of broadcasters grouped into media groups and conglomerates. Convergence, as a series of vertical (acquisition of television, radio, site ownership) and horizontal (acquisition of several television) enlargements can give strong market advantages to one media over the others; and
- restrictions on the concentration of media property on the basis of national laws and regulations.

The opportunities for entry and the sustainable development of a company in a television market depend on whether they are in control of a new technology, the availability of free investment capital, and national regulations on media market concentration.

Key social and institutional dimensions affecting the network configuration and dynamics

Audiovisual services in Europe have a dual character: together with their economic aspects, they are also a cultural exception. Cultural diversity, stated in Article 167 of the Agreement of Functioning of the European Union and in the UNESCO Convention for the Preservation of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions, is in the bottom line of the concept of cultural exclusion. This concept defines the political role of the state in the sector, and the socio-cultural characteristics of the audiovisual services also predetermine the need for state regulation and support.

The audiovisual industry is a network of markets and combines three things: talent (content creation), technology (an important ground for the changing business model in the digital era is how the audiovisual product is created, distributed, consumed, and preserved), and economics (advertising, entertainment, and profit goals). These industries create culture, and they can be instruments for ideology and propaganda. They form moral and aesthetic values, and they are models of behaviour (Tomova, 2017). Access to these cultural and informational goods is a universal constitutional value in the European states (Gradinarov, 2011), which is why these markets are regulated and considered from the viewpoints of ownership, financing, and concentration. In these markets, cultural diversity and media pluralism are also basic values.

The EU's role in the audiovisual field is to create a single and strong European market for audiovisual services. A pillar of this objective is the regulatory framework explained in detail in Section 1.1.4. In addition to the legislation of co-productions and state aid already mentioned (1.2.1), we reiterate the importance of the EU basic regulations that affect European television broadcasters and, more specifically, the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), which introduces common minimum standards, such as to guarantee and maintain minimum shares (quotas) of independent television producers as creators of television content, as opposed to the invasion of the US television industry. AVMSD Article 16 requires European broadcasters to reserve a minimum of 50% of their broadcast time—except for the time allocated for news, sporting events, games, advertising, teletext services, and television sales—for European works. In addition, 10% of their transmission time or 10% of their programming budget must be earmarked for independent works (Article 17, AVMSD). The minimum share of European works in VOD catalogues should be at least 30%.

It is undisputed that funding institutions have a decisive influence on the audiovisual production process. They have a resource that is scarce in Europe, which makes competition for funding strong. The effectiveness of individual financial instruments can only be judged when viewed as a whole system and applied to both cultural and economic criteria. There is no European standard assessment system, and different methodologies are used at the national level.

Countries with larger markets have a greater variety of financial instruments and greater involvement of market funds in individual funds, in the form of fees for advertisers or VOD providers. There are funds (e.g. in Germany) that support not only filmmaking but also television product creation.

The assessment of the effectiveness of different funds—national and regional (local)—is not the same. For example, there is an opinion that regional funds that have flourished over the last decade are weaker administrators of financial resources than the national and European ones. According to Marco Cucco, regional funds are in a legal vacuum, although they comply with the principle of subsidiarity. They have a variety of criteria, conditions and specifics, and this makes them difficult to predict despite their usefulness to the regional economy. Based on his assessment of the Italian audiovisual environment, he believes that "There is a clear need to strengthen the vertical axis between local governments, Member States and the EU, in the belief that everyone can deftly contribute to the management of Im activities (avoiding overlaps and political contradictions) and that the answers provided today at contingent needs (e.g. local funds provided to support the production and legitimated by the EU) must be congruent with the broadest shared development plans in the medium to long term" (Cucco, 2017).

The film industry's tax reduction is not straightforward. Their rapid entry into the EU over the last decade has been accompanied by a process of reducing or freezing direct state aid. The introduction of tax reduction is a tool for attracting foreign investments, and predominantly US investments. Questions arise, and stimulating local economic development through new jobs and investment is a plus. But this is not a unilateral economic assessment of this instrument. The people involved in these productions are mainly qualified technical staff, but the productions do not attract local creative teams of directors and screenwriters. Despite the cultural test required to fund a film under this scheme, the films produced are not part of the European value system, which in fact supports the creation of films that are competitive with European filmmaking.

We must not forget that the funds in this tax relief scheme are budgetary funds. Thus, a possible multiplier effect of these investments for the development of national film production is displaced and subsequently lost. Introducing a tax incentive requires a preliminary analysis of the country's national tax system (Andreeva, 2017).

Section 1.1.2 above explains the employment in the audiovisual industries as highly specialised, atypical, and project-based. In the film production period, for example, the working day can last up to 12 hours in difficult conditions. Labour costs represent 30–40% of the budget of a production, which is very work-intensive. Independent producers are usually part of small enterprises with a total of two to five employees, which makes them financially vulnerable. The abundance of professional associations and trade unions in the field is no surprise. Neither is their powerful position as stakeholders in the film industry and the creative sector of Europe. They represent the entire value chain and participate in the creation of sectoral regulations and other European initiatives.

According to Poort et al (2019), the positions and arguments of the professional associations, relating to territoriality and new models of film financing, can be clustered in three categories: film financing, the interest of consumers and cultural diversity, and current challenges for European film.

The most active stakeholders are (1) members of CREATIVITY WORKS and (2) contributors to joint documents) (ibid):

- Association of Commercial Television in Europe (ACT) (1) (2);
- CREATIVITY WORKS!, a coalition of organisations, federations, and associations representing Europe's cultural and creative sectors;
- EUROCINEMA, an association of cinema and television producers (1) (2);
- EUROPA DISTRIBUTION, a European network of independent film distributors (2);
- European Coordination of Independent Producers (CEPI) (1) (2);
- European Film Agency Directors (EFADs);
- European Producers Club (EPC) (2);
- Federation of European Film Directors (FERA) (2);
- Federation of Screenwriters in Europe (FSE) (1) (2);
- Independent Film & Television Alliance (IFTA) (2);
- International Federation of Actors (FIA) (2);
- International Federation of Film Distributors' Associations (FIAD) (1) (2);
- International Federation of Film Producers Associations (FIAPF) (1) (2);
- International Union of Cinemas (UNIC) (1) (2);
- International Video Federation (IVF) (1) (2); and
- Motion Picture Association of America (MPAA) (1) (2).

Professional unions of filmmakers in Central and Eastern Europe have a historical role. Some of the ideas for democratisation and freedom of artistic expression in these countries have originated from film creators, in the form of films promoting different opinions on the status quo. Some of these films were banned, or their authors became dissidents. Today, many more organisations are shaping civic professional involvement in the management of the film industry. These organisations participate in advisory and expert bodies. At the national level (e.g. in Bulgaria) these are Filmautors, Union of

Bulgarian Film Makers, Union of Bulgarian Artists, Association of Film Producers, Association of Bulgarian Film Producers, Bulgarian Association of Film Directors, Association of Film and Television Directors, Association of Bulgarian Film, Television, and Radio screenwriters, Association of Bulgarian Operators, Association of Bulgarian Film Sound, Association Academica 21, and Bulgarian Association of Independent Artists and Animation.

Film and television industry—Changes over time

Digitisation over the last decade has led to identical changes in the film and television industry, despite their different business models. Moreover, much of the technological innovation has had a spillover effect on the audiovisual sector.

During this period, hybrid business models and, accordingly, hybrid value chains emerged, cross-cutting value chains across industries: film–television–games–video. Solomon defines this phenomenon as the result of multiple, joint, and mixed business models (Salomon 2015). The new cultural models of creation and consumption are digital, and this creates a huge variety of formats (film screening windows) that reaches one product, and the way (device, place) in which the product is consumed. The result is that there are many variants of digital value creation and many variants of value distribution between different stakeholders in these sectors.

For example, Salomon shows that, in the video sector, several business models are at work and are accompanied by distinct uses: buying a DVD based on a model involving a one-off physical payment; buying a digital film based on the electronic sell-through (EST) model involving a one-off digital payment; renting a physical film in a video store, which is available in a digital format as a Video On Demand (VOD) film; and buying a subscription to a service giving access to a catalogue of films based on the Subscription Video On Demand (SVOD) model (ibid).

As a result, the network configuration in the audiovisual industry is constantly changing and has not yet reached a sustainability period. New players are emerging in the market: internet providers, telecoms, and streaming companies. New players in the role of distributors have the opportunity for strong positions of power, and some of them begin to create original content.

Table 9. Value chain in the audiovisual industry: phases, old and new players

Content creation	Aggregation of content	Distribution	End device	End customer
- Film studios - Television studios - Independent producers	- TV networks - Cable operators	- Cinema theatres - Commercial, cable, satellite television	- Television - Video player	- Passive behaviour

- Software developers - Gaming studios - Supplier of OTT services, but also creator of its own content-Netflix - TV and internet supplier-Bulsatcom with its own channel and content Channel+ - Individual consumer	- Internet suppliers - OTT suppliers - Telecommunication companies Google, Apple, iTunes, Vivacom, MTel	- Internet television (UPTV) - Internet suppliers - OTT suppliers - Telecommunication companies - Internet television platforms - Streaming platforms specialised in the secondary broadcast of film and television products - iTunes - Distribution channels/windows: VOD, PPV, Pay television, streaming platforms	- "Connected television" ¹⁷ - Computer - Tablet - Smartphone - Game console	- Interactive behaviour - Possibility to control the choice of time, device, price
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Source: The table is based on the idea of Nabyla Daidj. 2011. *Strategies in the Media Industry: Towards the Development of Co-opetition Practices?* Journal of Media Business Studies. 8(4):37-57

The results of the changes are as follows.

- A new digital value is created, reflecting changed modes of production (digital, lower value) and new ways of digital consumption (subscription, free).
- The value of physical infrastructure in content creation and distribution decreases, or the need for it even disappears. In contrast, marketing tools come to the fore.
- Traditional distinctions in the media from the point of view of creation, distribution, and display result from digitalisation of content, as well as standards and technologies for the transmission and display of digital content (ACMA, 2011, Kirilova, 2016).
- New value distribution models are emerging that are not yet sustainable due to the dynamics of business models in the cultural industries.
- Social networks are evolving into multimedia platforms where major players (Google, Amazon, FB, Apple, and Microsoft [GAFAM]) create complete ecosystems in which streaming services or content creation (movie, television product, game) is just one element. Platforms benefit from cross-selling, with their most valuable resource being consumer access. This online mode of existence makes them extremely strong players in the cultural industries market as well. Almost all the GAFEM companies have movie, television, and video streaming platforms and are starting to create their own content.
- Hybrid business models, as well as multi-platform media, drive the emergence of a new format when creating content: multimedia storytelling. In search of consumer attention, history crosses the boundaries between comics, movies, games, and television.

¹⁷ Connected television" refers to "technologies, as well as applications and interactive features that use broadband Internet to deliver on-screen television content already broadcast content, on-demand content and OTT content, and others - perhaps more sensitive to changes in patterns of consumption - prefer the concept of "Multiscreen television" - in Modot, Lambert, Moullier. 2013. *The Challenges to Connected Television*, EU p.3 [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2013/513976/IPOL-CULT_NT\(2013\)513976\(SUM01\)_BG.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2013/513976/IPOL-CULT_NT(2013)513976(SUM01)_BG.pdf) (In Bulgarian)

The digital market has also tested public broadcasting, which, in addition to declining government support, has also faced the global television market:

- Public television is not commercial, but the television content market is not geographically restricted to viewers. Therefore, national public broadcasters face not only national but also global competition in the global television content market. Public broadcasting is expected to offer content that is not infotainment, which predetermines a low rating (Tomova, 2019).
- The market for television content produced by public national television directly competes with non-linear media content (on-demand delivery) on the national market. Content creators and rightsholders are often large global players such as Netflix and HBO (SVoD). They are also available off-the-shelf via OTT delivery. New competitors are also telecoms, which, in addition to signal transmission, are beginning to offer specialised paid channels with premium content in two formats, television and online. (ibid)

Two initiatives that are beginning to take shape will affect the cultural industries in Europe, and in particular the audiovisual market:

- The EU Digital Single Market Strategy (2015) should improve cross-border content dissemination. However, there are fears related to the presale of broadcasting rights (during the creation phase). Loss of territoriality threatens money becoming unrecoverable if the order of distribution windows is disrupted by the elimination of geoblocking (Oxera and Q&Q, 2016; Tomova, 2017).
- A guarantee mechanism for financing the culture will be managed by the European Investment Fund on behalf of the European Commission in order to support SMEs and micro-, small- and medium-sized cultural organisations. Its purpose is to provide guarantees to financial intermediaries offering funding for cultural and creative products and initiatives.

Film and television industry: national variations and specificities

Factors underlying the differences in the network configuration of European countries may be:

- The degree of concentration of capital, which determines the possibility of appearance of media conglomerates. Concentration and economies of scale are crucial for the audiovisual markets.
- The specificity of national media ownership regulations on number and size would limit the process of media convergence in Europe, and the consequence is a weak opportunity to protect against the aggressive presence of US conglomerates. This is why Harcourt and Picard are calling for novel approaches to addressing ownership concerns in the contemporary environment (Harcourt and Picard, 2009).
 - According to Scheeberger (2019), market size, varying economic conditions, cultural proximity to other countries, and individual licensing regimes all play a part in explaining the sometimes-significant differences between national television landscapes, particularly regarding the total number of services based in a country. At the end of 2018, there were 11,123 television channels available in Europe, of which

5,039 were local television channels. There is a series of hubs in Europe, from which audiovisual media services serve several countries. These hubs are home to numerous pan-European brand channels and pay-on-demand services predominantly owned by large broadcasting and entertainment corporations.¹⁸

- The type and degree of penetration of new technologies in individual national markets.
 - According to the IABM Europe 2019 Annual Survey (IABM, 2019), the steps in technological change are transition to digital broadcasting, transition to HD, transition to DVB-T2, transition to new viewing experiences, OTT and multi-platform delivery, and the Digital Single Market Initiative. In this direction, they also note the following trend: As of May 2019, Romania, Albania, and Bosnia and Herzegovina were the only countries within the EU which had not completed the analogue switch-off, according to the ITU data.
 - The number of HD channels offered in Eastern Europe remains lower compared to Western Europe, and thus there are stronger expectations for HD channel growth in the Eastern part of the continent.
- The historical role of the public broadcaster in each country and sources for its financing: budget, fee, tax, advertising, and rights management. For example, a public broadcaster financed exclusively by the budget will be susceptible to political pressure, which will form a specific media system and a different network configuration.
- Accepted model for state support of the film industry: automatic or selective assistance.
- Availability of free alternative (non-budgetary) funding for film and television activities.
- The different stages of the value chain may have different leading variations across countries and will be the basis for different network configurations:
 - value creation, via producing one's own content or buying licensed production;
 - having one's own production company or hiring an outside independent producer;
 - distribution of content via cable, satellite, OTT, or DTH; and
 - signal transmission, whether analogue, digital, or IPTV.

Nevertheless, when looking at the pay-television market as a whole in Europe, there are significant differences in the penetration rate from country to country. For example, some markets such as Romania have nearly 100% pay-television penetration while the Czech Republic is one of the few in which free-to-air (FTA) services still dominate. Overall, among the 96% of households in Europe that owned a television in 2018, no fewer than 72% subscribed to a Pay-TV service. (IABM, 2019)

¹⁸ Countries in the top 10 ranking with a significant number of television channels under their national licensing regimes, and targeting other European territories, included: Sweden (i.e.,31), Bulgaria (i.e.,28), Romania (i.e.,28) and Germany (i.e.20). In Schneeberge 2019 Overall, two out of five European* countries had more than 100 television channels established in their territories, among which were also smaller audiovisual markets including the Netherlands (i.e. 253), the Czech Republic (i.e. 225), Bulgaria (i.e. 177), Greece (153) and Romania (i.e.152). (IABM,2019)

- The degree of maturity of the individual sub-markets, or the stages of value creation). Here, a distinction would be drawn between Western Europe and the emerging markets of Eastern Europe, as well as the North–South division. The 2019 IABM report confirms this territorial specificity:

Although Europe is a large collection of sovereign nations with varied economic situations, the market can be broadly divided into three sub-regions, each of which includes countries with similar broadcast and economic fundamentals. It is important to note that the division is purely geographical and thus includes both EU and non-EU countries. (IABM, 2019)

The three sub-regions delineated in the report are

- 1) North Western Europe, which is featured by very high pay-television penetration and a dominant broadcast infrastructure consisting of cable and satellite;
- 2) South Western Europe, with relatively low pay-television penetration and dependence on terrestrial transmission; and
- 3) Eastern Europe, with a moderate penetration rate of pay-television and reliance on cable and satellite distribution (IABM, 2019).

1.2.3 Gaming industry

Identification of the key phases of the production network of video game industry

Creation

At this point, the idea of the game is born. This can happen internally or based on an outsider's idea, whether through a license, a topic related to another game, or a movie. At this stage, the main actor is the studio, which is engaged with planning all other phases, including the creation of the business model and the conduct of marketing research. This phase is crucial, not only for fundraising but also in creating value.

The creation phase is highly interconnected with many players and mainly involves software development. This stage involves not only software developers but also designers (2D and 3D), just like storytelling experts, financial experts, and others who determine the genre of the game. Equally important are those who are engaged in key elements of the game, such as the creators of sound and music, as well as those involved in testing and debugging. At this stage, software and hardware are being combined by highly skilled people who work in different fields.

It is important to note that all this can be done by company internals or outsiders, as the studio can outsource some of the processes by working with partners, whose roles are also significant.

With mobile games or independent games, the team is usually significantly smaller and fewer people may perform more functions. If the developer is independent, they own the intellectual property, and if they are part of a studio, the studio owns the intellectual property.

Production/Publishing

The second phase covers preparing the game for its market debut. This includes making all-important agreements with distributors and suppliers.

The publishing process is related to making physical copies of the game for a console, and parts of the game for PCs. Mobile games must be prepared so that they can be offered in app stores, but first they must meet certain requirements imposed by the providers themselves. At this stage, software and hardware are united, and value is added during the process. In large studios, the company that developed the game can play the role of publisher.

Distribution/Trade

In online gaming, distribution happens in the digital environment. This includes games that are based on different platforms, such as social networks. Marketing is especially important in this case, as it brings value by increasing visibility among the many products available.

In mobile games, such an opportunity is provided by Google and Apple through their platforms, Google Play and App Store, as well as by many other small and less-popular digital distributors.

In e-sports, content distribution occurs through streaming platforms. In this case, the quality of the internet connection is particularly important. Therefore, this part of the industry is highly dependent on the next generation of mobile 5G networks.

Exchange/transmission

Online players can have important roles. If the game developer wants, they can offer an alpha or beta version to be tested by the audience, and then gather feedback and follow a process of troubleshooting, and even further developing gameplay in a different direction than before. In this case, the players are empowered by becoming an important part of game creation. They can be fourth-party developers when it comes to open-source models of game development or design.

Users are united in a social community resulting from the fact that games are often played in teams or in networks with a partner. Their opinions of the game's demo versions creates added value: it improves the product and is a form of marketing and promotion.

Archive

The preservation of video games is related to the archiving of digital elements such as its source code, art assets, and digital copies. In this phase, video game console emulators are created, which use software that replicates the hardware of a video game console. There is another option, migration, in which the software is re-launched on another platform while maintaining the gameplay, art assets, and narrative. There is a possibility of re-selling through specialised platforms.

Governance typologies

There are several types of games, depending on the hardware used to play them:

- 1) **PC games.** Dominating company is Steam, the developer company is Valve.
- 2) **Console games.** This market is dominated by the major hardware manufacturers Nintendo, Sony, and Microsoft.
- 3) **Handheld-based games** are played on portable consoles. A major manufacturer is Nintendo. Nokia and Sony have attempted to enter the market.
- 4) **Mobile games** are played on a smartphone or tablet.

The different games have different histories of appearance, and today they are developing with different dynamics. The biggest revenue and force of growth is being made by mobile games, which outpaced the revenue from console and computer games for the first time in 2016 (Chan, 2017).

Gaming companies generate revenue through several business models:

- 1) **Pay per download**, in which players pay a fee to acquire the app;
- 2) **Subscription**, in which users pay a monthly or annual subscription to access games, as is typical for cloud-based gaming services;
- 3) **Freemium**, in which users can try a free trial version but must then purchase the full version or make in-app purchases to acquire different elements or skills.
- 4) **Ad-supported games**, which are free but have banner advertising or other types of in-app advertising.

In the gaming industry, hardware manufacturers are often associated with software producers, which is why the sector is characterised by vertical integration between gaming developing studios (the game producers) and the game's hardware manufacturers.

Fig 1. Differences in the value chains of the different types of games

Source: EGDF, 2011

Console games are dominated by three big companies, Nintendo, Sony, and Microsoft. The enormous competition among them is an engine of innovation in the sector. To that end, they are investing heavily in R&D and trying to offer more advanced technologies to meet consumer expectations. As all three companies develop both hardware (consoles) and software (games), they need a highly skilled workforce, as well as strong relationships with many different companies and subcontractors, including component manufacturers, software developers, distributors, and resellers. All of this leads to barriers to entry for other players (Johns, 2006).

Europe is absent from the console hardware segment, and very few European companies are among the major publishers (Zackariasson and Willson, 2012).

The mobile gaming market has many distribution channels and platforms, but the main two are owned by Apple and Google. They have different forms of openness and accessibility to the users. They also have forms of vertical integration that go beyond the gaming industry to reach the film, television, and telecommunication industries.

Mobile players have diversified this vertical chain, making it possible for developers themselves to reach the market on their own. This market diversification and overcoming of the oligopoly in console and computer games have allowed European firms to enter the gaming industry.

Mainly at the development stage (i.e. during the creation of the game), these software creators make “middleware,” or the connection between the operating system and the software application, or develop a game engine (i.e. the software for designing and creating the games). For the most part, these are independent developers or independent studios with particularly strong development in recent years in Eastern Europe. An explanation of this new territorial location can be found in the good education and the low labour value of this part of Europe. The specialised financial instruments that support the sector also have roles. One of the major publishers is UBISOFT in France. Four of the 15 largest developers or publishers of mobile games are European (KEA, 2017).

In the power and control structures of the gaming industry, we can observe the following patterns. Game developers have control over their products and over the entire value chain in mobile games. In older types of games, several major manufacturers, both software and hardware publishers, dominate and control globally, although there are multiple medium and small manufacturers on the market as well. The dominant companies are vertically integrated.

Overall, the gaming industry is highly technology-dependent, which means that it is driven by innovation created both internally and externally (Johns, 2006). Its biggest influence is on electronics manufacturing and technology development (currently AR and VR, for example).

Table 10: Video games: Actor, role, and value

Actor	Developer	Publisher	Distributor	Retailer	Consumer
Role	<p>Usually a studio or small team of software engineers which creates the game;</p> <p>Can be owner of the idea;</p> <p>May specialise in a certain video console or type of games (mobile, etc.)</p> <p>May specialise in certain genre;</p> <p>Generally described like publishers.</p>	<p>Company that publishes video games;</p> <p>Often finances the project;</p> <p>Can be a distributor;</p> <p>Has a role associated with high risk;</p> <p>Acts as a gatekeeper to select the product reaching the market.</p>	<p>Delivers the games to the retailer or directly to the consumer;</p> <p>Can be the same company as developer and publisher;</p> <p>Or can have distribution contracts with the publisher.</p>	<p>Negotiates shelf space and marketing strategy with the publisher.</p>	<p>The person who plays the game;</p> <p>Can give feedback to the company.</p>
Value	<p>Owns an idea with market potential;</p> <p>Has control over other phases;</p> <p>Creates new code;</p> <p>Owns the knowledge;</p> <p>Can get funding from the publisher.</p>	<p>Final game code;</p> <p>Revenue minus distribution fee.</p>	<p>Distribution revenue;</p> <p>If the distributor is an online platform, it can generate more revenue through advertising;</p> <p>Collects big-data information about the consumers and their preferences.</p>	<p>Gets part of the sales revenue;</p> <p>Retail value.</p>	<p>Entertainment;</p> <p>Education;</p> <p>Training.</p>

Source: EGDF, 2011

Barriers to entry the video game market include

- 1) **Console market oligopoly.** These manufacturers set the conditions for anyone who wants to develop a game for their devices.
- 2) **Conglomerates** are major companies in the sector, such as Sony, that create and own the idea, build consoles, develop games, distribute them, and actively engage consumers. They have closed systems that new players in the industry do not have, making them less competitive.
- 3) **Intellectual property and multi-platform storytelling.** Some of the big companies also have movie units (e.g. Sony), which are an inexhaustible source of ideas. For example, comic book characters are used to make movies, games, and more (e.g. Sony’s Spiderman). Conglomerates use the multi-platform storytelling technique. As a result, they close the cycle both horizontally and vertically.

- 4) **High initial investment.** The mobile games market is now mature, which means it is significantly more expensive to build a free-to-play game than it was a few years ago.
- 5) **App Stores.** The app stores mostly show top-grossing and top-played games, and consumers prefer these titles.

The analysis shows that the network configuration is strongly linked to game type, as the value chains in different games change under the influence of technology. Diversity in gaming also leads to new business models based on industry innovation

Key socio-institutional dimension of the gaming industry

Some cultural aspects of the gaming industry result from its technological aspects. With the development of digital gaming platforms, more multi-player games have emerged, which is why players are becoming more social and have communities.

Games are characterised by a spillover effect, in which the boundaries of the industry intersect with those of other industries, including film, book publishing, retail (merchandising), and television, but also with key areas such as healthcare and education. This is related to the transfer of value in both directions.

According to ISFE, there is growing interest from teachers and educational institutions in including video games in educational initiatives. This happens through the gamification of classroom learning. It encourages teamwork, raises children's interest in the topics covered by the teacher, and helps students become more engaged. The impact of games on education is evidenced by a study funded by the British Academy and published in the journal *Computers in Human Behavior*. It found that girls 13–14 years of age and classified as heavy gamers (playing more than eight hours per week) were three times more likely to pursue a PSTEM degree compared to girls who were non-gamers.

In the EU, the video game industry is regulated by the Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market.

There are two major organisations at the European level:

- 1) **European Games Developer Federation (EGDF).** This organisation represents game studios based in Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Norway, Malta, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, Turkey, and the UK.
- 2) **Interactive Software Federation of Europe (ISFE)** is an independent federation that represents the interests of the software sector in Europe to major players such as EU institutions, international organisations, academia, and society. It is based in Brussels, Belgium.

At the state level are several organisations and associations whose goal is to help the industry grow. For example, the Polish Games Association's members are the largest and most popular video game developers in Poland. The Dutch Games Association was also created to make favourable conditions for the development of the Dutch gaming industry.

At the same time, there are non-profit organisations in the industry that are committed to recruiting, retaining, and supporting the development of women in the gaming industry, such as the London-based Women in Games (WIGJ).

There are also programs in Europe that aim to improve the competitiveness of the industry in the region, such as the Creative Europe programme, which supports video game ideas and projects. Its requirements include proposals that are innovative, original, and creative, but it also seeks out those that enhance Europe's cultural identity and heritage.

At both the European and national levels, the industry must comply with rules relating to fair competition, copyright, human rights, and labour. The role of the state in this strong market sector is limited to creating a stimulating environment.

At the same time, the industry relies on self-regulation, which is why the **Pan European Game Information (PEGI)** established a video game content-rating system to help European consumers make informed decisions when buying video games or apps using age recommendations and content descriptors. It is now used in 39 countries and is supported by the European Commission. In some countries, like the UK, PEGI video game ratings have become law. Although there are calls in the industry for unionization, video game developers are typically not unionized.

Overall, the video game industry is not heavily regulated at the European level because it is not very old. However, it self-regulates or relies on state-level regulation. Industry players, however, are seeking opportunities to nurture workforce diversity, share knowledge and know-how, and develop the entire ecosystem through various associations.

Gaming—changes over time

New technologies are major drivers of changes in network configuration. Games were born as offline entertainment without using electronics and internet connections. Later, however, the electronic games appeared thanks to hardware developments such as televisions and consoles (Towse, 2019). The development of the gaming industry over time is due to other devices, including PCs, smartphones, and tablets. Today, new technologies such as wearables and augmented and virtual reality are also factors in the development of the industry. They offer new revenue streams but, in the case of AR and VR, are at an early stage of development.

New technologies have made the market more open. Self-study opportunities, for example, have led to the emergence of many new developers who have taken the path of indie studios. This has led to the boom of indie studios in the industry and the disintermediation of the value chain (KEA, 2017), especially in mobile games where developers themselves distribute their games across platforms.

The digital shift and online distribution have also changed some of the tasks of software developers. Playing online games in-network is related to tasks related to network management (KEA, 2017).

Digitisation and changing processes in the industry have led to the need for people with new competencies. New professions were born (e.g. software developers, 3D animators), with new

educational opportunities. Universities have created new programs, but at the same time, new academies offering online and offline training for gaming professionals have emerged outside the traditional educational system.

Digitisation is the main reason for the change in business models in the industry and the emergence of new business models other than the traditional pay-to-play model. Today's games have different models: ad-based, subscription, freemium, and pay-per-purchase models.

The most important changes in the gaming industry network are related to the advent of mobile games, which are the fastest-growing industry within the industry and are particularly aggressive on the market. As Europe later joins the gaming industry, there is a greater evolution of mobile gaming in this market.

Due to their simpler structure and easier distribution and reachability, mobile games are becoming a factor in the emergence of more indie developers, leading to more competition in the market. Many developers are leaving big studios to create their own gaming companies. Their accumulated knowledge in the industry so far has led to the emergence of this new segment.

The birth of independent platforms and streaming has also helped mobile developers. Mobile games are cheaper to develop, require smaller teams and less development time, and are more easily distributed through the platforms in question. Due to their games' simplified structures, mobile gaming companies, which are not as cumbersome as large conglomerates and studios, are becoming more flexible and more adaptable to consumer preferences. Eventually, smaller players can cannibalize bigger ones because of their quick response and ability to offer a similar product at a lower value.

Technological changes in the industry have led to a major change in terms of power. Software developers have been empowered, making their way into independent careers. The more important change, however, relates to the transfer of power to the players themselves, who make game development decisions.

National variations and specificities in gaming—National variations and specificities

National variations depend largely on market developments. At the top of the list of countries that generate the most gaming revenue are the largest economies in the European Union.

Table 11: Top countries in EU based on game revenue

Country	Revenue
Germany	\$ 4.7 bln.
United Kingdom	\$ 4.5 bln.
France	\$ 3.1 bln.
Spain	\$ 2 bln.

Italy	\$ 2 bln.
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Source: Newzoo's Global Games Market Report

Later-emerging markets, such as those in Eastern Europe (Romania, Bulgaria, and Poland), do not generate as much revenue but are a factor in the industry from the perspective of highly skilled workers, including software developers and designers. This high level of skill is supported not by traditional education but by the presence of many specialised training academies in the IT field. In Bulgaria, for example, there are already several academies training IT staff; the main ones are the Telerik Academy and Software University. Qualified staff is the factor that drives large studios in the EU to open affiliates in Eastern European countries.

The goal of gaming companies is not only to sell their products domestically but also to seek an international scale. For this purpose, they use the localization of the game, translating it into other languages so that it is accessible to different markets. In the EU, where language barriers are large, localization is particularly important. Through this process, the full localization of the game arises. Localization could require translating text on the screen, or more substantial adaptations like recording a new voiceover or redesigning graphics, to address what is typical for the different markets. This guarantees companies a greater perception of the game by consumers and greater engagement on their part.

Territorial changes are related to the size of the market. In addition, differences in network configuration appear to be related to the market specifics of the Eastern and Western countries. Eastern countries have highly skilled workers in the video game industry, while Western countries are where the major studios are based.

European support to games industries

The MEDIA programme in the EU supports videogames as part of European cultural and creative industries. The programme focuses on the production of high-quality audiovisual content, and more specifically on the development of creative storytelling and on immersive and appealing content development, which should increase the global competitiveness and audiences of these games. The development of videogames is one of its fastest-growing segments (15% on a yearly basis). From 2014, when this type of support began, until 2020, over EUR 24 million has been awarded to 210 projects (Creative Europe 2020 Monitoring report, p.51).

PART 2. Statistical mapping of the audiovisual industries

2.1 Quantitative analysis of the radio and audiovisual industries

The audiovisual and media industries, and specifically the film, television and radio, and video game industries, are among the most dynamic markets in the cultural and creative sectors in which globalized value chains and digital platforms play a central role. These industries are best covered by statistics in Europe, compared to the rest of the CCIS (such as architecture, performing arts, or crafts). The ESS-net report (ESSnet 2012) has mapped the extant statistical codes that cover CCIS, shedding light on the main needs and shortcomings of European statistical data collection in the field. The report concludes that economic statistics collected at the European level provide good coverage of all audiovisual categories but that data is missing for some countries (ESSnet 2012, p. 323).¹⁹

This paper includes a statistical analysis and conclusions based on three information clusters: Eurostat data on audiovisual industries (outlined in Section 2.1.1. below); analysis of national statistical data in Bulgaria as represented through national mapping methodology (Section 2.2); statistical data mapping of game industries in Austria (Section 2.3); and analysis of other international data sources, more specifically, the European Audiovisual Observatory and its “satellite” monitoring tools and databases.

The following analysis maps out the statistical frameworks at the European level, in Bulgaria and Austria (the two countries covered by the fieldwork in Part 3) in order to understand how they reflect the realities of the global production networks of the audiovisual industries, to identify possible gaps or inconsistencies, and to suggest ideas for improvement.

2.1.1 Eurostat data analysis of the audiovisual industries

This section introduces the statistical mapping of the audiovisual sector at the EU level (Eurostat). For the purpose of statistical analysis of, we divide the audiovisual industries into (1) film, (2) radio and television, and (3) video games, and we analyse them separately. In each of these sub-industries, we focus on the statistical data availability for each of the GPN phases, outline key trends and findings, and make conclusions.

In the analysis of the audiovisual industries, there are three main indicators from the classification of structural business statistics (NACE codes), which allow comparative analysis: **the added value, the number of enterprises, and employment**. The data sets in this chapter cover EU 28 (including the UK), outline the leaders in each category in each phase, and include the leaders among the Central and

¹⁹ ESSnet-CULTURE European Statistical System Network on Culture FINAL REPORT, 2012 https://ec.europa.eu/assets/eac/culture/library/reports/ess-net-report_en.pdf

Eastern European cluster of EU Member States (where market-based industries have existed since 1989).

Eurostat data availability for the film Industry Global Production Network

The table below shows the level of data availability in the film industry production network at the European level. The analysis has shown three general specificities of the data collected and aggregated by Eurostat for this industry:

- There is no data available for some of the phases in the global production network.
- The usage of two-digit codes at the national level, and hence, information, cannot be provided or is not collected for these economic activities by the national statistics in all EU countries.
- For some of the four-digit codes that cover different phases in the global production network, there is overlap and distortion of information about the audiovisual sector.

Table 12. The film industry in Eurostat data by global production network phases

	NACE	NACE	Minimal	Extensive
Creation	90.03 (*)	Artistic creation	X	
Production	59.11	Motion picture, video, and television programme production	X	
	59.12	Motion picture, video, and television programme post-production	X	
Distribution	59.13	Motion picture, video, and television programme distribution	X	
	47.63	Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores	X	
	77.22	Renting of video tapes and discs	X	
Exchange	59.14	Motion picture projection activities	X	
	82.30	Organisation of conventions and trade shows		X
	58.11	Book publishing		X
	58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals		X
	73.1	Advertising		X
Archive	91.01 (*)	Library and archive activities	X	
	91.02 (*)	Museum activities		X

NACE Codes with () are available only at 2 digits in the Business Demography Database*

Eurostat data on the added value of the EU film industry²⁰

Table 13: The film industry: added value by global production network phase (in millions of EUR)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU – 28 (2013-2020)	-	20,971.8	6,173.9	3,328.1	-	30,473.8
Belgium	-	489.6	29.7	69.6	3	591.9
Bulgaria	-	53.1	4.1	8.3	240	305.5
Czechia	-	0	2.9	-	151	153.9
Denmark	-	470.9	-3.3	67.5	103	638.1
Germany	-	2,454.7	801.5	543.5	1,816	5,615.7
Estonia	-	0	1.7	7.1	33	41.8
Ireland	-	200	30.4	88.8	252	571.2
Greece	-	86.8	17.2	30	650	784
Spain	-	1,457.9	239.4	232.4	3,144	5,073.7
France	-	4442	391.4	690.6	1230	6754
Croatia	-	25.1	21.2	10.1	20	76.4
Italy	-	1,203.3	486.6	193.3	1,037	2,920.2
Cyprus	-	9.9	0.3	0	-	10.2
Latvia	-	8.3	0.9	5.4	50	64.6
Lithuania	-	14.1	2.5	8.4	31	56
Luxembourg	-	42.5	4.2	0	2	48.7
Hungary	-	56.9	68.6	20.9	368	514.4
Malta	-	0	0	-	0	-
Netherlands	-	0	8.6	199.7	2,970	3,178.3
Austria	-	295.2	5.8	62.1	205	568.1
Poland	-	213	75.9	117.1	-	406
Portugal	-	115.9	48.6	27.5	232	424
Romania	-	116.4	0.9	0	393	510.3
Slovenia	-	50.1	1.3	3.1	114	168.5
Slovakia	-	73.4	0.7	6.2	107	187.3
Finland	-	193.8	15.1	45.4	70	324.3
Sweden	-	542.1	47.2	85.7	-	675
United Kingdom	-	7,255.4	3,672	747.6	1,890	13,565
TOTAL	-	19,870.4	5,975.4	3,270.3	15,111	44,227.1

Source: Eurostat

²⁰ The data about EU includes also the United Kingdom.

By calculating the value added of the EU28 film industry across all phases of the global production network, we concluded that the **total added value of the entire production cycle of the EU film industries amounts to EUR 44,227.1 million**. The production phase has the largest share in the added value of the film industry, at EUR 19,870.4 million, followed by the archiving phase at EUR 15,111 million, the distribution phase at EUR 5,974.5 million, and the exchange phase at EUR 3,270.3 million. The analysis shows the countries with the highest value added in all phases of the global production network in film industries in Europe to be the UK at EUR 13,585 million, France at EUR 6,754 million, and Germany at EUR 5,815.7 million.

[Creation–NACE code 90 and Artistic creation and Archiving–NACE code 91.01](#)

Regarding the first and the last phases of the film industry production networks, creation and archiving, there is no Eurostat data available. For that matter, information is collected from the national statistical institutes of the Member States of the European Union (as shown in Table 8 above).

[Production–NACE code 59.11 and 59.12](#)

The analysis of Eurostat data on production (in particular, the codes 59.11 *Motion picture, video and television programme production* and 59.12 *Motion picture, video and television programme post-production*) has revealed the following facts about the EU film industry production network:

- At the EU level, the value added in the creation phase as part of the global production network is EUR 20.972 million, including its shares of the creation of films, video games, and television programmes (EUR 17.048) million and of the post-production activities for the creation of films, video games, and television programmes (EUR 3.924 million).
- The EU country with the largest market shares is the UK, with a total value added for the two codes (creation and post-production) of EUR 7.255 million. Of this, the creation of feature films, video games, and television programmes is EUR 5.121 million and post-production is EUR 2.134 million. The second-highest share of value added in the production phase is France, with EUR 4.442 million in total for the entire production phase, with value added from the production of films, television programmes, and video games amounting to EUR 3.819 million, and with post-production to EUR 623 million. Germany is also in the top three in terms of the relative size of value added, with a total in the creation phase of EUR 2.455 million, the share of value added from the creation of films, television programmes, and video games being EUR 2.170 million, and from post-production being EUR 285 million.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, Poland (EUR 175 million) and Romania (EUR 107 million) have the highest shares of value added in the creation phase.
- All EU Member States have a preponderance of added value in the production of films, television programmes, and video games, except for Bulgaria, where the added value in factor costs for the production of films, television programmes, and video games is EUR 26 million, and for post-production EUR 27 million.

Distribution – NACE codes 59.13, 47.63 and 77.22

Based on analysis of Eurostat data on the distribution phase (motion picture, video, and television programme distribution; retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores; and renting of video tapes and discs), we concluded the following:

- In the EU Member States, film distribution amounts to EUR 6.174 million. Of this, the distribution of films, television shows, and video games has the highest added value at EUR 5.899 million, followed by the sales of music and video recordings in specialised stores at EUR 194 million.
- The rental of video tapes and discs contributes the least to the added value (EUR 82 million, which has steadily decreased in the past decade due to the emergence of digital platforms and streaming). In 15 EU countries, its added value is zero.
- The top three countries in terms of value-added contribution to the EU in the film industry are the UK (EUR 3.672 million), Germany (EUR 802 million), and Italy (EUR 487 million).
- Among the Central and Eastern European countries, Poland has the highest added value at EUR 76 million, followed by Hungary at EUR 69 million.

Exchange–NACE code 59.14

The added value of activities related to the exchange of films (*Motion picture projection activities*) in the EU Member States is EUR 3.328 million. The largest share is in the UK (EUR 748 million), followed by France (EUR 691 million), Germany (EUR 544 million), Spain (EUR 232 million), the Netherlands (EUR 200 million), and Italy (EUR 193 million). Poland has the largest added value among Central and Eastern European countries at EUR 117 million. The Czech Republic has EUR 23 million, Hungary EUR 21 million, and Bulgaria EUR 8 million.

Exchange–Extended—NACE codes 82.30, 58.11, 58.14, and 73.1

In this analysis, we extended the scope of the exchange phase by adding more codes that cover activities beyond the film industry (Table 9). This was needed because of the specific reporting of the NACE codes in the Eurostat system, which did not allow us to isolate certain activities unique to the film industry. Hence, the data would not reflect an area beyond the film industry. These codes are 82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*; 58.11 *Book publishing*; 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*; and 73.1 *Advertising*.

Table 14: The film industry: added value by production phase (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	-	-	-	86,010.5	-	86,010.5
Belgium	-	-	-	1,488.1	-	1,488.1
Bulgaria	-	-	-	166.5	-	166.5
Czechia	-	-	-	900.1	-	900.1
Denmark	-	-	-	1,260.6	-	1,260.6
Germany	-	-	-	17,716.7	-	17,716.7
Estonia	-	-	-	115.4	-	115.4

Ireland	-	-	-	625.6	-	625.6
Greece	-	-	-	396.8	-	396.8
Spain	-	-	-	5,856.5	-	5,856.5
France	-	-	-	11,154.9	-	11,154.9
Croatia	-	-	-	206.2	-	206.2
Italy	-	-	-	4,912.4	-	4,912.4
Cyprus	-	-	-	46	-	46
Latvia	-	-	-	105.5	-	105.5
Lithuania	-	-	-	188.5	-	188.5
Luxembourg	-	-	-	121.7	-	121.7
Hungary	-	-	-	404.8	-	404.8
Malta	-	-	-	270	-	270
Netherlands	-	-	-	2,476.9	-	2,476.9
Austria	-	-	-	1878.5	-	1,878.5
Poland	-	-	-	2,599.1	-	2,599.1
Portugal	-	-	-	571.9	-	571.9
Romania	-	-	-	595.8	-	595.8
Slovenia	-	-	-	143.6	-	143.6
Slovakia	-	-	-	375.2	-	375.2
Finland	-	-	-	911.9	-	911.9
Sweden	-	-	-	2,380.1	-	2,380.1
United Kingdom	-	-	-	26,366.6	-	26,366.6
TOTAL	-	-	-	84,245.9	-	84,245.9

Source: Eurostat

In the larger EU Member States, five-digit statistical codes are used that allow more in-depth knowledge about the film industry and better distinguishing of activities into sub-categories.

Our analysis of the exchange- (extended-) phase statistical data about the film industry at the EU level estimated a **total value added of about EUR 86.011 million**. The largest generator of added value appears to be advertising (EUR 53.020 million), followed by publishing of magazines and periodicals (EUR 13.387 million), publishing of books (EUR 10.985 million) and organising congresses and trade fairs (EUR 8.619 million).

- The largest share of value added is the UK at EUR 26.367 million, including EUR 16.674 million from advertising, EUR 4.779 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 3.402 million from publishing books, and EUR 1.512 million from organising congresses and trade shows.

- Germany was second with EUR 17.717 million, from advertising at EUR 10.190 million, publishing magazines and periodicals at EUR 3.286 million, publishing books at EUR 2.395 million, and organising congresses and trade fairs at EUR 1.847 million.
- The country with the third-highest share of value added in the European Union is France, with EUR 11.165 million, including EUR 5.874 million from advertising, EUR 1.875 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 1.657 million from publishing books, and EUR 1.759 million from organising congresses and trade fairs.

In the Central and Eastern European countries, the country with the highest added value is Poland at EUR 2.599 million, including EUR 1.851 million from advertising, EUR 347 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 277 million from publishing books, and EUR 124 million from organising congresses and trade fairs. The Czech Republic was next in terms of value added, with EUR 900 million, including EUR 696 million from advertising, EUR 72 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 72 million from publishing books, and EUR 60 million from organising congresses and trade fairs. The value added in the exchange (extensive) phase is EUR 84.245.9 million, including the largest added value for advertising at EUR 53.020 million, as well as publishing of magazines and periodicals at EUR 13.387 million, publishing of books at EUR 10.985 million, and organising of congresses and trade fairs at EUR 8.619 million.

Eurostat data on the number of enterprises in the EU film industry

The analysis of Eurostat data about the number of enterprises in the European film industry, distributed per GPN phase, extracted data for all EU Member States (including the UK).

Table 15: The film industry: enterprises by production phase (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	0	120,436	10,244	4,240	-	134,920
Belgium	8,775	3,052	276	57	3	12,163
Bulgaria	1,209	863	112	49	240	2,473
Czechia	6,085	0	167	-	151	6,403
Denmark	3,103	2,073	83	121	103	5,483
Germany	57,296	8,623	903	810	1,816	69,449
Estonia	2,496	574	38	4	33	3,145
Ireland	6,755	2,183	259	80	252	9,529
Greece	8,335	1,186	779	183	650	11,133
Spain	39,445	6,860	1,203	476	3,144	51,128
France	53,595	17,601	964	613	1,230	74,003
Croatia	597	458	51	22	20	1,148
Italy	29,939	5,391	1,389	689	1,037	38,445
Cyprus	0	105	33	0	-	138

Latvia	1,992	390	42	18	50	2,492
Lithuania	7,303	1,185	35	14	31	8,568
Luxembourg	392	139	23	6	2	562
Hungary	13,901	5,116	253	51	368	19,689
Malta	-	0	0	-	0	-
Netherlands	81,723	14,962	481	130	2970	100,266
Austria	11,454	1,932	198	92	205	13,881
Poland	0	6,805	520	134	-	7,459
Portugal	23,889	2,416	169	65	232	26,771
Romania	8,475	1,958	129	39	393	10,994
Slovenia	5,110	1,098	31	18	114	6,371
Slovakia	1,599	2,021	134	10	107	3,871
Finland	7,006	1,077	85	65	70	8,303
Sweden	0	7,824	484	105	-	8,413
United Kingdom	33,780	22,079	1,081	271	1,890	59,101
TOTAL	415,174	117,971	9,922	4,122	15,111	561,380

Source: Eurostat

Creation

- There are **415,174 enterprises in the film industry Creation phase in the EU28**, which is about two-thirds of all firms in all phases. The largest number of firms in creation is the Netherlands, with 81,723, followed by Germany (57,296) and France (53,595).
- Central and Eastern European countries have a relatively low share in the number of enterprises in the film industry. The leader in value added in this geographic cluster, Poland, has no information available on the number of enterprises in the film industry. In this analysis, Hungary has the highest relative share in terms of number of enterprises, 13,901.

Production

Eurostat data on the production phase include the codes 59.11 *Motion picture, video and television programme production* and 59.12 *Motion picture, video and television programme post-production*. The analysis of the collected figures has shown the following:

- At the EU level, the number of enterprises in the production phase of the GPN is **117,971**, including 99,289 enterprises in the film, video game, and television programme production phase and 18,682 enterprises in the post-production phase for film, video game, and television programme production.
- The EU country with the largest share of enterprises in the production phase is the UK, with 22,079 enterprises in total for both the creation and post-production codes; of these, the enterprises in the creation of feature films, video games, and television amounted to 19,187

and post-production to 2,892 enterprises. The second largest share of the number of enterprises in this phase is France, with 17,601 enterprises in total for the entire creation phase, with the number of enterprises in the creation of films, television programmes, and video games at 15,562 and in post-production at 2,039. The Netherlands third among the EU countries in the number of enterprises in this phase, with a total of 14,962 for the creation phase, with 11,034 enterprises in the creation of films, television shows, and video games and 3,928 enterprises in post-production.

- In Central and Eastern Europe, the largest number of enterprises in the production phase are in Poland, with 6,805 enterprises, and in Romania, with 5,116.
- In all EU Member States, there is a preponderance of enterprises, as well as in the value added, in the production of films, television programmes, and video games.

Distribution

The distribution phase includes the following codes: 59.13 *Motion picture, video and television programme distribution*; 47.63 *Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores*; and 77.22 *Renting of video tapes and discs*.

The analysis of Eurostat's structural business statistics data on the number of enterprises in the distribution phase shows the following trends:

- The total number of enterprises in distribution phase in the EU Member States is 9,922. Of these, the largest number is in the distribution of films, television shows, and video games (59.13) is 3,668; the sale of music and video recordings in specialised shops comes second at 3,280; and the rental of video tapes and discs comes last at 2,974. Similar to the findings in the previous phases, this busyness is shrinking due to the platforms and streaming services.
- The top three countries by number of enterprises in film distribution in the EU are Italy at 1,389, Spain at 1,203, and the UK at 1,081.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the largest number of enterprises in the distribution phase are Poland at 520 and Hungary at 253 enterprises.

Exchange

According to NACE code 59.14 *Motion picture projection activities*, the number of enterprises engaged in activities related to the exhibition of films in the Member States of the EU is 4,122. Germany has the largest share of enterprises in this phase at 810, followed by Italy at 689 and France at 613. Poland has the largest relative share in the number of enterprises in Central and Eastern Europe at 134, followed by Hungary at 51.

Exchange–Extensive

At the EU level, the number of enterprises in the Exchange–Extensive phase (following the NACE codes 82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*; 58.11 *Book publishing*; 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*; and 73.1 *Advertising* is 380,848. This number is formed largely by advertising enterprises at 287,374, as well as by book publishing enterprises at 46,432, publishing of magazines and periodicals at 26,810, and organising congresses and trade fairs at 20,232.

Table 16: The film industry: enterprises by production phase (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	-	-	-	381,325	-	381,325
Belgium	-	-	-	8,373	3	8,376
Bulgaria	-	-	-	3,973	240	4,213
Czechia	-	-	-	21,421	151	21,572
Denmark	-	-	-	3,683	103	3,786
Germany	-	-	-	43,667	1,816	45,483
Estonia	-	-	-	1,564	33	1,597
Ireland	-	-	-	2,133	252	2,385
Greece	-	-	-	5,928	650	6,578
Spain	-	-	-	48,139	3,144	51,283
France	-	-	-	38,080	1,230	39,310
Croatia	-	-	-	2,678	20	2,698
Italy	-	-	-	25186	1037	26,223
Cyprus	-	-	-	595	-	595
Latvia	-	-	-	2,464	50	2,514
Lithuania	-	-	-	4,549	31	4,580
Luxembourg	-	-	-	567	2	569
Hungary	-	-	-	10,351	368	10,719
Malta	-	-	-	374	0	374
Netherlands	-	-	-	34,658	2,970	37,628
Austria	-	-	-	112,800	205	11,485
Poland	-	-	-	32,563	-	32,563
Portugal	-	-	-	6,297	232	6,529
Romania	-	-	-	9,548	393	9,941
Slovenia	-	-	-	2,722	114	2,836
Slovakia	-	-	-	10,078	107	10,185
Finland	-	-	-	4,187	70	4,257
Sweden	-	-	-	17,356	-	17,356
United Kingdom	-	-	-	28,434	1,890	30,324
TOTAL	-	-	-	380,848	15,111	395,959

Source: Eurostat

In total, for the codes that come out of the narrow scope of exchange in the film industry and archiving phases, the total number of enterprises is 395,959.

Archiving

NACE code 91.01 *Library and archives activities* at the level of the EU Member States is very extensive and includes the activities of libraries and archives, except for film archives, which in the Member States are usually within the same organisation. The available data in this phase could not be used as relevant for the film industry, and we extended the scope to library and archive activities.

Under this code, the data on the number of enterprises show that there are 15,111 enterprises in the EU. According to NACE code 91.02 *Museums activities*, the total number of enterprises in the EU is 15,111.

Eurostat data on employment in the EU film industry

Table 17: The film industry: employment (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	0	321,626	37,001	94,538	-	453,165
Belgium	7,647	6,378	623	798	0	15,446
Bulgaria	1,104	3,285	291	450	454	5,584
Czechia	1,754	0	276	-	505	2,535
Denmark	6,230	5,927	429	2,297	2,865	17,748
Germany	75,889	43,631	5,281	25,453	33,524	183,778
Estonia	1,097	0	49	199	54	1,399
Ireland	3,410	4,215	615	1,742	2,597	12,579
Greece	21,414	6,431	1,985	1,208	3,007	34,045
Spain	70,572	24,832	2,911	7,151	14,655	120,121
France	28,484	57,981	3,576	10,275	9,656	109,972
Croatia	547	987	250	286	147	2,217
Italy	11,866	18,503	2,878	5,786	10,506	49,539
Cyprus	0	331	32	0	-	363
Latvia	1,830	780	65	244	102	3,021
Lithuania	1,049	1,384	93	293	303	3,122
Luxembourg	118	441	29	0	0	588
Hungary	15,426	7,146	881	381	2,262	26,096
Malta	-	0	0	-	0	-
Netherlands	22,402	17,645	1,306	4,907	22,570	68,830
Austria	5,924	4,830	248	1,844	1,764	14,610
Poland	0	10,052	1,377	1,940	-	13,369
Portugal	3,496	4,389	365	1,033	1,586	10,869

Romania	3,572	4,421	288	613	1,845	10,839
Slovenia	595	1,543	62	81	301	2,582
Slovakia	795	2,727	320	50	245	4,137
Finland	2,406	3,533	508	609	288	7,344
Sweden	0	10,083	1,152	1,661	-	12,896
United Kingdom	92,095	0	4,082	0	45,183	141,360
TOTAL	379,722	241,475	30,072	69,301	154,419	874,989

Source: Eurostat

Creation

- **At the EU level, the film industry employs 874,989 people** across all the GPN phases. Germany employs the most people in the film industry (183,778), followed by the UK (141,360), and Spain (120,121).
- Central and Eastern European countries maintain a relatively low share in the number of employees in the film industry, as with the other two indicators. The region with the highest relative share in the number of employees is Hungary at 26,096, followed by Poland at 13,369.

Production

Eurostat data about employment in the production phase of the film industry include the codes 59.11 and 59.12. The analysis of employees in this production phase shows the following trends:

- At the EU level, the number of employees in film production is 241,475, which includes 206,599 employed in film, video game, and television programme production activities and 34,876 employed in post-production activities for film, video game, and television programme production.
- The EU country with the largest share of employees in the production phase is the UK - total for both codes - creation and post-production (in the data, the UK appears to have zero employees in production, which distorts the total number of employees in this phase).

Distribution

Employment in the Distribution phase is observed in the following codes: 59.13 *Motion picture, video and television programme distribution*; 47.63 *Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores*; and 77.22 *Renting of video tapes and discs*. An analysis of Eurostat's structural business statistics data on the number of employees in the film industry in the distribution phase shows the following trends:

- In the distribution phase in EU Member States are 30,072 employees in total. Within this number, the distribution of films, television programmes, and video games has the highest share (14,095), followed by the sale of music and video recordings in specialised shops (9,247). The rental of video tapes and discs comes last, with 6,730.
- The top three countries by number of employees in film distribution in the EU are Germany (5,281), the UK (4,082), and France (3,576).

- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the highest number of employees in the distribution phase are in Poland (1,377) and Hungary (881).

Exchange

On the basis of NACE code 59.14 *Motion picture projection activities*, the number of people employed in the exhibition of films in the Member States of the EU is 69,301.

- In the sample for exchange, the UK again lacks data, skewing the total number employed. Germany has the largest share of the number of enterprises in this phase, at 25,453. The next largest relative share of enterprises is France, with 10,275, and Spain, with 7,151 employees.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, Poland has the largest share in the number of employees in exchange phase (1,940), and Romania has 613.

Archiving

The data under NACE code 91.01 *Library and archives activities* show that there are 154,419 employees in the EU in this field. There is no specific distinction for film archives in this number.

Exchange–Extensive

Also considering the codes out of the narrow scope of the film industry in the exchange and archiving phases, the number of employees is estimated at 1,561,510 employees in total for both phases.

In Exchange-Extensive only (including the NACE codes 82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*, 58.11 *Book publishing*, 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*, and 73.1 *Advertising*), the number of employees in the EU is 1,407,091. Advertising again has the largest relative share of employees at 991,128, followed by organising congresses and trade fairs at 150,628, publishing magazines and periodicals at 139,669, and publishing books at 125,666.

Table 18: Film industry: employment all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU 28 (2013–2020)	1,484,664	:	1,484,664	1,484,664	:	1,484,664
Belgium	22,946	0	22,946	22,946	0	22,946
Bulgaria	12,650	454	13,104	12,650	454	13,104
Czechia	36,673	505	37,178	36,673	505	37,178
Denmark	19,942	2,865	22,807	19,942	2,865	22,807
Germany	349,919	33,524	383,443	349,919	33,524	383,443
Estonia	3,833	54	3,887	3,833	54	3,887
Ireland	8,778	2,597	11,375	8,778	2,597	11,375
Greece	20,339	3,007	23,346	20,339	3,007	23,346
Spain	140,735	14,655	155,390	140,735	14,655	155,390
France	166,769	9,656	176,425	166,769	9,656	176,425

Croatia	8,732	147	8,879	8,732	147	8,879
Italy	91,802	10,506	102,308	91,802	10,506	102,308
Cyprus	1,997	:	1,997	1,997	:	1,997
Latvia	7,767	102	7,869	7,767	102	7,869
Lithuania	10,489	303	10,792	10,489	303	10,792
Luxembourg	1,989	0	1,989	1,989	0	1,989
Hungary	22,021	2,262	24,283	22,021	2,262	24,283
Malta	2,150	0	2,150	2,150	0	2,150
Netherlands	69,205	22,570	91,775	69,205	22,570	91,775
Austria	38,070	1,764	39,834	38,070	1,764	39,834
Poland	89,442	:	89,442	89,442	:	89,442
Portugal	19,674	1,586	21,260	19,674	1,586	21,260
Romania	32,143	1,845	33,988	32,143	1,845	33,988
Slovenia	4,403	301	4,704	4,403	301	4,704
Slovakia	19,837	245	20,082	19,837	245	20,082
Finland	16,499	288	16,787	16,499	288	16,787
Sweden	38,514	:	38,514	38,514	:	38,514
United Kingdom	149,773	45,183	194,956	149,773	45,183	194,956
TOTAL	1,407,091	154,419	1,561,510	1,407,091	154,419	1,561,510

Source: Eurostat

2.1.2 Eurostat data on the Television and Radio Global Production Network

Table 19. Television and radio in Eurostat data by global production network phases

Case	Phase	NACE	Description	Minimal	Extensive
TV	Creation	90.03 (*)	Artistic creation	X	
TV	Production	59.11	Motion picture, video, and television programme production	X	
TV	Production	59.12	Motion picture, video, and television programme post-production	X	
TV	Distribution	60.10	Radio broadcasting	X	
TV	Distribution	60.20	Television programming and broadcasting activities	x	
TV	Distribution	61.10	Wired telecommunications activities		X
TV	Exchange	61.20	Wireless telecommunications activities		X
TV	Exchange	61.30	Satellite telecommunications activities		X
TV	Exchange	58.11	Book publishing		X

TV	Exchange	28.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals		X
TV	Exchange	73.1	Advertising		X
TV	Exchange	82.30	Organisation of conventions and trade shows		x
TV	Archive	90.01(*)	Library and archives activities	X	
TV	Archive	90.02(*)	Museum activities		x

Source: Eurostat

The analysis has revealed that the data collected and aggregated by Eurostat for television and radio is not available for some of the phases in the global production network. In television and radio, there seems to be an issue with two-digit codes, for which information cannot be provided or is not collected by the national statistics of the EU Member States.

There is also an overlap with the film industry and duplication of codes in the creation phase (NACE 90.03), in the production phase (codes 59.11 and 59.12), in the exchange phase (codes 58.11, 58.14, 73.1, 82.30), and in the archive phase (codes 91.01 and 91.02 are duplicated with the film industry).

Eurostat data on added value in television and radio

Table 20: Television and radio: added value total all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total (production)
	-	20,971.8	24,032.1			45,003.9
Belgium	-	489.6	237.2			726.8
Bulgaria	-	53.1	85.9			139.0
Czechia	-	0.0	187.5			187.5
Denmark	-	470.9	308.8			779.7
Germany	-	2,454.7	6,572.6			9,027.3
Estonia	-	0.0	0.0			0.0
Ireland	-	200.0	0.0			200.0
Greece	-	86.8	310.2			397.0
Spain	-	1,457.9	2,035.3			3,493.2
France	-	4,442.0	6,052.8			10,494.8
Croatia	-	25.1	149.4			174.5
Italy	-	1,203.3	1,746.0			2,949.3
Cyprus	-	9.9	21.0			30.9
Latvia	-	8.3	18.8			27.1
Lithuania	-	14.1	27.3			41.4
Luxembourg	-	42.5	0.0			42.5

Hungary	-	56.9	131.8			188.7
Malta	-	0.0	0.0			:
Netherlands	-	0.0	0.0			0.0
Austria	-	295.2	156.0			451.2
Poland	-	213.0	1,258.5			1,471.5
Portugal	-	115.9	338.5			454.4
Romania	-	116.4	283.7			400.1
Slovenia	-	50.1	9.2			59.3
Slovakia	-	73.4	46.4			119.8
Finland	-	193.8	117.2			311.0
Sweden	-	542.1	0.0			542.1
United Kingdom	-	7,255.4	2,122.1			9,377.5
TOTAL	-	19,870.4	38,970.0			42,086.6

Source: Eurostat

The analysis of value added in all phases of the global production network in television and radio has revealed the following:

- All phases of the production cycle in radio and television at the EU level contribute a total added value of EUR 45,003.9 million.
- The distribution phase has the largest share in the value added of radio and television at EUR 24,032.1 million, and the production phase is second at EUR 20,971.8 million.
- The countries with the highest added value in all phases of the global production network are France with EUR 10,494.8 million, the UK with EUR 9,377.5 million, and Germany with EUR 9,027.3 million.

Creation–NACE code 90 Artistic creation

Similar to the film industry, with this NACE code, no Eurostat data is available; therefore, information was collected from the national statistical institutes of the EU Member States.

Production

The analysis of NACE codes 59.11 *Motion picture, video and television programme production* and 59.12 *Motion picture, video and television programme post-production*, shows that these codes are repeated with the film industry and here the analysis will be the same as in Table 8, above.

Distribution

Analysing the NACE codes 60.10 *Radio broadcasting* and 60.20 *Television programming and broadcasting activities* has led to the findings:

- The total added value in distribution of radio and television programmes in EU Member States is EUR 24,032 million. Television programming and broadcasting activities added the most value at EUR 20,816 million and radio broadcasting at EUR 3,216 million.
- The top three countries that contribute value added in this phase in the EU are Germany with EUR 6,572.6 million, France with EUR 6,052.8 million, and the UK with EUR 2,122.1 million.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the highest added values are in Poland at EUR 1,259 million, Romania at EUR 289 million, and the Czech Republic at EUR 188 million.

Archiving and Exchange

There is no aggregated Eurostat data available on the value added in the archiving and exchange phases in television and radio. Data was collected from the national statistical institutes of the EU Member States.

Table 21: Television and radio: added value—all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	-			209,935.8		209,935.8
Belgium	-			6,347.8		6,347.8
Bulgaria	-			835.3		835.3
Czechia	-			2,800.1		2,800.1
Denmark	-			2,785.4		2,785.4
Germany	-			39,819.1		39,819.1
Estonia	-			343.3		343.3
Ireland	-			2,250.0		2,250.0
Greece	-			1,843.0		1,843.0
Spain	-			18,013.1		18,013.1
France	-			36,723.5		36,723.5
Croatia	-			990.0		990.0
Italy	-			21,749.7		21,749.7
Cyprus	-			303.8		303.8
Latvia	-			421.1		421.1
Lithuania	-			540.0		540.0
Luxembourg	-			121.7		121.7
Hungary	-			1,813.3		1,813.3
Malta	-			270.0		270.0
Netherlands	-			2,476.9		2,476.9
Austria	-			2,272.6		2,272.6
Poland	-			6,745.8		6,745.8

Portugal	-			2,584.7		2,584.7
Romania	-			2,330.7		2,330.7
Slovenia	-			594.4		594.4
Slovakia	-			380.1		380.1
Finland	-			2,936.6		2,936.6
Sweden	-			7,214.2		7,214.2
United Kingdom	-			33,596.2		33,596.2
TOTAL	-			199,102.4		199,102.4

Source: Eurostat

Exchange – Extended

To complete the picture of the types of economic activities in the exchange phase in the television and radio industries, we extended the scope of the statistical observation to the following broader codes, which reflect activities beyond television and radio only: 61.10 *Wired telecommunication activities*, 61.20 *Wireless telecommunications activities*, 61.30 *Satellite telecommunications activities*, 82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*, 58.11 *Book publishing*, 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*, and 73.1 *Advertising*.

The analysis (Table 15) shows that the value added through this extended approach for the television and radio industries is up to EUR 199,102.4 million. This includes wired telecommunications activities at EUR 71,228 million, advertising at EUR 53,020 million, wireless telecommunications activities at EUR 41,488 million, publishing of magazines and periodicals at EUR 12,692 million, publishing of books at EUR 10,332 million, organising congresses and trade fairs at EUR 8,203 million, and satellite telecommunications activities at EUR 2,140 million as the largest in added value.

- Germany has the largest share in the added value with EUR 39 819.1 million, and France is second with EUR 36,723.5 million. The country with the third-highest share of value added in the European Union is the UK with EUR 33,596.2 million.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the highest added value is in Poland (EUR 6 745.8 million). The Czech Republic is next in terms of value added (EUR 2,800.1 million) and Romania (EUR 2,330.7 million).

Eurostat data on the number of enterprises in television and radio

The figures shown for the number of enterprises in television and radio in the creation and production phases are the same as those in the film industry, as the same NACE codes are used. There is no differentiation in the number of companies between television and film industry.

Table 22: Television and radio: number of enterprises all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	0	120,436	10,853		:	131,289
Belgium	8,775	3,052	158		3	11,988
Bulgaria	1,209	863	196		240	2,508
Czechia	6,085	0	142		151	6,378
Denmark	3,103	2,073	125		103	5,404
Germany	57,296	8,623	464		1,816	68,199
Estonia	2,496	574	14		33	3,117
Ireland	6,755	2,183	0		252	9,190
Greece	8,335	1,186	827		650	10,998
Spain	39,445	6,860	1,610		3,144	51,059
France	53,595	17,601	382		1,230	72,808
Croatia	597	458	204		20	1,279
Italy	29,939	5,391	1,447		1,037	37,814
Cyprus	0	105	51		:	156
Latvia	1,992	390	125		50	2,557
Lithuania	7,303	1,185	93		31	8,612
Luxembourg	392	139	20		2	553
Hungary	13,901	5,116	789		368	20,174
Malta	:	0	20		0	:
Netherlands	81,723	14,962	339		2,970	99,994
Austria	11,454	1,932	85		205	13,676
Poland	0	6,805	371		:	7,176
Portugal	23,889	2,416	356		232	26,893
Romania	8,475	1,958	392		393	11,218
Slovenia	5,110	1,098	313		114	6,635
Slovakia	1,599	2,021	47		107	3,774
Finland	7,006	1,077	66		70	8,219
Sweden	0	7,824	238		:	8,062
United Kingdom	33,780	22,079	1,934		1,890	59,683
TOTAL	415,174	117,971	10,150		15,111	558,124

Source: Eurostat

Distribution

In the distribution phase, unlike in the previous two, is a clear distinction of the television and radio industries for two NACE codes: 60.10 *Radio broadcasting* and 60.20 *Television programming and broadcasting activities*. The analysis of Eurostat's structural business statistics data on the number of enterprises in the distribution phase has shown the following:

- The total number of enterprises in television and radio distribution in the EU is 10,150, out of which Radio broadcasting has 7,733, and television distribution has 5,075.
- The top three countries in broadcasting enterprises in the European Union are the UK with 1,934, Spain with 1,610, and Italy with 1,447 enterprises.
- In Central and Eastern Europe, the largest numbers of enterprises in this phase are in Hungary (789), Romania (392), and Poland (371).

Similar to the film industry, the Eurostat aggregated data in archiving could not be used as relevant for radio and television, as it is too extensive (NACE 91.01). Exchange does not have aggregated data at the EU level.

Table 23: Television and radio: number of enterprises all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
				403,842	:	403,842
Belgium				8,543	3	8,546
Bulgaria				4,464	240	4,704
Czechia				22,475	151	22,626
Denmark				3,870	103	3,973
Germany				44,518	1,816	46,334
Estonia				1,602	33	1,635
Ireland				2,421	252	2,673
Greece				6,949	650	7,599
Spain				51,024	3,144	54,168
France				39,362	1,230	40,592
Croatia				2,903	20	2,923
Italy				25,475	1,037	26,512
Cyprus				681	:	681
Latvia				2,760	50	2,810
Lithuania				4,694	31	4,725
Luxembourg				598	2	600
Hungary				11,095	368	11,463
Malta				374	0	374
Netherlands				35,055	2,970	38,025
Austria				11,421	205	11,626

Poland				37,474	:	37,474
Portugal				6,525	232	6,757
Romania				10,984	393	11,377
Slovenia				2,953	114	3,067
Slovakia				10,085	107	10,192
Finland				4,489	70	4,559
Sweden				18,520	:	18,520
United Kingdom				31,767	1,890	33,657
TOTAL				403,081	15,111	418,192

Source: Eurostat

Table 23 shows the total number of enterprises in television and radio to be 418,192, which includes codes that extend over two phases, exchange and archiving: 403,081 enterprises in the exchange phase and 15,111 enterprises in archiving).

Exchange—Extensive

The analysis of Exchange - Extensive scope includes the NACE codes 61.10 *Wired telecommunications activities*, 61.20 *Wireless—telecommunications activities*, 61.30 *Satellite telecommunications activities*, 82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*, 58.11 *Book publishing*, 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*, and 73.1 *Advertising*. It has shown the following:

- The total number of enterprises in the exchange—extensive phase in the EU is 403,081. Within this figure, the largest numbers of enterprises are in advertising (287,374), organisation of congresses and trade fairs (46,432), publishing of books (26,810), publishing of magazines and periodicals (20,232), wired telecommunications activities (13,493), wireless telecommunications activities (7,843), and satellite telecommunications activities (897).
- The top three countries are Spain, with 51,024 enterprises, followed by Germany with 44,518 and France with 39,361.
- The Central and Eastern European countries with the highest numbers of enterprises in this phase are Poland (37,474), the Czech Republic (22,475), and Hungary (11,095).

Eurostat data on employment in television and radio

Table 24: Television and radio: employment all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
	0	321,626	260,722		:	582,348
Belgium	7,647	6,378	1,961		0	15,986
Bulgaria	1,104	3,285	3,013		454	7,856

Czechia	1,754	0	1,309		505	3,568
Denmark	6,230	5,927	3,495		2,865	18,517
Germany	75,889	43,631	43,329		33,524	196,373
Estonia	1,097	0	0		54	1,151
Ireland	3,410	4,215	0		2,597	10,222
Greece	21,414	6,431	7,654		3,007	38,506
Spain	70,572	24,832	28,235		14,655	138,294
France	28,484	57,981	46,506		9,656	142,627
Croatia	547	987	4,848		147	6,529
Italy	11,866	18,503	15,051		10,506	55,926
Cyprus	0	331	852		:	1,183
Latvia	1,830	780	728		102	3,440
Lithuania	1,049	1,384	501		303	3,237
Luxembourg	118	441	0		0	559
Hungary	15,426	7,146	3,343		2,262	28,177
Malta	:	0	283		0	:
Netherlands	22,402	17,645	7,532		22,570	70,149
Austria	5,924	4,830	1,641		1,764	14,159
Poland	0	10,052	16,485		:	26,537
Portugal	3,496	4,389	3,687		1,586	13,158
Romania	3,572	4,421	9,543		1,845	19,381
Slovenia	595	1,543	713		301	3,152
Slovakia	795	2,727	580		245	4,347
Finland	2,406	3,533	840		288	7,067
Sweden	0	10,083	0		:	10,083
United Kingdom	92,095	0	46,075		45,183	183,353
TOTAL	379,722	241,475	399,618		154,419	1,023,537

Source: Eurostat

Employment in the creation and production phases overlaps with the film industry, as both involve data under codes 59.11 *Motion picture, video and television programme production* and 59.12 *Motion picture, video and television programme post-production*. We could therefore conclude that the exact numbers of employees in these two subsectors cannot be clearly distinguished.

Distribution

Since the television and radio broadcasting has separate codes (60.10 *Radio broadcasting* and 60.20 *Television programming and broadcasting activities*), we could analyse Eurostat's structural business statistics data on the number of employees in the distribution phase:

- The number of employees in television and radio distribution in the EU is 260,722; of them, television distribution employs 199,809 and radio broadcasting employs 48,395.
- The top three countries by number of employees in the European Union are France at 46,506, the UK at 46,075, and Germany at 43,329.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the highest numbers of employees in this phase are in Poland (16,485), Romania (9,543), and Hungary (3,343).

Aggregated Eurostat data about archiving is again not usable due to the high level of aggregation of the code 91.01 *Library and archives activities*.

Table 25: Television and radio: employment all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
				2,228,686	:	2,228,686
Belgium				43,255	0	43,255
Bulgaria				30,037	454	30,491
Czechia				56,358	505	56,863
Denmark				27,583	2,865	30,448
Germany				426,822	33,524	460,346
Estonia				6,703	54	6,757
Ireland				14,605	2,597	17,202
Greece				39,833	3,007	42,840
Spain				189,349	14,655	204,004
France				201,701	9,656	211,357
Croatia				17,521	147	17,668
Italy				170,053	10,506	180,559
Cyprus				4,493	:	4,493
Latvia				12,304	102	12,406
Lithuania				15,539	303	15,842
Luxembourg				1,989	0	1,989
Hungary				38,738	2,262	41,000
Malta				2,150	0	2,150
Netherlands				96,561	22,570	119,131
Austria				40,315	1,764	42,079
Poland				141,751	:	141,751
Portugal				31,974	1,586	33,560
Romania				68,615	1,845	70,460
Slovenia				8,882	301	9,183
Slovakia				19,930	245	20,175

Finland				27,796	288	28,084
Sweden				65,213	:	65,213
United Kingdom				205,003	45,183	250,186
TOTAL				2,005,073	154,419	2,159,492

Source: Eurostat

In total, for both the exchange and archiving phases, the number of employees in television and radio is 2,159,492 employees. This includes the extensive scope of the exchange phase (including the codes 61.10, 61.20, 61.30, 82.30, 58.11, 58.14, and 73.1), which leads to the figure of 2,005,073 employees. Again, advertising has the largest share of employed (991,128), followed by wired telecommunications activities (351,281) and wireless telecommunications activities (230,381).

2.1.3 Gaming Industry Global Production Network in Eurostat data

Table 26. Video games in Eurostat data by global production network phases

Case	Phase	NACE	Description	Minimal	Extensive
Videogames	Creation	62.01	Computer programming	X	
Videogames	Creation	90.03(*)	Artistic creation		X
Videogames	Production	58.21	Publishing of computer games	X	
Videogames	Production	26.40	Manufacturing of computer games		X
Videogames	Distribution	47.41	Retail sale of video game consoles and retail sale of non-customised software, including video games	X	
Videogames	Distribution	47.91	Retail sale via mail order houses or via internet		X
Videogames	Exchange	58.11	Book publishing		X
Videogames	Exchange	58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals		X
Videogames	Exchange	73.1	Advertising		X
Videogames	Archive	91.01(*)	Library and archives activities		X
Videogames	Archive	91.02(*)	Museum activities		X

Source: Eurostat

NACE Codes with (*) are available only at two-digits in the Business Demography Database

The analysis of the data collected and aggregated by EUROSTAT has some peculiarities:

- No data is available for some of the phases in the global production chain for video games. As with the film and broadcasting industries, there is a problem with two-digit codes, for which information either cannot be provided or is not collected in the national statistics of European Union Member States.
- For some of the four-digit codes that cover the different phases of the global production network, there are overlap and distortion of information about the audiovisual sector.

- Most of the EUROSTAT codes for video games are expanded, which distorts the statistics for video games.

Table 27: Video games: added value all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)	105,776.7	105,776.7	4,994.9			216,548.3
Belgium	2,156.5	2,156.5	175.1			4,488.1
Bulgaria	551.3	551.3	29.1			1,131.7
Czechia	1,851.1	1,851.1	70.6			3,772.8
Denmark	2,138.0	2,138.0	38.8			4,314.8
Germany	27,230.0	27,230.0	1,125.8			55,585.8
Estonia	0.0	0.0	15.1			15.1
Ireland	3,225.5	3,225.5	139.3			6,590.3
Greece	602.1	602.1	75.4			1,279.6
Spain	4,748.6	4,748.6	651.4			10,148.6
France	5,327.4	5,327.4	538.0			11,192.8
Croatia	422.8	422.8	9.2			854.8
Italy	11,103.4	11,103.4	352.3			22,559.1
Cyprus	383.9	383.9	17.1			784.9
Latvia	343.8	343.8	6.8			694.4
Lithuania	300.7	300.7	8.9			610.3
Luxembourg	459.6	459.6	19.4			938.6
Hungary	866.7	866.7	71.3			1,804.7
Malta	:	445.7	0.0			:
Netherlands	0.0	0.0	0.0			0.0
Austria	2,277.9	2,277.9	112.6			4,668.4
Poland	3,422.2	3,422.2	185.1			7,029.5
Portugal	537.9	537.9	123.7			1,199.5
Romania	2,002.5	2,002.5	33.3			4,038.3
Slovenia	312.9	312.9	6.2			632.0
Slovakia	324.3	324.3	45.7			694.3
Finland	3,495.6	3,495.6	117.5			7,108.7
Sweden	3,889.7	3,889.7	175.5			7,954.9
United Kingdom	18,725.2	18,725.2	727.1			38,177.5
TOTAL	97,145.3	97,145.3	4,870.3			198,269.5

Source: Eurostat

Regarding the analysis of value added in all phases of the global production network, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- All phases of the production cycle of video games at the European Union level have an added value of EUR198 269.5 million.
- The largest shares in the added value of video games are in the production phase (EUR 97,145.3 million) and the production phase (EUR 97,145.3 million), with distribution in third place (EUR 4,870.3 million).
- The countries with the highest added value in all phases of the global production network are Germany at EUR 55,585.8 million, the UK at (EUR 38,177.5 million), and Italy at (EUR 22,559.1 million).

CREATION AND PRODUCTION—NACE CODE 62.0 *Computer programming*

- The codes for the creation phase and production phases coincide as numbers, and there is no separation of the code into computer programming and only video game creation.
- In the creation and production phases, all EU Member States have EUR 97,145.3 million of added value.
- The countries with the highest added value in these two phases are Germany (EUR 27,230 million), the UK (EUR 18,725.2 million), and Italy (EUR 11,103.4 million).

DISTRIBUTION—NACE CODE 47.41 *Retail sale of video game consoles and retail sale of non-customised software, including video games*

Regarding the Eurostat data on the distribution phase of the global production chain, we could draw the following conclusions:

- In the Member States of the European Union, at the distribution level, the added value totalled EUR 4870.3 million.
- The top three countries in terms of value added in the EU are Germany (EUR 1,125.8 million), the UK (EUR 727.8 million), and Spain (EUR 651.4 million).
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the highest added values are in Poland at EUR 185.1 million and Hungary at EUR 71.3 million.

Table 28: Video games: added value all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)		3,830.8	21,889.6	77,391.6		103,112.0
Belgium		0.0	137.7	1,277.9		1,415.6
Bulgaria		11.9	33.4	158.1		203.4
Czechia		68.6	:	839.9		908.5
Denmark		92.8	279.6	1,148.4		1,520.8
Germany		0.0	8,801.2	15,322.2		24,123.4
Estonia		2.8	26.1	107.5		136.4
Ireland		0.0	69.2	518.1		587.3

Greece		1.1	11.8	341.5		354.4
Spain		67.9	516.3	5,219.1		5,803.3
France		101.7	1,987.4	9,406.2		11,495.3
Croatia		0.0	19.1	198.3		217.4
Italy		158.7	746.8	4,310.2		5,215.7
Cyprus		:	2.3	42.5		44.8
Latvia		2.5	13.5	100.9		116.9
Lithuania		0.0	56.3	176.4		232.7
Luxembourg		0.0	0.0	110.6		110.6
Hungary		0.0	81.2	384.4		465.6
Malta		:	:	270.0		270.0
Netherlands		49.9	1,222.4	2,476.9		3,749.2
Austria		45.5	320.0	1,730.8		2,096.3
Poland		169.6	699.3	2,475.2		3,344.1
Portugal		197.1	34.8	486.9		718.8
Romania		0.6	258.0	566.7		825.3
Slovenia		29.4	63.3	126.4		219.1
Slovakia		339.0	16.7	359.3		715.0
Finland		13.5	70.5	843.6		927.6
Sweden		87.8	713.6	2,190.3		2,991.7
United Kingdom		303.5	5,369.9	24,854.8		30,528.2
TOTAL		1,743.9	21,550.4	76,043.1		99,337.4

Source: Eurostat

- At the level of the European Union, the value added by the extensive codes is EUR 99,337.4 million, with the largest added value in the exchange phase (EUR 76,043.1 million), followed by distribution (EUR 21,550.4 million) and production (EUR 1.743.9 million).

PRODUCTION—NACE 26.40 *Manufacture of consumer electronics*

- The total value added for the European Union in this phase is (EUR 1743.9 million). The largest shares are accounted for by Slovakia (EUR 339 million), Great Britain (EUR 303.5 million), and Portugal (EUR 197.1 million).

DISTRIBUTION—NACE 47.91 *Retail sale via mail order houses or via internet*

- The total value added for the European Union in this phase is (EUR 1743.9 million). The largest shares are accounted for by Germany (EUR 8,801 million), Great Britain (EUR 5,370 million), and France (EUR 1,222 million).

EXCHANGE—NACE 58.11 Book publishing, 58.14 Publishing of journals, 73.1 Advertising

In terms of the exchange phase, codes have been used that replicate those for the film industry and radio and television.

- At European Union level, the value added in the exchange-intensive phase is EUR 76,043.1 million. Within this number, the largest added values are in advertising (EUR 53,020 million), publishing of magazines and periodicals (EUR 13,387 million), and publishing of books (EUR 10,985 million).
- The UK has the largest share in value added at EUR 24,854.8 million, followed by Germany at 15 322.2 and France in third place at EUR 9.406.2 million.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the country with the highest added value is Poland, with EUR 2,599 million, including EUR 1,851 million from advertising, EUR 347 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 277 million from publishing books, and EUR 124 million from organising congresses and trade fairs. The Czech Republic was next in terms of value added with EUR 900 million, including EUR 696 million from advertising, EUR 72 million from publishing magazines and periodicals, EUR 72 million from publishing books, and EUR 60 million from organising congresses and trade fairs.

ARCHIVE: For this phase of the global production network, no EUROSTAT data are available. Information can be collected from the national statistical institutes of the Member States of the European Union.

Table 29: Video games: number of enterprises all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)	327,702	327,702	46,476			701,880
Belgium	6,914	6,914	1,974			15,802
Bulgaria	2,302	2,302	1,244			5,848
Czechia	12,899	12,899	2,415			28,213
Denmark	4,037	4,037	217			8,291
Germany	39,967	39,967	7,281			87,215
Estonia	1,595	1,595	151			3,341
Ireland	3,085	3,085	536			6,706
Greece	4,932	4,932	1,020			10,884
Spain	14,086	14,086	6,460			34,632
France	31,825	31,825	3,224			66,874
Croatia	3,029	3,029	164			6,222
Italy	20,568	20,568	6,078			47,214
Cyprus	696	696	264			1,656
Latvia	2,072	2,072	216			4,360
Lithuania	2,732	2,732	242			5,706
Luxembourg	883	883	129			1,895

Hungary	12,590	12,590	1,567		26,747
Malta	:	507	0		:
Netherlands	33,812	33,812	939		68,563
Austria	5,464	5,464	1,132		12,060
Poland	47,096	47,096	4,045		98,237
Portugal	4,719	4,719	2,644		12,082
Romania	7,661	7,661	984		16,306
Slovenia	3,433	3,433	80		6,946
Slovakia	2,867	2,867	794		6,528
Finland	4,244	4,244	353		8,841
Sweden	21,193	21,193	749		43,135
United Kingdom	32,494	32,494	1,461		66,449
TOTAL	327,702	327,702	46,363		700,753

Source: Eurostat

With regard to the analysis of the number of enterprises in all phases of the global production network, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Across all phases of the production cycle for video games at the European Union level, there are 700,753 enterprises.
- The largest shares of the number of enterprises in video games are in the production phase with 327,702 and the manufacturing phase with 327,702, followed by distribution with 46,363.
- The countries with the largest numbers of enterprises in all phases of the global production network are Germany (87,215), France (68,874), and the UK (66,449).

CREATION AND PRODUCTION—NACE CODE 62.01 *Computer programming*

- The codes for the creation phase and the production phase coincide as numbers, and there is no separation of code into computer programming and only video game creation.
- In the creation and production phases, all EU Member States have 327,702 enterprises.
- The countries with the highest numbers of enterprises in these two phases are Germany at 39,967, France at 31,825, and Great Britain at 31,494 .

DISTRIBUTION—NACE CODE 47.41 *Retail sale of video game consoles and retail sale of non-customised software, including video games*

Regarding the Eurostat data on the distribution phase of the global production chain, we could draw the following conclusions:

- In the Member States of the European Union, the number of enterprises at the distribution level is 46,363.
- The top three countries in terms of the number of enterprises in the European Union are Germany with 7,281, Spain with 6,460, and Italy with 6,078.
- The Central and Eastern European countries with the highest numbers of enterprises in this phase are Poland at 4,045, Czech Republic at 2,415, and Hungary at 71.3 million.

Table 30: Video games: number of enterprises all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)	0	2,765	232,260	334,788	:	569,813
Belgium	8,775	0	1,438	6,079	3	16,295
Bulgaria	1,209	21	2,660	3,839	240	7,969
Czechia	6,085	250	:	20,969	151	27,455
Denmark	3,103	73	1,425	3,445	103	8,149
Germany	57,296	0	30,919	36,518	1,816	126,549
Estonia	2,496	15	1,110	1,451	33	5,105
Ireland	6,755	0	712	1,535	252	9,254
Greece	8,335	31	1,690	4,994	650	15,700
Spain	39,445	93	7,149	40,938	3,144	90,769
France	53,595	173	25,466	31,103	1,230	111,567
Croatia	597	31	668	2,428	20	3,744
Italy	29,939	207	12,170	21,204	1,037	64,557
Cyprus	0	:	140	533	:	673
Latvia	1,992	24	1,467	2,351	50	5,884
Lithuania	7,303	12	3,807	4,325	31	15,478
Luxembourg	392	0	262	496	2	1,152
Hungary	13,901	0	6,057	8,018	368	28,344
Malta	:	:	:	374	0	374
Netherlands	81,723	224	42,600	33,148	2,970	160,665
Austria	11,454	34	1,272	10,632	205	23,597
Poland	0	297	27,318	30,247	:	57,862
Portugal	23,889	19	2,317	4,866	232	31,323
Romania	8,475	25	6,767	8,528	393	24,188
Slovenia	5,110	55	1,788	2,154	114	9,221
Slovakia	1,599	71	582	9,714	107	12,073
Finland	7,006	30	726	3,944	70	11,776
Sweden	0	168	11,176	15,999	:	27,343
United Kingdom	33,780	521	36,676	24,584	1,890	97,451
TOTAL	415,174	2,374	228,362	334,416	15,111	994,517

Source: Eurostat

With respect to the analysis of the number of enterprises in all phases of the global production network with extended codes, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Across all phases of the production cycle for video games at the European Union level, the number of enterprises is 994,517.
- The creation phase has the largest share in the number of enterprises in video games with 415,174, followed by the exchange phase with 334,416, distribution with 228,362, archive with 15,111, and production with 2,374.
- The countries with the largest numbers of enterprises in all phases of the global production network are Germany at 126,549, France at 111,567, and the UK at 97,451.

CREATION—NACE CODE 90.03 (*) *Artistic creation*

- At the European Union level, there are 415,174 enterprises in the film industry. The leading Member States in terms of number of enterprises are the Netherlands at 81,723, followed by Germany at 57,296 and France at 53,595.
- Central and Eastern European countries have relatively low shares in the number of enterprises in the film industry. The leading country in the region in terms of value added, Poland, unfortunately has no information available on the number of enterprises. Hungary has the highest relative share in the region in terms of number of enterprises at 13,901.

PRODUCTION—NACE CODE 26.40 *Manufacture of consumer electronics*

- At the European Union level, there are 2,374 enterprises in the film industry. The leading Member State in terms of number of enterprises is the UK with 521, followed by Poland with 297 and the Czech Republic with 250.

DISTRIBUTION—NACE CODE 47.91 *Retail sale via mail order houses or via internet*

- At the European Union level, there are 228,362 enterprises in the film industry. The leading Member State in terms of number of enterprises is the Netherlands at 42,600, followed by the UK at 36,676, and Germany at 30,919.
- Central and Eastern European countries have relatively low shares in terms of the number of enterprises in video games. The leading countries in the region by number of enterprises are Poland with 27,318, Romania with 6,767, and Hungary with 6,057.

EXCHANGE—NACE CODES 58.11 *Book publishing*, 58.14 *Publishing of journals*, 73.1 *Advertising*

- At the European Union level, the number of enterprises in the exchange-intensive phase is 334,416. Within this number, the largest relative shares are in advertising (287,374), book publishing (46,432), and magazine and periodical publishing (26,810).

ARCHIVE—91.02 (*) *Museums activities*

- The total number of enterprises under this code at the European Union level is 15,111.

Table 31: Video games: employment all phases (minimal)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)	1,500,000	1,500,000	154,881			3,154,881
Belgium	23,566	23,566	5,004			52,136
Bulgaria	18,090	18,090	3,454			39,634

Czechia	46,553	46,553	4,273		97,379
Denmark	22,679	22,679	795		46,153
Germany	331,035	331,035	29,608		691,678
Estonia	0	0	626		626
Ireland	20,956	20,956	2,148		44,060
Greece	18,522	18,522	4,784		41,828
Spain	80,245	80,245	22,269		182,759
France	75,753	75,753	8,828		160,334
Croatia	13,807	13,807	718		28,332
Italy	147,008	147,008	13,401		307,417
Cyprus	2,927	2,927	710		6,564
Latvia	11,732	11,732	746		24,210
Lithuania	10,997	10,997	854		22,848
Luxembourg	5,208	5,208	340		10,756
Hungary	31,100	31,100	4,518		66,718
Malta	:	3,800	0		:
Netherlands	108,269	108,269	2,877		219,415
Austria	29,375	29,375	3,616		62,366
Poland	131,624	131,624	12,788		276,036
Portugal	15,737	15,737	6,905		38,379
Romania	69,455	69,455	2,920		141,830
Slovenia	7,761	7,761	215		15,737
Slovakia	9,787	9,787	2,242		21,816
Finland	37,983	37,983	2,001		77,967
Sweden	72,321	72,321	3,861		148,503
United Kingdom	188,218	188,218	13,914		390,350
TOTAL	1,534,508	1,534,508	154,415		3,215,831

Source: Eurostat

CREATION

- At the European Union level, 3,215,831 people are employed in video games. Germany has the highest number of employees in the film industry, with 188,218, followed by the UK with 331,035 and Italy with 147,008.
- Central and Eastern European countries maintain a relatively low share of the number of employees in video games, as with the other two indicators. The region with the highest relative share of employees is Poland with 131,624 employees, followed by the Czech Republic with 46,553 employees.

PRODUCTION

- At the European Union level, 3,215,831 people are employed in video games. Germany has the highest number of employees in the film industry with 188,218, followed by the UK with 331,035 and Italy with 147,008.
- Central and Eastern European countries maintain relatively low shares in the number of employees in video games, as for the other two indicators. The regions with the highest relative share of employees are Poland with 131,624 and the Czech Republic with 46,553.

DISTRIBUTION—NACE CODE 47.41 *Retail sale of video game consoles and retail sale of non-customised software, including video games*

Regarding the Eurostat data on the distribution phase of the global production chain, we could draw the following conclusions:

- In the Member States of the European Union, at the distribution level, the number of employees is 154,415 in total.
- The top three countries by number of employees in the European Union are Germany at 29,608, Spain at 22,269, and the UK at 13,914.
- In the Central and Eastern European countries, the largest numbers of employees are in Poland (12,788) and Hungary (4,273).

Table 32: Video games: employment all phases (extensive)

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Total
EU28 (2013–2020)	0	54,976	643,762	1,333,664	:	2,032,402
Belgium	7,647	0	3,083	20,608	0	31,338
Bulgaria	1,104	607	4,692	12,002	454	18,859
Czechia	1,754	3,847	:	35,144	505	41,250
Denmark	6,230	1,219	7,616	17,236	2,865	35,166
Germany	75,889	0	201,572	305,240	33,524	616,225
Estonia	1,097	119	1,956	3,636	54	6,862
Ireland	3,410	0	1,376	7,012	2,597	14,395
Greece	21,414	54	3,358	17,171	3,007	45,004
Spain	70,572	1,206	17,878	124,124	14,655	228,435
France	28,484	924	54,696	146,986	9,656	240,746
Croatia	547	97	1,629	8,338	147	10,758
Italy	11,866	2,248	26,340	82,504	10,506	133,464
Cyprus	0	:	189	1,750	:	1,939
Latvia	1,830	115	3,059	7,454	102	12,560
Lithuania	1,049	0	6,843	9,900	303	18,095
Luxembourg	118	0	0	1,828	0	1,946
Hungary	15,426	0	10,115	18,645	2,262	46,448

Malta	:	:	:	2,150	0	2,150
Netherlands	22,402	723	43,446	64,884	22,570	154,025
Austria	5,924	382	5,225	35,123	1,764	48,418
Poland	0	5,840	54,101	86,020	:	145,961
Portugal	3,496	4,215	3,604	16,450	1,586	29,351
Romania	3,572	79	15,599	30,212	1,845	51,307
Slovenia	595	641	2,763	4,073	301	8,373
Slovakia	795	5,070	1,467	18,781	245	26,358
Finland	2,406	216	1,305	15,524	288	19,739
Sweden	0	969	17,642	35,419	:	54,030
United Kingdom	92,095	0	140,221	128,249	45,183	405,748
TOTAL	379,722	28,571	629,775	1,256,463	154,419	2,448,950

Source: Eurostat

With respect to the analysis of the number of employees in all phases of the global production network with extended codes, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Across all phases of the video game production cycle at the European Union level, the number of employees is 2,448,950.
- The exchange phase has the largest share in the number of employees in video games (1,256,463), followed by the distribution phase (629,775), creation (379,722), archive (154,419), and the production phase (28,571).
- The countries with the largest numbers of employees in all phases of the global production network are Germany with 616,225, the UK with 405,748, and France with 240,746.

CREATION—NACE CODE 90.03 (*) Artistic creation

- At the European Union level, the film industry employs 379,722 people. The leading Member State in terms of number of employees is the UK with 92,095, followed by Germany with 75,889 and Spain with 70,572.
- The Central and Eastern European countries have relatively low shares in the number of employees in the film industry. The leading country in the region in terms of value added, Poland, unfortunately has no information available on the number of employees. The region's largest relative shares by number of enterprises are Hungary with 15,426 and Romania with 3,572 employees.

PRODUCTION—NACE CODE 26.40 Manufacture of consumer electronics

- At the European Union level, there are 28,571 employees in video games. The leading Member State in terms of number of employees is Poland with 5,840, followed by Slovakia with 5,070 and Portugal with 4,215.

DISTRIBUTION—NACE CODE 47.91 Retail sale via mail order houses or via internet

- At the European Union level, there are 629,775 employees in video games. The leading Member State by number of employees is Germany with 201,572, followed by the UK with 140,221 and France with 54,696.
- The Central and Eastern European countries have relatively low shares of employment in video games. The leading countries in the region by number of employees are Poland with 54,101, Romania with 10,115 and Hungary with 10,115.

EXCHANGE—NACE CODES 58.11 *Book publishing*, 58.14 *Publishing of journals*, 73.1 *Advertising*

- At the European Union level, the number of employees in the exchange-intensive phase is 1,256,463. Within this number, the largest relative shares are in advertising (991,128), publishing of magazines and periodicals (139,669), and publishing of books (125,666) employees. The leading Member State in terms of number of employees is Germany with 305,240, followed by France with 146,986 and the UK with 128,249.

ARCHIVE—91.02 (*) *Museums activities*

- The total number of enterprises under this code at the European Union level is 154,419.

2.1.4 Quantitative data provided by the European Audiovisual Observatory and other sources

In Part 1 (1.1.4), we introduced the intergovernmental legal frameworks that laid the foundations of the most important data source for the film industry and television in Europe, the European Audiovisual Observatory (EAO). The EAO has provided sustainable mechanisms for comprehensive and comparable data collection for audiovisual industry, via specialised national agencies and statistical bodies from 41 countries, as well as from a number of dedicated “satellite” monitoring tools (the MAVISE database for television digital services, IRIS for legal updates, Media Salles for cinemas, and EFARN, the Film Research Library, etc.).²¹ EAO collects data on the audiovisual market, which includes public funding of public broadcasters, television and radio advertising, pay-television and VOD services, cinema screens, admissions, box office (turnover), and home entertainment. It also analyses key legal issues in the audiovisual sector, including in its production phases, including reporting on major legal developments and cases which affect media legislation in Europe; hence, it is a valuable source of information for our research.

CICERONE researchers have explored a variety of data sources for the audiovisual industries’ production networks to identify gaps and make suggestions (Pratt and Benett, 2021). We have found that the EAO provides data on the following elements of the Global production network.

Creation & production

Key information about this GPN phase is the number of enterprises in the AV industry, about the public subsidies for film creation and production and incentives for the film industry. The EAO Trends

²¹ <https://www.obs.coe.int/en/web/observatoire/what-we-do> (last seen 16/03/2021)

(yearbooks) provide data on circulation, admissions, revenues from digital platforms. MAVISE Database provides quantitative data about the number of licenced television providers and company ownership (public or private) for Television channels (TV), FOD (free on-demand service), TVOD (transactional video-on-demand), SVOD (subscription video-on-demand), UGC (video sharing platforms). The aggregated reports by the EAO on the European audiovisual market, for example, show data for all EAO members, not exclusively for the EU.²² However, it is key for analysing the state of affairs in on-demand and digital AV services, which are often lacking at the national level. EAO's yearbook analyses data from its monitoring tools (e.g. [MAVISE](#)) and provides reports on localized audiovisual services in Europe and on the main hubs of those services (both on-demand and linear) in Europe that target foreign markets.

Distribution and exchange

The circulation of European films and television series via TVOD and SVOD in Europe is analysed by EAO, which provides data about the shares of European and non-European catalogues. The most recent report on trends in the VOD market in EU28 (EAO, February 2021) examines the TVOD, SVOD, and AVOD/ BVOD²³ and reports an “Explosive growth in the past 10 years,” based on SVOD revenues (EAO 2021, p. 7). The EAO data for EU28 shows stagnant and declining market segments for the rest of the AV industry for 2010–2020, which were compensated for by the rapid growth of VOD revenues. EAO/LUMIERE collects data on the circulation and worldwide cinema admissions of European films outside Europe, showing the global dimension of the European audiovisual industries' GPN.

The most recent report shows that in subscriber count per national market, in 18 of the 28 observed EU markets, the top three places are taken by global players such as Netflix and Amazon (EAO, 2021). Information about distribution and exchange is provided also by EFARN Network (EAO), by MEDIA Salles, which publishes European Cinema Charts, cartograms and inter-active maps that allow international comparison of indicators.²⁴

The EAO Yearbook Key Trends 2018/2019 has analysed the breakdown of the income sources of European fiction films for 21 countries (EAO 2019, p. 13). Data on revenues of television services (linear and on-demand), as well as the “explosive growth of SVOD,” shows the fast tenfold growth of the subscription audiovisual services in Europe between 2013 and 2017 (Ibid. pp. 51-52). Data on the linguistic diversity of the audiovisual services in Europe is also available for 61 languages.

The EAO provides data about the market share of European films worldwide, the number of feature films produced in the EU and US (comparative), and the number of cinema screens, as well as on cinema admissions (in millions EUR or USD) (EAO 2019, pp. 20-21). It also collects data on television audiences and viewings in Europe.

The LUMIERE database by the EAO systematically collects data from the Member States on admissions for films released across Europe in order to support research into and valuation of the success of the films and their creators. The LUMIERE database contains calculation tools designed to facilitate

²² Schneeberger, A. Audiovisual media services in Europe, EAO 2019 ([link](#))

²³ Trends in the VoD market in EU28 (EAO 2021 [link](#))

²⁴ <http://www.mediasalles.it/> (last seen 16/11/2022)

analysis of market share, comparison between supply and demand, degree of concentration of film attendance, exportation rates, and film attendance charts; however, these tools are not available online.²⁵

IRIS provides monthly observations of the most important legal developments for the audiovisual industry in the framework of the EAO, such as court decisions related to the audiovisual industries in the 41 countries in broadcasting, cinema, VOD, and IPTV. These legal aspects cover the latest developments in the fields such as market regulations, ownership, court decisions, copyright law, data protection, and competition.²⁶ In addition, through the AVMSD tracking tool, one could find national transpositions of the Audiovisual Media Services Directive in each EU country. Here, we observe a good synergy and complementarity of the EU legislation and Council of Europe's tools, which serve both public policies and the industry.

Archiving

One of the problematic data fields in the GPN network is archiving. The EAO, in cooperation with the European Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO), published a 2017 report, *Deposit systems for audiovisual works* (EAO, 2017). While it gives a comprehensive picture of the legal and practical aspects of the subject, it does not yet answer the question of how the different deposit systems existing in the Member States would bridge the statistical data collection gap.

On the other hand, the EAO has developed its own research library (EFARN), which collects film industry research published across Europe and includes a search engine using different strings (topic, country, organisation, etc.).²⁷ A thorough examination of some of the specialised databases and reports, zooming in other cells of our CICERONE GPN data matrix (Pratt 2021), has shown that in fact fewer countries could provide sufficient data for research. For example, the [EFARN Research Database](#) does not yet contain figures for all EU Member States (let alone the CoE members). The Bulgarian National Film Centre, for example, has been publishing annually facts and figures about the national film industry ([link](#)), but this information is not included in the EFARN library.

²⁵ <http://lumiere.obs.coe.int/web/search/> (last seen 16/03/2021)

²⁶ <http://merlin.obs.coe.int/page/info> (last seen 16/03/2021)

²⁷ <https://filmresearch.eu/about-efarn> (last seen 16/03/2021)

2.2 The audiovisual and radio industry in Bulgaria

This section introduces the national mapping of cultural and creative industries, which includes data and conclusions on the key audiovisual industries: film, television and radio, and games.

2.2.1 Film industry

The film industry has a complex production process. In this business, we often observe information asymmetry between unfocused demand and oversupply. Unreliable returns, coupled with high capital demand, defines the product as risky and with high running costs. This conclusion is also a rational argument for state support, which predetermines the leading role for public funding of the film industry, not only in Europe or Bulgaria but also in other parts of the world. The multiplied effect of public investment in Bulgarian cinema proves that the role of the state as an investor is decisive at the macro level. In Bulgaria, public investment has awakened production demand and managed to convert this market from a crisis state into a successful one. In order to make this industry viable and ensure its sustainability, further action is required to maintain this trend, such as stabilising micro-production companies through greater access to alternative capital. The current competitive environment has market failures that need to be eliminated, namely the distribution oligopoly and the vertical integration between distribution and screening (Tomova, 2018:49).

To address some of these issues and gaps in the aggregated statistical data, the Observatory of Cultural Economy (OCE) has been conducting **annual statistical data mappings of the arts, cultural, and creative industries** in Bulgaria since 2008. The main research task of the annual mapping is to measure the economic contributions of arts and CCIs through value added, employment, and number of firms, which provide evidence for the dynamics and economic sustainability of the CCIs and of the audiovisual business in particular. There is also some evidence for spillover effects and possibilities for clusters (Tomova, 2013, p.112).

The mapping methodology (including data matrix) developed by the OCE is based on the Eurostat approach, which is itself (based on German and Austrian models and generates comparable, i.g. data is comparable. The approach to shaping the scope of the arts and, the cultural and creative industries, and the film industry in particular, follows the recommendations of the Leadership Group on Cultural Statistics (2000) as reflected in the European Statistical System Network on Culture (ESSnet Culture, Bina et al. 2012), Cultural and Creative Industries in Germany 2009: Monitoring Report 2010 (Söndermann 2010) and others.

OCE used data from business statistics (not publicly available), provided by the National Statistical Institute at the national, regional (for the six planning regions in Bulgaria), as well as local levels - for Sofia, the capital city. As an independent non-governmental research organisation, OCE carried out the mapping in partnership with the Sofia Municipality, within the framework of the Cultural Strategy of Sofia 2013–2023 entitled "Sofia: Creative Capital" The same method was used in two other

strategies: "Sofia: Creative City of Film 2017–2021," which contributed to designating Sofia a UNESCO City of Film, and the "SMART Specialisation Strategy of Sofia" (2016).²⁸

The statistical mapping could be defined as systemic approach to identifying and classifying the cultural resources of a city, region or a country. The main steps applied are the collecting, analysis, and synthesis of cultural resources comprised in the CCI system. **Why is this approach so useful for cultural and creative sectors?**

- To develop evidence-based policies, including for the distribution of public funding.
- It has expanded knowledge about the potentials of the cultural markets, as well as enabling culture and CCIs to be viewed as investment-worthy sectors where business management and revenue models could apply.
- It helps to position CCIs in the economy, provides important data, and creates possibilities for comparative analysis.

OCE used the same mapping methodology for the film industry in Bulgaria (Tomova, 2018). The algorithm of the methodology proceeds through three stages:

- 1) The subject of statistical observation is theoretically determined, for example, by the definition of the term "film industry."
- 2) Based on existing statistical classifiers such as "economic activity classifier" (Bachvarov et al., 2008), this first and broadest definition is limited to real-sector statistical activities in this sector. This is termed the "statistical definition" (i.e. the general definition is limited to specific activities in this case monitored by Structural Business Statistics).
- 3) The last stage of narrowing the subject is to conduct an "operational statistical definition," in which activities with clear cultural content remain while activities in this sector that are monitored by statistics but have no cultural or partial content are excluded. The figure below shows the final statistical range of the film industry.

The data in this chapter covers the audiovisual sector in Bulgaria, including the film industry, and shows the dynamics of the 11 subsequent years (2008–2018) using mapping methodology and the NACE economic classification system (Eurostat).

Film industry	
Code	Activity
59.11	Motion picture and television broadcasting services production
59.12	Technical activities relating to the production of films and television programs (post-production)
59.13	Distribution of films and television broadcasts
59.14	Film screening
77.22	Renting of video cassettes and discs

²⁸ Strategy for cultural development of Sofia 2013-2023 p.25 ([link](#)); Strategy - Sofia - Creative City of Cinema 2017-2021", <https://www.sofia.bg/sofia-unesco> and [link](#).

Figure 2: Number of Enterprises—Film Industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

According to the data, enterprises in film industry in Bulgaria more than doubled in ten years, from 460 in 2008 to 1,025 in 2018. The largest number of enterprises is in the *Production of films and television programs (59.11)*. The number of enterprises in *technical activities related to Film production and television programs (post-production) (59.12)* has seen the largest increase by nearly three and a half times. In *Distribution of films and television (59.13)*, the number of companies increased from 51 companies in 2008 to 62 in 2018. In *Film screening (59.14)*, the number more than doubled, from 20 in 2008 to 46 in 2018. In *Renting video cassettes and discs (77.22)*, the number of firms disappeared from the market, from 42 companies in 2008 to 0 in 2018.

Figure 3: Added value in the film industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

The data shows a triple increase of value added in the Bulgarian film industry over 11 years, from BGN 45,852,000 in 2008 to BGN 129,271,000 in 2018. The highest added value was observed in the *production of films and television programs (59.11)*, where it more than doubled from BGN 27,708,000 in 2008 to BGN 57,889,000 in 2018. The largest increase in value added is in *Technical activities & post-production (59.12)* by nearly five times, from BGN 11,375,000 in 2008 to BGN 56,268,000 in 2018. The value added in distribution (59.13) peaked in 2013 (BGN 13,240,000) and has

declined more than ten times since then, to BGN 1,422,000 in 2018. In **Film screening (59.14)**, the **added value increased more than five times** from BGN 2,678,000 in 2008 to BGN 13,692,000 in 2018, as opposed to the practical disappearance of rental of video cassettes and discs (77.22) from the market.

Figure 4: Foreign Direct Investment in the Film industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Data on foreign direct investment (FDI) shows an 150% increase over 11 years, from EUR 15,646,000 in 2008 to EUR 27,632,000 in 2018. **The largest share of FDI is observed in the Production of films and television programs (59.11)**, at EUR 24,310,000, which doubled by 2018, compared to 2008. **No data is available for FDI the other NACE codes in the film industry due to data confidentiality**, as statistics cannot provide data when there are less than four units under a code. We therefore assume that under the other NACE codes in the film industry, the FDI has a minimal share of the total volume, which is often distributed between two or three companies. Foreign direct investment is a key argument in favour of adopting national legislation to attract foreign film productions to the country. FDI is an accurate measure of the effectiveness and efficiency of financial incentives for foreign film productions.

Figure 5: Employment in the film Industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

The data analysis for **employment in the film industry for 2008–2018** shows a triple increase. The largest number of employees is in the *Production of films and television programs (59.11)*, which more than tripled. Employment in post-production (59.12) has increased nearly four times. In distribution (59.13) there was a slight increase from 221 employees in 2008 to 250 in 2018, whereas in film screening (59.14), the number of employees almost tripled. In rental of video cassettes and CDs, we observe a disappearing market activity (from 184 employees in 2008 to 0 in 2018).

Figure 6: Temporary employment in the Film industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Temporary employees in the film industry almost tripled, from 1,493 in 2008 to 4,369 in 2018. The largest number of temporary employees was in the production of films and television programs: 2,500 in 2018, compared to 700 in 2008. The largest increase (3.5 times) of temporary employment is in post-production, from 268 in 2008 to 1,029 in 2018. In distribution of films and television programs, temporary employees slightly increased from 189 in 2008 to 208 in 2018. In film screening, temporary employees tripled from 180 in 2008 to 562 in 2018. In renting video cassettes and discs, the decrease in this disappearing activity was from 156 temporarily hired in 2008 to 0 in 2018.

Figure 7: Turnover in the film industry (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

The data shows more than doubled turnover for the period 2008–2018, from BGN 172,747,000 in 2008 to BGN 411,671,000 in 2018. The largest turnover is in the production of films and television programs (59.11): BGN 201,134,000 in 2018 (almost double of 2008's BGN 109,449,000). The **largest increase in turnover is in Post-production (59.12), at 3.7 times** from BGN 27,018,000 in 2008 to BGN 101,512,000 in 2018. In distribution of films and television programs (59.13), the dynamics show an almost two and a half times increase from BGN 21,250,000 in 2008 to BGN 50,998,000 in 2018. Film screening showed a 4.4-times increase in turnover from BGN 13,272,000 in 2008 to BGN 58,027,000 in 2018. Like the previous indicators, the turnover of 77.22 showed a negative dynamic, as a disappearing activity (from BGN 1,758,000 in 2008 to 0 in 2018).

Hybrid products and digital audiovisual products are insufficiently and inadequately covered by the NACE taxonomy. We need consistency in the definitions of the different activities and products at the European level. For example, in code 77.22, both the national data (above) and the EAO Key Trends showed continued dramatic decreases in *Revenues from DVD and Blu-Ray retail and rental* (EAO 2018/2019 p. 58) and the opposite trend of substantial increases in TVOD and SVOD. On the other hand, TVOD and SVOD, which showed substantial increases, are not covered at the national level in Bulgaria.

Creation and archiving cannot be detected through NACE mapping, either. "Mapping the Creative Value Chains" (IDEA et al. 2017) suggests improving statistics and data collection to better monitor the impact of digitisation on the economic structure and market dynamics in creative value chains. More specifically, this could be done "by new quantitative and qualitative data gathering on market relations/dynamics within value chains to complement current official structural business statistics" and by finding "new research methods to better monitor the impact of digitisation on creative businesses and CCIs in general" (IDEA et al. 2017, p. 14). This is something CICERONE should explore in the context of our Observatory.

2.2.1 Radio, Television, and New Media

The classic electronic media market in Bulgaria has reached its maturity. It is impossible to expand any further without transforming the models of production, distribution, and audience satisfaction. This is most obvious for television, which is gradually (yearly) losing in the competition with web-hosting and web-based information services. Nevertheless, television operators may not appear to be such losers because of their transition to multi-platform media companies and the spillover of their activities. *Cross-media spillovers* are yet to be differentiated for statistical observation.

The merging of resources, as well as ownership, leads to spillover effects and the emergence of clusters, where communications, entertainment, and internet or digital environments and applications converge into modern media ecosystems (Tomova, 2015). In such an environment, public national television (BNT) is pressured by increasing competition and limited budgets. BNT is part of an oligopoly market in which commercial operators use the opportunities of the converging environment much better through creating media conglomerates, thus enabling cross-advertising and cross-financing (Tomova, 2019).

The figure below shows statistical activities in the two areas corresponding to the statistical definition of “radio, television and new media” (source OCE, 2017).

Radio, Television, and New Media	
Code	Activity
60.10	Creation and broadcasting of radio programmes
60.20	Creation and broadcasting of television programmes
63.11	Data processing, hosting, and similar activities
63.12	Web portals
63.99	Other information services (non-classified elsewhere)

Figure 8: Number of Enterprises: television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Data on enterprises in television and radio for 2008–2018 shows almost a 2.5-times increase from 1,021 in 2008 to 2,493 in 2018. The largest number of enterprises is in *Other information services, unclassified elsewhere* (63.99) at 1,114 for 2018 (over a 2.5-times increase compared to 377 in 2008). We observed almost a **3.5-times increase in the number of enterprises in Data processing, hosting and similar** (63.11), from 258 in 2008 to 800 in 2018. In *Web portals* (63.12) we observed positive dynamics, from 76 enterprises in 2008 to 367 in 2018. In *Creation and broadcasting of television programs* (60.20), we observed a decrease in the number of enterprises from 224 in 2008 to 155 in 2018. In *Creation and broadcasting of radio programs* (60.10), about half of the enterprises on the market have left, decreasing from 86 in 2008 to 47 in 2018.

The data shows about a 2.5-times increase in added value for television and radio, from BGN 239,347,000 in 2008 to BGN 718,365,000 in 2018. **The highest added value is in Data processing, hosting and similar activities** (63.11) at BGN 283,368,000 in 2018, a **4.5-times increase** compared to BGN 63,144,000 in 2008. A relatively large increase in value added was observed in *Other information services, non-classified elsewhere* (63.99), from 22,717 in 2008 to 196,568 in 2018. We observed a substantial increase in turnover (six times) in *Web portals*, from BGN 4,061,000 in 2008 to BGN

36,713,000 in 2018. In *Creation and broadcasting of television programs*, regardless the decrease in the number of enterprises, there was an increase in value added (from BGN 143,165,000 in 2008 to BGN 188,214,000 in 2018). In *Creation and broadcasting of radio programmes*, we observed a similar trend: a decreased number of enterprises and a slight increase in value added (from BGN 11,184,000 in 2008 to BGN 13,502,000 in 2018).

Figure 9: Added value - television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Figure 10: Foreign direct investment—television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Data on foreign direct investment (FDI) in television and radio for the period 2008–2018 show interesting dynamics, with numbers fluctuating from EUR 153,813,000 in 2008, a sharp decline in 2011 to EUR 4,031,000, and a steady growth rate for the period 2014–2018 to EUR 142,508,000 in 2018. Ad in the film industry, the remaining NACE codes are not available for television and radio due to data confidentiality.

Figure 11: Employment—television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Employment in television and radio for 2008–2018 almost doubled, from 8,597 in 2008 to 15,150 in 2018. The largest number of employees was observed in *Data processing, hosting and similar activities* (63.11), with 6,774 for 2018, or almost a triple increase compared to 2,373 in 2008. We observed a relatively large increase in employees in *Other information services* (63.99), from 1,234 in 2008 to 4,668 in 2018. In *Web portals*, we observed high dynamics and an increase from 184 employees in 2008 to 803 in 2018. In *Creation and broadcasting of television programs*, the number of employees decreased from 4,042 in 2008 to 2,469 in 2018. A similar trend was observed also in *Creating and broadcasting radio programs*, with a decreased number of employees on the market from 764 in 2008 to 436 in 2018.

Figure 12: Temporary employment—television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Temporary employees in television and radio almost doubled from 7,927 in 2008 to 13,393 in 2018. The largest number of temporary employees is in *Data processing, hosting and similar activities* with 6,168 in 2018, an almost threefold growth compared to 2008 (2,160). A substantial increase in temporary employees was observed in *Other information services, non-classified elsewhere*, from 975

in 2008 to 3,926 in 2018. In *Web portals*, temporary employment more than tripled, from 140 employees in 2008 to 534 in 2018. In *Creation and broadcasting of television programs*, we observed a slight decrease in the number of temporary employees, from 2,556 in 2008 to 2,369 in 2018. In *Creating and broadcasting radio programs*, we observed a decrease as well, from 457 companies in 2008 to 396 in 2018.

Figure 13: Turnover—television and radio (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

The data shows about a 2.5-times increase in turnover in television and radio, from BGN 645,072,000 in 2008 to BGN 1,335,353,000 in 2018. The largest turnover was in *Creation and broadcasting of television programs*: BGN 465,078,000 in 2018, compared to BGN 417,225,000 in 2008. We observed a relatively large increase in turnover in *Data processing, hosting and similar activities* (from 109,876 in 2008 to 438,779 in 2018). For *Other information services*, we saw relatively high dynamics varying from BGN 77,777,000 in 2008 to BGN 342,075,000 in 2018. **Turnover in Web portals increased almost eight times, from BGN 7,783,000 in 2008 to BGN 61,529,000 in 2018.** In *Creation and broadcasting of radio programs*, the turnover decreased from BGN 32,411,000 in 2008 to BGN 27,892,000 in 2018.

2.2.3 Video Games

Today the Bulgarian gaming industry is a complete ecosystem. At present, there is a substantial increase in the number of companies and employees in the sector in Bulgaria (see Figures 13–18), as the country has become one the best IT outsourcing destinations in the region. Three of the biggest gaming companies are represented in our country: UBISOFT, Gameloft, and SEGA. We have our own success stories: the creators of Tropic Series, Victor Vran, and Tsar are Bulgarian games. One of the best MMORTS studios in the world is Imperia Online (Kadinov, Velinova, 2018). The sector has potential as a growing game development community, is already a European leader in IT development, and has a history of technological accomplishment and innovation.²⁹

²⁹ Tim Heaton, Studio Director at Creative Assembly, <https://www.creative-assembly.com/node/5141##>

Video games	
Code	Activity
58.21	Release of computer games
58.29	Release of other software products
62.01	Computer programming

Figure 14: Number of enterprises in video games (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Data on enterprises in software and video games show a 2.5-times increase from 965 in 2008 to 2,638 in 2018. The vast majority of these enterprises are in *Computer programming* (62.01), with 2,511 for 2018 almost a triple increase compared to 2008 (877). Enterprises in *Release of other software products* also increased (from 78 enterprises in 2008 to 101 in 2018). In *Release of computer games* (58.29), there were 10 companies in 2008 and 26 in 2018.

Figure 15: Added value in video games (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Value added in video games has increased over five times in an 11-year period, from BGN 235,597,000 in 2008 to BGN 1,378,980,000 in 2018. The highest added value is in *Computer programming*, with BGN 1,333,410,000 in 2018, almost five times more than in 2008 (BGN 226,453,000). Value added in *Release of other software products* increased about four times (BGN 9,079,000 in 2008 to BGN 38,703,000 in 2018). Value added in *Release of computer games* (58.29) saw the highest increase, from BGN 65,000 in 2008 to BGN 6,867,000 in 2018 (100 times).

Figure 16: Foreign direct investment in video games (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Foreign direct investment in video games increased over five times, from EUR 25,524,000 thousand in 2008 to EUR 134,869,000 in 2018. The largest increase in FDI was in *Computer programming*: the figure of EUR 104,909,000 in 2018 was eight times more than the EUR 13,079,000 in 2008. The rest of the NACE codes are not available for video games due to data confidentiality.

Figure 17: Employment in video games (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Employment in software and video games increased over threefold, from 7,109 in 2008 to 21,108 in 2018. Most of the employees were obviously in computer programming (20,071 for 2018, over a 2.5-

fold increase compared to 6,750 for 2008). In *Release of other software products*, the employment almost tripled, from 343 employees in 2008 to 912 in 2018. In *Release of computer games*, the 16 employed in 2008 increased to 125 in 2018. In small and independent computer studios, activities often overlap (i.e. developers are publishers and vice versa).

Figure 18: Temporary employment—video games (2008/2009–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

Temporary employment in video games tripled, from 6,437 in 2009³⁰ to 19,272 in 2018. The vast majority of the temporary employees in the sector are in computer programming: 18,311 in 2018, compared to 7,200 in 2009. In *Release of other software products*, the temporarily employed increased slightly (765 in 2008 to 853 in 2018). In *Release of computer games*, temporary employees increased from four employees in 2008 to 108 in 2018.

Figure 19: Turnover in video games (2008–2018)

Source: NSI/OCE

³⁰ Data by type of activity is not available for 2008, hence we considered 2009 as baseline in this case (OCE).

Data on the turnover in video games for the period 2008–2018 show more than a fivefold increase, from BGN 374,429,000 in 2008 to BGN 1,921,949,000 in 2018.³¹ The largest turnover was observed in *Computer programming*: BGN 1,833,712,000 for 2018, almost a five-fold increase compared to BGN 359,383,000 in 2008. *Release of other software products* increased from BGN 14,999,000 in 2008 to BGN 77,704,000 in 2018. In *Release of computer games*, we observed the **highest increase in turnover**, from BGN 47,000 in 2008 to BGN 10,533,000 in 2018.

Key features of the mapping methodology:

- The timeframe of the recurring mapping survey covers data from 2008—2018 , which allows for tracking the dynamics of observed indicators and outlining trends.
- Observed metrics included the number of enterprises, turnover, number of employees, value added at factor costs, direct foreign investment, and other.
- The method does not cover creation or archiving.
- When revenue is measured, value added is used at factor cost, which is an indicator imposed by EUROSTAT, rather than gross added value. It is accepted that this indicator can be obtained from accurate measurements in the field of cultural and creative industries, going down to the level of enterprise. (Turnover data and value added at factor costs relate only to non-financial enterprises)

³¹ Exchange rate is fixed at 1,9558 BGN per 1 EUR (see [ECB exchange rate](#)).

2.3 The video games industry in Austria

The PGDA association, or the Pioneers of Game Development Austria (PGDA 2022), monitors the activities and developments of the Austrian games industry and regularly publishes reports in cooperation with the Austrian Economic Chamber WKO (WKO/IWI 2019) and the Institute for Industrial Economy (IWI). The newest report, from 2019, showed that there were 90 companies employing approximately 500 professionals. The revenues were about EUR 25 million. Export activities look important for the domestic industry, as eight out of 10 Austrian companies export their products; while export partners are located all over the world, most of them are located in Europe (80.9%), followed by the USA (68.1%), Australia (57.4%), and Asia (53.2%). The graph below shows the export territories of domestic game developers.

Figure 20: Export of Austrian domestic game developers

Source: WKO/IWI 2019, p. 35

Concerning the exchange phase, in other words, the consumption of games, the report “Gaming in Austria 2021” by ÖVUS (2021) shows that the number of gamers is continuously increasing and that 5.3 million Austrians are currently playing video games, which equals about six out of 10 citizens. The average gaming time is 12.9 hours a week, with most gamers using smartphones (43%) as a device, followed by consoles (28%), PCs (26%), tablets (16%), and handhelds (7%). Fifty-two percent of the gamers are male, 48% are female, and the average age is 36 years.

2.4 Conclusions and open issues on the statistical mapping of the audiovisual industries

With this analysis, we aimed to critically assess the available sources of data on the audiovisual sectors, looking into the three large sub-sectors—film industry, television and radio, and video games—through the perspective of the global production network (GPN). The conclusions follow the structure of the analysis in Part 2.

Conclusions on the analysis of Eurostat data on audiovisual industries using the GPN approach

Compared to the other cultural and creative industries, the audiovisual sector—film industry, radio and television market, and video games— is relatively well-represented in the economic activity coding system (NACE). In total, for all three sub-sectors of the audiovisual sector, the exchange and archive phases have the same codes, which do not allow the separation and presentation of relevant information for the three individual sub-sectors of film industry, radio and television market, and video games. All three sub-sectors are characterised by an intermingling of codes, which distorts the information as there is no methodology to use relative weights of each activity for specific codes, nor do we have the option of using five-digit codes, which is one of the biggest problems with statistical reporting through the NACE codes of EUROSTAT. In analysing the statistical reporting of the audiovisual sector, we could draw the following conclusions and recommendations that are relevant in better accounting for the different phases of the global production chain in the audiovisual sector.

The EUROSTAT database does have an issue in accounting for the global production chain in CCI at the regional level. The European countries are divided into administrative regions, but the available statistical information is in two-digit codes only. In fact, there is no possibility quantitatively analysing one of the most important dimensions of the CCIs in Europe: the regional dimension. We know how important the role of the EU regions is, and CCIs are acknowledged as a catalyst and contributor to economic development and social cohesion. Unfortunately, we could not measure their contribution through Eurostat. The CICERONE project could therefore recommend to Eurostat to improve their data collection for CCIs at the regional level.

Film industry—conclusions and recommendations

- Employment in creation and production phases overlaps with the film industry, as both involve data under codes 59.11.
- In the creation phase (code 90.03 *Artistic creation*), Eurostat does not provide information that is relevant to the Member States of the European Union.

- For the production and distribution phases, the codes include two sub-markets: the film industry, and video and television programme production. Hence, these industries cannot be distinguished at these phases.
59.11 *Motion picture, video and television programme production*
59.12 *Motion picture, video and television programme post-production*
59.13 *Motion picture, video and television programme distribution*
- In the exchange phase of film industry, the data in the “Extensive” codes includes not only the exchange phase in the film industry but also other economic activities, as well as cross-cutting activities with other cultural and creative industries.
82.30 *Organisation of conventions and trade shows*
58.11 *Book publishing*
58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*
73.1 *Advertising*
Such aggregated information does not allow us to distinguish the specific economic activities relevant for the film industry, nor to attribute to them specific weight. Hence, we need a fifth code with a precise definition, which would provide information specifically about the exchange phase in the film industry.
- In the archiving phase, Eurostat level codes 91.01 *Library and archives activities* and 91.02 *Museums activities*, are only available as two-digit codes. Information can be collected individually through structural business statistics from the National Statistical Institutes of the Member States of the European Union. The same issue exists for the archiving phase in the television and radio industries, where the same two codes apply. Film and television archives do not have specific codes.
- There is no separate code for streaming platforms, which are a very important distribution channel for film production.
- There is no separate code for the importance of film festivals or the development of a satellite account to measure direct economic effects, especially at the regional level.
- There is no separation of code 78.10, which includes the selection and distribution of roles in cinema, theatre and television (casting services).

Radio and television market—conclusions and recommendations

- The creation and production phases are identical for the film industry and the radio and television market. For this reason, we could not distinguish, on the basis of the codes, relevant information about the radio and television markets.
- In the creation phase, for code 90.03 *Artistic creation*, Eurostat does not provide information that is relevant for the Member States of the European Union.
- In the exchange phase of the film industry, the data for the “extensive” codes is identical to that for the radio and television markets and aggregates information about other economic activities.
- There is no clear separation of activities in the cable, satellite, and wireless retransmission codes in the exchange phase that would allow us to obtain relevant information about the broadcast of a film product by retransmission.

- No aggregated Eurostat data is available on the value added in the archiving and exchange phases in television and radio. Data is collected from the national statistical institutes of the EU Member States.

Video games—conclusions and recommendations

- The creation and production of video games is included in NACE code 62.01 *Computer programming*. The codes for the creation and production phases are together under this same code, which does not allow for separate analysis of specific economic activities related to video games.
- In the creation phase, there is a two-digit code that could not indicate the relative weight of creation activity in video games: 90.03 *Artistic creation*.
- In the production phase, under the economic activity code 26.40 *Manufacture of consumer electronics*, the activities that relate solely to video games cannot be distinguished as separate economic activities.
- In the distribution phase, we used the code 47.41 *Retail sale of video game consoles and retail sale of non-customised software, including video games*. It is necessary to separate into a five-digit code the retail-only sale of video games. Code 47.91 *Retail sale via mail order houses or via Internet* includes all activity related to internet commerce; hence, one could not distinguish the share of consumption via internet or mail order of video games and related activities.
- The exchange and archive phases are informed by the same codes as the film industry and the radio and television market:
 - Exchange 58.11 *Book publishing*
 - Exchange 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*
 - Exchange 73.1 *Advertising*
 - Archive 91.01 *Library and archives activities*
 - Archive 91.02 *Museums activities*

Conclusions on the national statistical data specificity in Bulgaria, a small audiovisual market

The analysis is based on national mapping methodology for CCIs covering the period 2008–2018. When examining the Eurostat NACE codes for the three vast sectors included in the scope of audiovisual industries, we observed the following discrepancies and gaps at the national level.

- Four codes are missing from the Eurostat database: 90.03 *Artistic Creation*, 91.01 *Performing arts*, 91.02 *Support activities to performing arts*, and 94.99 *Activities of other membership organisations*.

There is a limitation by industry and activity in the EUROSTAT methodology and metadata. Therefore, these codes are available in national databases but are not publicly available.

- “Problematic” NACE codes are those two-digit codes which include more than one industry such that one cannot distinguish the shares of cinema, television, games, and multimedia within the same code. Such overlapping codes exist in almost all cultural industries. Therefore,

at the national level we need four-digit codes, with deeper levels of detail, in order to collect statistical data about each cultural or creative industry.

Such two-digit codes for audiovisual industries are

- Creation: 90.03 *Artistic creation*
- Distribution: 47.63 *Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores*
- Archiving: 91.01 *Library and archives activities*

The same limitations apply also to the extensive codes in film, television, and gaming, such as

- Exchange: 94.99 *Activities of other membership organisations n.e.c*
 - Exchange: 58.11 *Book publishing*
 - Exchange: 58.14 *Publishing of journals and periodicals*
 - Exchange: 73.1 *Advertising*
- Regarding non-cultural activities, there are codes that could give incorrect information about the nature of the audiovisual industry. We believe that the inclusion of non-cultural or creative activities may skew the aggregation of information.

For example, code 26.40 includes "the production of the manufacture of electronic audio and video equipment for home entertainment, motor vehicle, public address systems and musical instrument amplification," and somewhere there is the production of game consoles. Code 47.91 provides information that includes e-commerce in general. These codes, if they cannot address the production of the game console, for example, will result in overcounting some industries.

- 26.40 *Manufacture of consumer electronics*
- 47.91 *Retail sale via mail order houses or via Internet*

Relative weights should be made for the four-digit codes, which cover activities beyond the cultural and creative industries.

Activities that are not covered by statistics (i.e. that have no codes) include

- **Film - Exchange - Online distribution - Digital distribution** via over-the-top services (OTT) and VoD, the main the large multimedia platforms, including GAFAs;
- **Videogames - Transmission - Audience feedback**, including alpha and beta versions in the digital environment; and
- **Videogames - Archive - Digital archiving**, including re-selling digital platforms' digital assets and digital copies.

The EUROSTAT database does have an issue in accounting for the global production chain in CCIs at the regional level. Countries are administratively divided into regions, but the information that is provided is in two-digit codes only. In fact, there is no possibility of quantitatively analysing one of the most important dimensions of the CCIs in Europe: the regional dimension. We know how important the role of the EU regions is, and CCIs are acknowledged as a catalyst of and contributor to economic development and social cohesion. Unfortunately, one could not measure their contribution through EUROSTAT.

The CICERONE project therefore recommends that EUROSTAT improve their data collection for CCIs at the regional level.

The foreign direct investment (FDI) is an important indicator of CCI's development. EUROSTAT does not collect data on FDI for CCIs. Such data can be collected from the national statistical institutes of the EU Member States on CCI's global production networks. FDI is crucial for the dynamic Central and Eastern European markets and leave an imprint on all GPN phases of CCIs, especially if we identify where its power leverage and market dominance are concentrated. The media and film industries are a good example of how important FDI is during the transfer of capital and influence.

Data on **employment** in the audiovisual sectors is also difficult to compile at the European level. The statistical definitions of audiovisual in national statistics vary from country to country in the AV sectors; the Netherlands is among the few countries where national definition is aligned with Eurostat). There are also different data collection methods at the national level. Data about employment in public broadcasters in many countries is not included in the Eurostat business statistics.

European Audiovisual Observatory's resources and the GPN

The observatory provides the most useful resources for audiovisual industries and policies in Europe, collecting data from various public and private sources and tracking the main trends in the European audiovisual global production networks.

PART 3. The fieldwork: analysis and results

3.1 Case studies in the audiovisual industries

3.1.1 Methodology, unit of analysis, and selection of cases

This chapter introduces four case studies, three from Bulgaria and one from Austria, covering the audiovisual industries film, television, radio, and video games.

Case study 1—Film industry: KLAS Film production company

The choice of this case study was based on several factors driven by our desire to gain new insights and information about the GPN of a film production company. Through the **network analysis of KLAS Film**, we expected to reveal some mechanisms, relationships, and dynamics relevant to CICERONE research. KLAS Film is a small (micro) production company based in Sofia, Bulgaria. Sustaining a small organisation in the film industry is a challenge in the national context. These micro-organisations have developed business models, which become interesting when they evolve into co-producers at the European level. We observed the national and the European dimensions of the KLAS Film production network: its geographical footprint, diversity of financial sources, including public and private, and its forms of embeddedness, as well as the factor of policy research. We therefore chose a Bulgarian film production company in order to provide insights about that largely unexplored area. Below, we introduce the specific historical, cultural, and socio-economic context of Bulgaria as a new democracy that has endured a long and painful economic and social transition after 1989. The Bulgarian film industry was therefore shaped by specific national conditions and policies, which influenced KLAS Film (lead firm) and its large and complex production network.

The empirical research took place between January 2021 and December 2022, when the researchers conducted 14 interviews with actors covering all phases of the global production network: creation, production, distribution, exchange, and archiving. Most of the interviews took place digitally, as they were conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. All interviews were conducted in the Bulgarian language, then transcribed and translated into English. The interviews reveal a full and comprehensive picture of all phases of the production network, which centre in Bulgaria but also spread across Europe. Among the interviewees, both horizontal relationships and production company roles are covered, as well as vertical relations with public institutions (national and local or municipal, as well as international or European). During the development of the KLAS Film case study, we encountered no difficulties and no refusals to participate in the research task. The questions in the interviews did not pose difficulty for the film professionals interviewed.

Table 33. KLAS Film case study

Role	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Stakeholder
Director, National Film Archive				X	X	

Film producer, owner	X	X				
Unit production manager	X		X			
National Film Centre, International Relations Department	X		X			
Producer, Association of Film Producers, member of European Film Academy	X	X				X
Film programmer, film critic			X	X		
Director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings, producer			X	X		
Executive director, FILMAUTOR-Collective management rights			X			
Film critic, representative of Bulgaria in Film New Europe, producer	X		X			
Film director, script writer	X	X				
Producer, former director of the National Film Centre Executive Agency	X	X				
Director of Culture Department, Sofia municipality	X					
Film producer, film director	X	X				
Director, Creative Europe-Media programme, Bulgaria	X		X			

Case study 2 — television industry: Eurovision, European song contests, European Broadcasting Union

The Observatory of Cultural Economics conducted two case studies of the European Broadcasting Union, reflecting two different audiovisual industries, television and radio, with Case Study 2 focusing on television and Case Study 3 focusing on public radio. For Case 2, the **network of Eurovision and European Song Contests**, the researchers carried out 11 interviews with actors from all phases of the global production network: creation, production, distribution, exchange, and archiving. The interviews present a comprehensive picture of all phases of public media participation in the Eurovision Song Contest. The interviewees reflected both horizontal relationships and roles in the Eurovision project, as well as participants in public–private partnerships in Bulgaria's participation in the song contest. During the development of the case study, we did not encounter any difficulties in conducting the interviews or refusals to participate in the research task. The questions in the interviews were understandable and logical for the media professionals interviewed.

Case Study 2, Network of Eurovision Song Contest, used *Bulgarian National Television* as an entry point in the production network. This case was chosen for the following reasons. First, the importance of public service media for the audiovisual sector in Europe suggests a particular interest in the socio-cultural embeddedness of the EBU, and the **Eurovision Song Contest network** in particular, in European societies. Secondly, the Eurovision Song Contest is an example of a sophisticated public media service project: the implementation of GPN can reveal interesting analyses, dynamics, and specificities. Third, the televised Eurovision contest has three simultaneous dimensions as a cultural product, which make it a rich case for analysis: as a stage product (concert), a television product (live broadcast), and music industry product.

No less complex and interesting is the chain of authors and participants who contribute to the spectacular size of its network and its pan-European territorial scope. The entry point is Bulgarian National Television, which participates in the competition through a specific business model: a public–private partnership. This gives a particular perspective on the connections and relationships within the Eurovision network.

The empirical research and interviews took place from August 2021 to April 2022. The interviewed participants cover all phases of the production chain of the public service media market.

Table 34. EBU case study

Role	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Stakeholder
Head of International Communications, Bulgarian National Television (BNT)	X			X		
Head of Delegation for Bulgaria at Eurovision since 2012, Executive Director of Junior Eurovision Song Contest 2015, BNT	X	X			X	
BNT, sport department				X		
Expert in international relations, Department of International Communications, Junior Television Coproduction's with EBU, BNT	X					
PR and media consultant, Entiendo	X		X			
EBU: Head of Member Relations for Central and Eastern Europe	X					
Media law expert, professor at Sofia University						

Case Study 3—Radio industry: Euroradio music exchange (digital platform and archive)—MUS, European Broadcasting Union

In 2021–2022, OCE conducted 11 interviews (plus one informal interview) with actors from all phases of the global production network of MUS-EBU in creation, production, distribution, exchange, and

archiving, using Bulgarian National Radio as an entry point to the EBU music exchange. The interviews present a comprehensive picture of all phases of music exchange in public media. They cover horizontal relationships and roles in national radio, as well as participants in public–private partnerships in music exchange. During the development of this case study, we did not encounter difficulties or refusals on behalf of the actors but rather the opposite: the interviewees were very cooperative. The nature of the questions were understandable for them.

The choice of the EBU music radio exchange (archive platform) reflects several elements. Music formats have a traditional place in radio programming. Employees of choirs and musical formations in the EU radio industry have relatively low pay. Such music formations across Europe are undergoing cuts. The cultural and economic roles of music creation, production, and exchange by public radio stations remain undervalued and under-researched. The musical outputs of choirs and orchestras, which are integral parts of European public radio, are also undervalued. The choice of this case study allows an in-depth analysis of these processes. The analysis of the EBU's **Music Radio Exchange Network** provides new insights into the mechanisms, processes, and institutions through the aspect of GPN. Music radio exchange sets a high standard of cultural exchange, and this mission of public radio stations should receive adequate public funding. This issue is a key policy focus for public service media. Bulgarian National Radio is the entry point for examining this network.

The empirical research and interviews took place from August 2021 to March 2022. The interviewed participants cover different phases of the global production chain in the two case studies.

Table 35. Music exchange case study

Role	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving	Stakeholder
Director of International Relations, BNR, Coordinator of the Regional Group of Central and Eastern European Public Media, EBU	X					
Former Director of Music Production and Ensembles, BNR, Producer; Bulgarian Association of Cultural Employers; professor of music Academy, Sofia;	X			X		
Chief expert, Department of International Relations, BNR	X			X		
Music editor, BNR	X	X			X	
Head of Member Relations for Central and Eastern Europe, EBU	X					
Media law expert, professor at Sofia University						X

Case Study 4–Video games: Viennese Gaming Sector

Our selection of the case study for the gaming industry came as a result of considering many parameters. In the first stages of our empirical research in this particular field, we considered different options for potential case studies with regard to size, international coverage, and relationships between them. We chose the Viennese gaming sector because it has an interesting ecosystem, one that is centrally relevant to the industry; Vienna is also home to Vienna Game City, one of the largest events in the games sector, and is therefore well-known to different stakeholders in the sector. We chose smaller-sized organisations and companies rather than bigger ones because we thought that, in terms of GPN theory, they would be more useful in offering insights into mechanisms, relations, dynamics, practices, perspectives, and actors that we would not be able to identify or research if choosing a larger-scale company.

The empirical research on the gaming industry case study started in June 2021 with the first interview, but most of the interviews were conducted between October and December 2021, and the last one took place in January 2022.

The researchers conducted 14 interviews and one informal interview with actors from all phases of the production cycle, focusing on the local Viennese situation. The interviewees came from gaming companies of different sizes, funding bodies, game fairs and festivals, academia, a large multinational company in the sector, and the freelance gaming sector.

Table 36. Video games case study

Role	Date
Academic & developer/CEO, serious games	16/06/21
Producer, startup, students	15/07/21
Games Culture Association	20/07/21
Support of local games companies	29/10/21
Networking & events for games	10/11/21
CEO & founder gaming company	11/11/21
Academic leader in games & business, legal expert	15/11/21
Music for games, composing & programming	22/11/21
Critical games expert, games developer	29/11/21
Financing culture, games & international networks	6/12/21
XR developer, CEO/founder, networking expert	7/12/21
Festival organiser/founder, developer, artist	10/12/21
Montreal, marketing product director	20/12/21
Vienna biggest games fair	19/01/22
Biggest games fair in Europe	25/01/22

Most interviews took place online because of COVID-19 restrictions, particularly from October 2021 onwards, but also because of interviewee availability. In some cases, interviews were conducted in the offices of the companies, where University of Vienna researchers also had the opportunity to see their working spaces and acquire a taste of the working culture. Some interviews took place outside (one in a café, one in the University of Vienna campus park), again because of COVID-19 restrictions but also because the interviewees chose an environment that was more informal and friendlier than an office or a Zoom session. We did not have severe difficulty accessing potential interviewees; the most significant barrier was their working schedules or the time difference, in the case of an interview conducted with an individual based in Canada, but in no case did we have major obstacles in finding a suitable slot for the interview. All our interviewees said they found the research very interesting; they had no problems discussing the issues we asked them about and were also keen to know more about the results when they would be published.

3.2 Case 1: KLAS FILM production company

“The Prosecutor, the Defender, the Father and His Son” - on the set of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY), Copyright: KLAS Film

Producers of “Letter to America”: Lazslo Kantor, Petra Goedings, and Rossitsa Valkanova. Copyright: KLAS Film

Poster of "Letter to America," film by Igljka Trifonova, producer KLAS Film, Rossitsa Valkanova. Copyright: KLAS Film

The main driver of growth in cultural and creative sectors and industries (CCIs) in Europe is the audiovisual sector (film, television and radio, video games). Between 2013 and 2017, their total value added grew by 7.2% to EUR 185 billion, and they employ 1.9% of the EU workforce (KEA, EIF 2021). The indicators for the film industry in Bulgaria in the past decade have shown the same increasing trend. For the period 2008–2019, the number of companies in the film industry grew by 147%, employment in the sector grew by 146%, and the value added for 2019 reached 151 million BGN, with a growth of 228% in the same period (OCE, 2021). The indicators for Sofia, the capital city, where the presence of an audiovisual cluster has also been identified, are much higher as the city accounts for 97% of the turnover of the film industry, 80% in radio, television, and new media, and 85% in software and video games (OCE, 2021). Data confirms that clusters are typical for a network that goes beyond

the linear outcomes of the value chain and carries potential for cross-sector linkages between different areas of creative economy (Weller, 2008 cited in Coe, 2015).

The Bulgarian film industry is experiencing the typical constraints of small markets and closed language communities, such as difficulty making economies of scale, and constraints in reaching out to a large public in an environment of global oversupply. The GPN approach enables access to new resources and markets (a type of rent-seeking) through participation in **co-production networks** (Coe, 2015). In applying the GPN approach to the film industry in Bulgaria, we found that national film production has strong prospects additional funding through co-productions provided mainly by the pan-European programs "Media" (Creative Europe) and the "Eurimages" co-production fund, regional funds in individual markets, and access to rents or benefits from inclusion in the production of an international, name-talent brand (Tomova, 2021).

Independent producers (micro-, small-, or medium-sized companies, autonomous organisationally and economically, and independent market participants) are the predominant organisational form in the European film industry. The independent producer has a leading role in European audiovisual policy, where "Audiovisual media services are more cultural than economic ones" (Directive 2007/65/EU), and cinema falls explicitly in the "cultural exception" column. This concept defines the role of the state in the sector, and the socio-cultural characteristics of the audiovisual services also predetermine the need for state regulation and support.

3.2.1 Phases, actors, and locations of KLAS Film

The film industry case study examines **KLAS Film**, a company that fits the typology of an independent producer and hence exemplifies best the key players in the film industry market. KLAS Film is a Bulgarian film production company founded in 1995 by Rossitsa Valkanova. It has produced 10 fiction feature films (six in co-production with the Netherlands, Hungary, Germany, France, Sweden, Denmark, and Romania); five feature-length documentaries, four fiction shorts, four minority co-productions, and six as line producer. The company has established sustainable partnerships as line producer for Teona Mitevska in three films; in four films co-produced with Petra Goedings (Phanta Vision, the Netherlands), including *Blind* (2007) by Tamar van den Dop; and in four films co-produced with Ada Solomon (Hi Film, Romania), including *Aferim!* (2015) and *I Don't Care if We Go Down in History as Barbarians* (2018) by Radu Jude. KLAS aims at high-quality production and to keep the artistic value of cinema, viewing cinema as art and not only as an industry. Most of KLAS' titles have become emblematic for Bulgarian cinema of the past 27 years and have received awards at numerous festivals.

Currently, KLAS Film is working on three Bulgarian feature films, and there are four minority co-productions in various stages of production, all supported by NFC, including the new film of Bulgarian director Konstantin Bojanov (with Swiss majority, co-produced also by France, and supported by Eurimages).

Rossitsa Valkanova is the founder and owner of the company. She worked as delegate, executive, and associated and line producer in the production of numerous Bulgarian and foreign films. She is a member of national and international film selection committees and juries and a member of European Film Academy. "Rositsa's work spans at least several different periods in Bulgarian cinema: the gradual emergence from the crisis of the 1990s, the renewed interest of Bulgarian audiences in Bulgarian films from the middle of the first decade of the 21st century, and the increasingly frequent festival successes in the following decade" (Punev, 2021).

The production network in the making of a film has clearly delineated phases. It is a long network with many participants, most of them involved in several phases. These actors have one profession, but their actual activity shows that they can be seen in several roles (director and scriptwriter; producer, distributor and festival organiser; producer and film critic; director, actor and producer, etc.). An explanation can be sought in the size of the market, its maturity, the specificity of the product being created, and the demand for sustainability by the actors and companies.

The time it takes to create a film from the idea to the distribution stage (i.e. when the product is ready but the process of return of funds, or when reimbursement has not yet started) is at least two years (Debande, Chetrit, 2001: 11).

Figure 21: Global production network for KLAS Film—phases and actors

In the conducted interviews (14 pieces), we found actors who bridge between the different phases, as well as actors who are not directly involved in the creation of the film but who shape policies and

influences (i.e. they are stakeholders: representatives of the state or municipality, professional associations, national or international funding organisations).

In the production network, KLAS Film is the **lead company**. It has a leading role both in the individual phases and in the network (i.e. the network is structured around this core firm). KLAS Film initiates, coordinates, and manages each project, and secures and manages the resources associated with it. The producer exercises financial and creative control over the process and product. The creative control goes through the contract signed with the director. The production company has strategic functions in the selection of the idea, teams, and the partner (i.e. it makes decisions about the inter-company division of labour). The network of making a film (film project) operates on several levels, especially in local, national, European, and global co-productions.

Creation

The initiation stage includes finding a strong idea (by the producer, writer, or director), developing the idea into a script (by the screenwriter) or buying the rights to a literary source (book) on which the script will be based, presenting the idea at specialised forums for project development (e.g. Sofia Meetings, Thessaloniki, Torino Film Lab), searching for talents producer, director) and locations for shooting (producer, director, cinematographer), and creating the first budget estimates (by the producer).

The creation phase involves the producer, the writer, the director, the cinematographer (when looking for locations), the casting company (when looking for talent), and forums for the development of ideas (pitching forums and meetings with institutions and programs financing this most risky stage).

This most risky stage has the opportunity to receive financial support, which is not returned if the project is not implemented either 1) at the national level from the National Film Centre (NFC) for "idea development and script writing," or 2) at the European level from the Media Programme when the project is a co-production.

At this stage, the producer (usually together with the director or screenwriter) participates in various International Pitching or Meetings forums, with the aim to present the idea and find the means to develop the script. Usually, these forums are part of major festivals and are specialised co-production and co-financing platforms. Separately, there are also co-production markets (e.g. CineLink in Sarajevo, where producers can meet sales agents as well as potential co-producers).

At the end of this phase, when the script is ready and co-producers are in place, support can be sought from a prospective distributor. This support is for the broadcasting rights of the future film (i.e. the purchase of the rights for television broadcasting or cinema exhibition). This is not a large sum, but at this stage it is very valuable because it is an expression of trust. This is usually called "green funding." In Bulgaria, this is the practice most often used by Bulgarian National Television.

The script is the heart of this stage: "the co-producers who have come into our projects and become part of the production of the film always decide if they will support us by reading the script...the script

sells," says writer and director Iglia Trifonova. She has made all her feature films with producer KLAS Film.

At the creation stage, the searches for co-producers, financing, and script doctors are the reasons why a film project must move from local (Sofia) and national (Bulgaria) borders to European (Thessaloniki, Sarajevo, Berlin) and global territories (the territories that a sales agent can provide for the distribution of the film).

Production

When talking about production in cinema, a clear distinction of three stages, which are also written in the "Calendar Plan" (or Production Schedule) of the film project, is used: **1. preparation, 2. shooting on location, and 3. post-production.**

When the producer starts preparation, it means that they have already secured funding. The producer may not have "closed" 100% of the budget but has a large part of the funds. Thus, this period is preceded by finding and securing funding from a producer. The producer applies to produce a film with a set budget, financial plan, and script. Presumably, all partners and co-producers have already been secured. At this time, the main players are the producer and the funding organisations, including the National Film Centre, City of Sofia, film funding funds in the co-producers' countries, and the Eurimages programme. The application requires that preliminary contracts be signed with the main copyright holders and offers be made by all service provider companies. The creators with copyright (director, screenwriter, cinematographer, composer) transfer their copyrights to the producer. Thus, the production company is now ready to apply for financial support to various organisations.

The producer, director, cameraman, and casting company are involved in the **preparation**. A final budget, final shooting locations, and final creative and technical teams are formed. During this stage, contracts are signed with all participants in the production project, both individuals and companies. In the preparation and production stage, the role of the production director is very important; outside Bulgaria this position is called the "unit production manager." In the past several years, KLAS Film has worked with Rossen Ignatov as unit production manager. He is the founder and co-owner of Roda Production LTD. Here is what he shares:

I represent KLAS Film, I represent the producer who holds the basic rights and contracts. If the producer, in the person of R. Valkanova is responsible for the financing of the project, then I enter, who am responsible for the production of this product. I abide by the budget she puts down for me... She and I work together all the time, i.e. she is constantly monitoring the financial situation, how every penny is being spent, when new instalments are coming - all these things I have to provide her with, monitoring the production process. Once she hires me, I start putting the whole team together, I start renting equipment, stacking locations, stacking accommodations, meals, the whole process of producing the product.

Production is the most expensive phase. Its heart is the shooting period, which, depending on the type of film production—documentary, feature film, complex feature film (set in a historical era or having many difficult-to-access locations for shooting)—can last from two weeks to almost two months, or up to three years depending on the film. The participants here are extremely diverse:

lighting, sound, wardrobe, makeup, catering, stunt, as the already-listed director, cinematographers, and more. All participants and equipment are insured, and a medical team and sometimes a firefighter are always present at the shoot. Each of the days has a high price, a certain number of working hours, and a precise number of scenes to film.

A shooting day requires you to have all the people come to work first, then all the equipment to be prepared for the right day, whatever has to be used to be there, at the right hour the actors have to be on location, lunch has to come on location, all the locations have to be prepared by the art department as they should be. The whole thing has to be kind of overseen by you, with each of the departments having a department head. You've got them because they're pretty good and you know them, but you still have to look at all these details to be calm.... This business is extremely expensive. I'm not saying others aren't, but in it things can escalate by tens to hundreds of thousands in a matter of seconds and you have to be very careful about that as well. (Rossen Ignatov, unit production manager)

Post-production concludes the production stage. At this sub-stage, hours of raw footage are cut and edited, and sound, titles, soundtrack, colour correction, and special effects added. These activities are highly specialised, using special software and laboratories. If the film is Bulgarian, the production takes place in Sofia and in specific national shooting locations. When a KLAS Film is co-produced, parts of the filming or post-production are organised in another European co-producing country. The map below gives a preview of the countries in Europe that are co-producers of KLAS films.

Figure 22. KLAS Film co-production partners

Distribution

In this phase, the producer sells the distribution rights to a distributor of his choice. Distribution in the film industry is territorially bound. Most often, Bulgarian distributors operate only in the territory of Bulgaria. When the film is a co-production, it is also distributed in the territories of the co-producers, with each co-producer receiving the income from their territory. The chart above also shows the distribution territories secured by the co-productions of KLAS Film. The distribution channels used by KLAS Film, besides the cinema distributors (ProFilms, A+, Art Fest, Purple Rain, NO BLINK), are streaming platforms (e.g. HBO Go), pay television, and public television.

The distribution phase also includes the marketing, advertising, promotion, and festival appearances of the film. These activities are carried out by distributors, film reviewers, social media, sales agents, and festival organisers.

Film critics set trends. Depending on the reviews that appear in Variety, Screen International and Wire—there are 4–5 reference publications in the business film world—they determine the future of a film actually. One must also know them in order to be able to invite them or at least know who to approach. I invite them. Sometimes I send them films so they can have their say. They are just the influencers. (Mira Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings, producer)

Festivals at this stage have a huge importance: they are the primary market for film production, they give visibility through critical acclaim and awards, and they lead to contracts between producers, sales agents, and distributors. A film's entry into the festival selection determines its future. KLAS Film's portfolio includes entries, selections, and awards from the Golden Rose Bulgarian Feature Film Festival, Sofia International Film Festival, Locarno (Golden Leopard for *Godless*), and Berlin (Silver Bear for *Aferim!*, minority producer). The minority Bulgarian participation in the production of *Aferim!* was quite large, involving all the shooting, cinematography, lighting equipment, camera assistants, sound equipment and field crew, and makeup artists, and most of the props and costumes. Distribution costs are supported at the national level by the NFC. Distribution activities, as well as festivals, can be supported by the Creative Europe Media Programme, Bulgaria.

In the EU over 70% of the total budget of the Media Programme goes to distribution, this is a very large percentage because the idea is to make it possible to circulate the audiovisual product between one member country and another member country. (Kamen Balkanski, Creative Europe–Media, Director, Bulgaria)

Exchange/ Exhibition/ Film screening

The bridge between distribution and display is the activity of the programmer, who buys films from distributors and arranges them into a programme for theatrical or festival exhibition. This phase is where the physical showing of the film in cinemas takes place, but it is also where the digital showing via streaming platforms from OTT (over-the-top) providers takes place, as well as the broadcast of the film by television channels.

The National Film Centre (NFC) financially supports cinemas showing Bulgarian and European films, and the Creative Europe-Media programme supports the Euro Cinema network of specialised cinemas across Europe. (The Cinema Block project is supported by the Culture Programme of Sofia Municipality (subsidised by the Cultural Calendar of Sofia), and received EU funding (in 2014). In 2014, Sofia was awarded the title Creative City of Cinema by UNESCO and thus became part of UNESCO's Creative Cities Network and of a global cluster in the film industry, along with 18 other cities on four continents; see the graphic below. The title branded the city and brought it not only symbolic capital but led to reformatting its cultural policy, and positioning the film industry as one of its focuses. In addition, a strategy for the city's film industry was created, including subsidies for film production, the Sofia Film Fest, and the Block Cinema (among other).

The exchange–exhibition phase has no territorial limitation. Quite naturally, when a film is shown in cinemas it is tied to a specific territory, but when other exhibition windows are used (platforms, streaming, VOD, pay television), the film acquires a global exhibition.

Figure 23: Network of UNESCO Creative Cities of Film

Archiving

Participants in this phase are the producer of KLAS Film, the Bulgarian National Film Library (BNF), the National Film Centre, Bulgarian National Television (BNT), platforms, and BNF partners. In this phase of the production network, the producer submits the film for archiving. In Bulgaria, KLAS Film submits the film to the National Film Centre and the Bulgarian National Film Library (BNF). If the film was a co-production, it also becomes part of the partner's archive (e.g. the film libraries of Romania, the Netherlands, France, and Bulgarian National Television).

The Bulgarian National Film Library (BNFL) is a state cultural institute of national importance in the field of movable cultural heritage:

One of the main tasks of any film archive is to process the information that accompanies a film—not the film itself, either on film or digital media, but all the information that accompanies it. It's a huge amount of information. We call it filmographic information here, but it's not just filmographic. (Antonia Kovacheva, Director of the BNFL.)

Materials and information are searched and exchanged on the International Federation of Film Archives network. Producers are both suppliers and consumers for BNF. Everything the film library has often becomes part of future films. The conclusion is that the archive enables a long-lasting secondary use of audiovisual content. Thus, in addition to its educational value and cultural capital, the archive continues to add value at the production stage:

There are inputs and outputs of film content here. In this sense, all film producers in Bulgaria are our customers in the supply stream of film materials, because under the Compulsory Deposit Act they are obliged to provide the National Film Archive with one copy that is as

close to the original as possible. There are technological requirements and details. (Antonia Kovacheva, Director of the BNFL)

As an archive, we can also take the fact that KLAS films are uploaded to YouTube. For example, the film *Letter from America* has been uploaded by users and is free to access. Uploading old movies produced by KLAS Film to worldwide platforms such as HBO Go can also be considered a form of archiving. This option again allows for a long secondary use and return of value to the creators. Digitising the archival materials from the BNF creates value again:

I dare say that this in itself is a kind of production. When you digitise a film from the 1930s and make it available that way, the process of digitisation itself adds value to that film. And in that sense, I dare say that we are producing added value and a new product, because a film on a 1930s tape, even if it's nitrate (we've already transferred them all), when you digitise the film, it's already a brand-new product. (Antonia Kovacheva, Director of the BNFL)

BNFL creates cultural capital through many other activities and partnerships:

We participate in all national and international festivals in Bulgaria. We participate in dozens of exhibitions that we do together with other museums, with theatres, with the Artists' Union, with individual publishers, in public spaces, in the space of the Odeon cinema, in the Synthesis gallery. We participate both as a donor in a concept that is the individual museum, institution or union's, and as a partner in such projects. (Antonia Kovacheva, BNFL)

3.2.2 Relationships between actors (governance)

The KLAS Film production company (owned by Rossitsa Valkanova) initiates, coordinates, and manages each project, securing and managing the resources associated with it. The producer exercises financial and creative control over the process and product. The creative control goes through the contract signed with the director. The production company has strategic functions through the selection of the idea, the teams, and the selection of the partners; in other words, it makes decisions about the inter-company division of labour.

Unquestionably, KLAS Film is a leading company in the network we are examining. The GPN approach allowed us to explore particularly interesting relationships between the actors in the global production chain when looking at **international co-production projects**. Most of the films produced by Rossitsa Valkanova are co-productions. Her most frequent partners are the producers Petra Goedings (Phanta Vision, Netherlands) and Ada Solomon (Hi Film, Romania). KLAS Film has created a total of eight co-productions in partnership with these companies alone. Their professional relationships are based on an excellent mutual knowledge and absolute trust built up over 20 years of collaboration. KLAS Film's first co-production with Phanta Vision, Netherlands was for the successful film *Letter to America* (2000). In this project, the Bulgarian company was the main co-producer. Involvement in a co-productions creates a product with higher added value in a strategic partnership because it gives access to new financial sources, usually including funds from the Media and EURIMAGES programmes (European Film Co-production Support Fund); it widens access to distribution markets (i.e. a larger audience); and it creates comparative advantages from the possibility of choosing talent and

technology. New territories, partners, suppliers, and audiences also emerge in this expectedly larger production network.

This is confirmed by the story of the producer Rossitsa Valkanova, owner of KLAS Film:

Today's film production in Europe is cross-border. Back when I was trained in the 90s, it had already set foot on these pillars for two main reasons. By pillars I mean the co-production and subsequent distribution in the co-producing countries of the product, the film. The two main reasons are to complement the funding, so that it is a combination of several financings in order to achieve a higher budget. And the other pillar is the so-called exchange of experience and skills. Working in co-productions, we have learned more than if we had gone to additional training courses, of course. Already with the first co-production, Letter to America, we were working with Dutch sound engineers in the field, with a Hungarian photographer, finishing the post-production in Holland with a Dutch editor, with a Dutch sound designer. Our first lessons were some of the most complex, and we learned things then that we wouldn't have if we hadn't been in such close contact with the processes in Holland and to some extent in Hungary, I dare say. In some ways they were ahead of us. They kept their industry in spite of the transition. We learned an awful lot, and that's continued with most of the films I've produced and of which I'm the majority producer.

The length of the value chain, the multiplicity of actors involved, and the highly specialised nature of labour in the film industry enable a strong presence of strategic partners and specialist suppliers. **Therefore, while power is clearly focused in the lead production company (when it is the majority co-producer), it is also dispersed.**

As a producer, KLAS Film exercises financial and creative control over the process, resources, and product. At the idea stage, when the financial and creative resources for the project are secured, strategic partners are the organisations that financially support the idea and later the script; at the national level this is the National Film Centre, and at European level this is the MEDIA Programme. At the production stage, funds from the countries of the participating co-producers (national, regional, city) and from the Eurimages programme are added to the funding sources. Important partners here also include broadcasters and future national and global distributors (e.g. Bulgarian National Television). The strength of each funding partner is proportional to the size of its participation in the project. The national funding comes first in the funding lines, giving national credibility to the project. This national credibility subsequently gives confidence to other project partners in seeking funding. The involvement of European funds from the MEDIA programme (EC) and Eurimages is particularly important because they brand the film and make a preliminary assessment of the project quality. This implies an assessment of the qualities of the producer, the director, and the scriptwriter, who become a kind of trademark of the film. Winning this diversified funding is linked to many criteria (quantitative, qualitative) that the project must meet, and the withdrawal of even one strategic financial partner could lead to an inability to close the budget, resulting in time delays and problems with already-contracted creative teams working on the project. If partners pull back at the initial creative stage due to insufficient funding, the project is in great jeopardy and may not be completed.

At the national level, these financial processes take place in a quasi-market environment, where the subsidy has a clear framework (because it is notified state aid under EU regulation). Pure market sources are almost non-existent, and competition for this "soft money" is huge. **Therefore, the role of national funding institutions as strategic partners is crucial.** For competing production companies that do not win support for their projects, the funding institutions are gatekeepers of sorts. Limited public funding creates strong competition for subsidies.

A better-quality script and project also give the film a better chance of finding international co-producers and funding. KLAS Film's participation in project development forums (Sofia Meetings) and co-production markets (Cine Link in Sarajevo) lead to finding co-producers and support through sales agents. Therefore, at the development stage, we can assume that the strategic intermediaries are Sofia Meetings, Cine Link, and the emergence of a sales agent, and that the producer is their client. The role of the sales agent is visible at a later stage as a link between the producer and the international distribution markets. The sales agents Virginie Devesa and Keiko Funato (Alpha Violet, Paris, 2011) are strategic intermediaries for KLAS Film. All these actors are motivated not only by the ultimate economic benefit but also by the cultural and aesthetic value of the future film. Moreover, **sales agents play a particularly important role for European art house films.** We can assume that the involvement of script doctors and sales agents, as well as advance purchases of broadcast rights from distributors are specific mechanisms to increase the value of the project at the making-of stage, which is also the riskiest.

The production of the film is the phase when value is most intensively created, and within certain days, each of the participants contributes. At this stage, the relationship between director and producer is an important allocator of power. The filmmaker, whom we can assume to be a strategic partner of the producer, is the bearer of the aesthetic and creative essence of the product, and the producer provides the financial and managerial basis for the project to become a film. The lack of synchronicity also affects the fieldwork. According to the producer and owner of KLAS Film, R. Valkanova, who also has a degree in directing:

In the production profession, as well as in directing, the ability to work in a team, to delegate tasks to separate departments, to collect the strings of the whole process and to follow from A to Z a mass of different directions in which work needs to be done to become a whole, are essential. This is the essence of this type of organisational, production and creative work all in one. Of course, my training as a director helped me tremendously... I have a piety for directing. I think it determines what the film is, and I think the producer as a partner, but second among equals, should be first in the production of the film.

On location, value is created by a highly diverse range of specialist service providers. Their selection, which is a form of power over the process, is not made by the producer alone:

The director and writer and I are involved in choosing the actors together. Sometimes there are actors for whom the script is written. We choose the team together based on qualities and previous experience, but also on personal contacts. It has happened to me, for example, I work steadily with one team, assistant directors, but a director comes in who works with another team. I have never interfered with that choice. I mean, the director for me is the first

priority. He has to be comfortable with his assistant director, his cinematographer, of course, his costume designer, his set designer. Most creative suppliers are chosen primarily by the director. (R. Valkanova, producer, owner of KLAS Film)

During production, the unifying role and authority over suppliers lies not only with the producer but also with the production director, who is the "unit production manager." They can be classified as a specialist supplier to whom all other field contractors report and are subordinate. Attracting specific companies as second-tier suppliers takes place in a condition of strong competition because some of these professions have a limited supply. Moreover, in Bulgaria these professionals are also sought after by foreign productions that come here to shoot certain scenes. Technical crews are in great demand, and they gain significant knowledge from participating in foreign, and very often not European productions, which naturally raises the price of the service. This price takes on higher market dimensions, which is hardly covered by the value of the subsidy granted by the state for the specific project. When the project is a co-production, this problem is partially solved because of the higher budget of the film. Therefore, according to the producer and the unit production manager, these service providers become sustainable partners based on honest relations and the fair and timely payment of labour. The interviewees also described situations in which subsidy instalments have not arrived, as expected, so that they had to find other solutions. The reputation thus built creates a relationship of trust over the years:

In general, the reputation of a producer and a consistent production flow of films (a film every year) have an influence on these suppliers - they prefer working with this producer and they try to discount the price... That sustainability, being able to work on several projects over the years, makes it possible to ask for lower prices. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

Technical teams are highly valued, not only because demand outstrips supply but also because they offer a very high level of service:

We do co-productions with the Europeans, but the technical teams work in the Boyana studio with the Americans. They want one pay. If you pay him a lot less, he just won't come when he can go and make some money elsewhere.... I open a parenthesis—in the years when we have worked abroad with a Bulgarian team, we have been repeatedly assured of admiration and amazement how a Bulgarian team works so synchronously, precisely, precisely with great know-how, with exceptional capacity. And they have said, "You work like Americans, but you have a European attitude to cinema. How did that happen?" That's how it happened—with American productions setting foot here... It's like we're in competition with American cinema in our own country. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

The entry of new players, such as streaming platforms, has also impacted technical markets by increasing the cost of services and making them harder for European co-productions to access:

Because with us things are so complex, nothing is irrelevant. Here's what's happened in the last 4–5 years since the advent of production platforms like Netflix and HBO. They, in their search for content, started producing. As they started producing, they inevitably stepped into territories where labour and production value was lower... I am currently a minority co-producer on a project by a Bulgarian author, but with a majority Swiss producer. The co-production is to be shot in India. We have French, we have Swiss, Bulgarians too, we have EURIMAGES. Two years ago, when we started the development of the project, the services

budget in India was X, now it is 3X. Why? Because in the meantime, Netflix built a studio in Bombay and sucked out the staff who are working at higher salaries, with permanent jobs, etc. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

There is no less tension in relationships at the distribution stage, especially when the distributor is only national. The state supports the distribution of Bulgarian and European films with modest sums that cannot compare with the possibilities of Hollywood, which has conquered Bulgarian cinemas. The screening itself, as well as promotion and advertising, add value to the film. Many of the distributors are tied to movie theatres and are representatives of the major American companies. This vertical integration gives them strong power and the ability to redistribute value. They impose a ticket revenue distribution ratio that can be as high as 70% to 30% in their favour, in some cases. **They thus have a dual role: they are strategic partners for producers, but the conditions they set for distribution can turn them into gatekeepers** at the distribution stage. Distribution is purely a commercial exercise. For the distributor, it is the price at which they buy the film and the possibility of selling it to the maximum number of viewers that are important. Here the role of the state is poorly fulfilled because it actively supports the production but has a weak presence at the distribution and exhibition stages. In fact, this limits the socialisation of the film product already produced. Producers are not happy with the care of their films, feeling that distribution rakes in some money without taking care of good marketing and promotion. Therefore, here the role of co-producers, as well as participation in festivals, is crucial. A festival, which is a kind of primary market, can give a good bounce to distribution. For example, Sofia Film Fest has managed to develop its own festival film network. However, there is also a logic in which every film studio should look for the distribution network that is best suited to it:

Not every Bulgarian film has a place in multiplexes. The audience of multiplexes is completely different from art cinemas. I continue to be amazed at Bulgarian films that are clamouring to get into multiplexes, but their place is in art cinemas...This is an overly redundant ambition. Commercial Bulgarian films have a place in multiplexes. (V. Trifonov, film programmer)

Those actors who are on the more commercial side of the film industry, such as programmers, also have direct oversight of cinemas and audiences. They find that the film system is in balance when

viewers appreciate the efforts of everyone in the chain—our efforts as programmers, the efforts of distributors to invest in commercials, and to get the word out about how the film they distribute is good enough to be seen by the most unsophisticated viewer. The efforts of the sales companies to market them adequately so as not to spoil the distributors, and above all the efforts of the producers and the writers to make a film that will really intrigue people, give them joy, give them pleasure, even if it is a heavy cathartic drama. Catharsis is a kind of aesthetic pleasure. The idea is that they make these films so that they are watchable. (V. Trifonov, film programmer)

All interviewees felt that the system of support for cinemas was inadequate and that the new film industry law was not well made. The administrative consequences negatively affect production practices. In the last year, due to mismanagement that can be characterised as regulatory risk, the subsidy for cinema was stopped, which affected the possibility of participating in co-productions. The pandemic of the last two years is a blow to everyone in this industry. The blow to cinemas has been particularly visible, and it has also brought losses to the distributors associated with them and not just

at the national level. According to an interviewee, it is no longer a question of the redistribution of power between producers and distributors because distributors are losing supremacy and power:

It's not a redistribution of power because we have a serious decline. In fact, things had intensified just before the pandemic. 2020 started very well, but with everything that's happened, the crisis and the decline is huge right now. (V. Trifonov, film programmer)

3.2.3 Positioning cases within the typology

In investigating the KLAS film case from a typology perspective, we focused on two dimensions or aspects:

- 1) Where is the power concentrated? Is it dispersed among different phases of the production network, and how?
- 2) Where are the production network phases located geographically? We assume a situation in which KLAS Film, as lead company, is a majority co-producer in an (international) co-production.

At the **creation phase**, when the idea and the script are developed, the power is concentrated in the lead company, KLAS Film. At this phase, we observed a territorial scope (footprint) beyond the national, when the script is presented at international meetings as well as at pitching sessions among film professionals to acquire international funding. The strategic partners at the creation stage are those who provide the funding, for example, the Bulgarian National Film Centre, the Creative Europe MEDIA programme (formerly MEDIA Programme of the European Union), and others. The involvement of funding bodies can be considered a dispersion of power, but only in the administrative (institutional) aspect. Creative and managerial powers are concentrated in KLAS film.

At the **production stage** (preparation, filming, post-production), there is a dispersion of power that reflects the involvement of the European co-producers in the making of the film. This affects the spatial footprint of the project. Depending on the specific project, its filming and post-production locations range from local to European. We assume that the diversified financial resources from the co-producing countries and international co-production funds (e.g. Eurimages or Media) could be considered as a dispersion of administrative and institutional power during the production phase.

Whereas the power of creative decisions is in the hands of the lead company, the choices of national and local specialised suppliers are made by the minority co-producers, who are strategic partners in the specific project. These choices are often influenced by the criteria of the co-producer's funders, who require that some percentage of their grant be spent on their territory.

At the **distribution stage**, the producer (KLAS film) and the co-producers sell the distribution rights of the produced film to national and European distributors to disseminate the film nationally, across Europe, and globally. There is a strong dispersion of power to the distributors, but it is a voluntary delegation of power. Distributors, film programmers, sales agents, festivals, film critics, major social streaming platforms, and television stations are all very important actors in this phase. They have multifaceted roles, depending on the specific market and product, which could be as specialised

customers, intermediaries, or partners. These actors add value to the project, but when they operate as monopolists in distorted market relationships with the producers, they capture value. This is commonly the case with national distributors, as well as with streaming platforms: they can become gatekeepers, thus gaining extraordinary power and authority over the distribution of a film. The film shows reflect the capabilities of the cinema theatres’ network, the television and streaming distribution contracts in place, and adds value by socialising the product. Films are usually distributed and exchanged all around the world.

Digital archives provide a revenue opportunity for filmmakers, as well as for movie theatres and other more modern archival spaces. Shared revenue also disperses power. The presence of film works in digital cloud spaces, dedicated platforms, and social networks has no territorial limitation, as access to them is global.

Key partners, suppliers, and customers are national, but when the project is a co-production, the majority of them are in Europe. The highest spatial scale at which the network is involved is global, through distribution, screening in cinemas and streaming platforms, and in archives.

We see the network as vertical because of the key role of the lead company, KLAS Film. An important specificity of this network is the presence of many actors: partners, suppliers, special clients, mediators, stakeholders, and gatekeepers. Their activity creates natural dispersion of power (administrative–institutional, creative, managerial, or distributional) at each phase.

Table 37: The typology matrix of KLAS Film

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation		Lead actor-KLAS film, Creators, Strategic partner public sector	Lead actor/creators, strategic partners public multilevel and private sector		
Production	Lead actor, generic suppliers	Lead Actor, Strategic partner public sector, Specialised suppliers	Lead actor, strategic partners multilevel and private sector, specialised suppliers		
Distribution		Intermediaries, distributors	Intermediaries, distributors	Intermediaries, distributors	
Exchange	Intermediaries, costumer B2B, consumers (audiences)	Intermediaries, costumer B2B, Consumers (audiences)	Intermediaries, costumer B2B, consumers (audiences)	Intermediaries, costumer B2B, consumers (audiences)	

Archiving		Lead actor, strategic partner public sector	Strategic partners public sector	Strategic partners public sector	
Network level				X	Lead actor: KLAS Film

3.2.4 Network dynamics: transformations over time

The dynamics over time show positive trends in the economic contribution of the film industry in Bulgaria and in Sofia in particular, in terms of growing the added value and increasing the employment and number of enterprises. The largest contribution in terms of volume is in the production phase, but the greatest dynamics are in the post-production sub-phase. Transformation has also been visible when seeking management solutions to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, the Sofia Municipality created a special support programme, named "Solidarity in Culture," which has had societal dimensions for the film industry in the city.

The "Solidarity in Culture" programme as a whole was aimed at supporting cultural operators and individual creators by assisting them in creating digital forms of content distribution. Many independent film organisations were also supported, as they could initially apply for financial support by paying for their teams' salaries and rents. At the time when the pandemic shut everything down, cinemas offering European and non-commercial cinema were also supported—the Cinema House, Eurocinema, etc. All the film festivals were subsequently realised with the assistance of the Sofia Municipality, which made it possible to transform them. Many of them made their own digital editions or some of them took their programme to the open stages. (B. Genova, Director of Culture Department, Sofia Municipality)

In the post-production phase, digital communication between Sofia and Bucharest has saved both time and money. During the COVID-19 pandemic, this solution was the only possible way for the projects to continue their activities. Even the project markets (e.g. the ideas stage) were conducted online. Participants in such events defined them as innovations:

The online running of the project markets (at the big festivals such as Cannes, Berlin) impressed me very positively. Somehow the need to run them online has led to the realization of such positives of this online running that in the future even without Covid some of these project markets will continue like that. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

3.2.5 Societal impacts of the production networks of the film industry case

Economic impact³²

Economic impact in the film industry is measured by its contribution to economic growth, including through GDP, gross value added, and jobs. After 1989, Bulgaria began an economic and political transition from a state-planned economy to a market economy. The Bulgarian film industry was among the first reformed cultural sectors, with the state stepping down from consistent support, with no vision of the future and no specialised regulations or mechanisms in place. This led to severe consequences for Bulgarian cinema in the 90s, when national film production collapsed from 25–30 feature films per year to a maximum of three. When the formerly massive state-governed and state-subsidised film industry system collapsed, more than 80% of the film industry professionals it employed were made redundant. Some of them started to form the first independent production micro-companies, which, while they were agile in the new market realities, could not be economically sustainable without a public support system in place.

These challenges reflected the overall economic instability of the country due to the transition and does not reflect a lack of creative talent in the industry. Bulgaria is a relatively small European country and a closed linguistic community, in which economies of scale from production to the distribution of the product are very unlikely. Any new entrepreneurial model to emerge in the film sector had to deal with these limitations and search for international partnerships.

From 2004 onwards, the Bulgarian film industry has begun to rise from this collapse after the adoption of the Bulgarian Film Industry Act, which provided for state subsidies for film production. The project-based subsidies are allocated on a competitive basis, with public funding covering 50% to 80% of the total budget of a film project. The managing authority is the executive agency the "National Film Centre," which is an administrative and corporate body under the governance of the Ministry of Culture (Tomova, 2018).

The positive trend has continued since then, reaching 27 feature films supported by Bulgarian National Film Centre completed in 2020, including features, shorts, and co-productions, according to the National Film Centre Executive Agency Report 2020.

Today, the Bulgarian film industry contributes added economic value that is significantly higher than the public subsidies it has received. Its main economic indicators for the period 2008–2020 show positive dynamic trends. The 12-year observation period, by mapping the sector, has identified indicators that may be considered trends: an added value increase of 133.7%, an increase in number of organisations or companies of 139.3%; and an employment increase of 122.5% .

These remarkable results contrasted with some trends in the Bulgarian economy during that period, such as recession, unemployment increase, and negative economic growth in 2009–2010, as well as

³² All statistics in this section (unless otherwise stated) are from the annual mapping of CCIs conducted by the Observatory of Cultural Economics, Sofia in partnership with the City of Sofia and the National Statistical Institute.

economic growth under 1% in 2011–2012. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic will be reflected in the data after 2020. At this stage, we see a slight and negligible decline in comparing the indicators for 2019 and 2020.

The added value at factor costs, or the economic contribution of the film industry was about EUR 23.6 million (BGN 46 million) in 2008, rising to nearly EUR 56 million (BGN 107.2 million) in 2020, or well above twice the value, with 98.1% of it for Sofia.

In 2020, the greatest contribution to the added value in the sector was that of film production and technical services. Dynamics of the economic growth for 2008–2020 are impressive in terms of technical services (post-production). This increment reflects the expansion of film production and the arrival of new technologies. In contrast, the indicators for the sub-market of “video cassettes and discs’ rental” show a vanishing market.

Over the 12-year period, the number of companies in the film industry steadily grew, to 1,101 organisations in 2020. Most companies are at the production stage. However, companies providing technical services (post-production) have grown almost four-fold during that period. Enhanced specialisation is one reason for this growth.

The number of employed people in the film industry increased by 122.5% over the 12-year period, reaching 4,037 in 2020; over 80% of these people work in production and post-production.

GPN and socio-economic development at different spatial scales. Type of integration between network and territory (strategic combination)

The film industry’s economic contribution through added value generated was many times higher, compared to the total of public subsidies received through the National Film Centre, Bulgarian National Television, the Media Programme, the National Culture Fund, and the Sofia Municipality. For the year 2020 alone, the added value was EUR 55 million, while the public subsidies from all sources were up to EUR 9 million. This shows multiplication effect of 6.1.

The indicators for Sofia, the capital city, show much higher employment and number of companies, which reflects the fact that a natural audiovisual cluster has formed in the city.

Table 38: Bulgarian film industry and Sofia film industry—economic indicator dynamics for the period 2008–2020 in %

	Added value	Organisations	Employed
Bulgaria	133,7	139,3	122,5
Sofia	123,7	155,8	149,5

Source: NSI/OCE

Clusters are a typical example of the role of the network that goes beyond the value chain results, which are linear. This creates the potential of cross-sector linkages between different parts of the creative economy (Weller, 2008 cited in Coe, 2015). Evidence for this potential is the audiovisual cluster in Sofia, which can be characterised as a spillover effect of the network type. The enterprises are bound by a common creative process (i.e. they represent different parts of the value chain in the creation and distribution of cultural goods and services). They have some related activities and use common resources that spill over (Tomova, 2021).

These characteristics of production create elements of a so-called network structure. Such structures at a certain technological level (entry of new technologies, innovations of different types) can create vertical and horizontal links, even integration, i.e. a cluster is created. Geographical concentration—the separateness of the area—is a prerequisite. Sofia has a distinct cluster and it is in the film industry, But what is very important for a cluster and is present here is that the film industry is linked to activities such as television production, online media, computer games, sound recording, photography, design (which are also concentrated in Sofia) and is technologically linked industry again with television, performing arts, music business, advertising, digital media, book publishing, education. (Tomova, Andreeva, 2015, p. 40)

In 2020, the film industry created 92% of its economic growth in Sofia. The city is also home to 91% of the employees and 81% of companies in the film sector. Between 70% and 90% of the other audiovisual industries—television and radio, and computer games—are concentrated in Sofia. To some extent, this is related to the specificity of the creation and consumption of cultural product, which is an integral part of the urban infrastructure. In the last decade, however, the high concentration is increasingly a reflection of the growing interdependence between cultural industries, as expressed in the spillover of resources: human, technical, capital, and educational.³³

Benefits for the local community

Encouraged by the existing audiovisual cluster in the city, Sofia Municipality applied for and became a UNESCO Creative City of Cinema (2014) and is now part of the network of 18 UNESCO Creative Cities. The film industry has become a resource for development and innovation in the city. Subsequently, Sofia Municipality adopted a strategy for film industry development.

The vision for Sofia—Creative City of Cinema for the decade 2017–2027 is to establish the city as a leading centre of the film industry in Europe. Sofia—with a dynamic development with a population exceeding 1,500,000 people, of which more than 30% are between 18 and 35 years old—a city whose future goal is to continuously expand the opportunities for access to the film industry. (Sofia Municipality website)

The city established its own film committee “to provide expert support for the implementation of the municipal policy to support cinema and film production in connection with the UNESCO title Creative City of Cinema awarded, as well as to conduct procedures for logistical support for filming” (ibid). In

³³ Creative the Audiovisual Cluster of Sofia is featured in first database of 98 documents from 17 countries on spillover effects in cultural and creative industries in Europe. (Andreeva, T. in Erskine, A. & Fleming T. 2016; Tomova B., Andreeva, D., 2016; Tomova B., 2017).

this direction, the municipality is working together with experts, representatives of film institutions, and research organisations.

Our strategic instrument is the Culture Programme of the Sofia municipality. The programme's Cinema strand supports production of documentaries on the cultural heritage of the city, as well as short films and animation. The second strand aims to create cinema communities and clubs, to bring cinema into schools, among young people. This strand also supports filmmakers, educational initiatives related to communication between organisations in Bulgaria and abroad, the creation of partnership networks. (B. Genova, Director of Culture Department, Sofia Municipality).

Sofia also supports the biggest film festivals in the city: Sofia Film Fest, Cinelibri Film Festival, Master of Art, Kinomania, Young European Cinema Meetings, Sofia International Mini Children's Film Festival, and Open Air Summer Cinema. Each of these festivals has accompanying modules for meeting artists from different countries and for networking for collaborative film projects, as well as for the development of young filmmakers. All these events provide the audiences access to substantial European film content, for example, through panoramas of renowned film directors and by inviting the best European filmmakers to the Sofia Film Fest.

Social impact

As in any cluster, besides the companies from the industry, the state (through the Executive Agency "National Film Centre"), and the city authorities, a number of other players have important roles:

- the universities providing specialised education and training: National Academy of Theatre and Film "Krustyo Sarafov," New Bulgarian University, and the music and art academies;
- professional associations: Union of Bulgarian Filmmakers, Association of Film Producers, Association of Film and Television Directors, Filmautor, Bulgarian Association of Film Directors, Association of Bulgarian Cinematographers, Akademika 21, Bulgarian Association of Film, Television and Radio Screenwriters, Association of Bulgarian Film Producers, Bulgarian Association of Independent Artists and Animators—Proyko Proykov, Association of Bulgarian Animation Producers, Association of Bulgarian Cinemas, and Association of Film and Television Producers; and
- research centres in the sector: Centre for Audiovisual Policy and Media Studies (The University of National and World Economy), and Observatory of Cultural Economics.

Each of these actors has a role in the film sector ecosystem in Sofia, which also has the following social dimensions:

- the emergence of new higher-education curricula focusing on production (UNWE);
- the emergence of research initiatives (e.g. Research Forum for Sustainable Development of the Bulgarian Film Industry by the Centre for Audiovisual Policy and Media Studies); and
- the emergence of new financial instruments for the audiovisual sector, as a specific section in the Competitiveness Programme of the Ministry of Economy.

The alliances among the various professional film organisations are particularly strong. They are represented in the National Film Council, the leading advisory body to the National Film Centre. The National Film Council is the engine for many policies and changes in the sector. The professional associations play a role in advocating for common standards when applying for project grants. Their actions also have strong civic dimensions, which are particularly evident in their defending of common professional interests through legislative initiatives. A recent example is the joint lobbying for amending the Film Industry Act, against all odds and not always with the support of the Ministry of Culture, nor of the National Film Centre, in 2019–2021. KLAS Film is among the founders of the Association of Film Producers, and Rossitsa Valkanova herself is a frequent media voice for the issues and struggles of the film community.

The functions of the aforementioned Municipal Film Committee and National Film Council give us reason to define their activity as "synergistic governance" in this naturally occurring cluster. Gereffi & Lee (2016) explain "synergistic governance" as

a way to advance more comprehensive and sustainable forms of upgrading, both economically and socially. Synergistic governance is [...] not easy to achieve, but it offers a promising pathway to bringing together corporate, governmental, and civil society actors in a global setting to achieve joint objectives, where active collaboration among GVC and industrial cluster actors is required in order to simultaneously achieve economic and social gains. (Gereffi & Lee, 2016)

The audiovisual and film ecosystem built up over the years has yielded achievements that go beyond higher-quality film industry work, as already discussed in the case study. The increase in employment in the sector has been coupled with better pay, which has exceeded both the pay in other economic sectors and the average CCI pay in Bulgaria on an annual basis.

Table 39: Average annual gross salary in BGN for 2020 in Bulgaria

All economic sectors	Arts, cultural and creative industries and cultural tourism	Film industry
16 687	18,942	22,228

Source: NSI/OCE

In the co-productions, which are supported by various regional funds, the influence of labour and tax legislation at the regional or national level is particularly evident. There are influences on the prices of different types of labour, which are higher in countries with higher standards, and the possibility of local protectionism arises.

Of course, there are very strong protectionist laws in certain countries. France being on the top. In France, they require that a very large percentage of the production of a film in co-production to be concentrated in France, and have French actors. If you want to attract third parties, and there are some willing parties, they cannot be involved because all the positions are occupied by French people whose salaries are high because of the very high social security contributions that are paid. This increases budgets. Something that can be done for BGN

1,000 in Bulgaria is done for BGN 4,000 in France. We are paying a very high price for that. Back in the day, when we started working with Germany, the individual regions (“Landkreis”) and funds, had a different percentage that they required to be spent in the region. In Berlin it was 100%, so as much as they give you, you must spend. MDM in Leipzig required 150% of their support to be spent in the region. They give us 100k and we had to give another 50k from our low budget and standards to get that 100k. We've done it. Cologne required 300% to be spent there. They had such an influx. Economically they had very high subsidies, but the cost was very high. This is gradually being regulated by the European legislations. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

Although cinema is known for a strong male presence in important positions (producer, director), in the Bulgarian film industry we have many leading female names in the producer profession. For this phenomenon, producer Rossitsa Valkanova looks for an explanation in the recent past:

It's very sustainable. For some reason, women in the former socialist camp were not burdened by any complexes. They were even forced into working instead of staying at home and looking after their children. But this created a mentality that allowed women's initiative and achievements to be very visible in our societies.

In this environment, educational initiatives exist not only in universities. A good example of this is the role of Sofia Meetings, which hosts master classes by global names in the film industry, who are very often also representatives of European professional associations. Here is what Mira Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings producer, said during the interview:

I invite Europa Cinemas and Europa Distribution, they do conferences and workshops. This includes professional film publications, professional associations—Europa Cinema, Europa Distribution, FIAPF, the European Film Academy. For example, the European Film Academy wants to have its annual conference and board meeting at Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings. They are in a way my supplier because they bring me big names to do workshops with as well. They also bring me prestige. They provide me with a service.

Sofia supports financially the biggest film festivals: Sofia Film Fest, Cinelibri, Master of Art, Kinomania, Meetings of Young European Cinema, Sofia International Mini Children's Film Festival, and Summer Cinema on the Open Stages. They also have accompanying modules for meeting artists from different countries, for networking for common film projects, and for the development of young film artists. Through these events in the capital, audiences are given access to European film content.

Sofia Film Festival is the biggest in the country and is part of the network in this case. It has a special social policy, as its managing director and programmer, Mira Staleva, observes:

We do screenings for the visually impaired, as well as for the hearing impaired. Together with Maria's World Foundation we organise screenings for people who have intellectual problems. Then, the film is retold in a completely different way—through one set of headphones, through a special technique. This is my idea of developing the House of Cinema, of developing

the audience. We don't want it to go to one place, we want it to be there. We do these special screenings all year round. We need money for that because it means for us to adapt every single screening. Every month there is at least one for either the blind or the deaf or people with intellectual deficits. (M. Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings)

All of the above, in terms of social benefits and social upgrading, can be realized thanks to the critical mass of economic actors specialised in the audiovisual field.

KLAS Film is a micro-production company typical in Europe, and the fact that this company is the leader of a co-production network makes it a strong player in the local and national film ecosystem.

Cultural impact

The cultural impact of cinema has multiple dimensions manifested at local, national, and global levels. Awards, festival appearances and audiences, and mixed and very visible cultural appearances in cultural tourism and gourmet cuisine are among most undeniable types of cultural impacts. While awards and festival appearances can be traced through the production company KLAS Film, most of its cultural influences are detectable through the work of other participants in the network. Rather naturally, the most visible activities are at the distribution stage, where marketing, promotions, and festival appearances take place.

Film awards vividly recognise film creators, and they attract and guide critics, sales agents, and audiences. Their national pride and prestige cannot be economically measured; however, their effects are very tangible for the film's crew. Producer Rossitsa Valkanova appreciates festival selections and awards as "recommendations" and as key places for credit- and portfolio-building for film directors and producers, particularly when they set out to prepare for new projects.

KLAS film has numerous national film awards (see table below), as well as international recognition at Class A festivals in Europe. International awards have been attributed to its films. *The Prosecutor, the Defender, the Father and His Son* won the 2011 ScriptEast Award for Best Screenplay in Central and Eastern Europe at Cannes. Radu Jude's *Affair*, with KLAS Film as Bulgarian co-producer, won the Silver Bear in Berlin in 2015. *Ralitsa Petrova*, produced by Rossitsa Valkanova, won the 2016 Golden Leopard Award at the 69th Locarno International Film Festival.

Table 40. Highest national awards for the production company KLAS Film

Bulgarian Film Academy Awards	2010 Best Film (Nai-Dobur Film)	<i>Podslon</i> (2010)
Golden Rose	2016 Winner Golden Rose	Best Film, <i>Godless</i> (2016)
Golden Rose	2000 Winner Golden Rose	Special Jury Award, <i>Letter to America</i> (2000)
Sofia International Film Festival	2017 Winner Grand Prix	Best Film <i>Godless</i> (2016)

Sofia International Film Festival	2016 Winner Burgas Municipality Award, <i>Silver Seagull</i>	Best Film, <i>The Prosecutor the Defender the Father and His Son</i> (2015)
Sofia International Film Festival	2011 Winner Grand Prix	Best Film, <i>Shelter</i> (2010)

Source: Bulgarian National Film Centre

The Sofia International Film Festival is part of the KLAS Film network and is particularly visible in the aspect of cultural upgrading. It is one of the three largest festivals in the Balkan region, together with the festivals in Sarajevo and Thessaloniki. The Sofia Meetings, a market for first and second projects and co-productions, are important elements of the festival, with over 700–800 professional meetings taking place. The awards that are given by Sofia Meetings feature contractors from all over the world.

Our partners in the awards are, for example, the Hungarian Cinema and Film Lab, the Romanian Film Lab. We once had an award for Sundance, where the film should go. They are mostly European, but actually there are counterparts from all over the world. (M. Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings)

The big names that are part of the festival determine its rating and influence its reputation, attracting the audience that is the event's resource. Mira Staleva shared:

Yes, Wim Wenders is an influencer. On the one hand, Wim Wenders or Claudia Cardinale work for the media, for the public, and on the other hand, they speak for the rest of the professional world.

Festivals are not only a primary film market but are also celebrations of the cities in which they take place and a factor in social cohesion. The SFF is no exception, as the festival's screenings and events stimulate many special events in the city throughout the month, for example, gourmet dinners in restaurants, PR events, wine tastings, exhibitions, and more.

We also do a fashion gala involving hairstylists and stylists who give assignments to students from New Bulgarian University, Sofia who prepare a collection depending on which film it is for. We gave the students an assignment, they did a collection inspired by Dior. They did a fashion show. This gives different groups the opportunity to grow professionally. (M. Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings)

The KLAS Film case study shows that innovation often occurs the set and comes as a solution to some specific problem or task, for example, inventing a technical facility that allows 10-minute shots.

The grip technicians came up with it, they built it, they provided the way of filming that the cinematographer and director wanted technically. It was an innovation. Something new was created. Their know-how at every level was learning something new. Then it could be applied. It worked for a project. It didn't work for another. So, the individual features and needs of each project makes our profession absolutely unique. (R. Valkanova, producer, owner of KLAS Film)

Another example of innovation is a creation of a model of a dolphin for the film *Fishbone* (co-produced with Romania).

One [dolphin] had to be made in its entirety, another model to be cut, a third, that in close-up the skin looks real, and a fourth [model] of which the looks real. That happened to me for the first time. [...] This experience accumulated as new for me, but also outside me, because we were looking for famous props' studios, specialised in creating animal models. We ended up in Denmark, which is where Lars von Trier is from, who loves to have animals in his films. The model making there is known for being at a very high level. Our set designer and I exchanged experiences with them. We finally came to a decision that we would produce it here, and they are now asking us how we produced it. (R. Valkanova, producer, owner of KLAS Film)

Innovation at the marketing and distribution stage is particularly visible because these activities make both the film and the festivals attractive, distinctive, and accessible to the audience. Sofia Film Fest invented a marketing tool to sell cinema ticket vouchers in a can (like a Coke or beer can), which has a barcode and is on sale in supermarkets, bars, cafes, and bookshops. The ticket itself is for one screening, to be chosen from the festival programme screenings. The ticket number inside the can is for logging into an online system where the user can book a ticket for whichever screening and whichever venue they want to visit.

You don't have go to the box office, you don't wait in line. On the other hand, it's good as a gift. You are positioned in places you wouldn't otherwise be with your brand—it involves developing your own distribution network. To be able to position yourself, you have to find those places, negotiate with them, figure out a rate. Just like with a commodity, you develop your own distribution network. But that distribution channel of yours works for you. You position yourself with advertising in all those 300+ locations in Sofia. (M. Staleva, director of Sofia Film Fest and Sofia Meetings)

Innovations contribute to growing reputations, reveal the professional qualifications of the people involved, and optimize the production process. The team gains new and better job opportunities and project proposals.

However, as always in such processes, [innovation] is something of a permanent learning curve. The lecture exists—the lecturer is better/worse, more innovative or less innovative—but it is up to the student and their effort what they learn and how they apply that knowledge. In the end, somehow the individual approach is strong in our case so that everything learned, new contacts, activities, etc. can be reflected in each subsequent project. (R. Valkanova, Producer, owner of KLAS Film)

Policy implications of the KLAS Film case

The KLAS Film case study is positioned both at national and European level. This enables generalisations and recommendations to be made at two levels - to national cultural policy in the film industry and at a pan-European level.

The interviews highlighted several problem areas for which solutions could be sought in specific instruments and policies. The film community had high expectations of an upsurge after the changes in the 1990s, when the state monopoly was removed, project financing entered, and the first independent producers appeared. Unfortunately, the speed of development slowed down and the first Film Industry Law with state support only appeared in 2003.

The assessment of the new legislative framework in force since 2021 (the Film Industry Amendment Act 2021) is not high, on the contrary. It introduced two new state aid schemes : 1) a reimbursement scheme for foreign productions filmed in the country and 2) a support scheme for series.

Much of the film community has questioned the cost-effectiveness of the reimbursement scheme for foreign film productions, considering it problematic in terms of public finance, national interests, and cultural policy. One of the former directors of the National Film Centre, Georgi Cholakov, says

We know very well that the tax in Bulgaria is 10%, social security contributions are paid up to 3000 leva, and if you receive more money, you do not pay social security contributions. At the same time Bulgaria gives a cash rebate, which is the most attractive form. The state returns some money on some expenses, which is not clear what they will be exactly and who will control them, despite the fact that the report must be certified by an auditor. Because the expenditure may also have been made, especially when I am giving myself services, i.e. I can be the beneficiary as a company providing services in film production, and I can set my own prices. Of course, how I set my prices is my policy and my decision. I can charge such prices that the Bulgarian State will then be dizzy, but that is a matter of policy. To be clear, the new scheme is NOT a tax rebate. It is a cash rebate. Unlike the so-called tax incentive, which usually you repay to the budget, here the state is returning some money based on some expenses incurred. It's not even a tax rebate, it's a gift of some money.

The interviewed producers believe that this will lead to an unjustified increase in the prices of technical labour in the Bulgarian film industry, as has already happened in other countries in the region, and give as an example the difficulty of assembling a team in Croatia. Higher prices will result not only from stronger competition from foreign productions entering Bulgaria but also from the possibility of speculatively raising the costs of foreign productions in order to obtain a higher cash rebate. Of course, it cannot be denied that this will also lead to an increase in the skills and qualities of the teams hired. In the US, where the use of this tax instrument in the cinema is traditional, the most common scheme is the tax incentive. The scheme covers tax liabilities for a certain percentage, depriving the budget of some revenue. With a tax rebate, the budget not only does not receive any revenue but also gives some money directly.

The difference is huge in terms of money and in terms of scheme. For example, in the most cinematic state in the US, the tax incentive is to the tune of 330 million dollars, and that's just on film production. This effectively incentivises other players in the business who have large profits and large tax liabilities to support the film industry. Whereas in Bulgaria there is no incentive to support the film industry. Here there is an incentive to give one money to one beneficiary. (G. Cholakov, producer, former director of the National Film Centre Executive Agency)

With this tax relief option, one cannot disagree with the finding of some economists that “This model leads to the financing of previously unviable projects and the net result is that on a global scale it is an influx of European capital into American industry through co-financing initiatives”(Morawetz et al., 2007 cited in Coe, 2015, p. 495). The situation in Bulgaria shows that European policies cannot always be applied without reservation to every national market.

In practice, at the moment we are a country overrun by entities engaged in the production of films that have nothing to do with European cinema policy as content [referring to the work of the American studio New Boyana Film in Bulgaria]. No one doubts that this thing could be harmful for Bulgarian cinema. Even when I've tried to convince, both my editor-in-chief and other people who think European, they can't grasp why in Bulgaria the incentives are something that is quite reprehensible, something that doesn't correspond to the primordial needs of national cinema. Immediately the answer is: 'Yes, but this is a phenomenon that is all over Europe. Bulgaria is on the tail.' We still cannot rely entirely on European productions. They are a very big framework, but if you haven't built up the necessary understanding of what you should be doing yourself inside your own country, there's no one outside to do it for you. What has happened with these ruthlessly unprofessionally imposed amendments to the Film Industry Act just shows that. Yes, for me there is definitely a problem in this direction. (P. Zheleva, producer, film critic, representative of Bulgaria in Film New Europe)

We can conclude that "the introduction of financial incentives for the film industry, mainly for American productions in a European context, and the inclusion of an explicit text in the State Aid Communication of the European Union in 2013, as well as the pressure for changes in the national legislations of the Member States of the European Union, regardless of their tax system and economic effects, shows the line of geopolitical pressure by the United States on national sovereign states" (Andreeva-Popjordanova, 2021).

The lack of free and easily accessible investment capital for the Bulgarian film industry is another serious problem that emerges in the production phase. There is a growing distrust of the cultural sector and the lack of sector-specific financial instruments. Among the deficits are 1) the lack of bridge financing to support producers when there are delays in instalments during the product creation period; 2) the lack of a cinema fund in Bulgaria, which is filled by market sources such as ticket taxation, cable operators, and platform operators and which, even if it were a hybrid one (i.e. including funds from the budget), would give a financing horizon that goes beyond the budget year; and 3. the highly centralised financial tax system, which limits the possibilities of local and regional cultural financing. Here is the assessment of a leading Bulgarian producer, with participation in many co-productions:

There is no such system in Bulgaria that stimulates you to give money in the field of culture. Basically, I have to be financially insane to give money to any charity or cultural activity because I would spend less money if I just paid my taxes. Until the stimulation of a particular activity takes on the character of fulfilling a tax obligation, there won't be any money to put into that area. Simply because it is uneconomic. After all, there is no interest on the part of big business to invest in culture and any other charitable activity. (G. Cholakov, producer, former director of the National Film Centre Executive Agency)

The listed financial constraints at the national level make small production companies untenable. In this environment, the role of good public management of the film industry is crucial. The main players here are the Ministry of Culture and the National Film Centre, and their correctives are the copyright societies (e.g. Filmautor) and the numerous film associations for almost all types of film professions, including film and television producers, directors, scriptwriters, cinematographers, artists, animators, and art schools.

Unfortunately, the film community's assessment of the work of the executive—the NFC—is low. Interviewees expressed particularly strong disappointment for the period 2020–2021, the period of the COVID-19 pandemic, defined in cinema as a "dramatic...killing." Worse, during this period there was not a single special measure or instrument in Bulgaria directly aimed at supporting the film sector.

Covid reflected badly. No measures were taken by the NFC to help the people associated with the cinema. The only thing that the NFC assisted with during Covid was the admission of Nu Boyana Film's clients to the country. It was not interested in the work of Bulgarian producers. For example, we wanted help to vaccinate the crew because we were shooting in March (2021) at the height of the crisis. We didn't get any support, unlike Nu Boyana, who vaccinated on a general basis, regardless of all other things. It was not only the NFC but also the Ministry of Culture. We sent a letter to the NFC and the MC with a list of the team, but nothing happened within our shooting period. Thank God there were no sick people. None of the production organisations, neither the actors nor the directors, received any help. Unfortunately, the political interest in people of culture and art was nil. (G. Cholakov, producer, former director of the National Film Centre Executive Agency)

The executive agency National Film Centre is the administrator of the state aid (i.e. the subsidy for the Bulgarian film industry). The new additions to this controversial law have been delayed, and the Agency has been delayed in requesting the European Commission to extend the application of the old state aid scheme for the film industry (Regulation EU No 651/2014). The delay has been for six months, which has led to the suspension of funding for the film production process since the beginning of 2021 and has put at risk all projects approved for funding until the end of 2020 under the old provisions of the Film Industry Act. At the end of 2021 BGN 18 million (EUR 9.2 million) were non-utilised and returned to the state budget. In June 2021, the director of the NFC was replaced.

There is also a need to improve the legislative framework at the national level in the area of copyright protection. Filmautor, the association for the collective management of copyright in cinema and television, is trying to advocate for the drafting of legislative texts that do not allow for interpretation

and which actually work. Filmautor lodged a complaint with the European Commission at the end of 2019 regarding the lack of possibility for collective management to work in the field of retransmission of audiovisual works as required by Directive 1993/9383. Formally, the text of the Bulgarian legislation complies with the directive, but the result is that the mandatory collective management cannot function.

Regarding cable retransmission, unfortunately, Bulgaria is one of the few countries in the European Union—I do not know if there is another Member State where this type of rights is not regulated and collected. In Bulgaria, everything is seemingly accepted as correct legislation, but we have a serious enforcement problem, and definitely in the field of audiovisual. It is not quite the same for music. We had some long negotiations with the Bulgarian Association of Cable and Communications Operators (BACCO) to arrive at a tariff that we could not approve in an agreement. (Maria Palaurova, Executive Director, Filmautor)

Directive 2019/789 established collective management in cable retransmission and extended this regime to all other types of retransmissions, for example, via satellite providers. Previously, these providers were not covered by this regime and only paid for the rights by negotiation. It remains to be seen exactly how this directive will be transposed into Bulgarian law.

Stakeholders who are guarantors of the search for solutions in Bulgaria also include the Sofia Municipality, the National Film Library, the Committee on Culture and Media in the National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria, NATFA, and others. At the European level, the main stakeholders are the EURIMAGES Fund, the Creative Europe–Media programme, the Association of Film Institutions, the Association of Eastern European Countries, the European Audiovisual Observatory, the Film New Europe publication, the Association of European Directors, the European Film Academy, and others. Bulgarian film organisations are members of these, and it is also through them that European film policy is reflected at the national level.

We need a serious reflection on the fact that cinema is in fact a big cultural policy and perhaps the biggest one a country has. In that sense, it really pains me when institutions behave formally. (P. Zheleva, producer, film critic, representative of Bulgaria in Film New Europe)

Symbiotic solutions to these gaps and problems should be sought at the national and European levels. Not different, but much more visible and pan-European, is the issue of the invasion of the audiovisual sector by large streaming platforms (Netflix, HBO, etc.), as well as the role of global social networks.

Netflix are trying to remove the institution of the producer as being the exhibitor and the producer at the same time. They go directly to crews, directors and play the role of both producer and exhibitor. There is a divergence in Europe. The television producers, the big users of film content agree with this, but what would happen if the role of the producer was ignored and destroyed. The producer is the one who initiates in different ways. He markets his film on the platforms. And when they remove the producer, it becomes a monopoly influence and tastes and competition between projects disappears. They will be from one producer or one platform. (Galina Toneva, producer, Chairman Association of Film Producers, Bulgaria)

Here also arises the question of the need to stimulate small national European platforms, which are weak competitors against the global American mastodons.

3.2.6 Conclusions on case study 1

Given the problems listed above, the film industry in Bulgaria clearly needs to improve the legislative, financial, and administrative framework of the sector. Recommendations in this direction are as follows:

- Stabilization of micro-production companies through greater access to alternative capital resources:
 - ✓ Stimulating the attraction of private investment (low-interest bank loans) by setting up a guarantee fund,
 - ✓ Reducing credit risk through upfront distribution guarantee agreements from television channels and national and foreign distributors, and
 - ✓ Accumulation of market and quasi-market revenues in a fund.
- Increasing the funds earmarked for the promotion of Bulgarian films. Promotion and advertising are factors in overcoming information asymmetry, a disadvantage for all film markets around the world.
- A compulsory television show for promoting the production of short films, documentaries, and cartoons by amending the Radio and Television Act.
- A more effective institutional management of the Bulgarian film industry can be achieved by turning the National Film Centre into a separate agency independent of the Ministry of Culture.
- European Support to the Associations for the Collective Management of Copyright in Cinema for the achievement of fair contractual prices in the implementation of Directive 1993/9383.
- For the Creative Europe–Media sub-programme, the creation of separate criteria to support platforms with European video content, considering that the size of the market "can be divided into small markets, medium markets, large markets, because otherwise we will all just watch NETFLIX."

The political agreement reached between the European Parliament and the EU Member States on the Digital Services Act (DSA) proposal tabled by the Commission in December 2020 also works in this direction. The agreement will have to create uniform rules for the EU internal market, which will thus also give support to small European platforms that are today invisible to the general public.

3.3 Case 2: Eurovision Song Contest

The singer Victoria on the stage in Rotterdam, as the representative of Bulgaria at the Eurovision and European Song Contests 2021, Copyright: Ligna Studios & Entiendo

Bulgaria's core team for the Eurovision and European Song Contests 2020 and 2021, Copyright: Ligna Studios & Entiendo

Between 21 October 2021 and 26 January 2022, twelve respondents from the Bulgarian radio and television market were interviewed, most of them online due to continued pandemic restrictions. The conducted interviews covered all phases of the production network.

The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) is an international organisation of broadcasters from Europe and the Mediterranean. It is the largest professional organisation of its kind in the world. Established in 1950 by 23 broadcasting organisations, the EBU currently has 69 active members representing 113 organisations in 56 countries.³⁴ Membership is for broadcasters from countries of the European Broadcasting Area, as defined by the International Telecommunication Union, or for members of the Council of Europe. The EBU is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland and has offices in eight cities: Moscow³⁵, New York, Washington, Singapore, China, Brussels, Rome, and Madrid.

EBU members operate nearly 2,000 television, radio, and online channels and services and offer a wealth of content across other platforms. Together, they reach an audience of more than one billion people worldwide, broadcasting in more than 160 languages. The EBU operates the Eurovision and Eurovision Radio services. Member countries have the right to vote in the organisation's General Assembly and EBU elections. They are encouraged to participate in EBU committees and assemblies, and to nominate candidates for EBU bodies such as the Sports Committee, the News, the Legal and the Policy Committees, the Television, the Radio and the Technical Committee. Members also enjoy all the benefits of EBU membership, including participation in the Eurovision Song Contest, access to know-how, networking, and training from the EBU Academy, and access to news sharing and sports acquisitions if they contribute to these services.

EBU members pay an annual subscription. Every five years, the EBU Executive Board checks members' compliance with the conditions.

The core mission of the organisation is to secure a sustainable future for public service media by providing its members with content that meets high global quality standards through the Eurovision and Eurovision Radio brands. The EBU promotes solidarity and cooperation to create a hub for learning and sharing.

In 1954, the EBU conducted the first international television broadcasts in Europe. The network of television transmitters, repeaters, and satellites was named Eurovision. It informed Europeans of the most significant events in the history of mankind in the second half of the 20th century. In 1961, Eurovision broadcasted live the welcome of the first cosmonaut, Yuri Gagarin, in Moscow. In 1962, Eurovision conducted the first intercontinental television broadcast via the Telestar satellite. Today, Eurovision is a network of 50 digital satellite stations connected to Eutelsat telecommunications satellites. Eurovision broadcasts daily information exchange as well as live coverage of all major political, sporting, and musical events taking place on the continent, including the Olympic Games and World and European sports championships.

³⁴ All information in this case study is from the EBU website, unless another source is explicitly stated.

³⁵ Russia's membership (Russian public broadcasting) was suspended by the Assembly from summer 2022.

Each year, Eurovision provides key Europe-wide broadcasting, such as the New Year's Concert in Vienna on 1 January and the Papal Addresses ("To the City and to the World") at Easter and Christmas. The Union organises numerous annual music competitions, the most famous of which is **the Eurovision Song Contest**, in which EBU member broadcasters can participate. **The Junior Eurovision Song Contest** is also for EBU member broadcasters. **The Eurosonic Festival in Groningen**, the Netherlands, is where the EBU member radio operators participate.

The EBU's operational activities in television include the day-to-day running of the Eurovision Network; the acquisition of sports rights, exchange of sports programmes, and establishment of sports activity groups; and the exchange of news and organisation of special news activities at the EBU offices in New York, Washington, and Moscow.

Television operating activities exposed to ever-increasing competition cannot ignore the market laws; hence, in order to continue, they must be economically viable. Thus, since January 1995, these activities have been entrusted to separate television operating centres (e.g. Network Centre, Sports Rights) under the responsibility of the Director of Operations. These centres have their own budgets and are organised as management units to ensure their optimum efficiency at minimum cost. The EBU expects them to be self-financing. Some operational activities in television are essential for all the members and could be jeopardised without the involvement of all members. These are the news exchanges and sports operations groups, as well as the negotiation and administration of sports contracts. Such activities are funded by all EBU members.

The main EBU operational activities in radio include news, current affairs, and sports, and Euroradio, which mainly involves the exchange of music. These activities are the responsibility of the Radio Department under the responsibility of the department Director. Since January 1996, the operational radio activities have had their own budget. Operating costs related to sports radio content, news, and current affairs programmes and Euroradio are charged directly to members. Some radio operational activities are essential to all members and could continue only if all members participate, as with the music exchange programme (apart from Euroradio) in which the costs continue to be funded by all EBU members.

The Bulgarian public media, Bulgarian National Television (BNT) and Bulgarian National Radio (BNR), have been full members of the Union since 1993. This membership gives them the right to participate in the EBU governing bodies, in decision-making within the organisation, and in the exchange of content among the participants in the network.

The two networks, Euroradio and Eurovision, are the pillars of the EBU. The EBU's highest body is the General Assembly, which meets twice a year. Bulgaria has worthy representatives in the governance of the organisation. From 2001 to 2012, the director of Euroradio was a well-known Bulgarian radio journalist, Rayna Konstantinova. Today, Albena Milanova is the coordinator of the largest regional group in the European Broadcasting Union, the 22 Central and Eastern European countries, and Radka Becheva is the head of EBU Member Relations for Central and Eastern Europe.

This case study features the annual Eurovision Song Contest, focusing on Bulgaria's participation in the contest. The entrance point for the global production network is Bulgarian National Television (BNT).

The Eurovision Song Contest (ESC) is an international co-production of broadcasting organisations with full membership status in the European Broadcasting Union (EBU). It is a high-tech event, with its broadcasting and filming involving innovations in television technologies, and it is a complex live format to manage. The number of viewers watching Eurovision ranges from 150 to 204 million according to the EBU, and since 2000 the contest has been viewable online. Audiences, especially young people, prefer the internet and social networks as a source of entertainment. The interest in Eurovision 2022 proves this. According to the EBU, there were 75 million unique viewers on YouTube across all official Eurovision content in 232 territories.

The competition is a platform to promote European cultural values of democracy and cultural diversity. Participation in the competition often has political dimensions for some countries, which can take the form of cultural diplomacy or “soft power,” and it can cause political scandals at times. Eurovision is one of the oldest competitions, being held every year since 1956. Many musicians have gained international recognition and fame following their participation. In 2021, the contest final was held in the Netherlands and was watched by over 183 million viewers across Europe, and it propelled the winner (the young Italian band Måneskin) to worldwide fame.

Bulgarian National Television (BNT) and Bulgarian National Radio (BNR) are public providers of radio and television services, according to the Bulgarian Radio and Television Act. Through their programmes, BNR and BNT provide audiences access to national and European cultural heritage. They create content that informs, educates, and entertains.

The creation of programme content and particularly its funding are strategic issues for public service media. Commercial broadcasters are funded by private sources, mainly through advertising and sponsorship. There is no single funding model for public service broadcasters, and different countries apply different models. The amount of investment determines whether a broadcaster can produce quality content, what that content should, and whether it can afford to participate in international competitions.

The public broadcaster BNT ranks third in popularity on the Bulgarian television market, following two private television channels bTV and Nova, which have been leading for years in audience share and advertising market share. Although BNT and BNR are less popular in terms of audience outreach, compared to their commercial competitors, they are the most trusted Bulgarian media. A 2020 study by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism at the University of Oxford showed that 72% of Bulgarians trust BNR news. BNT came in second at 71%, followed by Nova (69%) and bTV (68%).

3.3.1 Phases, actors, and locations

The Eurovision Song Contest has a unique television format, as a co-produced product in which each of the participating countries (both the host broadcaster and the participating broadcasters) create

and add value. With three live-broadcasted nights of the music competition (two semifinals and a grand final), Eurovision is the world's largest non-sports live broadcast, as a live performance which can be classified as both performing arts and as a music industry production. Hence, Eurovision is a **cross-sectoral event** that includes a) a **performing arts product** in the live music performance of a song concert; b) a **music industry product**, or a recorded songs and videos; and c) a **television format and a live broadcast** that brings it all together.

The competition, and everything created and broadcasted at it, takes place within the EBU framework: its concept, rules and specific requirements, and control and overall management. Extremely complex in terms of organisation, Eurovision has clearly defined participants with distinctive roles, power, and tasks or activities. In addition to **the lead organisation, EBU**, other key roles include the **Host Broadcaster** and the **Participating Broadcasters**. The Host and Participating Broadcasters are partners of the leader organisation, with the Host Broadcaster being a strategic partner. Each country (Public Broadcaster) has the power and autonomy in choosing an artist, creating and producing a song, and choosing how to promote and market their product. The amount of power and autonomy for each country are defined by the rules and limitations set by the leader company, EBU.

The production network of the Eurovision Song Contest has clearly delineated phases with uneven duration and intensity.

Creation

Each competition is governed by the EBU Uniform Rules, which take the form of a contract. BNT declares its participation using a special form, which means that it undertakes to comply with the rules: in addition to the payment of the entry fee, the acceptance of the rules is explicitly stated in this form. It is an important part of the contest documentation and regulates the obligations both between the BNT and Eurovision and, subsequently, between the BNT and its partners in the organisation of the contest.

The rules cover a wide range of issues, for instance, how to organise the contest, how long the songs must be, and what their content should be in order to be suitable for a wide audience. The contract that the local media (BNT) forms with the EBU team responsible for Eurovision defines the participation in the contest, the rights to the music and television content, and who can broadcast the contest and how.

National participation in the Eurovision Song Contest is created by BNT as a co-production. The first phase usually starts in the summer preceding the year when the contest will take place (April or May the year after). Then the country receives an official invitation from EBU. In 2014, for the first time, BNT partnered with a private producer company Seven-Eighth, to participate in the Junior Eurovision Song Contest. This allowed BNT to arrange public-private partnerships and cost sharing. Statistics show that Bulgaria's four best rankings in recent years have been achieved through partnerships between public television and a music label.

Budget constraints at BNT since 2019 have created the need for private companies to join in the eventual public-private partnership to cover all the costs. Half of the participating countries in the

Eurovision contest organise public–private partnerships for their participation; for the other half of the countries, the costs are fully borne by their public institutions. A public–private partnership is a way of carrying out an activity in the public interest by involving non-state actors. It is inherent to the market economy for more complex projects that require considerable and continuous financial resources.

The Eurovision Song Contests are television co-productions between all participating EBU member broadcasters willing to take part. In the case of the Junior Eurovision Song Contest these broadcasters are between 15 and 19, and in the case of the big Eurovision they are between 40 and 43. [...] This means that we cooperate, but there is always one host country that creates the main product, produces the programme and we all cooperate with it.” (Joana Levieva-Sawyer, producer and journalist at BNT, the Executive Director of Junior Eurovision Song Contest 2015 and Head of Delegation for Bulgaria at Eurovision since 2012)

When BNT decides to participate in the competition, the licence fee is set and the preparation cycle starts in early October. The songs of all the contestants, whether from Bulgaria or another country, must have been published no earlier than September the year before. There are various ways by which a country could select its song and to produce all the content that must be submitted to the contest. This selection could be made through a national competition to determine the Eurovision entrant. In this case, the participating organisation makes a very large investment in a music format. In Italy, for example, the Eurovision songs are selected and broadcast by the San Remo festival. Sweden uses Melodifestivalen, a very long format that includes live concerts and televised eliminations. The selection can be done using a so-called internal selection, which is the practice in Bulgaria. The public broadcaster selects a participant and invites and negotiates with him, her, or them. The broadcaster can also choose a co-producer, which is a common practice in Bulgaria and many other countries.

The main participants in the creation phase are the EBU, which sets the standard of work and conditions, Bulgarian National Television, and the private partner company (Ligna Group) and their subcontractor company Entiendo. Bulgaria’s participation in Eurovision 2020–2021 was through a public–private partnership in which the private partner takes over the production activities from BNT (i.e. it is organised by an external company and not directly by BNT). The company Ligna Group, a Bulgarian digital music and production house, strives to launch regional musical talents on the international and world music stages. They specialise in promoting artists to sell their music globally across all leading streaming platforms. Ligna Group subsequently hired Entiendo as a subcontractor to manage the Bulgarian Eurovision entry. Entiendo specialises in media and audiovisual content creation and distribution, publishing and distribution, film and television production and distribution, software and website development and maintenance, music publishing, sound recording, mediation and agency, production, and advertising. This wide portfolio of services shows that it can perform all the activities necessary for the preparation of the Bulgarian performer in Eurovision.

This model shows that BNT holds participation rights in the competition as a full member of the EBU, which gives it the opportunity to partner with a private company interested in investing in the creation of an intellectual product and presenting it on a world stage. Access is granted by BNT through its participation fee.

The minimum participation cost for a Bulgarian performer at Eurovision is about EUR 200,000. This comprises, for example, EUR 78,000 as the participation fee for Bulgaria (the fee is different for each edition and is determined depending on the number of participants), about EUR 20–30,000 costs for the stay in the contest location, and tens of thousands of euros for the staging of the performance and marketing promotion.

Ligna Studios, the company entering the role of music producer for the Eurovision song contest and which stood behind the overall strategy of the Bulgarian participation in 2020-2021, is a key actor in the creation phase of the Eurovision song contest music product. Initially, the company's team needed to check how the Bulgarian artist (Victoria) was doing and whether she was suitable for the international market. For that purpose, they enrolled her in the Berklee School of Music summer camp in Valencia, where the mentors liked her and confirmed her potential as a singer. Ligna Studios found a songwriter for Victoria's song, going to Los Angeles in 2019, where an artist of Bulgarian origin created the song. Victoria's first song ("Tears Getting Sober") for Eurovision 2020 was the favourite to win, according to bookmakers and contest analysts. The song was created during an international songwriting camp in which the singer took part, but unfortunately Eurovision 2020 was cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The second song, which Victoria did perform at Eurovision 2021 ("Growing Up is Getting Old"), was part of her mini-album called *a little dramatic*. The album contains five songs, each of which was a potential Eurovision entry. The singer's team created a special platform where fans from all over the world could give their opinions of the songs. This information went directly to Victoria and the team. In this way, the song was selected.

A key element of Bulgaria's success at Eurovision³⁶ is its song- and artist-selection model, which involves focus groups of hundreds of experts and music lovers. The expert focus groups are organised by Entiendo, which develops the platform, finds the people, conducts the research, and analyses the results. The focus groups include Bulgarian music radio and television programme directors, international radio and television programme directors from European countries, delegates from other public media in the participating countries, journalists from the European media, fans of the contest, music lovers, European and world artists, composers, songwriters, and producers.

This model was implemented by Entiendo in 2016 and has been used every year since to find the best song and artist to represent Bulgaria at Eurovision. An expert from Entiendo said that "many other countries, which in one of the years decided to choose their representative through internal selection, used the Bulgarian approach with large expert focus groups."

Entiendo has built the overall concept of "Bulgaria" branding for the Eurovision contest's international stage. The British record company Ostereo is also involved in the creation process and became the

³⁶ Bulgaria ranks second among the most successful countries that participated in the Eurovision Song Contest in terms of the total number of points received in the final - for the period (2016-2021). The country ahead of Bulgaria is Italy, which will win the contest in 2021. Bulgaria's ranking is due to good results in recent years - in 2017 Kristian Kostov came second, in 2016 Polly Genova came fourth, in 2021 Victoria Georgieva remained 11th, and in 2018 the EQUINOX group came 14th in Lisbon. In 2019 Bulgaria did not participate in the Eurovision Song Contest. If the year zero is counted, Bulgaria would be in 3rd place, ahead of Italy and Sweden.

official label of the Bulgarian artist in 2020. In addition to the record label, Ostereo is a publisher, influencer, and marketing company.

At this stage, the process is mainly implemented on a national level with Bulgarian partners, but it has had European dimensions, as it happens according to the rules set by the main organiser of Eurovision, the EBU. In addition, one of the co-creators, Ostereo, is a London-based international publisher with a “vast, international network of marketers, producers, writers and engineers.”

Figure 24. Main phases – Eurovision Song Contest

Production

The production phase is non-linear, occurring simultaneously in several places and in two stages over time. **First**, there is song and video production (scripting, filming) in each participating country. There is also the creation of the overall vision, “look and feel”: the set design, lighting, multimedia, and costumes. Everything that happens during this period is under the supervision of an EBU representative.

The main participants in this phase at the national level together with the EBU are Bulgarian National Television and the partner organisations subcontracted by the BNT, production companies Ligna Group and Entiendo, which mainly providing the digital marketing concept and the strategy of the Bulgarian project, and of course the singer, Victoria.

An important role in this case is played by Ostereo, which became the music label of the singer Victoria. This international company is known for discovering young talent and for its humane approach towards its artists. They develop the music video structure and design the stage show for the live performance of the artist at the competition finals. At this phase, representatives of other organisations may also be involved in the network by providing support services for the production of the video, the song, or the stage presence.

Second, at this phase, there is production work by the **host country or Eurovision Host Broadcaster**, which constructs the programme for the event: its artistic, technical, and financial dimensions. The host country has responsibilities in several aspects: it creates the overall programme for the event, aggregating the content created by each participating country by branding each singer and each participating country, and it also organises on-stage rehearsals a week before the live broadcast to ensure that all elements of the performance are in sync during the live music concert. The rehearsal is a must because of the complex synchronisation between the stage performances and the live television broadcast. The host country also films a “video-visit card” for each performer.

The production phase takes place at the national level, then on a pan-European level, as each of the countries (Participating Broadcasters) prepares a song and a video for it; production also happens in the territory of the host country, where the live concert takes place over three evenings and where the television filming takes place.

Distribution

In the distribution phase, the product—the song and the performer at the Eurovision—is promoted. The location of this phase is focused mostly on Sofia and less on other European countries where the song and the artist are presented, because this may influence the final vote for the Bulgarian song.

The creators of the song organise mini-tours in some countries, to promote the artist and the song in local media. The marketing company Entiendo makes media planning and prepares PR publications to introduce the artist and the song as an interesting and valuable cultural product on the market.

The record label Ostereo is also involved, managing the distribution. Ostereo were involved in the digital distribution of Victoria's work and her Eurovision song, for 2020 only. The company and its artists earn their income from music streaming and performance royalties.

Media partners are also contracted to promote the Bulgarian artist and the song: Bulgaria's largest radio group, BG Radio, and various representatives of the country's creative industry, including business magazine Forbes Bulgaria, design studio ARC Academy, and the popular local NGO Tuk-Tam, which promotes itself as the largest global community of Bulgarians in the world. Media partners are active at the distribution stage through advertising and promotion. Eurovoix, the world's largest provider of international song contest news and a leading source of music and entertainment news, covers Bulgaria's participation, as well as the entire event, on global social networks.

Eurovoix is not an official partner, but it has covered the whole process of Bulgaria's participation, as well as the fan site and YouTube channel Wiwibloggs. It is also the largest independent Eurovision website in the world, visited by hundreds of thousands of readers every month. Important support for Bulgarian participation is provided by partnerships with iCard, the general sponsor of the Bulgarian participation, Unimasters, the official carrier of the Bulgarian participation, and the Ministry of Tourism, which has run a successful campaign to promote Bulgaria as a tourist destination.

Dissemination is carried out by implementing information, communication, advertising, and marketing activities. The aim is to engage audiences using their own and partners' conventional and digital channels. These include press releases, annotations, posters, posters, catalogue, social media posts, and media partnerships.

Exchange

The next phase is performing the song at the music super-concert in the Eurovision host country and city, as well as for the live telecast. The event is broadcast nationally by BNT and, at the European level, by all participating European countries and their public media channels. It is also broadcast across non-EU countries such as Israel, Australia and China: this phase has a global dimension.

The main participants in this phase are the EBU, the Host Country/Eurovision Host Broadcaster, the participating countries' Participating Broadcasters (in this case Bulgaria/BNT), and countries that do not participate but broadcast the event by retransmitting the television signal.

The main actors in this phase are the people in the organisation responsible for the Eurovision Song Contest. These are 1) the organisation EBU, which sets the rules and standards; 2) the host country; and 3) BNT, as a participant in the contest and as a full member of the organisation. The media broadcasts the signal from the EBU using the international broadcasting network.

The EBU broadcasts globally via satellite link: the contest is broadcast on both standard television channels and on social networks. The host country, represented by the host broadcaster, transmits the television signal. The broadcast is intended for national and international audiences. The participating television channel broadcasts live the semi-final and final of the event. The show involves the media outlet's technical teams, who undergo special training in EBU standards.

Representatives of local businesses—hotels, restaurants, and transport companies—are also involved as service providers in this phase. This phase takes place at national and international level, with all participants from the different countries visiting the host country.

The level of the show is global because it is broadcast in many countries, including beyond the European continent.

The participants at this stage are the EBU, the host country, and the local public broadcaster, as well as the participants broadcasting the signal. The EBU is the supervising organisation and has the responsibility to ensure that all its requirements are met regarding the preparation and implementation of the Eurovision music and television show. As the creator of the contest, the EBU also owns all rights related to it. According to the contest rules, the subsequent edition of the contest will be held in the home country of that year's winner. Therefore, Eurovision is hosted by the local broadcaster of the country awarded the Eurovision Grand Prix in the previous year of the event. Together with the controlling organisation, the EBU, the local broadcaster in the host country organises the live and televised broadcast of the contest. For example, in 2022, Eurovision was hosted by the Italian public broadcaster RAI and the city of Turin. The preparation for the final in Italy was financially borne by the government and the host city.

The other participants are broadcasters who broadcast the contest live and who are entitled to receive the signal intended for international broadcast.

A special category in this group are the countries that, in addition to broadcasting the signal, have sent a finalist to participate in the Eurovision final. The costs of their inclusion in the final and semi-final are borne by the participating country and include a participation fee, travel costs, and hotel and subsistence allowances. Prior to this, the participating countries invest in the phases of idea creation, and content development: lyrics, music, and video shooting. There are also inputs at national and international level related to the marketing and distribution of the music product.

Archiving

The main actors in this phase are the organisers: the EBU as the controlling organisation, the host country, the local broadcaster, and the countries broadcasting the final concerts. In the case of Bulgaria, the public broadcaster is BNT. In the archiving phase, the aim is to create a digital archive in which the performances of the participants in the song contest, from the final and semi-finals, will be preserved. This turns Eurovision into an artefact with a longer lifespan. The recorded content can be broadcast additionally. Each country has the right to broadcast the contest for a certain period and a certain number of times because all EBU member countries have partial broadcasting rights. Their video business cards can be viewed there. This makes the site a good advertising platform for the contest, as well as for the groups and performers. The accessible online content allows any country or participant to have additional advertising through social sharing.

In addition to archiving the whole event, EBU has on its website rich information about the history of the contest, about each performer, about the path each country has chosen for the selection, and about the performer's promo-touring meetings in different European cities.

Archiving locations are concentrated at the European and national levels. The main event's content and information are stored in both analogue and digital formats, making them globally accessible.

The Eurovision Song Contest has rich content and a mix of cultural traditions. The creation phase is initially focused on promoting a piece of new and contemporary Bulgarian music presented by a young artist. Over time, the contest has given a number of emerging, as well as some established, Bulgarian artists the opportunity to perform internationally. In addition to composers and musicians, the contest is a provocation and a springboard for producers, video-makers, stage designers, and PR and marketing specialists. The production networks involve new participants: international partners, authors, stage designers, costume designers, choreographers, musicians, dancers, theatre managers and music promoters.

Along with the realisation of the Eurovision contest, BNT has involved new external partners: the performer of the Eurovision song and the executive producer hired through the public-private partnership. New information channels are created, expanding the products' distribution, including a dedicated national contest website and a dedicated Facebook page with 2,900 members at present and 51,000 likes. These are the biggest and most active fans of Bulgarian participants, who follow, comment, and share every step of the Bulgarian and international artists.

The Eurovision Song Contest also attracts and showcases new venues, because in addition to the participating countries, there are many more television channels that broadcast the show. The contest is also broadcast in countries that are not EBU members, such as Australia, Canada, India, South Korea, USA, New Zealand, and China. Since 2000, the contest can also be watched online. There is evidence that the number of countries interested in Eurovision is increasing. A DW post from March 2022 discusses the United States' launching their own version of Eurovision as a response to the contest's growing fan base in America.

The distribution phase is enriched with new information channels, successfully balancing the traditional means of music distribution, advertising, and marketing. New entrants include internet publications, bloggers, and providers.

Influence of COVID-19

The Eurovision 2020 organisers announced the cancellation of the event in 2020 due to the wide spread of the coronavirus. This did not stop the countries from maintaining their interest in the contest and preparing young performers for it. With the partial reinstatement of Eurovision 2021, it has become clear that the pandemic has impacted the number of country delegates due to the temporary restrictions on live events in the Netherlands that year (50% of the venue capacities): they were half as many. On the other hand, the restrictions have increased the role of social networks.

Several media outlets and producers have pointed out that the pandemic is affecting television content creation. In response to the halting or drastic reduction of new content production in 2020, the EBU is creating the EBU Content Appeal initiative. Unlike the radio exchange, the television exchange content is paid for—but not during the Covid pandemic, thanks to this initiative.

Twenty-five EBU member community public service media organisations provide over 200 television programmes, amounting to 1,300 hours of content for use by all public service broadcasters. The EBU-backed appeal was launched following COVID-19's disruption of production schedules and predictions of a resulting industry crisis. The EBU's community of members has provided programmes with established rights across multiple genres, including drama, history, lifestyle, performing arts, education, and a range of programmes aimed at children. In the spirit of the state of emergency, there was no requirement for broadcasters to contribute content in order to access the programmes (Advanced Television, 2020). According to the EBU 2020–2021 report, this good practice in content sharing continues: "With the success of the EBU Content Appeal, which was developed in response to the shortage of programmes resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, we have established a framework for ongoing content exchange between our members: the Eurovision television programme exchange. This allows our member broadcasters to share television content across a range of genres and has seen over 100 programme points submitted by 20 member organisations, who have provided a total of 250 programme hours."

When the pandemic started in Italy, colleagues made a WhatsApp platform, which we still use every day at a certain time. Colleagues in Italy informed us step by step how to set up the security protocol. We have submitted every day to the FET the protocol that is followed in the work of the media. If I have to summarise what is the difference in the work of the EBU, the word is solidarity. (Sevda Dimitrova, Head of International Communications, BNT)

3.3.3 Relationships between actors

As an organisation, the EBU is the leading network organisation for the Eurovision Song Contest. Its participants are the national public service broadcasters, and its dimensions in terms of audience access go beyond the European Union and are global (Australia, Israel, China).

EBU is the owner and creator of the television format and the concept of the Eurovision rules. The organisation manages the network of participants and activities—not always directly managing the process but rather monitoring, controlling, and evaluating it. The executive supervisor has the task of controlling the activities in the Eurovision GPN. It has the individual authority to implement the event itself through a committee that acts on behalf of all participating broadcasters of the Eurovision Song Contest. The main job of the committee is to oversee and guide the organisation and evolution of the contest as a whole" (Eurosong contest fandom).

We can accept and look for arguments that the EBU is a distant echo of the concept of a "global factory: "a flexible structure that combines internalised and externalised governance within geographically dispersed activities and actors." In the EBU network, in the Eurovision project we observe:

- 1) an integrated network of independent companies that involves individual public service broadcasters;

- 2) the transfer of knowledge, more specifically, in television technologies that the host country uses to carry out the live television broadcast;
- 3) the transfer of shared values;
- 4) access to a global resource—the global audience of the television contest as well as the satellite-transmitting television network;
- 5) the possibility of applying new forms of governance (in the case of BNT, that is a public private partnership in the national participation. There is a case where these are based on the leadership role of the EBU, which unites this European network of television broadcasters in implementing common "projects," objectives, lobbying, and cooperation for better management and positioning of public broadcasters. In the EBU's "global factory," economic dimensions are not the leading ones).

Different actors in the GPN have different types of power, and the relations between them for the one-year period of preparing, creating, and broadcasting the contest are spelled out in the contest rules (Niemi, 2019).

Table 41: Tools to manage ESC international collaboration

Tool/ Process	Actor/ Organiser
The ESC rules, updated annually	The EBU
The host broadcaster agreement	The EBU
The general contest format	The EBU
The individual ESC event format	The EBU, the host broadcaster
Defined roles and responsibilities of each organising party	The EBU, the host broadcaster, the reference group, the participating broadcasters
The ESC broadcasts	The host broadcaster
Annual meetings	Reference Group meetings Heads of delegations meetings
Face-to-face meetings, phone calls, emails	Executive supervisor, executive producer, heads of delegations
Reports	The host broadcaster, the participating broadcasters
Newsletters for participating broadcasters	The EBU
Annual workshops	The EBU, the heads of delegations
Internal digital database to share information, best practices, and learnings from previous events	Host broadcaster, the EBU, reference group

Source: *The ESC rules 2014 & 2015, Eurovision.tv (2018), Interviews with Ekholm (2016) and Sand (2019) in Niemi P. (2019) How to manage international collaboration? Eurovision Song Contest, Master's Thesis, Tampere University*

In addition to the EBU's leading role in the circuit, each of the participating countries has power. This is clearly visible at the creation stage, as well as in the distribution and promotion of the song and artist. This power is shared when through public–private partnerships. This has been the case with Bulgaria's participation in the competition in recent years. The external producer, their subcontractor, and the singer Victoria's music label company have all been involved in the creation of the song and video, the promotion of the event and song, and Bulgaria's representative for 2021, Victoria. Their activities are aimed not only at creating national prestige—at creating a winning song—but also at taking special care of the performer's career. Thus, each of them participates in the creation of value in the network.

The host country of the event is mandated by the EBU and has direct responsibility for the organisation and execution of the stage concert, the live broadcast, and the logistics of the visiting teams. These processes are supervised by the executive supervisor. The current supervisor is Martin Osterdahl, a Swedish television producer.

An initial barrier to participation in the competition is membership in the EBU. After this barrier at the national level, there is a financial barrier: whether the Bulgarian public broadcaster, which is the only public broadcaster in Bulgaria, can afford to allocate the necessary funds. For smaller public broadcasters, this is a serious constraint. The state may come to the rescue to overcome this barrier by providing an additional targeted subsidy; however, this is done when a country hosts and much less often when it simply participates in the competition, as was the case when Bulgaria hosted the Junior Eurovision Song Contest in 2015. Very often, the cities where the event is held also support it. Another possible approach is a loan from a public operator. Bearing in mind that there is no direct financial gain for the participants, bank loans are excluded here. Of course, there also remains the option of public–private partnership, which BNT has chosen.

The funds used for the competition include the fees paid by each country for its right to participate. In addition to public funds, the contest has private sponsors and partners that are attracted by its global audience of over 200 million viewers and the opportunity to reach over 40 markets (The Moodie Davitt Report, 2019). The massive outreach of the event creates conditions for revenues from exclusive agreements for advertising and merchandise. The main partner for the period 2019–2024 is the Israeli cosmetics giant Moroccanoil, which receives rights for advertising placement and branding across all types of media platforms. They also provide a team of world-class hair specialists to style the participating artists. Other partners providing various types of services in recent years include VISA, Vueling Airlines, Booking.com, Riedel, and others.

All co-funders, companies, and partners have some form of power, and they add value to the GPN. However, each also receives value in the form of branding, access to a global television audience, and participation on the event's social platforms.

3.3.4 Dynamics: transformations over time

The EBU's requirements to create a quality and high-tech product worthy of being broadcast during the Eurovision Song Contest stimulates the development of new services and companies in the

participating countries. Often, smaller European countries with underfunded public broadcasters do not have strong and dedicated teams that can meet the EBU's high technological requirements for broadcasting and filming the music product, forcing local television channels to hire subcontractors from the local private market or to directly invite specialists from other developed markets. The conditions set by the EBU stimulate the development of the television market. Often additional technology companies specialising in creating advanced television production emerge in local markets. The competition requires hiring modern equipment and training teams to operate it. A market for high-tech labour is thus formed.

Another significant change on the local markets is the development of public–private partnerships. Because of its limited budget, BNT is often unable to invest in the creation of a Eurovision product due to the high budgets that are required. The media outlet therefore searches for an external contractor for the project. In 2019, Bulgaria did not participate in the Eurovision Song Contest, as BNT's policy of maximum cost containment prevented the broadcaster from producing its project. Thus, the role of external producers, who invest or co-finance the music product and prepare the performer for participation in Eurovision, is strengthened and developed on the local market.

Partnerships and additional funding make producers work even harder, because in the preparation there is a dire need for digital marketing to reach a larger audience. Bulgarian participation, funded entirely by a private company, finds itself in a David-versus-Goliath situation facing the huge state budgets of the other contenders.

Comparing to the approximately EUR 200,000 budget of the Bulgarian project, Malta, for example, invested EUR 650,000 on advertising alone. Lithuania invested EUR 100,000 only for performance staging, and Germany has a budget of over EUR 1 million. Against this backdrop, the Bulgarian team behind Victoria decided to invest smartly and strategically, targeting its advertising efforts at Bulgarians abroad who are eligible to vote for Bulgaria.

Another significant change to the contest at the international level happened in 2016, when Eurovision introduced a change in their voting system, which had not been reformed since 1975. Originally, in the final, the jury scores were first announced separately by each participating country in the contest, and then it was the turn of the audience to vote on the results. Thus, instead of announcing the results from each country individually, they were announced collectively for each country. In the final, the results of the viewers' votes were added to those of the judges, resulting in a points total for each country in the final that could cause a reversal in the ordering. The same voting system was used in the semifinals.

In 2019, the presentation of the viewers' voting results during the final was changed. The way the jury points are presented remains the same, with a live speaker in each participating country revealing their national jury's song, which receives the maximum 12 points.

Over the years, the voting system has always been the most sensitive aspect of the competition. Major changes to how the voting in the Eurovision Song Contest 2023 will work have been announced by the organisers, the European Broadcasting Union (EBU). Only viewer votes will decide countries' qualification in the semifinals. Viewers in non-participating countries will be able to vote online.

Jury votes will, as before, be combined with viewer votes to decide the final result. Martin Österdahl, the Eurovision Song Contest's Executive Supervisor, said on the EBU's site: "Throughout its 67-year history the Eurovision Song Contest has constantly evolved to remain relevant and exciting. These changes acknowledge the immense popularity of the show by giving more power to the audience of the world's largest live music event."

3.3.4 Socio-cultural embeddedness

Socio-cultural embeddedness has broad dimensions that encompass the relationships between entities in the network and its territorial location. Traditions, culture, and the institutional dimensions of actors and territories help us to see the specificity of any global production network.

The EBU competition has a long history. According to the historical reference on the contest's website,

The history of the Eurovision Song Contest began as the brainchild of Marcel Bezençon of the EBU. The Contest was based on Italy's San Remo Music Festival and was designed to test the limits of live television broadcast technology. The first Contest was held on 24 May 1956, when seven nations participated. With a live orchestra, the norm in the early years, and simple sing-along songs on every radio station, the Contest grew into a true pan-European tradition. (source: [Eurovision website](#))

To this day, the contest is a benchmark of superior television technology and organisation. The contest is not only a cultural event—it is already part of the traditions of united Europe— but also a political barometer of every change and upheaval on the continent. Known for its free spirit in every respect, Eurovision is often remembered not only for its winning songs but also for its unusual and flashy set design, its bizarre and daring choreography, and its political bias in voting. Eurovision is not afraid to change.

From the seven countries at the start, the contest grew to a record of 43 participating countries in 2008. The number has grown exponentially since 1990, with the beginning of the democratization of Central and Eastern Europe and the collapse of the Soviet Union.

The language requirements for the more than 1,500 songs submitted have also changed several times: should they be in the singer's native language or in English? Audiences numbers have been growing steadily, helped by social media over the last 10 years. In 2001, over 38,000 people attended a live concert in Copenhagen. The other extreme was in 2020, when for the first time in its history the festival was cancelled due to the pandemic. For the television audience, outreach the figures vary along the years. In 2022, the final television audience was 161 million viewers. According to the contest website, the largest television audiences reached were in 2016, when the television spectators over the three nights of the concert reached 204 million.

A 67-year-old television competition is an achievement. Tradition, as a socio-cultural phenomenon, guarantees the sustainability of the format and the effect of its conduct. Numerous performers over the years have become famous after their participation. Historically, Eurovision has given the winners

of the contest a unique chance to develop. The most famous among them have been ABBA (1974) and Céline Dion (1988). The gala concert featuring the contest finalists is broadcast live every year and is among the longest running television shows in the world. Its audience in recent years has been between 150 and 250 million viewers around the globe. No national media could ever provide that visibility for a national musician. The number of views of the contest’s YouTube channel is also impressive: it was created on 5 March 2006 and as of 29 January 2023 its content had been viewed 6,558,8842,570 times.

The Eurovision Song Contest is mainly embedded at the European level, but it always creates prestige and high ratings for every national public broadcaster that participates. The period of its broadcast is usually also the one with the highest viewership for the Bulgarian National Television, comparable only to the broadcasting of world sport events. The national representative of the contest—in the last year, the young singer Victoria (Georgieva)—is gaining popularity. Participation in the contest, regardless of ranking, gives a boost to any musical career and is an opportunity to position the singer also on the European scene ([The Eurovision Song Contest impacts the Official Charts](#)). This happens more easily when the artist is specifically catered to by an international label and influencer such as Ostereo, as was the case with Victoria.

3.3.5 Positioning cases within the typology

Table 42. The typology matrix for Eurovision Song Contest

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/ regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation		Lead actor (EBU), strategic partner public sector 1-BNT (participating broadcaster), strategic partner private sector, specialised supplier, creators	Lead actor, strategic partners public sector (host and other participating broadcasters), creators	*	
Production		Creator, strategic partner private sector, specialised supplier	Lead actor, creators, strategic partners public sector, specialised suppliers	*	
Distribution		distributors, specialised supplier	Lead actor, distributors, strategic partners public sector, strategic partner private sector	Distributors, strategic partner private sector	
Exchange		Creator, strategic partner public sector, strategic partners private sector,	Lead actor, creators, strategic partners public sector,	Strategic partners public sector,	

		consumers	specialised suppliers, consumers	specialised supplier, consumers	
Archiving		Strategic partner public sector	Lead actor, strategic partners public	Lead actor	
Network level				X	Lead actor – ESC–EBU dispersed power - in network of EBU and strategic partners

*When the participating or the host broadcasters are, e.g., from Australia and Israel.

The structure of the global production network phases is not linear in time. It is simultaneous and overlapping in the course of activities in the different phases, both at the national and the European levels. The highest spatial scale at which the network is involved is global, through the distribution, the broadcast phase, and the online archives. We observed here the creation of a complex product that is not only a live television event but also an intersectional event that includes a) a performing arts product, a live musical performance of a song (concert); b) a music industry product, a recorded song and video; and c) a television format and live broadcast that brings it all together.

The **creation** phase takes place simultaneously at both the national and European levels. The lead actor, ESC–EBU, is the creator of the concept and the rules. Each participating country is a co-producer of the competition. The EBU has the main rights for the contest, but each participating country also has a share and creates the concept for the national participation (song selection, artist, and financial support for the participation). In this case, with the participation of Bulgarian National Television, a strategic partner from the private sector is involved in the creation phase due to the chosen model of participation through public–private partnership. This phase takes place simultaneously in all participating countries.

The **production** phase takes place in many places simultaneously: in Bulgaria, the BNT, and usually private partners, record the song, shoot the video, and create the set design for the performance on stage. In all participating countries, the same process takes place. In the host country, the event programme is created, videos are filmed for each country's participation, and funding is finalised. At the EBU level, these processes are monitored; in other words, this phase is not linear but takes place synchronously at the national and pan-European levels, with actors from all around the world, for example, Australia and Canada (part of 19 EBU-associated member countries). EBU member countries that are not part of the European Union and countries in the Mediterranean are also participants. From this perspective, the production phase takes on a global scale.

The **distribution** phase is dedicated to the promotion of the artist and the song and involves at the national level media and PR agencies. The aim is for the artist to be liked and branded as a representative of their nation through marketing, media campaigns, and touring. This process is identical in each country, and the tours and concert appearances are also European. Specialised providers and intermediaries for these services have major roles to play here. The distribution process also reaches a global audience through social media and coverage by the specialist company Eurovoix.

The **broadcast** phase is the showing of the contest. The participants at this stage are the EBU, the host country, and the local public broadcaster, as well as the participants who broadcast the signal. The EBU is the supervisory organisation responsible for ensuring that all its requirements are met in terms of the preparation and conduct of the Eurovision music and television show. As the creator of the contest, the EBU also owns all rights related to it. According to the contest rules, the next edition of the contest is to be held in the home country of that year's winners. Eurovision is therefore hosted by the local public broadcaster of the country that won the Eurovision Grand Prix in the previous year's event. Together with the controlling organisation, the EBU, the local public broadcaster in the host country organises the live and televised broadcasts of the contest. For example, in 2022, Eurovision was hosted by the Italian public broadcaster RAI and the city of Turin. The preparation of the final in Italy is covered financially by the government and the host city.

The other participants are broadcasters who broadcast the contest live and who are entitled to receive the signal intended for international broadcasting.

A special category within this group are the countries which, in addition to broadcasting the signal, send a finalist to participate in the Eurovision final. The cost of their inclusion in the final and semifinal is borne by the participating country. The costs include an accompaniment fee, travel expenses, hotel, and subsistence. Prior to this, the participating countries have already invested in the idea generation and content development phases for the lyrics, music, and video shooting. There are also national and international inputs related to the marketing and distribution of the music product.

In the **archiving** phase, a digital archive of the event and all related materials is created and preserved. The EBU has primary responsibility, and access is global. Member States have the right to a limited number of re-broadcasts, and the archive is mainly used for advertising and marketing. Part of the archive, which is more than 50 years old, can also be considered as common European cultural heritage.

3.3.6 Societal impacts of production networks

Economic impact

The final economic gains from this multicultural mega-show of performance, music, and suspense, are debatable. There is no doubt that it creates jobs, but the number is difficult to determine.

Revenue is generated for the host country from advertisements during the three-day event, but there are also advertising revenues for the participating countries. Eurovision attracts significant interest from sponsors and partners in advertising time at its events and in advertising space on social media, where the event is followed. Exact figures are not available, but there are indicators of a huge interest and following of the event online, presumably by the younger generation.

Kendall Bard (2018) has made an interesting, but to some extent controversial, study of the economic impact on countries of winning, and subsequently hosting, the Eurovision Song Contest. Using his statistical methodology and examining a period of almost 60 years (1960–1957), he demonstrated that exports, tax revenues, and international tourism all increase as a result of successful Eurovision participation, which is in line with expectations. However, he found negative coefficients for GDP. One explanation offers is the change in the Eurovision voting rules in 2000. After that year, the big five countries have gone directly to the final but do not win as they used to. Very often, the winners are smaller and less-wealthy countries. Despite its controversial nature, this study is a testament to scientific curiosity in the subject. As one of the most influential media organisations, the EBU looks after the collective interests of public service broadcasters. It provides them with quality content exchange, training, and knowledge.

As one of the EBU's most popular products, Eurovision is positioned as a platform for the exchange of cultural content and an opportunity to promote the participating countries. However, it is an expensive endeavour for each country. For example, the total budget for Eurovision 2019 was EUR 28.5 million, according to www.eurovisionworld.com. Each participating country finds different options to finance their participation. In order to host the 2019 contest, the Israeli public broadcaster KAN took a state loan of EUR 16.5 million to secure its Eurovision financial budget. The broadcaster has planned to repay its loan over the next 15 years, to avoid any economic burden from its current annual budget (ibid).

Being a host is not easy either, because the revenue generated from participants, advertisements, and sponsors does not always cover, and most likely exceeds, the costs. When Bulgaria hosted the Junior Eurovision Song Contest in 2015, it was a financial burden for the public BNT. The government decided, at the request of the broadcaster, to grant additional funding to the media outlet because it considered that hosting any Eurovision contest was good publicity for the country.

Table 43. Eurovision Budgets

Eurovision 2018 Lisbon	EUR 23 million
Eurovision 2017 Kyiv	EUR 30 million
Eurovision 2016 Stockholm	EUR 14 million
Eurovision 2015 Vienna	EUR 35 million
Eurovision 2014 Copenhagen	EUR 45 million
Eurovision 2013 Malmö	EUR 15 million
Eurovision 2012 Baku	EUR 60 million
Eurovision 2009 Moscow	EUR 33 million

Eurovision 2007 Helsinki	EUR 18 million
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Source : Klein S., *Total budget for Eurovision 2019: EUR 28.5 million – Israeli broadcaster takes loan from government* <https://eurovisionworld.com/esc/israeli-broadcaster-will-take-a-loan-to-fund-eurovision-2019>

One of the businesses that Eurovision stimulates the most is tourism. Relevant to this area are interesting figures published by economist Stephen Boyle from Nat West Group. The figures are based mainly on local travel agencies and city authorities, as well as on submissions from official Eurovision-related websites. The competition attracts tourists, which creates new jobs, mainly in hotels, restaurants, and arts and entertainment venues. Sometimes there is the creation of a special infrastructure (Baku) or a major reconstruction of an old building (e.g. an old shipyard, like in Copenhagen). The latter involves serious costs that cannot be covered by the revenues from the event. Additional value from hosting the competition is generated from advertising and branding of the host city.

Table 44: The cost of winning the Eurovision song contest (2012–2015)

Year	Host city	Cost (£m)	Jobs created (FTE)	Tourist visitors	Tourist spending (£m)	Reference
2015	Vienna, Austria	28	416	30,000	22	escbubble.com oikotimes.com
2014	Copenhagen, Denmark	36	139	39,000	13	visitcopenhagen.dk eurovisionworld.com
2013	Malmö, Sweden	17	130	32,000	16	malmotown.com
2012	Baku, Azerbaijan	48	529		7	tourism.edu.az

Source : Boyle S. *The cost of winning the Eurovision Song Contest (rbs.com)* <https://www.rbs.com/rbs/news/2016/05/the-cost-of-winning-the-eurovision-song-contest.html>

We should not forget the serious social media presence of the event, which we can consider its longest-lasting advertising on which Eurovision has a serious impact. The EBU 2020–2021 report mentions 2 million contacts on official Eurovision Song Contest accounts, with 72% of them on Instagram; they are viewed by over 73 million people in 38 markets. The EBU also reports viewers on the event's YouTube channel from 127 territories.

Social impact

For Eurovision, the EBU employs 468 staff worldwide, in permanent and temporary positions at its headquarters in Geneva and in the organisation's global branches and subsidiaries (as of March 2022). Of these, 173 are staff working for Eurovision. It can be assumed that all employees of EBU who have direct obligations with Eurovision services, 176 people, are also involved in the event, albeit indirectly. There is no specific information in this direction other than the leadership role of the Executive Supervisor and The Reference Group.

Interesting information about the organisation's employees is presented in the table below. A comparison between their studies, what they do, and their skills reveals that a focused education in media, communications, economics, and management is combined with a very wide range of duties and an extremely broad skill base. These comparisons give an indication not only of a high level of education but also of professionals and experts with great professional skills.

Figure 25. EBU headcount

Source : <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ebu/about/E>

Table 45: Broadcasting Union–Jobs

What they do	What they studied	What they are skilled at
152 Media and communication	29 Communication, general	173 Broadcasting
97 Operations	24 Journalism	169 Television
95 Business development	23 Economics	155 Digital media
58 Information technology	23 Political science and government	124 Social media
49 Arts and design	18 Marketing	117 New media
49 Community and social services	17 History	114 Broadcast television
39 Engineering	16 Communication/media studies	103 Video
37 Management	16 English language and literature	100 Project management
35 Marketing	16 Business administration	98 Video production
35 Administrative	15 International/global studies	96 Journalism
27 Education	14 Business/commerce, general	90 Media production
25 Human resources	14 Organisational leadership	85 Radio

23 Finance	12 European studies/civilization	73 Editing
18 Legal	11 Engineering	73 Public relations
18 Sales	11 Language interpretation	71 Broadcast journalism

Source: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ebu/jobs>

In an interview with the producer for the Eurovision side of BNT, a rough estimate of the guest participants and the technical teams is around 4,000 people when running the live event. The figure refers to 2021, when delegations from all countries were deliberately limited due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and does not include the large number of host participants who cater to the guests and provide their off-stage amenities.

Cultural impact

Eurovision Song Contest is praised, liked, contested, and denied. However, we must explicitly stress that this contest is only one element of the EBU's vast and varied activities. The contest is the tip of the iceberg: visible, interesting, and controversial. An explanation can be sought in the fact that Eurovision is a multi-dimensional phenomenon.

The competition is a **media phenomenon**, as the biggest live television show that is not sports. In recent decades, it could also be followed on social media, so in media terms, the contest generates a huge European and global audience. Some call it a "dinosaur" because of its classic television product dimensions and the fact that the main commercials for the event are part of it.

The competition is a **music show** in which live musical content is created and presented in the form of a glamorous stage performance. On a personal level, this show boosts talented early-career musicians such as ABBA, Céline Dion, and most recently Måneskin, to the big stage and fame. Even for those who do not become international stars, participating in the contest brands them as "Eurovision" contestants or winners. The contest is also a triumph of tolerance for differences of all aspects, not shying away from issues of ethnic and cultural minorities, LGBTQ and human rights, and burning issues such as war, global inequalities, and environment.

It is a cultural event that unites the eyes, the assessments, and the voices of one continent—Europe—but it goes far beyond Europe. As a competition, as a business model, and even in scope, this competition format is increasingly popular. Examples in this direction are the purchase of the licence in the USA and the experience of holding the competition in Asia.

Eurovision is also referred to as a political event. The reasoning for this political dimension is exemplified in its way of voting (you cannot vote for yourself, but you can vote for other countries), through which one can support a performer; country voting is often defined by certain geopolitical and/or neighbourly sympathy. The contest is familiar with a number of comments and scandals that give more reasons to claim that some 12-point choices are politically loaded. For example, consider

that the Eurovision contest to some extent branded and recognized the new independent states that emerged after the collapse of the USSR. The choice of the audience and the jury can be a gesture of support (Ukraine, Estonia), and punishment can follow (Belarus). A country could be banned, as happened to the Russian Federation because of its aggression towards Ukraine in 2022. After Ruslana's victory in 2004 and Jamala's in 2016, Ukraine won Eurovision for the third time in 2022, with the Ukrainian band Kalush Orchestra lifting the Eurovision trophy with their song "Stefania." The win came via viewers' televotes, which as well as an appreciation for the music, is a sign of solidarity with Ukraine.

This contest has never been apolitical, says DW political commentator Andreas Bremer:

It wasn't apolitical in its first edition, when 11 years after the end of a horrific war, seven countries that until recently had been at war with each other were brought together in Lugano. Nor was the contest apolitical when, at the height of the peace movement in Europe, the German singer Nicole sang the song "Ein bisschen Frieden" (A Piece of Peace), neither was the song contest apolitical when more and more Eastern European countries joined in. The Eurovision Song Contest has always been a mirror of events in Europe. (DW, 2016)

Evidence of cultural influences, again on a global level, include the many films dedicated to Eurovision, but apart from documentaries, a feature film arrived before 2021: "Eurovision Song Contest: The Story of Fire Saga" is a NETFLIX original film, on which EBU is a co-producer.

Finally, the contest has fans who are united in an international organisation. The Organisation Générale des Amateurs de l'Eurovision (OGAE) cooperates with the organisers of the contest but is independent. The fan network has 44 national offices, including in Bulgaria.

Each year, each contest brings in a different proportion of the above elements, but Eurovision's creation of cultural capital is undeniable.

Policy implications

In the case of the public broadcaster BNT, the Eurovision Song Contest is positioned at the national and European levels, which allows us to make generalisations and recommendations on these two levels: firstly on the role of public service media and related state policies, and second, at a pan-European level since BNT is a member of the European Broadcasting Union (EBU).

There is no one to help public media and countries like Bulgaria if it is not the EBU. And in terms of changes in media legislation and in terms of standards for the work and functioning of public media. The EBU has a role to play in modernising European Union law. Then we have the role of the EBU in modernising national legislation. They send their experts and prepare perspectives on draft national laws. (Nelly Ognyanova, Media law expert, professor at Sofia University)

The in-depth interviews point to several problem areas for which solutions can be sought through specific instruments and policies. After 1989, the state monopoly in press, radio, and television was abolished and the market gradually opened to foreign investors. This period saw the introduction of EU freedom to provide services rules. At the same time, the media transition took two forms: the adoption of democratic media standards in the European Union and technological modernisation. All of this is refracted through the peculiarities of the Bulgarian media market and organised in accordance with the level of local media culture.

Liberalisation is the process of transforming a media sector based primarily on state ownership and guided by ideological dogmatics (exceptions can be pointed out before 1989) for a media sector based on free competition and pluralistic views. Liberalisation is mainly associated with the legal possibility of privately owned media existing legally. It is also becoming possible for publishers and owners from the EU and third countries to enter the market freely. This became visible in the years when Bulgaria started negotiations for EU membership.

Every democratic transition raises the issue of citizens' access to information. Having lived for many years with a media that essentially presented ideologically filtered news, citizens now truly expect a new, free, and pluralistic media.

At the beginning of the 1992–1999 transition, BNT had advantages in terms of its technical capabilities for national coverage of the country and the preferences of the television audience. Private initiatives took off in 1992, first in the print media market and then in the radio market, followed by the first cable private media being established. The emerging of private media and television supply led to a reorientation of part of the television audience. In the face of cable channels, BNT now has competition. In 2000, the first private national television channel, bTV, began to operate. Its emergence drove the formation of a real advertising market, which is the main source of funding for commercial media to this day. The public broadcaster, BNT, is mainly financed by the state budget.

Over the last 10+ years, the importance of funding for public service broadcasters has gone beyond the economics of public service media, becoming a content issue for all electronic media and audiences for the following reasons. First, funding is linked to content. If the broadcaster is independent, it fulfils its public service function according to the law and the capacity of its editorial team; if the broadcaster is dependent on advertisers or on a particular political majority, the content of the programme certifies this dependence, and audiences receive one-sided or biased information. The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) therefore recommends that national laws regulate sustainable, predictable, and long-term funding. In Bulgaria, if funding from the state budget, which is known to be regulated annually by the State Budget Law, continues, sustainability can be ensured through the Broadcasting Act.

In addition to their own resources—state subsidy, sponsorship, and advertising—public service media BNT and BNR are entitled to use ready-made programme content by virtue of their membership in the European Broadcasting Union (EBU).

Before Bulgaria was in the European Union, the EBU taught us how to work with European standards. In this preliminary phase, we communicated with the Council of Europe and the other organisation important for the media was the EBU. From these organisations and media, we learned how people work in a team and how standards from an international framework go to an internal national level. (N. Ognyanova, media law expert, professor at Sofia University).

In Bulgaria, a strong public sector involvement in the media stands out. The EBU public service media take these factors into account: high direct competition and unstable audiences, growing threats from new technologies, and the need to seek additional advertising revenues. Public media address these constraints through the creation of common projects or products.

Six core values distinguish public service media from all others. They are universality, independence, professionalism, diversity, accountability, innovation. (A. Milanova, Director of International Relations, BNR, Coordinator of the Regional Group of Central and Eastern European Public Media, EBU)

The television market is global, open, and dynamic. The Eurovision Song Contest, in which Bulgaria participates, is a good example of a television production relevant to the local and general European market. The EBU's assistance is not financial but is much more complex.

This is a collaborative organisation. It reflects on the very structure, the way the EBU is built. If we are talking about television, we are talking about huge volumes available for co-production, not content exchange. To produce together, or once produced, to infuse it, solves tasks that Bulgaria could not solve on its own, because the EBU is involved, in the whole process, right from the planning they are involved, programming, contributing rights, contributing to production. In their documents you will see how much they contribute to the dissemination, I mean also organisationally, in terms of registration of the produced content. (N. Ognyanova, media law expert, professor at Sofia University)

The audience of the Eurovision Song Contest is in Bulgaria, but the offered production is not limited geographically. The competition is not only between BNT and other Bulgarian broadcasters but also between BNT and anyone who offers a television product, that is, the representatives of the European broadcasters. The advertising offered by national television is geographically linked. There is an oversupply in the television market, with increasing specialisation and focus on particular niche markets seeking to be offered in a “three-screen” format. It is no exaggeration to say that Eurovision is not just a contest but also a platform that promotes the development of the music industry in European countries. It also provides an opportunity to promote the different schools and traditions of music in a united Europe. Beyond the stage, the contest develops cities as cultural destinations, making them more recognisable. Eurovision winners are cultural ambassadors for their countries and cities and for more than a year become positive brands. The Eurovision Song Contest is a sustainable project which, in addition to its economic dimensions, is a symbol of the EU's core values of solidarity, diversity, and democracy.

Television ratings reflect viewers' preferences. The public BNT does not have the highest ratings in Bulgaria because it cannot withstand competition from the reality formats created by the private television channels, but still among its main achievements with high ratings are those that have high value and are related to its mission, for example, the Junior Eurovision Song Contest, as well as world sporting events and presidential debates.

3.3.7 Conclusions

Following the above-mentioned advantages and disadvantages in the EBU–BNT–Eurovision chain, Bulgaria clearly needs to improve its legislative framework in the field of broadcasting, the financing of the two public media, and the governance model of the two media.

An algorithm in this direction is difficult to give, but the EBU needs to start changing with the market because it is changing faster than the organisation. The intrusion of platforms, the loss of a serious part of sports rights, and the entry of new players into the sector are all changes that limit the power of public service media. Public organisations are more conservative, and limited funding and difficult legislative changes at the national level are serious barriers to change.

Today, radio and television share space as types of media with other types of services that weaken their roles, and they need to seriously transform their business models. Creating a stable and predictable funding model for public service media is a step in this direction.

3.4 Case 3: Euroradio music exchange

Symphony Orchestra of the Bulgarian National Radio, Credit: BNR-Ani Petrova

This case study investigates the Euroradio (MUS) radio exchange project of the EBU, using Bulgarian National Radio (BNR) as an entry point.

This case study features the European Broadcasting Union, focusing on Bulgaria's participation in music exchange within the organisation. The entry point for the global production network is Bulgarian National Radio (BNR).

The EBU network is large and covers many players. There are 60 organisations in the EBU that deal with music radio operations, based in 48 countries in Europe. Network members have the key assets needed to create quality music productions and sound recordings and for their international exchange, distribution, promotion, and presentation.

Table 46: EBU music radio members and their activities

	All EBU Members	EU-27 EBU Members
Inter/national terrestrial channels	276	170
Regional/local terrestrial channels	301	232
Online streams	244	226
Orchestras	56	40
Choirs	47	34
Ensembles	24	10

Source: 'The Economic Impact of Public Music Radio's Music Activities' report by Oxford Economic, 2018

For 2018, the activities of all EBU public radio members contributed EUR 1.08 billion directly towards Europe's GDP, and the total contribution for the period amounted to EUR 3.15 billion in GDP, according to the Oxford Economics report for the EBU, "The Economic Impact of Public Radio's Music Activities." The direct contribution relates to the economic activity of the organisations themselves and related employment in their units in the countries covered by the study. The indirect effect relates to the economic activity and employment stimulated along the European supply chain by radio operators sourcing goods and services from suppliers based in their home markets, in neighbouring countries and beyond. At the same time, there is also an induced impact, which "comprises the wider economic benefits that arise from the payment of wages by the radio operators, and the firms in their supply chain, to employees who spend these earnings" (EBU, 2020). The direct, indirect, and induced economic impacts together form the total economic impact.

As of 2018, more than 17,000 jobs fell under the EBU-Euroradio network, including 5,800 musicians working in choirs, orchestras, ensembles, and more. Indirectly, public service radios were responsible for over 50,000 jobs. The direct contribution to the EU GDP as of 2018 was EUR 0.85 billion and the total was EUR 2.36 billion (EBU, July 2020).

The EBU operates the Eurovision and Euroradio services. Bulgaria is represented in the EBU by Bulgarian National Radio and Bulgarian National Television. Bulgarian National Radio is an active participant in Euroradio, a network set up by the EBU that provides a daily exchange of music, concert performances, live performances, news, and programmes.

Radio exchange consists of activities between individual EBU members, including the creation of sound recordings and their sharing with other public radio operators via a digital platform, with the aim of enriching the music programme of the individual radio stations in the network, promoting cultural diversity and fulfilling the mission of public service media.

The conduit through which all this happens is an electronic database called MUS, through which the public radio stations of EBU member countries offer each other different types of audio content and can use the offerings already available through the service.

The EBU defines MUS as "the foundation of Euroradio's music exchange" (EBU website). It is a digital database where all EBU members offer their concerts and where these concerts are stored for a certain period of time, from a month to a year, for other radio stations to use.

In this sense, the platform provides input and output for the EBU radio exchange, as an aggregator of music content, as a digital database, and as an archive. The music content in the archive is available for one year, during which time it is free for use by member countries. This is possible because each radio station sends music content to the platform that is free for broadcasting, that is, the individual radio stations have previously arranged the broadcasting rights and production rights. In individual cases, for concerts of associate members, the EBU may pay for the rights. After the end of the one-year period, the recordings remain in the archive but outside the active music exchange; they can be broadcasted upon special request from a radio station, as well as through separate rights settlement.

The scale of this exchange is evident from the EBU's statistics for recent years.

Table 47. Exchange of concerts in the EBU network in the period 2016–2020

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Concerts offered	2,962	3,392	3,285	3,056	3,060
Concerts ordered	24,541	22,500	23,607	24,001	21,787
Satellite/ROIP transmissions	343	270	302	377	147
Concerts cancelled	35	39	42	239	65

Source: 2020 Statistics. Music Exchange, EBU, February 2021

The relationship between the EBU member radio stations is based on cooperation and the joint planning of concerts and events. Both the BNR and the other participants in the network comply with basic operating rules set by the EBU, but all participants in the network are on an equal footing.

According to the Bulgarian Radio and Television Act, Bulgarian National Radio is a public radio service provider. According to the Regulations on the Structure and Organisation of the Activities of the Bulgarian National Radio, the Director General of BNR is the primary budget authoriser.

BNR was officially launched on 25 January 1935, when King Boris III signed a decree making broadcasting in Bulgaria state property. At that time, state radio in Bulgaria covered the regional radio stations in Sofia, Varna, and Stara Zagora. Just two years later, Bulgarian Radio became a member of the International Broadcasting Union and began broadcasting abroad in Italian, German, French, English, and Esperanto. In 1944, part of the Radio Sofia building was destroyed by bombing and was later rebuilt. Eight years later, the iconic BNR Symphony Orchestra was established, followed by the BNR Folk Music Orchestra and the BNR Mixed Choir. This is how the major music ensembles in radio were formed. It was not until 1960 that the BNR Big Band was formed. On 1 January 1993, Bulgarian National Radio became an active member of the European Broadcasting Union and began actively contributing to the Euroradio exchange.

BNR has two national channels: "Horizon" and "Hristo Botev." The Horizon channel is the leading programme for news and current affairs. The Hristo Botev channel is specialised in culture, arts, science, and education.

In Bulgaria only Hristo Botev Channel creates and offers its listeners authentic radio theatre and original humorous programmes. On its frequency the brightest stars of classical art can be heard with concerts and performances from the biggest music scenes. It is the only radio programme in the country dedicated entirely to the presentation of Bulgarian and world culture. (BNR, Binary, 2022)

Today, BNR has nine regional radio stations which function as separate structures. They are secondary budget holders. Their task is to produce regional radio programmes. The regional radio stations are in the cities of Varna, Plovdiv, Stara Zagora, Shumen, Blagoevgrad, Vidin, Burgas, Kardzhali, and Sofia.

3.4.1 Phases, actors, and locations

Radio exchange is at the heart of EBU activities. It is a process that has been gradually digitised over the years and is based on mutual cooperation and respect, and on cultural and creative exchange. At the heart of radio exchange are the music formations of public radio, which are expected to produce music that is of high value, enriches radio programmes with new formats, reaches new audiences, and discovers new talent. "PSM broadcasters share a number of values which should arguably be evident in the ensembles for which they are responsible. These core values, as expressed by the EBU, are universality, diversity, innovation, independence, excellence, and accountability" (EBU,2019).

The main organisation (i.e., the leader organisation), is the EBU, but the national organisations (i.e. the national member radios), are strategic partners within a large network. Each of these organisations has an essential role in the creation, distribution, promotion, and archiving of the sound recordings exchanged.

The GPN applied to the EBU MUS has clearly defined phases which may, however, overlap for certain activities or run in parallel rather than linearly:

The product that members in the EBU exchange on a daily basis is the sound recording or audio content transmitted live, or concert. The definition of the "concert" includes musical content which may be live or recorded.

On the Bulgarian side, the participation of BNR in the EBU network is linked to two key units in the public service media: the BNR Music Production and Ensembles Department and the International Relations Department. As the name of the latter suggests, its task is to look after the radio's international partnerships, including with the EBU. The BNR Music Production and Ensembles Department manages the ensembles and produces music recordings, concerts, and tours. It also manages BNR's famous First Studio. It was established as a directorate in 1990.

Today, BNR has six musical ensembles that record, perform and tour. They are

- the BNR Grand Symphony Orchestra, founded 1948 (<https://new.bnr.bg/music/page/simfonichen-orkestar>);
- a mixed choir founded in 1952 (<https://bnr.bg/music/page/smesen-hor>);
- the Bulgarian National Radio Folk Music Orchestra, founded in 1952 (<https://bnr.bg/music/page/orkestar-za-narodna-muzika>);
- the BNR Big Band, established in 1960 (<https://bnr.bg/music/page/big-bend>);
- the Children's Radio Choir of the Bulgarian National Radio, established 1960 (<https://bnr.bg/music/page/detski-radiohor>); and
- the vocal group Radiodetsa, of the Bulgarian National Radio, founded 1990 (<https://bnr.bg/music/page/radiodeca>).

These musical ensembles are tasked with creating the musical content used in the radio exchange. Obviously, BNR also makes available for radio exchange musical content created outside of national

radio and by musicians who are not employed by the radio. These contents are not the main focus of our case study, although we comment on them. BNR hires the personnel who fill its musical ensembles. They work mostly on long-term contracts, with an exception for soloists and conductors who are invited for specific performances. The workplace in which all these people perform their duties is the BNR and, in particular, its studios. The radio also hires foreign musicians but on a short-term basis.

The figure below shows the tasks and phases of the MUS-EBU network and the BNR as its entry point.

Figure 26: Tasks and phases MUS-EBU

Creation

In the creation phase, the main actors are composers, lyricists, and arrangers. They are the creators of the work to be recorded; for classical works, the situation is different. At the level of administration, a decision is made at this stage as to the music that will be created and offered for exchange. This decision can be made by the music editors in the international department or by the management of the BNR Music House, which has production functions. If the BNR is involved in a radio exchange with an archived musical work, this stage, as part of the chain of creation, is in the past. Therefore, this phase does not always proceed linearly in time.

The creation of the sound recording may be an initiative of the BNR, but it may also be linked to a specific EBU project. The EBU runs regular competitions and festivals, as well as special initiatives such as Christmas Music Day, a Euroradio production with a 24-hour programme running on all radio

stations in the EBU network, which is filled with Christmas music presented by member countries, with each organisation receiving a slot of one hour. For example, for Christmas Music Day, the BNR usually creates a specific product: a concert performed by the radio's choir.

Production

Recording activities take place in the BNR studios. In this phase, Music House BNR is the producer. This includes, depending on the specific musical work, the six musical ensembles of the BNR: Large Symphony Orchestra, Mixed Choir, Folk Music Orchestra, Big Band, Children's Radio Choir, and Radio Children's Vocal Group. In addition to the performers are dozens of technical experts, specifically, sound engineers, technicians who take care of the mastering and all other technical processes.

Sound recording can also take place outside the BNR, during live concerts or festival events. In that case, the performers are not part of the BNR's musical ensembles; in order to be entitled to broadcast them, they negotiate in advance with the BNR for broadcasting and production rights.

This stage is geographically located in Bulgaria (i.e. it takes place at the national level).

Archive or BNR Phonotheque (audio-archive)

The Phonotheque Department manages the BNR's collection of sound recordings. The Phonotheque consists of thousands of old and new recordings but mainly offers new recordings. The operation of the Phonotheque is governed by special rules. The Phonotheque receives music content from the music producers of the radio, which can be used upon request. Requests could be for national or for international (EBU) broadcasting. The request contains specific information about the programme, the broadcast, and the date on which the recording will be used. To be able to use the recording in the future, and to remain in the library, each recording is processed, its sound "cleaned," and its sound quality assessed by a special committee. Metadata is added to the recording and, for international music exchange, an English-language text.

The Bulgarian National Radio's Phonotheque stores originals and operational copies in specially adapted repositories, observing certain technological parameters according to the type of physical medium on which the sound recordings are stored. These recordings are not part of the so-called "Golden Fund," housing historical artistic works and performances.

This phase and its related activities are geographically located in Bulgaria. The location of the archive is different from the classical value chain. The Phonotheque is the archive of contemporary musical recordings; the phonotheque prepares them for distribution by improving their quality and classifying them with metadata. Whether the recordings are for national broadcast or international exchange, they must have passed through a "phonoteca" phase.

The MUS Exchange Platform—bridging production and distribution

The music content selected for broadcasting is uploaded to the EBU's dedicated platform, MUS, which can also be accessed by other member organisations. From it, partners—customers or suppliers, as the case may be—in the network can download or upload music content and embed it in their programmes as and when they see fit.

The music exchange is done through the EBU's MUS platform, which all radio stations very often simply call "the platform." The server for the platform is based in Geneva and has a huge database embedded in it, allowing each radio station to automatically download and upload music content.

Therefore, considering the music exchange as a platform that aggregates a database in real time without interruption, 24 hours a day, its place in the chain is between production and distribution; in the case of broadcasting live concerts, its place is between the BNR Phonotheque and the commissioning country's distribution, when a recording is uploaded. This is particularly evident in events that are broadcast live on the web, for example, the Vienna Philharmonic's annual performance on 1 January. However, we should not forget the multifaceted nature of this international exchange: the database also has an "archive" function for a one-year period.

Therefore, the database has two aspects and two functions—as an exchange platform and as an exchange archive.

Whether for a database or for an archive, for MUS to exist and work there are also many supporting technical activities: specialised software and applications, and the management and maintenance of a large and robust internet network.

Distribution

The works recorded by BNR are distributed in the national channels of BNR—Horizon, Hristo Botev, and Radio Bulgaria—as well as through the regional channels of the radio.

At the same time, BNR is making a special selection of which recordings and concerts to offer for broadcast on the EBU network.

On its behalf, the Bulgarian National Radio sends recordings of Bulgarian artists to the Euroradio Music Exchange. They are broadcast in the music programmes of foreign radio stations, and in most countries of Europe there are separate channels for classical music on public radios. They are well maintained and developed. In this way the names of Bulgarian musicians become known to an audience of many millions in Europe and North America where Bulgarian music has been broadcast. (S.M., interview)

This exchange process is called "pink offers."

There are so-called "pink offers" that go from Bulgaria to here and from there to us. These are offers in which the production of different radio stations is offered, and everyone picks and chooses what interests them in the respective genre. For example, we have a lot of consumption of opera music, which is played at night on the Hristo Botev channel. BBC Promenade concerts are also quite frequent. We very rarely take live concerts as we have a very rich exchange with recordings. The principle is this - there is a common bank from which each interested radio station starts looking. For example, when a contemporary German composer premieres in Bulgaria, naturally the German radio stations will be interested in the BNR recording, and then the recording can be offered to 13 public radio stations in Germany. They will be interested in this musical content. (Momchil Georgiev, Professor—Music

Academy, Sofia; Producer; Bulgarian Association of Cultural Employers, former Director of Music Production and Ensembles BNR)

Each EBU member radio that participates in the music exchange distributes the music of the other members to its national network. Therefore, the distribution of recordings takes place both nationally and internationally. This also includes all the activities of advertising, promotion, and marketing of the music content to be broadcast on the radio.

The table below shows the intensity of music exchanges from 2018 to 2020. It includes all countries eligible to participate in the MUS database, both Euroradio member countries and radio stations from associate members such as Australia, Brazil, USA, China, South Korea, Japan, and New Zealand. Public radio stations offer and commission music production and may have special requests for access to live concerts. A total of 78 countries around the world belong to this global music sharing network created by the EBU.

Table 48: Concerts offered and ordered by members of EBU from 2018 to 2020

Incl. EURO, MET, ER, and Members' selection		Concerts offered by the organisation			Concerts ordered by the organisation			Concerts requested from the organisation		
Organisation	Country	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020
ALRTV	Albania	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	8	0
AMPRA	Armenia	0	0	0	100	165	0	0	0	0
ATORF	Austria	233	156	159	496	483	356	1841	1387	1220
AUABC	Australia	6	8	15	258	172	142	41	43	130
AZICTI	Azerbaijan	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	3
BERTBF	Belgium	22	22	20	444	413	421	190	164	160
BEVRT	Belgium	29	26	6	298	346	258	163	184	59
BGBNR	Bulgaria	46	35	29	538	672	561	188	121	76
BRRRC	Brazil	8	0	0	327	256	246	58	5	0
BYBTRC	Belarus	0	0	1	139	185	51	0	0	11
CACBC	Canada	1	0	1	107	94	93	13	0	3
CASRC	Canada	11	13	1	21	20	11	59	151	73
CHRSI	Switzerland	34	33	50	171	174	167	318	405	520
CHRTR	Switzerland	0	0	0	11	4	0	0	0	0
CHRTS	Switzerland	117	104	62	150	178	155	874	848	705
CHSRF	Switzerland	130	83	94	66	72	133	882	863	778
CNCNR	China	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
CNSMG	China	10	10	29	561	464	408	56	84	268
CYCBC	Cyprus	0	3	0	276	420	386	0	25	0
CZCR	Czech Republic	99	99	124	509	304	400	547	579	568

DEARD	Germany	-	-	1	90	113	29	-	-	2
DEBR	Germany	120	145	93	228	238	211	1249	1455	887
DEDKU	Germany	89	98	110	367	198	219	657	915	844
DEDLF	Germany	6	14	9	148	74	76	27	108	38
DEDWR	Germany	0	2	0	9	16	26	0	12	0
DEHR	Germany	25	27	7	257	237	204	248	240	101
DEMDR	Germany	34	25	25	115	147	126	3408	402	188
DENDR	Germany	181	133	108	449	288	334	1133	988	946
DERB	Germany	45	45	4	8	9	11	282	286	108
DERBBB	Germany	31	44	19	27	54	68	312	502	208
DESR	Germany	8	16	1	113	136	129	66	149	
DESWRB	Germany	37	38		158	119		239	253	287
DESWRS	Germany	37	48	43	6	8	183	319	502	
DEWDR	Germany	55	57	59	296	115	145	491	701	866
DKDR	Denmark	53	50	49	260	207	174	349	470	507
EEERR	Estonia	17	20	15	269	262	253	195	177	186
ESCAT	Spain	76	70	85	380	437	460	616	792	620
ESRTVE	Spain	76	60	24	603	581	391	409	434	257
FIYLE	Finland	46	63	47	548	330	314	395	455	498
FRSRF	France	100	72	99	90	82	175	808	759	730
GBBBC	UK	342	315	519	592	425	481	2716	2746	2266
GEGT	Georgia	1	2	1	4	11	1	0	7	6
GRERT	Greece	1	4	12	368	442	274	7	29	98
HKRTHK	Hong Kong	1	1	2	149	138	185	3	0	10
HRHRTR	Croatia	30	22	10	371	520	378	227	179	48
HUMTVA	Hungary	16	43	10	298	354	383	106	229	122
IERTE	Ireland	57	68	18	488	359	370	269	310	153
ILIPBC	Israel	0	3	0	110	103	145	0	24	0
ISRUV	Iceland	4	6	27	300	258	213	43	81	123
ITRAI	Italy	27	36	62	437	381	760	248	271	720
JPNHK	Japan	81	35	75	111	153	117	304	167	307
JPTFM	Japan	1	1	0	49	50	12	1	0	0
KRKBS	Korea	18	20	13	369	684	477	31	78	50
LTLR	Lithuania	5	5	8	415	432	763	30	28	52

LUERSL	Luxembourg	10	29	18	284	205	219	62	137	87
LVLRL	Latvia	11	18	16	687	642	557	79	116	167
MDTRM	Moldova	22	21	14	286	269	197	48	90	136
NLNPO	Netherlands	93	170	182	635	472	356	767	723	655
NONRK	Norway	33	40	34	240	222	285	256	358	477
NZRNZ	New Zealand	0	12	24	168	119	97	0	47	182
PLPR	Poland	111	69	108	892	1369	441	921	387	465
PTRTP	Portugal	13	13	4	774	696	650	98	84	23
ROROR	Romania	61	59	52	752	665	710	683	407	441
RSRTS	Serbia	46	44	20	429	434	320	121	134	68
RUMK	Russia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RUOP	Russia	58	31	33	62	54	78	487	184	356
RURK	Russia	0	0	0	44	4	0	0	0	0
RURTR	Russia	4	3	1	45	78	40	28	31	0
SESR	Sweden	101	99	104	695	747	811	626	967	932
SIRTVS	Slovenia	25	48	14	659	555	486	110	307	130
SKRTVS	Slovakia	7	6	34	510	558	477	27	41	147
TRTRT	Turkey	0	0	0	136	31	32	0	0	0
UAPBC	Ukraine	1	8	14	197	201	178	6	33	65
USAPM	USA	60	44	17	69	55	98	336	276	218
USMET	USA	26	28	45	-	-	-	300	335	293
USNPR	USA	0	0	0	1	1	3	0	0	0
USWFMT	USA	111	50	35	56	40	40	503	245	200
VARV	Vatican	0	3	1	35	33	40	1	15	24
ZZEBU	Euroradio	126	80	144	-	-	-	719	469	899
Members		2875	2764	2718	17985	17152	15600	21286	21778	19431
Associates		334	222	257	2247	2247	1929	1704	1431	1736
Approved participant		76	70	85	380	437	460	616	792	620
TOTAL		3285	3056	3060	20812	19836	17989	23607	24001	21797

Source: 2020 Statistics. Music Exchange, EBU, February 2021

According to the table above, Bulgaria is a full participant in the EBU radio exchange, actively using music productions from other countries but also offering its own recordings. There is also strong

interest in and orders for large volumes of content produced by the BNR, which is testament to the quality and diversity of the music recordings it offers. There is particular interest in Bulgarian folklore.

Given the nature of BNR as an organisation, it successfully promotes everything it creates and disseminates. As M. Georgiev said, "As far as BNR itself is a media, it always uses its own channels to promote its own concerts, recordings."

Social networks also play a role in radio promotion. The BNR actively uses services such as Facebook and Instagram to promote the concerts of its ensembles, some of which are then sent to the EBU. These ensembles have both recordings and public concerts, which are also regularly posted on social networks. In this way, the BNR can reach a wider audience.

At the same time, BNR also promotes the content it receives from other EBU members because it further enriches its own programme. The promotion process is bilateral because EBU members also promote the recordings coming from Bulgaria.

Exchange/Broadcasting

The role at this stage is played by all EBU members that broadcast (analogue, digital) the exchanged music content. They enrich their audiences with new music, develop the cultural content of their programmes, and promote in Europe and worldwide the best music being created in national markets.

Table 49: Evolution of the ratio of ordered/offered, from 2018–2020

Type	2018	2019	2020	Evolution '19–'20
Euradio season	10.39	9.04	19.60	+117%
Metropolitan opera	10.58	13.48	8.52	-37%
Summer festivals	10.27	10,57	6.27	-41%
Members' selection	5.81	5,65	5.26	-7%

Source: 2020 Statistics. Music Exchange, EBU, February

Classical works are most actively exchanged on the EBU network, within the Euroradio Season. Their demand during the period from 2018 to 2020 grew by 117%. Metropolitan Opera's works are the second most popular, followed by summer festivals, which, however, show a decline for 2020. This decline reflects restrictions on live performances and concerts during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic.

This phase is taking place in Europe, Asia, North America, Australia, and New Zealand, not in a linear fashion but in parallel in each member country. Thus, its geographical location is a complex symbiosis of faceted national markets across several continents.

Archiving

The main participants at this stage are the EBU, Bulgarian National Radio, and all other public radio members in the network. EBU is the administrator which created the rules of the exchange and the manager who monitors their compliance. The EBU is also the physical creator of the archive platform

and is responsible for the technical preservation of the musical wealth created and shared by the member countries.

The BNR Phonotheque collects recordings from all genres, including everything made by the radio's ensembles. As previously explained, a product offered to the EBU is first added to the BNR archive, then goes through international radio exchange. The content that is fed to other EBU members is only a small part of the total archive of the BNR. Annually, "tens, hundreds of times less is sent than what is recorded, than what is made as live" (Momchil Georgiev, interview). For example, the international festival Sofia Music Weeks, which presents to the Bulgarian public the most significant international and Bulgarian music and performance art, includes about 50 concerts that enter the BNR archive, but only the best of them are then offered on the EBU network.

The EBU's digital archive is located at its headquarters in Geneva, Switzerland. Although the MUS has the qualities of an archive, it does not have the same preservation duration as traditional archives. Most often, the broadcasting rights for content uploaded to the platform are ceded for one year. For some musical works, this period is much shorter, depending on the decisions made by the artists themselves.

After the period in which the sound recordings can be used by EBU members for free (they always have pre-cleared broadcasting rights from the radio station that gave them), they remain in the platform's archive but are out of use for radio exchange. If any radio station requests a recording older than a year, it could receive it under special conditions.

Figure 27 Tasks and Actors MUS-EBU

Phases	CREATION	PRODUCTION	DISTRIBUTION*	EXCHANGE BROADCASTING	ARCHIVING
Actors	Composers Writers/Lyricists Bulgarian National Radio's Music House Management (music producers, editors of the BNR International department) EBU specific requests (e.g. Christmas concert)	Music House BNR - Director Producers Music directors Musicians, bands and orchestras of the National Radio Accompanists Sound engineers	EBU- Euroradio MUS - Platform *MUS platform is used across the Production, mostly Distribution, Exchange, Archiving phases	MUS by all EBU Euroradio Members	MUS - Archiving
Tasks	Music writing (notation) Composing; Music decisions & requests by management of BNR, music editors, producers etc. Copyright and neighbouring rights arrangements (BNR)	Recording music in BNR studio Production Post-production Recording of festival concerts of external orchestras and performers	Content aggregation Creation and following of usage rules Database support Promotion, PR Marketing of music contents from MUS by all EBU Euroradio Members in separate cases: Copyright and neighbouring rights arrangements (EBU for all members. e.e.	Broadcasting of music contents from MUS by all EBU Euroradio Members Programme announcements	Archiving of recordings for maximum one year miro

Influence of COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic had a devastating effect on much of the music industry, shutting down all tours, concerts, and live events. Musicians, composers, concert halls, and event organisers have suffered financially from the health crisis and the restrictive measures imposed because of it, which have affected social and cultural life in individual countries.

The COVID-19 pandemic has also influenced the events in the EBU network over the last two years. The global health crisis has hit Europe hard, causing many music events to be cancelled completely or replaced by digital editions. The EBU Folk Festival, for example, did not take place out of concern for its attendees. Instead, the EBU replaced it with a folklore project, as there was no way for the folklore groups from EBU member countries to come together in one place. Instead, the EBU organised the creation of a special compilation: a large concert from all over Europe with works from individual EBU Member States.

The Let the People Sing festival also did not take place because of the pandemic. However, EBU members are continuing their musical exchanges using all the digital tools at their disposal. COVID-19 failed to stop radio exchange in the EBU but created difficulties with holding live events. For its part, the organisation is becoming more flexible and adaptable to the times, so as not to interrupt Euroradio's activities in these challenging times.

The network is becoming a source of support for the member countries, and motivates everyone to be proactive and look for alternative opportunities for cooperation. Although events have been cancelled, the number of concerts published on MUS in 2020 remained the same as in 2019. Organisations are reaching into their archives to offer previously unrepresented content on the EBU network. Thanks to this decision, there continues to be a variety of music on air.

It is the makeup of the whole that changed, with 2020's total comprising more than 20% of new archival material (concerts never offered before). In addition to these new offers, 29 radio organisations extended the rights of 634 previously offered concerts. Together, Member representatives and the EBU Music staff in Geneva accomplished this shift in focus brilliantly. (Pascale Labrie, Head of Music in EBU) (EBU,2021)

The impact of the pandemic on the EBU network does not end there. The health crisis is stopping courses and training being offered to people in network organisations. This limits the exchange of knowledge, skills, and knowledge internationally.

COVID-19 has also been a factor in the digitalisation of some EBU processes.

Colleagues responded extremely quickly at the BIA. We at the EBU, too. We instantly adapted to online courses, conferences, events, seminars. We created a WhatsApp group, social media too. (Radka Becheva, Head of EBU Member Relations in Central and Eastern Europe, EBU)

What happened between March 2020 and the calming of the pandemic in Europe shows the great solidarity among EBU members. "For the second consecutive year, the programmes responded to the call of the EBU and Radio 2 of the Belgian public broadcaster VRT and simultaneously broadcast the song 'You will never be alone' on 19 March as a sign of solidarity and support in the fight against the

pandemic. Over 100 radio stations from 17 European countries participated in the initiative" (BNR, 2021) The BNR Children's Choir also took part in the initiative. Its soloist recorded at home a song calling on the children of the choir to show empathy and support in the fight against the pandemic.

3.4.2 Relationships between actors

The relationship between the actors can be considered at two levels: internally for the BNR and externally for the whole EBU network.

The relations between the employees of the BNR are also influenced by the trade unions, the Confederation of Labour "Podkrepa," the Confederation of Independent Trade Unions, and the Union of Musicians. They are related to the Collective Agreement. The industry, both in Bulgaria and internationally, is also influenced by collective copyright management companies.

For its part, the EBU is the network organisation when it comes to Euroradio. Its participants are the public radio stations. The EBU has 68 members representing a total of 112 organisations in 56 countries. The members fall within the European Broadcasting Area or are members of the Council of Europe.

Although the EBU is the leading organisation, its members determine the direction of its development. They have the right to vote in the General Assembly of the EBU and in its elections. Public radio stations that participate in the EBU are encouraged to join the Radio Committee.

As a barrier to entry, we can point to EBU membership, which requires a financial contribution as well as the capacity and knowledge to create a product suitable for the network.

Each of the member organisations signs a general agreement with the EBU, under which it becomes part of the network. By signing the agreement, the member country undertakes to pay an annual membership fee. The EBU network includes all counterparts with which audio content can be exchanged.

All EBU members

- create music content in the form of recordings, concerts, and live events;
- serve the public interest and comply with it at all times;
- select which of their content is suitable for distribution on the EBU network and is relevant to the needs and expectations of other participants; and
- freely use sound recordings provided to them by other members.

Through the EBU digital network, member countries exchange studio recordings and/or concerts from the current concert season, whether live or recorded.

The exchange between the parties is continuous, with no time limits on offering specific content. Each organisation in the network periodically sends its proposals to the EBU, making them available to all member countries. Sound recordings, including concerts that are not broadcast live, are uploaded

directly to a dedicated server, where they are stored and free for use by all other members. There are no additional intermediaries in this process.

Power in the EBU network is dispersed and shared among all participants. As M. Georgiev said,

There is no hierarchical interdependence or material interdependence, there is simply cooperation based on certain parameters, for example, exchange of recordings, exchange of live performances, joint planning of concerts, festivals, competitions that are held under the EBU and in which member countries participate, distribution of recordings that are commissioned on-demand or live, summer festivals and other joint initiatives.

There is empowerment on a micro level: there are special committees in the BNR that decide which works are submitted to the other EBU participants. They decide which of the summer festivals—Sofia Music Weeks, Varna Summer Music Festival, Bansko Jazz Festival, and others—can be broadcast live on the web or offered on record. For some of the events, such as Sofia Music Weeks, the decision is made jointly by radio experts and event representatives, who first select what to broadcast on the Hristo Botev Channel and then offer the best-value content to the EBU.

The EBU has a role in quality-controlling the recordings exchanged to ensure that all members receive a product that is suitable for broadcast.

The daily exchange of music is not limited, except in sound quality. You can't put a bad record on the air. The EBU listens to the concerts to make sure that what members upload is of good enough sound quality. (M.P., interview)

The EBU's music experts only have more power in deciding who should participate in initiatives like Christmas music

In general, the relationships between network members are based on trust, competence, and quality. Each EBU member makes its own contribution to the GPN and continuously benefits from the contributions of other organisations. No exclusive agreements are made within the network. Participation in special events such as Christmas Day does not require additional contracts but happens through internal agreements. The radio stations then work on behalf of the EBU, which sets the parameters of the product in demand.

BNR, like other EBU member organisations, are both creators and consumers and distributors of content. The nature of the network is such that each member is unique and irreplaceable as national public radio stations that have a special mission and role, with a very strong focus on musical pluralism. They offer music unique to each market, created with many resources that reflect national culture and identity.

When the EBU organises competitions and live events, the relationship moves from the national to the international level, with national participants visiting the host country. At this stage, more players get involved, including representatives of local businesses: hoteliers, restaurateurs, transport companies, sound companies, and others. In these cases, they are service providers to the EBU and not to specific members of the organisation. In this type of competition, all parties are guided by the rules set by the EBU but compete for international recognition.

In sum: EBU network participants work on common projects each year, because content is created at the national level and offered internationally, and in some cases on common products.

The Eurovision Music Exchange can be considered as a common project, without a time limit and with an increasing number of participants. According to the EBU, the Music Exchange is the largest live music offering in the world, with around 3,000 concerts shared each year, and its members request around 20,000 Music Exchange programs each year, making it a cost-effective way to bring the world's best music to national audiences.

Music Exchange's products—concerts—are created nationally but distributed and consumed nationally, across Europe, and around the world. In this way, they create economic, social, and cultural value at the national, European, and global levels.

The special events in this mega-project of musical exchange are a common product of the network; for example, the Eurosonic and Euroradio folk festivals, as well as special events such as Christmas Music Day. They are a joint product because the content is created at the national level but aggregated into a common programme of events that is distributed to all members of the Euroradio network. Each national participant meets the requirements, rules, and criteria of the leading organisation: Euroradio and EBU.

We can take the network they have created as a common product with economic, cultural, and social dimensions.

3.4.3 Positioning cases within the typology

Table 50 : BNR-MUS European Broadcasting Union

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/ regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation		Lead actor*, Strategic partner public sector, Creators	Lead actor**		
Production		Strategic partner public sector Creators	Lead actor	Strategic partners public sector***	
Distribution		Strategic partner public sector	Lead actor	Strategic partners public sector	
Exchange		Lead actor Strategic partner public sector Consumers	Lead actor Strategic partner public sector Consumers	Lead actor Strategic partners public sector Consumers	
Archiving		Strategic partner public sector	Lead actor		
Network level				X	

*Concept of the music product to be exchanged

**Concept of the music exchange platform - rules, participation formats, technological basis, etc.)

*** e.g., associated members outside Europe

The lead firm of EBU-MUS network is the EBU–Euroradio, which is the creator of the platform archive and of its rules of operation, and which maintains the technical exchange between the member countries by controlling the process. All Member States are strategic partners with the lead institution and are equal and united by the common mission of public service media. The global production network approach applied to EBU–MUS, has clearly defined phases which may, however, overlap for some activities or run in parallel rather than linearly. The setup phase takes place at the national level but the selection criteria very often at the pan-European level. The production of the specific product is at the national level but can take place in real time, as a live event recording, be part of a past production (e.g. in the national archive), or be a specially created new recording by radio orchestrators. The special function of any national phonographic library should be emphasised here; its role in the production phase can be compared to post-production in cinema. EBU–MUS has the functions of an archive, but its format is a digital platform. Therefore, we can see its appearance twice in the chain: 1) as an intermediary between the production and distribution phases and a platform on which concerts (recordings) are embedded and downloaded in real time; and 2) as an archive in which musical recordings are preserved for a short period of time. The distribution and broadcasting of the recordings takes place on a national level, for a national audience, but given that each partner distributes on its national airwaves the music of another partner, this process adds pan-European and global dimensions.

The table reflects the typology of the MUS–EBU network, assuming that the exchange product is created by the BNT, that is, by its orchestras and choirs. One more actor would appear in the table if the Bulgarian radio product were a recording, a live broadcast of a private concert, which would bring one or two new actors into the production phase: a strategic partner from the private sector and a specialised provider.

3.4.4 Dynamics

The main changes over the years have been triggered by the process of digitalization, the advent and development of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the administrative changes it imposed.

At the administrative level, BNR has in the past had highly qualified producers responsible for each individual genre. They were the sole decision-makers as to who could record which works at the BNR Music House. Today, these decisions are delegated to a board of directors, when it comes to the work of whole ensembles.

The digitisation of the radio exchange process and of the sound recordings themselves has had a transformative effect. In the past, international radio exchange was carried out by sending recordings on physical media, which were difficult to store and took up significant space. The exchange process itself was considerably slower and more cumbersome. Digitisation simplifies the process and makes it extremely fast.

Transformations in the network are largely related to the penetration of technology into the music industry, which has brought changes in the distribution and storage of the content created by radio. Before this process was digitised, EBU members sent each other “pink offers,” or radio recordings with pink labels. Although the expression is still used today, the offering and exchange of recordings takes

place through a digital system in which the recordings are still stored and to which each member has access.

The dynamics of the network are also related to changes in the number of music lineups in radio over the years. This, to a large extent, determines both the quality and quantity of recordings that are available.

Different countries have different numbers of lineups. We have one of the most—we have six lineups. In the former socialist countries, some of the configurations have been reduced. Let's say choirs or big bands, but in Budapest they kept the big band, the radio choir, in the Czech Republic the big band was cut. In some countries, the choirs were diminished. For example, in our country there are 44 people, and the idea is to have 48: 4 parts of 12 people. In Sweden, for example, it is 32. The Dutch radio orchestra was cut three years ago. Austria's radio orchestra was also, now it is half-staffed, half-unstaffed. There has been turmoil with the lineups in recent years. Especially in Germany, there are orchestras at every radio. (M. Georgiev, Professor Music Academy, Former Director of Music Production and Ensembles, BNR)

A factor in these changes in recent years has been the COVID pandemic, which has led many radio stations to change the way they work and restructure.

3.4.5 Socio-cultural embeddedness

BNR and the other EBU members are public radio stations. As such, they have a special mission, enshrined in specific national laws. According to the Bulgarian Radio and Television Act, BNR must provide media services for all, contribute to the development and promotion of Bulgarian culture, provide access to national and European cultural heritage, inform, educate, and entertain through its various programmes. Participation in the EBU allows the BNR and other public radio stations in Europe to exchange various musical works, providing access to international cultural heritage. The product itself, the sound recording of a piece of music, is instrumental in fulfilling the mission of these radio stations.

Public radio seeks a balance in which the content it offers covers social, cultural, educational, and other programmes. In this way, radio fulfils its mission as a public service media organisation, ensuring that it retains its licence as such.

The product that EBU members exchange is high culture, through which national music culture is developed and the national market stimulated.

Radio exchange on the EBU network also brings prestige to the participating radio stations because it gives them access to high-quality music content. It is specially selected by country-specific experts.

Prestige is also conferred by participation in international EBU competitions and events, recordings of which are then distributed on the web, including to and from Bulgaria.

Radio exchange also plays an important role in promoting Bulgarian creativity, as well as Bulgarian musicians and performers who can become popular abroad. Including them in the radio exchange is a way to support their careers and attract international recognition for their talent.

Exchange in the EBU network takes place not only at the European level but also at the global level, as the EBU has 30 associate members from other continents. At the same time, the Bulgarian audience gains access to the works selected by the EBU members, which are uploaded to the organisation's platform and which the BNR can use.

3.4.6 Societal impacts of production networks

Economic impact

Those employed in the BNR's music ensembles play major roles in creating the recordings that participate in international radio exchange. However, these musicians and performers do not receive high enough salaries. According to the interviews, the average salary in the ensembles in Bulgaria is around BGN 1349, but those in BNR receive around BGN 1000 (as of 2021), which is related to the underfunding of public radio. BNR allocates 5% of its budget to the music ensembles and music production.

This insufficient subsidy limits BNR in creating and offering more music content, in inviting external stars, in having decent pay for the employees in its music formations, in reaching a more diverse audience, and in experimenting with new formats.

Outside contractors are often used in productions for the EBU, making the product even more expensive. Outside musicians, conductors, arrangers, and others are hired. The cost of the sound recording, including the salaries of the ensembles, the external participants, the technicians, and the physical media, does not matter to the other EBU members because they receive everything for free. The same is true for the BNR, which receives foreign content for free without paying extra for it. How much content a particular radio uses on the EBU network has no bearing on the amount of membership fees the organisation pays.

Overall, the economic impact of participation in the EBU network is immeasurable due to the nature of the relationships between members. However, as already written, the effect of the work of all the music formations involved in the exchange is measurable, as is the economic contribution of public radio to the EU GDP (see beginning of case study).

The only clear financial relations between the EBU participants are related to membership fees, with everyone providing sound recordings free of charge without seeking payment from other members. However, we must not forget that each radio station has previously paid for, or received, the rights to broadcast this music content free of charge. There is, of course, the case in which the EBU directly negotiates the broadcasting rights.

With the metropolitan opera, the EBU negotiates the rights on behalf of all members with the Metropolitan Opera and the Metropolitan Opera is tempted by the fact that an audience of many millions can follow the performances. (S. M., BNR, interview)

The fact that the Metropolitan Opera does special matinees to be broadcast live for the EBU, because of the time difference, is proof of the mutual interest.

In 2018, EBU members employed around 17,700 people, with the number of employees varying from country to country.

Taking the results for direct GDP and employment together, average GDP per job across the European region's public service music radio activities—a crude measure of productivity—works out at EUR 61,100. That is a third higher than the equivalent GDP-per-job ratio for the European economy as a whole. ("The Economic Impact of Public Radio's Music Activities", EBU, July 2020)

Figure 28: Direct GDP per job in context: Europe-wide

Source: Oxford economics

Cultural impact

Radio exchange is not so much economic as cultural. The EBU member radio stations have one main task: to exchange high-quality cultural (music) products.

The EBU has a specific role to play in terms of creating a multiplier effect through its long-standing Music Exchange. Most of the public media ensembles are contributors, meaning that national media ensembles regularly broadcast internationally, providing a more European offer to listeners served by EBU Members and enhancing the distinctiveness of their services. It also means that the investment in music provision in one country, combined with

advantageous rights agreements, can benefit listeners beyond national boundaries, strengthening the whole public media sector. (EBU,2019)

This product is a conduit of different cultures from countries all over the world. A diversity of genres is offered, contributing to the public mission of the participants.

In the EBU there is an exchange of world music, and more specific national musics, which give many people the opportunity to experience the greatest achievements of world cultures. (A. Milanova, Director of International Relations, BNR, Coordinator of the Regional Group of Central and Eastern European Public Media, EBU)

The participation of the Bulgarian National Radio in the EBU is of key importance for the promotion of Bulgarian culture and identity, but it also brings benefits to the image of Bulgarian musicians, composers, conductors, and others.

The fact that the radio orchestra will be broadcast or even just proposed for broadcast raises its image. One recording of a clarinet concerto was broadcast 13 times on the BBC in just two and a half years. It was a recording of our orchestra. (Radka Becheva, Head of EBU Member Relations in Central and Eastern Europe, EBU)

The EBU cares about promoting new music and young talent. The music events—festivals and concerts—that the EBU organises and then broadcasts are also cultural and important for the exchange of messages and values between countries.

I think of Valya Dervenska, who in 2000 won an award at the Concertino Festival in Prague. There the prizes were in the categories of duet, trio, duet, etc. Then she was invited and performed at the EBU General Assembly, when the 50th anniversary of the organisation was celebrated. There she was invited as a laureate of that festival, after which I heard that she was already playing in the Vienna Philharmonic and had quite a glamorous career. (A. Milanova, Director of International Relations, BNR, Coordinator of the Regional Group of Central and Eastern European Public Media, EBU)

Policy implications

In general, radio activities are highly dependent on the subsidy allocated for its funding. Continued underfunding over the years has limited BNR's development opportunities. Nevertheless, BNR is the undisputed leader in the national news market.

BNR maintains its leading position in the ranking of trust among the Bulgarian society, according to a survey conducted every two years by the Reuters Institute, and in terms of market share the Horizon programme maintains its third position among the radio channels in Bulgaria, with [four] BNR programmes among the top 20 nationwide. Horizon is the information leader... has regained its position as the leading information channel, regaining the leadership it lost over the years in the competitive clash with television programs. (Baltakov, 2021)

In recent years, the budget has been further cut due to the significant costs of dealing with the pandemic in Bulgaria. In April 2021, there was a reduction of nearly BGN 450,000 and in May 2021, of another BGN 388,000.

Financially, BNR is in relative stability and can meet its current obligations as well as make modest capital investments. But BNR could not and will not be able to transform itself into a modern digital-oriented organisation if the financial resources continue to be at similar levels. Andon Baltakov (Director General of BNR January 2020–August 2021 in BNR's report for the first half of 2021)

Table 51: Budget subsidy of BNR for the period 2018–2021

Year	Budget subsidy (million BGN)
2021	54.1
2020	47
2019	44
2018	42

Source: State budget, Ministry of finance, Bulgaria, <https://www.minfin.bg/bg/1408>

The complicated media situation in Bulgaria and the additional interference of the ruling parties in recent years have caused several changes of BNR directors. These events led to a series of upheavals in public radio and discussions about freedom of speech and freedom of decision-making in the organisation. Despite all the political and economic turmoil, BNR has managed to assert its independence. "The professionalism of the journalists, music editors, sound engineers and all the administrative teams who, despite the crises and several changes of senior management, have managed to maintain a high quality of work of this complex and large organism—BNR—is commendable"(Baltakov,2021).

The Music Exchange is only one of the many networks the EBU has created. The EBU is involved in many initiatives and projects, together with major stakeholders, such as the Council of Europe, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, the European Union, the European Parliament, and the Organisation for Security and Cooperation in Europe. Radka Becheva, Head of Member Relations for Central and Eastern Europe, shared the following in this direction:

Mostly our projects are funded by the EC—as is the case with one project we are currently implementing for technical assistance to public media in the Western Balkans We are in a consortium—the European Federation of Journalists, the International Federation of Journalists, the Austrian Public Television, the Balkan Investigative Reporting Network, EBU music exchange. The leader of the project is the European Federation of Journalists.

Training and networking are strong aspects of the EBU's activities and are assisted by the Training Academy at BNR. An important part of the EBU's network with other institutions is the Council of Europe.

Especially the CoE's Platform for the Protection of Media Pluralism and Security for Journalists is very important. When there is political interference, budget cuts, firing of journalists, managers before their mandate expires, when laws are passed hastily—without public discussion. The good thing is that national institutions are obliged to respond" (R. Becheva)

This case study provides an opportunity for reflection and a search for new policies at several levels:

- National policies related to the problems of the public media and in particular the BNR. Underfunding and the need for changes in the Broadcasting Act are major challenges for public media in Bulgaria. One of the leading experts on EBU policies, R. Becheva, shares the common goals and activities between the EBU and the BNR:

We are in very close contact with various institutions regarding changes in legislation because the Broadcasting Act is outdated. It needs to be updated. There are a few key points. One is that the mission of public service media is not clearly defined in the law. The other is the division between control functions and managerial functions. It is not a good model for the regulator to be both a supervisor and to control the public service media. There is usually a buffer between politics and public service media. A board or governing body is created, which can be elected by parliament, but that governing body elects the director general and you get a sort of buffer of supervisor and manager. Because you cannot control yourself. Nor can the regulator who regulates everybody in the media space control the public media. There is also the problem of the very short tenure of CEOs, which doesn't allow them to develop strategies.

Discussions about public media budgets should go hand-in-hand with conversations about their mission.

Because what you get is this: you say, "build this house," but later you announce, "build it for less money!" But I can't build it with that money! Because there are standards in diversity of content: educational programs, sports, recreational, for minorities. This mission must be supported with adequate financial resources. (R. Becheva, Head of EBU Member Relations in Central and Eastern Europe, EBU).

- European policies, formed on the basis of the EBU's work to support and protect public service media in Europe.

Very often, public service media in Europe are under political or financial pressure.

Funding is just a key question because, first, we at the EBU have four principles for funding: to be independent, to be stable, to be adequate and to be predictable. It's not good practice every year for politicians to discuss whether public service media are sufficiently obedient and how much we're going to give them for their obedience. If a funding system is set up based on a percentage of GDP rather than being subject to subjective political judgements. This opens the door to political influence over media policy. (R. Becheva, Head of EBU Member Relations in Central and Eastern Europe, EBU)

- Global policies. As much media environment is changing globally, the EBU seeks to help its members adapt to or fight the new realities (e.g. the rise of tech giants and their related platforms, audience fragmentation).

The EBU supports political and media stakeholders with expertise to create European legislation in line with the new digital realities. The Digital Services Act is a historic bill aimed at fighting the spread of illegal content online and protecting fundamental rights of users. The DSA landmark standards for a safer and more open digital space for users and new obligations for platforms, proportionate to their size and societal risks they pose. (Bulgarian Parliament, 2022)

3.4.7 Conclusions

As a member of the EBU, the BNR engages in a two-way process of supply and demand for sound recordings of musical works and concerts. Within this GPN, each of the organisations (i.e. public radio stations) plays the role of creator, supplier, and consumer, with each radio station being unique and irreplaceable due to the uniqueness of the product it creates and offers. Radio exchange occurs on the basis of ground rules set by the EBU and following the payment of an annual membership fee. The relationship is based on cooperation, exchange of cultural product, values, and the fulfilment of the public service media mission. The economic impact of this activity is difficult to measure. More visible are the cultural and social effects in terms of preserving cultural diversity in Europe and the world by promoting new and old music. Power in the network is dispersed. Empowerment is observed at the micro level in the BNR, in the face of specialised committees that decide what to propose to the EBU and what to broadcast in Bulgaria. The pandemic has had a significant impact on EBU members over the last two and a half years. Initially, it restricted some music creation and exchange processes. Since then, however, it has become a driver of innovation and digitisation in a number of processes across the network. The participation of the Bulgarian National Radio in the EBU is important for Bulgaria in terms of cultural exchange, the global positioning of Bulgarian music content, and the exchange of knowledge, and creative products, offering the Bulgarian audience access to quality content.

Music exchange is only one element of the EBU's activities. The organisation also assists public service broadcasters in the implementation of policies. It is the guarantor of an adequate legal and regulatory framework for European media policies. Radka Becheva, Head of EBU Member Relations for Central and Eastern Europe, shared the following in this direction:

A healthy public media is an indicator of a healthy national debate. People are well informed, they know what the challenges are, they know where there are good practices, good stewardship of state resources. When we (EBU) support public media, we support debate, understanding, tolerance and creating a cohesive society... The purpose of journalism is not just to poke someone in the eye, but to show a problem that needs to be discussed and solved. If there is no public media, there is no one to look after all groups in society. The mission is tough. If you are a real public media, you are not loved by anyone.

3.5 Case 4: Viennese games sector

For the games sector, the five different production phases of the GPN approach seem to be clearly assignable to specific activities and actors, as there is usually a clear division of labour and responsibilities. By comparison, the locations and the spatial embeddedness of relevant stakeholders, strategic partners, and even end customers are much more complex and widespread. Game developers usually do not think in national boundaries but cooperate with partners all around the world and also reach to the international gamers' community.

3.5.1 Phases, actors, and locations

Relationship between actors—how the interview partners are linked to each other

When selecting the interviewees, it was important to talk to actors carrying out different activities from all five production phases. After our first interviews, we decided not to focus only on actors involved in the production of a single product but rather to take a broader look at the whole network around it. The length of production chains differs significantly, as game studios mostly offer a range of different products and services. Therefore, it did not make sense to focus on a single game but rather on the network of actors. Another decisive element was our availability and access to interview partners. Some interview requests were rejected because of a lack of time, and we can assume that others did not reply to our requests because of confidentiality agreements or the fear of revealing certain secrets to competitors.

The starting point was an academic colleague from the University of Vienna, who gave us our first insights into the local game sector. He recommended local game companies, associations, and other key actors, which we contacted. Another access point was a new independent game development team producing their own games; they talked about their experiences and led us to a local association for gaming culture and a successful mid-sized games company. Both stakeholders supported the independent newcomer games developer. The interview with the games company led us to their stakeholders, customers, and suppliers, such as a sound studio in Germany where they present their new products and reports, and FH Wien, an educational institution that recently started a programme for the interactive media and games business. The head of this programme then recommended other interviewees and led us to actors from related fields such as VR, XR, and visual arts.

In general, most actors and interview partners knew each other personally. Some actors turned out to be hubs connected to many other local actors. All interview partners, except one, were more or less linked with each other and active in the same networks.

As it was hard to access big international publishers, we could not interview stakeholders directly connected to our previous interview partners. One of our CICERONE partners, however, knew an actor from a large media company working in Canada who could provide us insights from a major company. Big media companies play a role for local game developers, as they publish their games and help with distributing; furthermore, they outsource certain activities, cooperating with other developers by buying their special products and services.

In addition, it was important to include interviews with actors from public funding institutions such as the Vienna Business Agency. Our interviewees were well-informed about the local game sector, knew the local community, were aware of problems and potentials, and acted as crucial stakeholders for all local professionals.

Eventually, we were able to talk to actors from different fields: 1) game studios, 2) art, 3) education, schools, research, 4) related tech fields, 5) founding structures, and 6) associations, communities, and events.

The creation phase involves initialising the conceptualisation of a new game. The main tasks involve creating story plots and characters but also team building, organising, and managing. It usually takes some years to produce a game, so the schedule and costs must be calculated in the beginning. The story plot and the main concept are then peer reviewed and accordingly adapted. Contracts and copyright issues are initiated in this phase as well.

The production phase is very long and involves many different actors and activities. There are highly specialised tasks such as programming, character design and art, musical composing, and voice recording, as well as testing, evaluating, giving feedback, and readapting. The production phase requires an enormous amount of teamwork, empathy, creativity, and resilience. The bigger the studio, the more activities are done in-house; for larger projects, the team size can reach some hundred employees. The smaller the studio, the more skills are required from each team member; generalists carry out multiple tasks, and some activities such as musical composition are usually outsourced. Legal issues concerning copyright and exploitation rights are negotiated in detail.

The distribution phase means, on the one hand, the physical distribution of games to retailers or online distribution on websites or platforms such as Steam or Google Play. On the other hand, distribution also includes marketing and PR, the production of trailers and merchandise, and being present at fairs and festivals, that is, communicating the new product to the gaming community all around the world. Distribution in the games sector is usually not limited to national or regional borders but aims at reaching gamers all around the globe. In this phase, there are rather big players and powerful gatekeepers controlling the market.

The exchange phase is the moment when the game is being played by the gamer and has reached its end consumers. Games can be played online, downloaded, or purchased as physical media. They can be played on different technical devices such as smartphones, tablets, PCs, PlayStation, Xbox, Gameboy, and more. There are different business models, such as single purchase, time-based subscriptions, free access financed by advertising, free version with the option to purchase specific

tools inside the game, and so on. Additionally, the exchange phase involves the consumption of merchandise or the soundtrack, or visiting festivals, fairs, or even museums.

Figure 29. Relationship between actors

The archive phase is comparably hard to identify, as games are a rather new cultural good. Archiving digital goods or technical devices demands other logical approaches than archiving books, fashion, or films. Not least due to copyright and exploitation rights, it is hard to store games or make them accessible. Interestingly, it is not simply the content—in other words, the game itself—that must be stored but also the technical device on which to actually play it. In other respects, the academic discussion and historical analysis of games can also be located in the archiving phase. More and more academics are addressing game studies. There are even museums, festivals, and art works and performances about gaming culture.

Locations and spatial footprint

We entered the network in the city of Vienna as it was hard to access interview partners in Bulgaria, especially those working in bigger companies. Vienna is, of course, not most popular for its gaming culture, and there are less than 500 people working in the sector in Austria. Still, there are game companies, of which some are quite successful. It turned out that a variety of different actors from different phases are located here and that the actors in the Viennese games sector are well-connected with each other. Internal communities such as XR Vienna and associations like Subotron strengthen the network and interlink the actors. In consequence, actors in the local ecosystem support, hire, and recommend each other. Even bigger fairs and festivals, such as the Vienna Game City in the city hall or the CIVA festival, take place here and serve both as an event for consumers and as networking events that enhance the visibility of the sector.

Despite supporting each other on a local level, game companies never think within national or regional boundaries but cooperate with partners and stakeholders all around the world. Our interview partners were well-connected with, for example, publishers in Japan, USA, Canada, and other European countries. They studied and worked abroad for some years and hired staff from other places. Mobility, flexibility, and job changes, for instance to bigger international companies, are not seen as a threat but rather as a way of gaining new knowledge and skills.

Vienna then benefits further from a larger talent pool, which makes the place more attractive for new startups or subsidiaries of bigger international players. Likewise, schools and education play an important role in increasing the talent pool. There are some schools and college and university programmes specialised in games and media art or design in Vienna.

There is a general lack of company startups in this field, as the foundation is quite risky and comes with extensive bureaucracy. However, the local government has strategies to enhance the local ecosystem: the Wirtschaftsagentur Wien (Vienna business agency), a publicly financed body, helps entrepreneurs in this field, gives grants, organises network events, and plays an important role in the local industry.

The geographical position of Vienna makes it an interesting place for game companies: the central European time zone makes it possible to communicate with other continents, and meetings with Japan and the USA can take place the same day. Furthermore, Vienna is a very attractive city for expats and employees who can benefit from Austria's good welfare system. The wages are attractive and the work-life balance good in comparison to other countries. As an interviewee explains:

Vienna is safe, clean, international because of the UNO and other headquarters (...); it is a super international city. For eight years in a row, we have been the number one city for expats (...) and there is the airport and the AUA (Austrian Airlines) (...). So if you want to travel in order to keep personal contact with your customers or partners, it is a very good place and this is a crucial factor.

We examined whether games themselves are location-specific and learned that especially the story plot, and even characters in the game, can refer to local social, cultural, and geographical characteristics.

The city itself also benefits from the gaming sector: apart from contributing to the local economy by generating job and paying local taxes, there are symbiotic cross-sector spillovers. Game developers add a creative think tank to the area, influence artists and designers, and work in other sectors as well. The lay public benefits from interesting cultural events such as the Vienna Game City or the Sound Frame festival.

Actors

We managed to interview a great variety of actors from all different production phases and fields. The game ecosystem gives room to a wide range of actors and company sizes: there are around 90 game

enterprises in Austria, of which most are located in Vienna. Many employees work in very small enterprises and there many very young startups. Actors are, of course, also cooperating on international levels (IWI/WKO.2019).

We talked to three different game studios: a young female grassroots startup located in Vienna, a medium-sized company also located in Vienna, and one of the biggest players worldwide, from which we conducted an interview outside the EU, talking with a staff member based in Canada.

Apart from game studios, we also talked to related actors from universities and research associations, funding structures, art, and other companies that form part of the games sector (e.g. musical and sound producers for games or XR professionals). The field is generally very interdisciplinary and combines technology, art, and business. Actors are often highly skilled and educated, have university degrees, and have extensive work experience in the sector.

Figure 30. Vienna games sector—different actors

There is a high degree of labour division in the field of games. Teams need employees specialised in programming and developing, art and design, music, legal experts and business managers, publishers, marketing and PR professionals, and so on. The smaller the company, the more versatile the tasks and the more skills are asked from each employee.

The medium-sized company that we interviewed, for example, has 30 employees and creates and produces games. Some tasks are outsourced, such as music, sound, and distribution. Apart from developing their own games, they develop products for other companies, often bigger international players. The company also supports young startups and is connected to local associations, schools, and communities. Professionals are also often involved in teaching.

Almost all actors we interviewed in Vienna knew each other and had friendly relationships. However, we also interviewed people from international media companies in Canada and Germany, to gain the

input of actors not based in, but related to, the Vienna gaming sector, and to hear the perspectives of bigger players, as in Austria there are no major players like Ubisoft or Sony.

Gamescom, for example, is the biggest event for the gaming community in the world; our interviewee called it a “festival.” It connects all important players, serves as a marketing and networking platform, offers academic and professional discussions, and is open to the public. Publishers and producers from all over the world meet there, present their new games, and exchange knowledge. Our Viennese interview partners were also at Gamescom, a fact which demonstrates the importance both of Gamescom and of networks within the games community.

We also talked to an actor in the archiving phase: a researcher in the field of critical games studies who is also a game developer and active in various networks and communities. Finally, we interviewed people from funding structures that support the local games sector.

3.5.2 Relationships between actors

Skills, high education, and years of work experience seem to be crucial components of power relations. Highly trained staff can even count as a USP. Even smaller companies or entrepreneurs can negotiate lucrative trading actions if they can provide highly specialised services. Local developers we interviewed referred to their business relations with larger international players. Firstly, they developed technological infrastructure (such as programmes, engines) for other companies, which is a task that can only be done by a few highly skilled professionals on the market. Secondly, they developed their own niche games and needed to deal with larger publishers in the phase of distribution.

The distribution phase is dominated by a concentration of big, powerful players. Publishers like Sony, Nintendo, and Ubisoft do not only publish and distribute games from other developing companies but also produce games on their own. Products developed by bigger players—often referred to as AAA games—can be budgeted at triple-digit millions of dollars and are produced by hundreds of employees over years. Smaller companies do not have these high investment sums but rather count on their niche knowledge, creativity, and USP. Still, SMEs often rely on publishers for distributing their games all around the world. Thereby, smaller players need to comply with the rules and contracts of the bigger ones.

Nevertheless, the relationships between smaller and bigger players are not seen as threats by the actors but as part of a functioning, healthy ecosystem. The German Game Association, for example, endorses the establishment of new branches by major publishers in Germany, as this can lead to a bigger talent pool, more job opportunities, and the local accumulation of knowledge and skills. Employees do not rely on permanent positions; it is quite common to change jobs and places within in the sector.

Legal contracts must be negotiated from the beginning of the project, in the phase of creation. SMEs and self-employees may also be at a disadvantage as there is currently no collecting society or

licencing association comparable to that of the music sector. Therefore, legal issues must be negotiated by individuals themselves. As the game sector involves a series of different, highly complex legal frameworks (e.g. international law, copyright, right of distribution), actors must be well-informed and approach legal experts in this field. One of our interview partners is a legal expert and the head of a university programme for games and business. He is currently advising the national licencing association for authors, musicians, and composers with respect to the gaming sector. There is, however, no definitive solution for actors in the field of games, and legal issues remain an issue that needs to be solved individually.

The next point refers to reputation and relation management. Visibility, reputation, and constant networking lead to more powerful positions. Therefore, actors team up, find their own associations, networks, and festivals, and enhance their local visibility. Most interview partners complained about a lack of visibility: the Viennese game sector is not very well known and sometimes even underestimated in terms of local employment, revenue numbers, and its talent pool, which could also be helpful to related sectors. However, there are not too many game developers located in Vienna; consequently, the few professionals are even more likely to be overlooked, as in places where there are more professionals, as for example in Barcelona, Berlin, or Copenhagen. One interview partner told us that “the bigger the institution, the more they hire people from outside because of the prestige of hiring someone international.” Still, local initiatives for networking in and around Vienna such as XR Vienna, Subotron, and the CIVA festival help actors to team up and enhance their visibility, which can also lead to more power.

Barriers to entry are not characterised by a large number of competitors but rather by a very high level of skills, education, and work experience. Companies are constantly looking for highly skilled staff with years of work experience. Our interview partner from Ubisoft told us that there are hardly any jobs offered at the junior level, and work experience in the sector is crucial for employers.

Another barrier to entry in the sector, from an entrepreneurial perspective, is the founding phase. Games are high-risk products and often need two or three years to be developed. There is no guarantee of success. Hence, founders need decent seed capital as well as a large amount of luck to be able to repay the credit. European countries, regions, and cities pursue different strategies to support founders. For example, the business agency in Vienna helps startups and schools encourage their students to found their own business during their studies, through specialised career centres.

Table 52. Fitting the case within the typology matrix

GPN phase	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation	Creators			Creators	
Production	Creators/ suppliers	Suppliers	Suppliers	Suppliers/ Strategic partners (private sector/ Customers	
Distribution	Distributors	Distributors	Distributors	Distributors	
Exchange	Consumers	Consumers	Consumers	Consumers/ Customers	

Archiving	Creators/ Distributors				
Network level					Multiple actors

As the scheme above shows, the creation phase can be located on a local but also a global level, as there are co-creation activities with actors from all around the world; this global character also applies to the production phase. Games are usually distributed and exchanged all around the world. Only the archiving phase remains on a local level: creators and distributors do not grant access to their products because of copyright issues and mostly store them locally. The network level shows the prevalence of multiple horizontal actors.

Instead of one archetypical typology of the Viennese games sector, there is a plurality of different constellations of production phases, actors, and activities, depending on the size and specialisation of the actors, and the kind of games produced in this field. This example shows the typology of a game that was produced by a SME gaming company based in Vienna and distributed all over the world. In the creation phase, it is the creators that prevail, and they are to be found at the local or regional level. There are some co-creation activities with other international actors in the creation phase.

As soon as we enter the next phase, production, there are more suppliers involved, as, for example, informatics experts, graphic designers, animation specialists, and musicians. They can be found in and around Vienna but also at all other levels, particularly in the global level as the strategic partners in the private sector, and they share the matrix space with customers. In the distribution phase, distributors are at every level, as it is consumers in the next phase who share their position with customers at the global level. On the one hand, there are powerful actors on a global level, such as large publishers, online platforms, and console companies that distribute the game all over the world. On the other hand, there are more local events like fairs, festivals, and exhibitions that address a more local audience. The archive phase is occupied by creators and distributors, the two categories of actors who engage in the archiving of the games.

At the network level, the prevailing spatial scales with reference to lead actors are the local and regional, where the creators are the lead actors, and the global, where the lead actors are the distributors.

3.5.3 Socio-cultural embeddedness

Despite being a global and digital sector, actors and activities are always located at a specific place and relate to its socio-cultural surroundings. There are various ways in which a place and its socio-cultural surroundings can interact with the medium of games.

- 1) The content and the aesthetics of the game itself can refer to specific places. For example, the story plot of *The Lion's Song*, a game produced by the Viennese company Mi'pu'mi, refers to

Austria and to local history, and it uses aesthetic expressions from Viennese Art history and classical local music.

“The game takes place in the age of Wiener Moderne; in the beginning of the 20th century, there was a lot of knowledge in sciences and culture in Austria. One episode is about a female mathematician, who tries to succeed in a male world in the beginning of the 20th century. And she can only achieve to succeed when she dresses as a man and then shows her male colleagues that she is a good mathematician. And she has a lot of success.”

Characters can also be inspired by specific socio-culturally assignable identities. One of our interview partners mentioned the challenge of avoiding stereotypes yet creating characters that refer to specific places, cultures, and biographies. She told us:

“We had a character that came out, who is Argentinean, for example, but he’s Argentinean, who lives in L.A. So, he’s not going to be wearing traditional Argentinian garb, he’s going to be more modern. And we got backlash for that because it doesn’t look Argentinean.”

Another example is a studio which only created female characters for their game *Where is Eleanor Rose* and told a unique story plot inspired by their own experiences. Also, their new “burger game” was co-created with the local music band The Dives, who wanted to address the issue of sexist behaviour while dating. Hence, games themselves as a medium can show their socio-cultural embeddedness in many ways: *“We did like the Burger Project. It was also quite political and about actually sexism microaggression. So yeah, we kind of bonded with the band, in this regard the female group.”*

- 2) The city of Vienna itself, and the lay public benefit, from cultural events: art events such as the CIVA festival or festivals such as the Vienna Game City are open to the public and are without entrance fees. The wide range of cultural events enhances quality of life by offering recreational pleasure and inspiration.
- 3) Game producers and related actors also act as creative think tanks and as inspiration for other sectors. Visual digital art can inspire future visions, push limits, and break rules.

Even within the sector itself, there are spillovers between XR, AR, VR, film, and media. Apart from related sectors, there are cross-sectoral spillovers and co-creation activities with other sectors; for instance, one of our interview partners developed apps and programmes for a nature reserve so that its visitors can experience nature with augmented reality.

Despite being a rather new medium, games have developed various genres and even certain aesthetic canons. Games may vary with regard to their purpose: there are, for example, educational games, serious games, and leisure games, as well as games for specific age groups and games that can be played alone or with a team. The content and story plot themselves also refer to different genres such as e-sports, emotional games, ego shooter games, and science-fiction.

Games usually target audiences all around the world, and the game community itself influences the production of games. Gamers give feedback, criticise, communicate their wishes, and even co-create with developers. The large influence of gamers themselves is one of the most interesting changes over time, as media is becoming more and more interactive and gamers can communicate their opinions in a more direct way.

3.5.4 Dynamics: transformations over time

The COVID-19 pandemic has had both positive and negative effects on the games sector. On one hand, home offices complicated the processes of teamwork, and smaller companies especially had difficulties in presenting their new products or doing pitches, which are hard to do online. The e-sports area experienced stagnation as there was suddenly a lack of sponsors and financial problems resulted. Furthermore, game events had losses, with some events not making it through the crisis. Other negative effects were supply bottlenecks and rising prices for technological products such as computer chips.

However, the positive effects outweighed the downsides as games have always been digital and, according to one of our interviewees, have a “target group, which can also play independently from physical places. Especially during the lockdowns it was a great opportunity for entertainment.” He added that the number of gamers has significantly increased.

Societal impacts of the production networks of the Viennese Games Sector

Economic impact

Despite having a continuous growth potential, the economic impact of the national games sector remains modest. One of our interviewees explained the situation as follows:

“It is a small sector, to be honest. We have about 500 jobs in Austria, allocated to 90 firms. There are a lot of self-employees, and we have a yearly turnover of ca. 25 mill (Euros) and a value creation of 50 Mio., generated by the sector. Which is very little in fact. There is a lot of potential. There is a lot of investment, also from the state.”

Currently, there is no big international studio in Austria, and the job market is rather small in comparison to other countries. The state and the city of Vienna, as with its Vienna Business Agency, invest in startups and businesses. There are programmes, consultations, and some schools and universities specialised in relevant areas, but there is a lack of specialists. The crucial point relates to retaining and attracting specialists, as one interviewee explains:

“There is value creation in so far as the sector creates jobs and pays taxes, just as anywhere else. But it is a global sector. And one needs to support—and the business agency does that in many ways—and try to get excellent staff into our country and keep them. And we also need to keep the experts, which have been schooled here but went abroad to earn a better salary, just because it is more profitable... if you go to England, France or Canada. IT education is a

big thing, there is a lack of specialists in Austria. And you get paid a lot. Not just in the games sector. It is a difficulty to keep the people in the local areas, so they earn good money here and also pay taxes here.”

On the one hand, it is important to keep the schooled staff in the sector itself; IT jobs in other sectors are often even higher paid than in the games sector itself (e.g., IT developers for bank or insurance companies). On the other hand, it is important to retain value creation on a local level, supporting local businesses and the funding of new startups. The local settlement of subsidiaries from bigger international companies could also boost the local sector:

A healthy market can only function, when there are bigger, smaller and medium-sized companies; we actually have a problem as the big ones are not here yet. They must either grow or settle here. (...) and if bigger studios would open a subsidiary here it would be good, because even if the owners are not in Germany, the investment takes place here in Germany, the know-how comes, because people live here, exchange...

In order to focus more on the economic potential in Austria and the local game sector, countermeasures need to be taken, as one interviewee says:

The European Union thinks it has already lost the game, and we are about to lose the second, the third game as well. (...) I keep saying: you can't win Formula1 with an old VW Bus. We need to create tax models that make more sense, that we have tax return models and tax repaid models, ... well, they can be connected to the claim that the value creation must remain in the country and the jobs must be done here. There is no other solution for that.

Considering the different production phases, the activities with the biggest economic impact take place in the production phase and often concern business-to-business contracts. Many local developer companies also produce and sell content (e.g., characters, engines, and programmes) to other companies. In comparison to other CCIs, the distribution and exchange phases do not strongly relate to their spatial surroundings as games are most often downloaded online from large international platforms.

Another interesting perspective is the unimportance of economic aspects for many actors in this field. Interview partners stressed the Viennese attitude—“some Viennese creatives say that earning is secondary, the product is the only thing that counts. That’s the Viennese way”—and said that many experts rather embrace the artistic parts of the job and neglect economic or legal issues. To that extent, one of the aims of the University Programme “Interactive Media & Games Business” is to underline the importance of the economic aspects. As there are no big companies in Vienna, many professionals are self-employed, have founded their own business, lead a company, or employ others. It is thus very important for professionals in the local games sector to gain business skills.

Social impact

Gaming can be a social activity and, especially during the pandemic, this enabled users to keep in touch with their social surroundings and experience a contrast to everyday life: “*Nowadays, the social*

element of games is prevailing; to stay in contact with friends and family; (during the lockdown) you could escape home and visit other universes. You could not go on holiday, but you could travel to another country with your grandma, your children and your friends. People have used it a lot,” said one of our interviewees.

A large number of people play games on smartphone apps, on consoles, or on PCs, but the image of playing games is not always favourable when it comes to social considerations. The Viennese Game City Festival was founded to raise awareness among citizens and provide information to concerned parents. *“We do not foster prohibition, but we offer educational work,”* explains one interviewee: *“There is an area by WienXtra, an area for families and children; specialised professional educators, who know the subject perfectly well, can answer questions by parents. This makes the Game City special, the approach of giving information on the medium.”* He further said that there are of course positive and negative parts of gaming. On the one hand, it can support learning and skill development. On the other hand, one can become addicted to it. Therefore, it is important to openly talk about the opportunities and risks of gaming.

There are also prevalent stereotypes of gamers as *“white, young, socially not so talented [men]. Yes, that’s the image of a game developer. And this image is so strong, it also influences a little bit, who wants to strive for this career. This results into marginalisation and diversity issues.”* It is a fact that there are hardly any women working in the sector. In our interview with other female professionals, we also heard about their discrimination experiences or the dual burden of being a mother and a self-employed developer at the same time. It is still the exception rather than the norm to work as a female professional.

Games can also function as mental game changers and foster social equality, as their characters and story plots can express equality and social justice.

There are some associations founded by actors of the Viennese community, such as XRVienna, Pioneers of Game Development Austria (PGDA), and Subotron. There are also initiatives by public bodies such as Vienna Game City or the Viennese Business Agency supporting the image and actors of the sector. One of our interviewees talked about her motivations in founding the community:

We try to make people talk. And at the same time, we wanted the community to be about the users as well because we also saw that users didn’t know what to expect from the technology. A lot of them were afraid. (...) I would say that they overall benefit; for all of us is the fact that we know that we have a support group. And also, a community acts as a hub, you know, like for example, people would write us and say, Hey, I met someone that was talking about this during the event. Could you connect us with this person?

Therefore, communities and associations in the Viennese game sector have the functions of connecting, networking, motivating, exchanging experience, and informing interested users and costumers. Among local actors, the relationships seem to be friendly and supportive.

Cultural impact

Fairs and festivals are important events that bring gamers and developers together physically, and not simply online. One interviewee from Gamescom, the biggest games event in the world, in Germany, told us about the local cultural impact of the event: *“The city is living Gamescom. When you are out, you don’t just see posters but also visitors dressed as cosplayers running through the city; the city identifies with the games culture for a week.”* The gaming culture can be aesthetically expressed with clothes, makeup, language, and verbal expressions or music. Even our habitus is affected by game culture, as many users play games on their smartphones on their way to work.

Gaming is a new cultural activity that is becoming increasingly more integrated into everyday life. It is a form of media consumption and competes with other media such as television, radio, and books. The city of Vienna has hosted an annual games event since 2008 and even offers the city hall as an attractive and representative venue. Currently, about 80,000 visitors join Vienna Game City each year. The event is free and offers room for 100 exhibitors. *“For the city of Vienna, it can be good for the image, I think. And it is for free, they want everybody to have some beautiful time. And it is also beneficial for the economy of the city,”* says the organiser of Vienna Game City. There is also cooperation with local and indie game developers, public radio FM4, local educational institutions, and academia.

Game developers and creatives in related areas such as virtual art, VR, XR, and AR often act in niches and can be seen as courageous and innovate pioneers. These fields can function as avant garde think tanks for inspiration, as they show utopias, dystopias, and alternative opportunities and introduce new aesthetic canons. It is not rare to see niche cultures gain greater attention, *“e.g., regarding e-sports. It has not been there for just 5 years, but much longer. But it happened in niches, where it was not perceived. By now, it takes place in stadiums and gets streamed, even on television. There is a lot of attention.”* The same interviewee also highlighted the pioneer and avant garde character of the games community:

“And often, communities of the games culture are an important part of avantgarde. Its them who develop culture, who are the driver for culture. A very exciting culture, especially because of the globality of the games sector and the globality of the games culture it often comes to the intertwining of exciting cultural expressions that mix with each other. Especially the part of the Asian area which connects with the western culture. E.g., anime and manga. These are fields, which are especially exciting, and they are often related to places and play a role in cities; For example, places, where e-sports tournaments take place or where streaming studios and the whole culture of creator are.

Actors within the games sector are open to new innovative ideas and technologies and often cooperate with other artistic genres and institutions. A Vienna-based virtual artist hosting the CIVA Festival and sound: frame festival cooperates with game developers, cinemas, traditional public theatres, universities, media, and museums. She has been organising the sound: frame festival for over 10 years now and is a pioneer contributing to the local creative think tank.

Policy implications

The results of the fieldwork on networks in the Viennese game sector is a case study and therefore cannot be generalised; its issues and policy implications may only have local validity and not extend to the entire European games sector. The opinions of our interview partners may also contrast with actors to whom we did not speak. However, by also talking to international actors such as Ubisoft in Canada and Gamescom in Germany, we were able to enlarge the perspectives of the case study.

Having asked each interview partner about problems, chances, policy issues, and ideas for possible solutions, we provide below a list of issues that seem relevant for the sector.

- **Keeping and attracting highly qualified staff**
As there is a shortage of IT professionals in general, the sector is competing with other sectors to keep and attract staff. The local educational system for relevant jobs appears to be in good order. Hence, there could be incentives to encourage highly qualified staff who were locally trained to stay and work in the sector.
- **Attract bigger firms to settle here**
A healthy ecosystem for game companies ideally consists of locally embedded larger-, medium-, and smaller-sized companies. The problem is that the biggest tech companies are still located outside of Europe. Consequently, the knowledge and the deep talent pool are also located elsewhere. Therefore, the establishment of subsidiary companies from large international tech companies could enrich the local networks.
- **Support startups and the funding of new businesses**
The games sector is a comparably young sector and, especially in Austria, the ecosystem consists of many SMEs and entrepreneurs. As the sector cannot yet offer a wide range of jobs to employers, professionals need to start their own businesses. The funding of innovative, creative startups can also enrich related sectors such as AR and XR.
- **More visibility for local professionals**
Apparently, Vienna is not specifically well-known for its game sector, and as there are only a few medium-sized and small companies, there is not enough visibility for local professionals. It sometimes occurs that local customers prefer to engage international staff, not because of the quality of the work but to address the lack of visibility.
- **Foster research on the sector**
As video games are a rather new cultural product that for a long time were not taken seriously as an art form or sector, the discipline of game studies is yet to mature. Research could, for example, include investigating the socio-cultural and economic impacts of games, as well as their use, aesthetics, and reception.

- **Enhance the full potential**

Games are not simply an entertaining product but can also be helpful for other needs, skills, and sectors, such as education and health. Furthermore, technological knowledge and skills gained in this sector can also be applied to other related IT fields such as AR, VR, XR, IT, and visual arts. Hence, the highly creative and innovative potential of the games sector have a beneficial cross-sectoral effect and support the entire technology and arts sector.

- **Other tax models to keep the value creation here**

In comparison to other regions, local tax models may seem rather unattractive to the business strategies of large tech companies and publishers.

- **Clarify copyright legislation for licensing associations**

In comparison to the collecting societies and licencing associations of the music and literature sectors, the game sector still needs to find new ways of establishing useful legal frameworks that can enable collecting societies such as the Austrian AKM or the German GEMA to become attractive partners for professionals regarding copyright, reproduction, and distribution rights.

- **Encourage gender and racial equality**

There is a lack of women and ethnic and racial minorities in the games sector. Most professionals are young, white, highly educated man. Reasons for these inequalities may be manifold. Negative effects are the exclusion and discrimination of staff, leading to a negative image, and shortages of professionals in the sectors.

- **Improve employment conditions**

The games sector also has a bad reputation when it comes to employment conditions and the exploitation of staff with endless working hours before deadlines, high pressure, and a lack of work-life balance. These circumstances have a deterrent effect on up-and-coming professionals, leading employees to quit the sector and leading to an even larger shortage of specialists. Innovative and friendly employment conditions are a good solution but more an exception than the norm.

Apart from these specific issues, there are some more general policy implications that apply to the games sector. Firstly, games are high-risk products, as their production requires significant resources and there is no ultimate guarantee of success. Producing a game usually takes two to four years and the collaboration of many highly trained professionals from different areas: developers, designers, project managers, musicians and composers, legal experts, and marketing specialists. Consequently, funding the production of a new video game involves a high financial investment, yet it is hard to tell in advance whether the global gamer community will embrace it.

One interview partner referred to the Finnish model of funding the games sector:

“15 to 20 years ago, Finland has started to publicly invest into this area and is now very successful among European nations with their model. What they did is: they bundled funding,

which have already been there, into one fund. And with the help of public support, they have introduced quality criteria and juries select projects. They are then paired with equity capital and equity investors do not only have the opportunity to invest into one project, but they can also minimize risks and invest. For example, the fund has more projects, and they get the revenue or a return of their investment. And projects which are successful need to reinvest a certain part into the fund again. Now the fund is a perpetuum mobile. So, it feeds itself.”

Considering game funding, the affiliation of the sector is also problematic: which sector do games belong to, and who is responsible for supporting them? Do they, for example, belong to the IT, arts, media, technology, or entertainment sectors? In the Viennese funding system, they usually do not belong to the art sector and are not funded by the public body MA8 but by the business agency, which is more focused on the industrial sector.

On a European level, game projects are often allocated to the audiovisual sector and receive funds that also support films, for example. However, games are different. It is one of the biggest growing CCIs and apparently earns more revenues than the music sector; for this reason, and because there are many related IT sectors that will benefit from it, there should be a specific focus on the games sector.

The next point addresses national peculiarities within Europe. There are European countries such as Sweden, Germany, Romania, Spain, and Poland that have a more developed games sectors than others. The latter, for example, is well known for its successful game *The Witcher*, produced by the Polish CD Project RED and written by the Polish author Andrzej Sapkowski.

In some areas there are more jobs, better knowledge, a bigger talent pool, and subsidiaries of large international players like Ubisoft in Madrid. In Europe, there are currently many medium-sized firms and associations that function as key stakeholders. Local actors have found their niches in developing high-quality products with unique advanced technology or creative story plots and characters in order to succeed on a global market. Another interesting finding is the high level of social interaction between actors from the sector, which shows that they are well-connected with each other. They are also highly educated and know how to express their needs. Many associations, on the local, national, and international levels, are founded by professionals themselves.

Still, the biggest media stakeholders are not located inside of Europe. Powerful key stakeholders and gatekeeping actors in the sector are usually publishers, especially major publishers such as Sony, Nintendo, and Microsoft, with headquarters in Japan and the USA. Reasons for this may lie in the different tax environments: in most European countries, taxes may not be as convenient as in other countries, and the power of large Asian and American media companies have historical roots. Other reasons may involve different legal systems when it comes to copyright issues. In the USA, for example, copyright can be sold; in Austria creatives cannot sell it, and the legal system may appear stricter. Furthermore, staff is more expensive in Europe, and there are higher standards for work-life balance.

PART 4. Conclusions

4.1 Conclusions

The global production network approach has allowed us to analyse the audiovisual sector through new research optics. Applying it to the analysis of the selected case studies, we traversed the journey from idea to audience to archive, seeking to enable the creation of new policies to make this sector more sustainable over time.

A stage-by-stage analysis of the value chain convinced us that the film industry, television and radio, and games were appropriate to examine through the GPN method because they have the characteristics of classical industrial production: mass production, mass consumption, and new communication technologies supporting the mass distribution of the content created. Yet at the same time, these are industries creating unique content through a chain of authors. Very often there is an overflow of labour, ideas, and resources between the different audiovisual markets, which stimulate the emergence of clusters and networks.

In all the case studies examined, the entry point was the national level, but the network of companies has European and, in some phases (most often distribution), global dimensions.

The phase-by-phase examination enabled us to make conclusions for each of the audiovisual industries.

In the case study of the production company KLAS Film, dedicated to the film industry, the different phases were clearly delineated and consistent. The defining role of the creation phase emerged, in which the development of the script, participation in pitching, and finding financial support (national and international) determine the fate of the future co-production. Here, the leading role of the producer and established relationships of trust and authority proved crucial.

In the two EBU cases, we observed something different. In the Eurovision Song Contest network, some phases were non-linear, as they took place in synchrony at both the national and European levels. The broadcasting of the event is also an interesting phenomenon in which three industries—music industry, live performance event, and live television broadcast—intersect.

In the radio industry, through music exchanges between member countries, we have found that the national archiving phase is not at the end of the global production network (unless it is a Gold Fund or live broadcast) but immediately after production. This fact stems from the technology and very nature of radio activities. In the games industry we also found out that the archive is not at the end of the value chain, but it becomes a source of material and ideas for new content creation (cinema, games). The ability to upload games on platforms for subsequent use produces good long-term revenues (TV).

The research revealed interesting and complex relationships in the networks' governance in the four case studies. As already noted, in classic global production networks one firm most often captures almost all of the created value. Our findings show specificities of the networks that differ from that common type.

In the case study of the production firm KLAS Film, the leader firm coordinates the network. It is a producer-managed chain in which the leader firm does not concentrate the value created in the network for itself. There are many other players at the distribution and exhibition phases who can certainly assign value.

In the two EBU network cases, we have found other specificities. In the Eurovision Song Contest case, the leader firm is the EBU, which coordinates and creates the rules for the contest; however, its power is not strictly hierarchical but highly dispersed. Each country and each public broadcaster participating in the network creates and receives value. The case of the EBU music exchange is similar. In both of them, one cannot see the classic asymmetric capture of economic value by the leader firm. Moreover, economic value is rarely the leading value here, as most often the cultural and social dimensions of the created product or service are the priority (as attributes of public good).

The case study of the Viennese games sector shows the dialectical relationship between the local and the global. Many actors within the network were located in the city of Vienna: games companies, developers, associations, and artists. Although actors are embedded in local surroundings, they interact on a bigger scale with stakeholders, customers, and suppliers from all around the globe and never think within national boundaries. Games are meant to be distributed and consumed on a global scale. Hence, there always remains a certain level of local embeddedness even while acting on a global scale. In regards to power concentration, a few major companies control the market. Smaller studios must find their highly specialised niches and often interact with bigger companies, as when majors outsource specific activities. The relationships between the actors seemed cooperative and balanced on a local scale but rather imbalanced and much more competitive on a global one. Working conditions are likely to be precarious, and there is a lack of women and minorities in the sector.

Local policy includes well-established funding structures with a special focus on company startups and networking events. Games are a high-risk product because they takes years and a high economic investment to produce. As games are a rather new sector within the CCS, the archiving phase was hard to identify; there are hardly any archives or museums for games culture, at least not open to the public, and academic disciplines such as games studies are still in their early stages. Nevertheless, the game sector is the fastest-growing one among the CCS, and it has significant creative, economic, and social potential.

All four case studies have a national entry point (Sofia or Vienna), but their networks have a transnational scope: while they take place in the EU, some of the phases and participants cross EU borders and have global dimensions.

What we learned about the Audiovisual industries in Europe through the GPN Approach

This study has increased our learning about value creation in the global production networks of the audiovisual industries and about their geographic spread and embeddedness. We also learned about the roles and the capacities of audiovisual actors, and of their partners, suppliers, and ecosystems, including national institutional frameworks, to operate within a dynamic political and economic context.

Research on the four case studies illuminated audiovisual companies or organisations at the micro level and allowed us to contextualize their global production networks in specific cultural and economic environments. We could reveal and describe how the network actors—lead firms, strategic partners and suppliers, public and private, as well as the state—interact in the network, in the context of the existing national and European regulations and local historical and cultural conditions and attitudes. Applying the GPN approach to these case studies generated useful insights for understanding both the general and the specific aspects of these industries.

On the global production chain and the actors

In the case study of the Eurovision Song Contest (ESC), where Bulgarian National Television is an entry point, there are synchronized actions at the national and European levels to create the common final product of the network: the ESC live event. Thus, there can be several lead actors participating in one phase at the same time, at both the European and national levels; however, these participants are leading in a specific phase and time, while for the whole network the leading company is EBU. The creation activities take place simultaneously in many geographical locations, in the country hosting the annual contest as well as in each participating country, one of which is Bulgaria.

The television contest has several aspects as a cultural product: as a stage product, a television product, and a music industry product at the same time. This makes the visualization of the network very complex. The final common product is the television contest, and hence the focus is on live television broadcasting. Examining the contest through the network phases of value creation, we observed an interesting overlap: the live television broadcast of the contest can be displayed simultaneously in two GPN phases the production of a stage product and the simultaneous broadcasting exchange of this product across many countries in Europe and the world, as it is broadcasted in Australia, Canada, Israel, and beyond.

Many actors participate in several GPN phases. In the Eurovision case study, a company that participates in the production subsequently participates in the distribution of the product. This is because the distribution phase, including marketing, is digitised, and because of the very functionality of the company.

The situation is different in the film industry. While it is natural for the producer (KLAS Film in the case study) to be involved or have a normative relationship to each phase, for other network actors, reprising multiple roles can be unhealthy or unproductive. This situation reflects the small market, the lack of clear regulation in the field, who could exercise this profession, or the education and expertise required for this type of activity. In this industry, the producer and director are commonly one person,

that the producer and distributor are one person (but a different company), or that the distributor and cinema owner are one person. Too much overlap in these responsibilities is not productive.

The audiovisual industries require a high level of interaction (network embeddedness) when creating a common product or project. Strong partnerships are based on a common idea, concept, and aesthetics, for example, interaction and network embedding in the creation phase. Therefore, the effect of GPN in value creation is particularly visible in the film industry at the idea and project-development stage. Involvement in pitching sessions and professional meetings, as well as in finding an international sales agent and a distributor during the creation phase, is vital for the project. These partnerships are a prerequisite for fundraising and the financial sustainability of the project and co-producers' network.

Thus, through the GPN approach, three phases of the value chain stand out as value creators: the creation phase in the film industry, through expanding geography and participation in forums that add value to the project.

In the radio industry, it is the role of the audio-archive (or resource) that has a role in the post-production phase and adds value. This means that the archiving phase, thanks to digitisation, has expanded its functions beyond the classical archive. In fact, the audiovisual archives and libraries create conditions for launching a new creation through the purchase of footage, music recordings, characters, and stories. They create the possibility of reusing digital (and digitised) audiovisual and music content for new projects. Film archives, television video libraries, streaming platforms, music sharing, and video games show proof of this new value creation.

Using the GPN approach has also highlighted some areas of conflict, unresolved issues, and misconceptions. Bulgarian National Television and Bulgarian National Radio (both entry points in two of the case studies), as well as KLAS Film, are part of a national context defined by specific cultural, historical, and social factors. The economic and democratic transition in Bulgaria in the past 30 years has carried some remnants from a past institutional culture of governance in the field. There is a strong tendency towards financial and institutional centralisation in cultural policies and governance. Whereas the public television and radio are directly subsidised by the Ministry of Culture, the National Film Centre Executive Agency distributes public funding for private film producers. However, the NFC is also subordinate to the central government. The overall cultural and audiovisual ecosystem is constrained by a lack of fiscal decentralization as well as by the absence of alternative and regional financial instruments.

At the EU level, the film industry benefits from a special exception rule and receives public support at all phases of the value chain. National regulations may differ in the EU Member States, but in all EU Member States, international co-productions are considered as value-creating and hence receive support from the EU Media sub-programme, from the Eurimages fund (of CoE), from national and regional film funds, and from incentives, as well as private sources.

The national regulation in the film industry in Bulgaria is in line with most EU regulations, but it conflicts with the European taxation instruments and hence needs revision. For example, a tax rebate

applied nationally to US-owned film producers is not a tax incentive *per se*. "Globally, it is an influx of European capital into the US industry through co-financing initiatives" (Morawetz et al., 2007, cited in Coe, 2015, p. 495). The Bulgarian film case shows that European policies cannot be applied in the same way in every national audiovisual market.

On the network embeddedness

The case studies of the European Broadcasting Union's Eurovision Song Contest (television industry) and the Music Radio Exchange Platform (radio industry) described activities related to the common mission of public service broadcasters, which is based on trust and on common aesthetic and cultural values. The integration of values and mission determines the power distribution in these networks. Despite the clearly articulated role of the EBU as lead firm for Eurovision and Euroradio, with control of the concept, the rules, the evaluation, and the brand, all EBU members have creative and administrative freedom in creating their part of the cultural product. Each national public broadcaster is a strategic partner with free choice about the degree and form of participation in the network. The desire to preserve common cultural capital through the transfer of policies, knowledge, and technology also determines how value is created in these networks.

The embeddedness of production networks in the **audiovisual industries** shows some different features, which we detected in the case studies described in Part 3 of this report.

- Territorial embeddedness in the audiovisual industries is not limited to the context of the specific geographic location where the network is positioned. The technical possibility of unrestricted signal transmission (i.e. broadcasting) removes the limits on the territorial embeddedness of a particular television or radio network.

Access to television content is not geographically restricted to viewers of a single country. In this neoliberal market context, public service media (PSM) face not only national but also global competition in the global television content market. Moreover, commercial broadcasters whose content is mainly infotainment dominate there. The market for television content produced by national PSM directly competes also with non-linear media content such as on-demand delivery. In the television market, the content creators and rights holders are often large global players such as Netflix and HBO (SVoD), which are also available without subscription through OTT-type delivery. Therefore, territorial embeddedness is not limited to the local geography of product creation, and hence the service is extended along with the retransmission of the signal and the specific television content. The geographical embeddedness extends to those geographical locations where the audiences are.

- This almost unlimited territorial distribution of **audiovisual content (film, television content, radio content, computer digital games)** is also a form of societal embeddedness: because content becomes globally accessible, it also shapes global cultural, aesthetic, and moral values. These values are no longer linked to the traditions of a specific geographical place or society but are supranational. Thus, we are witnessing the formation of global

values in a generation of viewers. These can range from innocent fashion trends and musical tastes to destructive aspirations towards violence, aggression, and nihilism.

The selected case studies of the audiovisual sector revealed complex inter-linkages between the different stages and showed a complex geography of power. This also helped us to see common problems, and this means the possibility of common policies not only at the national level.

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Appendix A. Methodology

A1. Research methodology

1. Introduction

The general aim of the CICERONE research, and in particular of WP2, is to understand the role of Cultural and Creative Sector (CCS) in the local development of EU countries starting from the configuration and dynamics of their global production networks (GPNs). This work package is based on a case study approach combining quantitative with qualitative research. The former is aimed at positioning the sector along a number of dimensions, while the latter will uncover the more in-depth aspects of the GPNs of the selected industries. While the project adopts a prevailing qualitative approach, it also envisages secondary data analysis. The case study approach is coherent with the research aim because of its ability to cover both the phenomenon and its context.

This appendix presents the main methodological issues of the WP2, some of which have been pointed to at the beginning of the reports.

Methodology stands for the systematic examinations of procedures and modalities of explanation that are used for the analysis of empirical data³⁷.

In social sciences, empirical research may adopt a descriptive or an explorative logic; however, all research is always informed by a theoretical apparatus, even though the connection between theory and empirical research takes different connotations in the different disciplines/fields.³⁸ Notably, epistemology draws a distinction between explanation and comprehension. Explanation implies the search for a stable nexus of causality between two (or more) variables, independently from the social and historical context. The underlying assumption is that we should be able to identify universal laws explaining the nature of observations (like in the so-called hard sciences). Comprehension refers to the traditional Weberian conception of understanding the meaning of the action for social actors. Such a meaning is influenced by institutional, normative and cultural dimensions that are spatially and historically specific. Reality is not simply described, but it is read, analysed and interpreted.

In a situation where universal laws are inapplicable, the logic is to search for empirical generalizations. In order to move towards empirical generalization, social sciences make use of models or typologies starting from Weberian insights. Weber describes ideal types as 'mental constructs, formed by the analytical and one-sided 'accentuation of one or more points of view and by the synthesis of a great many diffuse, discrete, more or less present and occasionally absent concrete individual phenomena, which are arranged according to those one-sidedly emphasised viewpoints into a unified analytical

³⁷ Selvin, H. C. (1958). Durkheim's suicide and problems of empirical research. *American journal of sociology*, 63(6), 607-619.

³⁸ Rueschemeyer D. (2009) Usable Theory: Analytic Tools for Social and Political Research.

construct'.³⁹ Through ideal types, reality is recomposed and synthesized starting from classificatory categories, so to help researchers to identify dynamics and mechanisms that underlie social processes.

Traditionally, empirical research is based on either qualitative or quantitative methods (or both). The distinction between the two has a technical nature: the choice depends on many elements, such as the research questions, data availability or the approach that drives it.

2. The choice of the qualitative method: the Case study approach

Among many qualitative methodologies, case study research investigates in-depth into a real-life phenomenon by considering its situatedness and contextual embeddedness.⁴⁰ Such a case can be an individual, a group, an organisation, an event, a problem, or an anomaly.⁴¹ Contrary to the quantitative logic, the case is chosen because it is of interest⁴² or for theoretical reasons.⁴³ Unlike experiments, the contextual conditions are not delineated and/or controlled but are part of the investigation.

In the case study methodology, the selection of cases is a crucial phase, and generalization of results is mostly based on that. There are two modalities to select case studies:⁴⁴ random and information-oriented selection. Random selection is usually chosen to avoid systematic biases in the sample; in such circumstances, the sample size is decisive for generalization.

In social science research, cases are generally not randomly selected because it is difficult to in depth explore a huge sample. Moreover, random selection not necessarily provides informative cases, while in a research based on information-oriented selection of cases, the generalizability of results can be increased by the strategic selection of cases. As Flyvbjerg claims:

“When the objective is to achieve the greatest possible amount of information on a given problem or phenomenon, a representative case or a random sample may not be the most appropriate strategy. This is because the typical or average case is often not the richest in information. Atypical or extreme cases often reveal more information because they activate more actors and more basic mechanisms in the situation studied.”⁴⁵

Information-oriented selection of cases implies that case studies are selected based on the expectations about their insights into processes, agency, strategies (information content). The experiment in hard sciences can also be seen as an extreme example of information-oriented selected case studies.

³⁹ Weber, [1904] in Rossi P. (1974)(ed.) *Lo storicismo contemporaneo*. Loescher, Torino: 124-125.

⁴⁰ Ridder, H.G. (2017). The theory contribution of case study research designs. *Business Research*, 10(2), 281-305.

⁴¹ Burawoy, M. (2009). *The extended case method: Four countries, four decades, four great transformations, and one theoretical tradition*. Univ of California Press; Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London; Yin, R. K. (2014). *Case Study Research Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA

⁴² Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London

⁴³ Eisenhardt, K. M., & Graebner, M. E. (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), 25-32.

⁴⁴ Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2).

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* p.229

“Carefully chosen experiments, cases, and experience were also critical to the development of the physics of Newton, Einstein, and Bohr, just as the case study occupied a central place in the works of Darwin, Marx, and Freud. In social science, too, the strategic choice of case may greatly add to the generalizability of a case study.”⁴⁶

Cases bring new knowledge either because they have a strategic importance in relation to the general problem or because they help to test the validity of the theory. Moreover, case studies allow cross-country comparison: the different contexts shed light on different dynamics related to economic circumstances, national and local regulatory framework, labour market, local culture and know-how, and so on. According to Robinson⁴⁷ the choice of the territory assumed as the basis of the comparison (being it a nation, region or city) should be carefully chosen in relation to the single case study rather than assumed a priori.

3. Research design and research steps

As said, WP2 is based on a mixed methods approach of investigation. This means using both quantitative and qualitative tools; primary and secondary data allow a complex research design composed by several interconnected research dimensions: a sector description, an analysis for the identification of the case studies and the case studies themselves.

3.1. Sector description

Quantitative data was used to have a factual overview of European GPNs in CCS together with literature and desk analysis.

Literature analysis and quantitative (secondary) data were used to explore and describe the features of each sector, its quantitative consistence and its European production network, its role in the European economy, the territorial distribution of its companies and the typical business models.

1. Literature review – for each industry
 - a. Configuration of the Production Network (input-output structure) in the selected industry
 - b. Prevailing governance typology in each industry (e.g. power relationships, barriers to entry, value adding mechanisms, labour processes/skills ...) + possible governance typologies considering single interfirm relationships
 - c. Key socio-institutional dimensions affecting network configuration/dynamics (e.g. fiscal incentives, property rights, labour legislation, path dependent cultural aspects) at various levels (European, national, regional)

⁴⁶ *Ibid.* p226

⁴⁷ Robinson, J. (2011). Cities in a world of cities: The comparative gesture. *International journal of urban and regional research*, 35(1), 1-23.

- d. (possible) Changes over time (e.g. digitalisation, technologies, ...) + possible firms upgrading processes (value capture strategies)
- e. (possible) National variations and specificities (e.g. national funds that support the film industry)

2. Statistical mapping the PN of CCSs in Europe

Statistical data at the EU level (by Nuts 1, 2, 3 if possible) on number of firms, employment, VA, ... relative to the *different network phases* (e.g. creation, production, distribution, etc.) composing the PNs of the 8 selected industries

3.2. Case studies in WP2

One of the strengths of the research lies in the fact that the great variety of case studies share a common unit of analysis. This is the production network of actors, firms, organisations involved in projects, which is very much in line with a whole body of literature on forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. According to Watson (2012, p. 168), the benefits of a such project-based approach are:

“... first it moves beyond [solely] structural analyses to allow for an understanding of the importance of agency in project work; second it allows us to move on from firm-level analyses to develop an understanding of the complex social networks involved in [production networks]; and finally it moves on from research at the meso-level on inter- and intra-firm networks to provide micro-level analyses of project work.”⁴⁸

Such an approach enabled the whole research to take into account agency *and* structure as well as their interaction, thereby heeding the view of Powell and Smith Doerr⁴⁹ who conceptualise networks both as relational forms and structural ones.

As anticipated in *The Cicerone approach to production networks* section of this report, cases were selected on the basis of their informative power and of the theoretical expectations about their insights. Particularly, case studies represent a sufficient range of variation in terms of key business model characteristics, geographical span within the EU limits and cross the borders of European countries, finally and obviously they are accessible to researchers.

Such choices aim at bringing new knowledge on the contribution of the European CCS to local development, sustainability, social cohesion and (local) identity. Furthermore, as already discussed, an information-oriented selection of case studies increases the generalizability of results.

⁴⁸ Watson, A. (2012). Sociological Perspectives on the Economic Geography of Projects: The Case of Project-Based Working in the Creative Industries. *Geography Compass*, 6(10), 617-631, p. 618.

⁴⁹ Smith-Doerr L, Powell W (2005) Networks and Economic Life. In Neil Smelser and Richard Swedberg, eds. *The Handbook of Economic Sociology*, Russell Sage Foundation and Princeton University Press.

In details, theoretically based case study selection was grounded on the review of the existing literature on CCS and their organisational forms⁵⁰ assuming a novel viewpoint. Three common aspects underlie this choice.

- A. GPNs in the CCS, as in any other industries, are characterised by differential power relations. Powerful actors (the lead firm) are those who drive networks and make things happen: as explained, their ability derives from their control of key resources, namely physical, economic, technological but also social, political and immaterial ones. The control of resources however does not automatically imply that the actor is powerful until power is exercised. Rather than being matter of actors' position in the network (more or less marginal actors), power should be conceived as the capacity to concretely exercise control within it. Governance identifies the authority and power relationships that affect how resources – material, financial, human, etc. – are distributed and flow along the chain. Following Gereffi it is possible to distinguish between two typologies of networks: the producers- and the buyer- driven chains. Governance as drivenness embraces a broad idea whereby governance refers to the whole chain dynamics: this concept is meant to capture the power that lead firms exert over other participants and to highlight its ability to govern the chain by making decisions about where, how and by whom goods/services are produced. In the identification of concrete governance typologies characterising a specific sector, the concept of governance as drivenness is one important aspect⁵¹.
- B. Relationships between lead firms and the other actors in the network differ across industries due to the particular features of the products/services produced, to the production process and the organisation of that specific industry. The configuration and coordination of global production networks are also shaped by the expansion of demand and markets. Goods and services' demand needs to be created and sustained by final consumers and end users (i.e. think about the increased role of merchandising). It is therefore important to satisfy customer pressures, (i.e. price, quality), the so-called time to market (i.e. time imperative) as well as the basic access to the market and to new markets (i.e. in emerging economies). Finally, the choices and strategies of production networks are also influenced by financial considerations, which relate both to firms' activities and to their shift to non- manufacturing ones. Such aspects refer more to technical, organisational dimensions and demand that are shaped primarily by the industries' internal logic.
- C. As underlined, the innovativeness of the CICERONE project lies in the application of the GPNs perspective to the CCSs. Whilst a vast array of studies has concerned the manufacturing industry, considerably less attention has been devoted to the cultural and creative sector. The empirical work required by the project intended primarily to make a contribution to the understanding of the CCS considered by the project at European level. Nonetheless, the empirical research aimed also to account for the broad institutional context in which production networks operate. Institutions do not only influence chains' dynamics but should be considered constitutive of these networks in ways that are critical for understanding their

⁵⁰ Different disciplinary insights have been gathered from literature in business, economics, sociology, economic geography.

⁵¹ Greco, L. (2016) *Capitalismo e sviluppo nelle reti globali del valore*. Carocci, Roma

social and economic consequences: institutions were therefore not be considered external to the networks even though they are not strictly connected to inter-firms' relationships.

For each industry, case studies numbers range between two to four, according to the identified typologies, complexity of the case studies, availability of interviewees and so on.

3.3. Case studies analysis

The empirical research based on case studies (namely the production network of projects) was carried on through the exploration of the single network-nodes and their relationships. Qualitative data was used to produce novel knowledge in the field and constitute the base for further research.

The explicative power of the selected case studies lies in the fact that the analysis is able to produce a 'substantive' representativeness of the EU CCS rather than their statistical one; in other words, case studies analysis allows understanding dynamics, mechanisms, relationships, etc. useful for explaining the functioning of such sector.

After selecting case studies, the empirical investigation was carried out using interviews, observations, ethnographies, digital ethnographies. The key dimensions of the analysis are: the network configuration and its geographical footprint; the governance dimension (power relations; value creation); the variety of embeddedness forms; the impact on socio-economic development.

As already indicated, production networks are socially and territorially embedded, beyond their organisational embeddedness. Societal embeddedness places economic actions within a multilevel institutional and cultural framework. Territorial embeddedness appreciates the differing ways in which firms are anchored to different places and to its specific resources and features, for instance the local culture, labour forces, policies, raw materials and so on. Ultimately CCS industrial dynamics in Europe was analysed both in their ideal-typical sense (by accounting for the specific sector-level characteristics affecting inter-firm linkages) and with concern to the differentially embedded nature of their economic activities. Attention was paid also to the ways in which actors mobilize and deploy resource, forge alliance, shape regulatory structures through discursive constructions and mechanisms that legitimate the GPN configuration, i.e. eco labels, fair trade, ethical labour, environmentally friendly productions, etc. Consideration was also devoted to any relevant policy (or the lack of it) at the different stages in chain, which may affect the way in which the whole chain is configured. Policy analysis has looked at different kind of policies, i.e. cultural but also industrial as well as regulatory and trade policies. Additionally, policy and policy environment were addressed in their multiscale nature.

A unifying matrix focusing on the two key dimensions of governance (power) and spatial footprint allowed synthesizing the case study results by conducting a series of comparisons in different contexts. In addition, the systematization in the matrix is designed as a tool for policymakers in support of better CCS-relevant policies.

4. Research strategy

4.1. Preparing the interview

For each node of the production network, interviews were made to all the informed people that were considered suitable to understand the mechanisms at play in the node. The number of interviews was decided by each team according to the availability of interviewees and the information to be gathered. Three or four pilot interviews were recommended in order to recalibrate / reorganise the interview script; in some cases, interviewees were not available for the interview, but they were asked a number of key questions via mail: this solution was adopted if no alternative was possible. Empirically, the field was accessed through a company, which represents a node/phase in the network; starting from that, the whole network (both relations among phases and phases themselves) has been explored. At the beginning of each interview, the interviewer presented him/herself and presented the research. The interviewee was given a leaflet containing information on the research as well as on the specific role that the EU can play in this field. After the signature of a consent form on the part of the interviewee, the interviewer started recording the interview. Interviews were done in person or in videoconference when the situation required it.

Each case study gathered qualitative data on a number of topics, which are detailed in the next section containing the interview outline, namely:

- The interviewee profile
- The organisation profile
- The network configuration
- The governance structure and strategies
- The embeddedness
- Policy
- Contribution to development

4.2. Qualitative data gathering

All interviews were recorded with a digital recorder. Interviews were then transcribed *verbatim*, pointing out emotional status only if particularly relevant. Each interview was labelled and stored using all the following variables:

- Industry
- # case study
- Phase of the production cycle
- # interview (within the phase)
- Geography (Nuts3)
- # interview (within the sector)
- Date (DD/MM/YY)

4.3. Interviews coding

A two-step codification was used:

1. Codification of the interview according to the homogeneous excerpts on the basis of thematic areas identified for the research:
 - Network configuration → CODE: NET-CON
 - Spatial organisation of the networks → CODE: GEO
 - The governance of the network → CODE: GOVERN
 - Embeddedness → CODE: EMBEDD
 - Institutional conditions → CODE: INSTIT
 - Policy → CODE: POLICY
 - Contribution of the production network to the development of European regions → CODE: EU_DEVELOP
 - Any other relevant issue that we might "discover" → CODE: OTHER
2. Codification of all the excerpts in each of the previously identified thematic areas (input-output structure, its spatial organisation, governance, institutional conditions, role in the EU development, other) based on relevant analytical categories.
 - Ex. Mechanisms of value appropriation; modalities of cooperation among organisations; upgrading mechanisms, working conditions, social/cultural embeddedness; any other new element

A2. Interview outline

Profiling the case study

A first step in the interview outline was to profile the interviewee and her or his organisation, company, or agency.

Interviewee's profile

Themes to analyse:

- Position within the organisation/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the position
- Main responsibilities
- Years spent in the organisation/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the industry
- Years spent in the field
- Competences required for the job
- Any other relevant theme

- What is your job position within the organisation/agency/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this position?
- What are your main responsibilities?
- How many years have you been working in this organisation/agency?/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this industry?
- What are the main skills/competences required for your job?

Organisation profile

Themes to analyse:

- Brief history of the organisation
- Core business
- Legal nature of company
- Employees
- Any other relevant theme

- What does your organisation/agency/company/etc. do/develop?
- What is the main activity performed by your company/organisation/agency/etc.?
- What is your core business?
- Is your organisation/agency/company/etc. independent or is it a part of a bigger company? (if yes) how responsibilities with the headquarter are distributed?
- How many employees does your organisation/agency/company have?
- Can you briefly tell me about your or organisation/agency/company? (*gather some information on its history, key moments, etc.*)

Network configuration

The second step of the interview outline aimed at shedding light on the whole cycle of cultural production from creation to final users (actors involved, roles, geography). In what ways is the industry X articulated/organised? How does the division of labour occur in the industry? Who are the main actors? Their roles? The geography?

The sketch of a diagram together with the interviewee can be a very useful tool at this stage: we suggest to use a large sheet of paper and start with the interviewee in the middle; then add the other organisations/agencies/actors/... involved in the different phases (locate the phases at the corners of the paper). Use this diagram as a map throughout the whole interview.

- Among the projects (services/activities/goods/event) that you briefly presented us, let us consider now the chosen one (possibly it should be one that involves an extended/extra-local/European/international network). Please, help us to identify the whole cycle of cultural production and your role in it.
- Who are the actors that are involved, together with you, in the carrying out of your project (i.e., customers, intermediaries, consumers/audiences, etc.)?

Actors involved

Possible actors involved:

- Artists, composers, designers, creatives
- Producers
- Suppliers, impresarios
- Audience, customers
- Intermediaries, dealers, experts, critics
- Media, influencers
- Archivists
- Any other relevant actor

Themes to analyse for each actor:

- Description of the actors
(Who they are? Big or small organisations/groups, independent, subsidiaries...)
- Role played by the actor in the network
- Type of resources mobilized (financial, economic, reputational, technological resources...)
- Any other relevant theme

- Who do you work with?
- Who are the people that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Who are the suppliers that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Can you tell us more about them?
- (i.e. SME / large organisations, public/private, local/global, independent/subsidiaries, etc.)
- What kind of resources do they mobilize in the project?
- (i.e. a service, an idea, technical or professional knowledge, raw materials, a semi-product, a final product, financial assets, etc.)
- Who are your customers? or your audience?

- Do you sell directly to the final consumer?
- Are there any actors in your business that you would define as intermediaries? Why? For instance, because they help your product/you to be visible, or they “translate” your work for the audience, or they appreciate particularly your work.
- Is there anybody that helps you in promoting your products/projects? (e.g. art curators, advisors, critics, etc.)
- Do they have an impact on your business? How?
- What do they do precisely?
- What does their intermediation consist of?
- Could you give me an example of a situation in which intermediaries were useful to your business?
- How did you come in contact with this intermediary?
- How did they find you?
- Has your relationship with intermediaries changed over time? Why?
- Do media and influencers play a role in your business?
- How do they impact on your activities?
- How do they get to know you?
- Let us consider the social media. Are there any influencers on Instagram/Facebook/etc. that have an impact on your strategies/activities?
- Have your own accounts an impact?
- Do you use them to promote your project?
- Have you or has your organisation got an archive of your projects (creations/services/activities/products)?
- Have you or has your organisation been part of a show/exhibition/etc.?
- Does collecting exist as a practice in your business?
- (If yes), Who are the collectors? Does a collecting market exist?
- Who decides on what will be archived and in which form?
- Have your projects ever been part of a collection?
- Are there any museums/institutions particularly important in your sector that collect major/innovative works?

Spatial organisation

Themes to analyse:

- The geography of the network
- The issue of physical distance
- The management of distance (if relevant)
- The management of communication (if relevant)
- Any other relevant theme

- Where are the actors/organisations of the network located? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- (consider all the phases of the PN)
- Have you ever experienced any problem due to the distance? (for instance, dealing with something implying face-to-face communication; the need to check a process personally; ...)
- How do you communicate with the different actors in the network?
- Do you need to travel a lot?
- How is the geographical distance managed?

Governance

What kind of relationships govern and regulate the network organisation in the Industry X? What are the economic, socio-institutional, political aspects affecting inter-firms' dynamics?

Relations among network organisations

Themes to analyse:

- Type of relationships between actors (formal/informal)
- Decision-making process concerning the project. (who decides, autonomy / cooperation / subordination, participation)
- Existence of standards / conventions to follow
- Resources: type of resources that the interviewee can mobilise, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ... type of resources that the interviewee needs, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ...

- What's your role in the network?
- What [actor/organisation x's] role in the network? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- How do your customers/suppliers/partners/... choose you?
- How did your customers/suppliers/partners/... get to know you?
- What are your relationships with customers/suppliers/partners/... based on?
- (i.e. trust, competences, flexibility, quality, price, uniqueness, etc.)
- Has your relationship with customers/suppliers/partners/... changed over time? Why?
- Has your relationship with your customer(s)/audience impacted on your business in terms of production/profit growth, number of people working in the company/organisation/agency/etc., visibility, etc. Could you quantify it?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide you with standard projects?
- Have you ever asked them to customise their products for you?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that are difficult to find?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that only they are able to provide you?
- Have you ever developed a project together with suppliers/partners?
- How do you select your suppliers/partners?
- How did your suppliers/partners get to know you?
- Have you ever had any problems with suppliers/partners? how did you solve them?
- Has your relationship with suppliers changed over time? Why?
- Do you have direct relationships with the consumers/audience of your project?
- (if yes) How do you manage it?
- Does audience/final consumer participate in your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes? How?
- How important are audience/consumers' preferences/judgments for your projects/business/activity?
- Does their judgment affect your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes?
- How are your relations with your customers/suppliers/partners/...regulated/governed?
- (i.e. formal agreements, informal accords, individual contracts, codes of conducts, etc.)
- Have you got any exclusive agreement with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- Does it include non-disclosure clauses?

- Does it include the use/concession of technologies/knowledge that are protected by (any kind of) agreement that you cannot use/replicate for other processes?
- (If yes) what kind of agreement?
- Who decides how to create/produce/develop/make/provide/etc. the project that you carry out?
- Does your customers/suppliers/partners/...participate in such a process?
- Do you have a say in such a process?
- Has your customers/suppliers/partners/... their own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Do you have your own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Can you/your customers/suppliers/partners/... negotiate terms and conditions of the creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving/etc. process?
- Is there any quality standard to be respected in such a process?
- What are the consequences in case of non-compliance with the contract/standard?
- Do you envisage any kind of reward for your best suppliers? What does it consist of?
- Do you have any knowledge of the destination of the project (service/activity/good) that you produce/ create/develop/make/provide/etc.?
- In your opinion, how easy would it be for you to replace your other customers/suppliers/partners/...with others?
- In your opinion, how easy would it be for your customers/partners/... to replace you with other suppliers/partners?
- What do you/ does your company/organisation/agency do better than others in your industry?
- What is your specific asset/advantage with respect to others?
- How important is reputation in your business? What elements are crucial for it?
- How do you build your reputation?
- How do you make yourself/your organisation/agency/company known?
- Have there been any crucial moments in your organisation' history/your career that have changed your reputation?
- Have there been any people that have been particularly important for your career/your organisation' growth?

Price and value

Themes to analyse:

- Mechanisms at play in the price and value formation (decisions, relevant aspects such as brand, status, reputation, production...)
- Actors involved (or excluded) in value/price formation
- Any other relevant theme

- Who decides the price of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- On the basis of what dimensions?
- (i.e. market position, competencies, reliability, reputation, brand, design, technology, etc.)
- Can you/your supplier(s)/customer(s) negotiate the price? On what basis?
- With respect to such a price do you think that your contribution is adequately rewarded?
- Could you tell us how much it costs the realization of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- How often do you receive a non-monetary reward for your work? What do you receive instead?

- Does the price of the service/activity/good that you exchange with your customer(s)/supplier(s) allow you to run your activity/business according to legal and social standards? Why/Why not?
- Do you know the final price at which the project (service/activity/good) is sold?
- In your opinion what are the elements that contribute to determine the final price of the project?
- (it might be the price of the final good, the price of the ticket of a concert/show/exhibition but also the price of the whole exhibition/festival)
- Do you think that the final price of the project is appropriate? Why?
- Do intermediaries impact on decisions about the price of your project? How?
- In your opinion does the final price of the good/service reflect its value?
- In which stage of the production cycle (refer to the diagram) is the value of the project mostly created?
- Who are the actors/organisations in the PN that gain the most from the realisation of the project? Why?

Working conditions, labour and collective actors

Themes to analyse (when applicable):

- Profile of the workforce/associates/collaborators/partners
- Recruitment process and wage definition
- Organisation of work
- Presence and role of trade unions in the organisation/agency/company/etc.
- Presence and role of trade unions and/or business/trade associations in the industry
- Any other relevant theme

- Do you have employees/collaborators/associates, etc.?
- How is your workforce composed?
- (i.e.: percentage of professionals/consultants/technicians/workers, etc. out of the total, but also percentage of women/men, percentage by ethnicity, etc.)
- How is work organised in your organisation/agency/company, etc.?
- (i.e.: on projects, regular working time, piece rates, etc.)
- What types of contracts does your organisation/agency/company mainly apply to them?
- (i.e.: fixed-term contracts, permanent contracts, agency staff, freelancers, consultants and contractors, etc.)
- Do they work mainly full time/part time?
- Where do they mainly work?
- (i.e. offices, ateliers, workplaces, at home, in co-working spaces, etc.)
- What aspects do you mainly consider when selecting the workforce?
- (i.e. skills, formal training and education, experience, reputation, flexibility, technical knowledge, etc.)
- Do you employ foreign professionals/workers? Why?
- Do you have internships? Do you have any specific agreement with schools/universities in this respect?
- How do you set salaries and working conditions for your workforce?
- (i.e.: collective agreements, plant level agreements, informal agreements, individual negotiation, etc.)
- Does your organisation/agency/company set any productivity incentives/bonus for your workforce?

- Do workers have a say in the activity carried out by the organisation/agency/company?
- Do your workers must respect any codes of conduct?
- Do your workers must respect any non-disclosure agreements/clauses?
- Are trade unions present in your organisation/agency/company/etc.?
- What are their main claims?
- Have they ever helped you? When?
- Do they influence your business? How?
- (i.e. through the bargaining process, strikes, demonstrations, disputes, etc.)
- Have you had any conflicts with unions recently?
- (If yes), Could you tell me what was the issue?
- How did you negotiate your positions?
- What is the role of business associations/trade associations/etc. in your industry? (at different levels: local/regional/national/international)
- Do you participate in some of them?
- (If yes), How is this beneficial?

Skills and knowledge

Themes to analyse:

- Main skills/competencies/resources required in the industry
- Skills/competencies/resources that make the interviewee / organisation crucial / important for the network.

- What kind of skills/knowledge/competencies/technologies/etc. are involved in/needed by your production/creative/distribution/etc. process?
- Do you have any specific expertise that makes you irreplaceable to your partners?
- Do you find skill/knowledge/competencies/technologies in the local labour market or do you need to acquire/buy them from abroad/very far from you/in a difficult way?
- Do you provide any training programme to your workforce? Who decides for them?
- Does/do your customer(s) play a role in such a process?
- (i.e.: sending consultants/technicians/skilled workers, organising training programmes, etc.)

Innovation

Themes to analyse:

- Main innovations for the industry and the specific economic activity
- Impact of innovations on the cycle of production
- Impact of innovations on relationships with partners
- Impact of digitisation
- Any other relevant theme

- How do you keep yourself informed on the latest technologies/innovations/trends/etc. that are relevant for your business?
- (i.e.: fairs, contests, consultants, journals, magazines and sector publishing, etc.)
- What is the most important/recent innovation that has been introduced in your creative/production/ distribution/exchange/archive process?
- (focus on different types of innovation: product, technological, stylistic, in the distribution, ...)

- Who/what urged this innovation?
- How did this innovation impact on your business?
- (Please, explore the different implications of this innovation)
- Did it allow you to develop new organisational capabilities?
- To hire new/qualified workforce?
- To reach other customers or/and enter new/different markets/businesses/activities?
- To acquire new/better capabilities?
- How did innovation impact with your work?
- Have you been asked to acquire new skills?
- How did this innovation modify your relationships with the other actors/organisations of the network?
- Have you ever needed/solicit collaboration with schools/universities/ laboratories/education centres/etc. for developing/learn any innovation?
- (i.e. for finding skilled professionals/workforces and/or for developing new skills/competencies/knowledge)
- Is there any research centre with which you cooperate to research and develop new services/products/ideas? Are they private, public or are they the result of public–private partnership?
- Has digitalisation had an impact on your activity? How?

Embeddedness

Relations between the production network and the region

Themes to analyse:

- Resources that the territory/context offers and relevance for the activity carried out
- Advantages/disadvantages connected to the area
- Role of Institutions
- Policies
- Any other relevant theme

- What kind of resources can this territory offer to your organisation/agency/company, etc.?
- (Here's a list of possible items that you may explore: know-how, traditions; logistics; skilled labour; research structures, academies and schools, innovation hubs, incubators; geography and natural resources);
- For instance, with reference to social resources:
- What kind of social resources can the community of this area offer to your company/organisation/agency/etc.? (i.e. local work ethos/culture, informal relations, attitudes towards the economy, openness to innovation, diversity, social values, cultural activities, etc.)
- In what ways are they relevant for your activity?
- Do you think that the local community supports your economic activity? (If yes) In what ways?
- Would you say that it is strategic to be here? Why?
- What factors keep you here?
- Has this territory a special reputation in your industry's tradition? How do you benefit from it?
- (i.e. territorial brand that may help your activity?)

- What are the problems of the territory that impact on your organisation/agency/company, etc.?
- Do institutions (regional, local authorities, ---) in this territory encourage economic initiatives in your industry? In what ways?
- Do institutions (i.e. region, local authorities, ---) encourage cultural initiatives in this area? In what ways?
- Does the economic and institutional context in which you work help/hinder your activity? How?
- (focus on fiscal requirements, industrial policies, labour regulation, environmental standards, trade policies, etc.)
- Do you think that the existing policies at regional level are adequate to the needs of your organisation/agency/company?
- (focus i.e., on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, etc.)
- Do you think that the existing policies at national / international level are adequate to the needs of your organisation/agency/company?
- (focus on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, trade policies, intellectual property right agreements, etc.)
- Has your organisation/agency/company, etc. tried to influence policy making?
- Has your organisation/agency/company, etc. benefited from policy initiatives developed in industries connected to yours?
- Do you participate in some regional-funded project/initiative?
- In your opinion what should be done at a policy level to promote/help your industry/activity?

Contribution to socio-economic development

Themes to analyse:

- Socio-economic impact of the PN on the region
- Birth/decline of new/traditional job/economic activities connected to the PN
- Birth of new professional/technical schools/courses connected to the economic activity
- Collaboration with institutions/universities/schools
- Participation of the interviewee/organisation in local cultural/social initiatives
- Economic/social/environmental sustainability
- Any other relevant theme

- Does your involvement in a network of (global) activities impact on the economy of the region you work in? In what ways? (i.e.: incomes, employment and wages, local taxation, touristic trends, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth/diffusion/expansion/decline of new/traditional jobs/professionals and/or economic activities connected to it?
- Has your participation in the network favoured any collaboration with universities or local schools?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth of new professional/technical schools/courses/etc. connected to your activity?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the development of local cultural and social initiatives?

- (i.e.: festival, fairs, competition and contests, community revitalization programs, urban regeneration, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network favoured the involvement of your organisation/agency/company, etc. in the social life of your locality/region? (i.e.: charity initiatives, with prisons, etc.)
- Do you support/promote any local association/organisation/initiative/festival/fair/sport club/etc.?
- Are you involved in any local association/club/organisation for the promotion of the local society?
- (i.e. local festival, local fairs, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the well-being of your workforce's conditions in this region? (i.e.: labour standards, diversity promotion, health and safety, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the environmental sustainability of your economic activity? (i.e.: introducing cleaner technologies, environmental sound processes, materials, etc.)
- Do you think that your business has contributed to change/improve your region's image/reputation? In what ways? (i.e.: local specialisations, brand rent effect, testimonials, etc.)

Concluding session

- In your opinion, how important is your contribution to the production network you participate in?
- How do you think you are contributing to the development of local society?
- What are the main values that inspire your activity/organisation?
- How do you imagine this industry in ten years' time?
- (focus on e.g. cultural hybridization, technological innovation, new markets, etc.)
- How do you imagine you/your activity in this industry in ten years' time?